

Documenting the sounds of the West-Coastal Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai region (DR Congo)

An integrated phonetic and diachronic-phonological approach

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Foreword

The present PhD dissertation is the result of four years of research within the framework of the FWO-funded 11D7223N project (2020-2024) titled “Documenting the Bantu Languages of the Last Hunter-Gatherer Communities of the Mai-Ndombe and Lower Kasai Regions (Democratic Republic of Congo): A Pioneering Phonetic and Laboratory Phonological Study”. Following my involvement in the diachronic-phonological research of the BantuFirst (2018-2023) project since 2020 and my two-month fieldwork mission to Mai-Ndombe (Democratic Republic of Congo) in 2021, I have chosen to expand the scope of my research from the documentation of hunter-gatherer varieties to that of non-Twa Bantu languages spoken in the Lower Kasai. This was due to their great wealth of interesting phonetic and phonological features, which could also shed new light on pre-Bantu Twa languages. After consultation with my doctoral committee and their approval, this broadening of my original FWO project was reported, along with an outline of research progress, to the FWO, which renewed my PhD funding in 2022 for a second term.

Chapter 1: Introduction

This thesis is presented as a collection of articles written between 2021 and 2024 in partial fulfilment of the requirements for my doctoral programmes at Ghent University and the University of Mons. The main objective of this thesis is to present ongoing research into the phonetics and diachronic phonology of the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai (see Map 1), a geographically composite area of the Democratic Republic of Congo straddling the two neighbouring provinces of Mai-Ndombe and Kwilu, near the southwestern corner of the Congo Basin rainforest. Ecologically, the Lower Kasai, dominated by the presence of the Kasai River, is a transition zone between different ecoregions within the Afrotropical realm: a tropical moist broadleaf forest to the north and northeast and tropical savannahs/shrublands to the south and southwest. Part of this transition zone features a so-called forest-savannah mosaic, an ecotone marked by the presence of patches of forest interspersed with savannah clearings, often constituting forest corridors/galleries (Olson et al. 2001).

Linguistically, the Lower Kasai region, along with the rest of southwestern Congo all the way down to the border with Angola, is among the least well-surveyed areas of the planet (Hammarström 2016). It hosts Bantu languages belonging to Guthrie's (1970) zones B, C, and H. Most of these varieties belong to West-Coastal Bantu, also known as West-Western Bantu (Grollemund et al. 2015), a major discrete branch of the Bantu family (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019). West-Coastal Bantu languages are thought to descend from the language spoken by the first Bantu settlers that immigrated into the study area around 2,500 years ago (Bostoen et al. 2015, Grollemund et al. 2015, Pacchiarotti et al. 2019). Interestingly, unlike neighbouring Bantu languages and unlike the majority of Bantu languages in general, often considered to lack phenomena of specific phonetic interest (Maddieson & Sands 2019), West-Coastal Bantu languages have been documented to present a relatively high number of unusual phonetic features, such as labial-velar stops, retroflex flaps and nasals, and interior vowel phonemes (Khang Levy 1979, Stappers 1986, Crane et al. 2011; see below, §1.1.1).

While these phenomena have received attention in the relevant phonetic and phonological literature (see general overviews by Connell 1994, Cahill 2008, 2018 for labial-velar stops; Bhat 1973, Hamann 2002, 2003, Tabain et al. 2016, 2020, Hussain et al. 2017 for retroflexion; Rolle et al. 2017, 2020 for interior vowels), evidence from

the Lower Kasai has been largely ignored in the definition of broader typologies. One of the aims of the present contribution is to provide key data from this neglected region and, therefore, contribute to improving our understanding of the phonetics and phonology of these sounds. However, the interest of this study extends beyond phonetics and phonology and raises important historico-linguistic issues. First of all, present-day Lower Kasai's striking phonetic and phonological diversity might be attributed to contact with no longer extant pre-Bantu hunter-gatherer languages. The notion of phonetic and phonological substrate interference from now-lost "Pygmy" languages on the Bantu varieties of the Congo Basin rainforest area dates at least as far back as Möhlig (1981). The Lower Kasai, whose languages have a distinctive sound profile within the wider Bantu family (Daeleman 1977, Rottland 1977), constitutes a particularly interesting case in the investigation of this hypothesis. This is especially true if one considers that the Lower Kasai's exceptionality extends to linguistic features beyond phonetics and phonology (Guthrie 1956, 1960, Bostoen & Mundeke 2011a,b, 2012, Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2014, Bostoen & Pacchiarotti 2024). Second, an alternative hypothesis is that some of the peculiarities of the region's languages could be due to successive spread events from areas further north, such as the Bantu-Ubangi borderland. This is an appealing possibility if one considers that labial-velar stops, retroflexion, and the presence of interior vowels have been interpreted as areal features of northern sub-Saharan Africa (Bhat 1973, Güldemann 2008, 2018, Clements & Rialland 2008, Rolle et al. 2017, 2020). However, the investigation of these two historical scenarios has been hampered by the lack of specific data collection, and the possible implications of the region's linguistic diversity for language and population history as well as for phonetic and phonological typology have not yet received adequate attention. As a consequence, on top of its general documentary component, this contribution aims to address this gap in the literature.

To this end, I have analysed data on labial-velar stops, retroflex consonants, and interior vowels in a selection of Lower Kasai Bantu languages. This has allowed me to propose an integrated descriptive-phonetic and diachronic-phonological approach, and to evaluate how well the two historical scenarios outlined above hold against the newly uncovered evidence on each specific sound class. Through the integration of low-level phonetic information with diachronic-phonological reconstruction, the present contribution endeavours to broaden both our knowledge of the typology of

Map 1 - The area of research

these rare sounds and our understanding of the socio-historical dynamics underpinning their distribution and characteristics in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai. Additionally, I have collected and transcribed extensive word lists from four different Lotwa varieties spoken in the Mai-Ndombe province (Equatorial Lakes region); these are made available here for the first time (Appendix 1) and represent key data in the study of present-day hunter-gatherer languages in the area.

To substantiate this investigation, four main research questions have driven and informed my research activities; these can be summarised as follows:

- *What are the synchronic features of labial-velar stops in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai?*
- *What are the synchronic features of retroflex consonants in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai?*
- *What are the synchronic features of interior vowels in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai?*
- *How did labial-velar stops, retroflex consonants, and interior vowels emerge in Lower Kasai Bantu languages and do these sound classes have the same diachronic origins?*

The rest of this introduction is structured as follows: section §1.1 summarises the relevant state of the art on the sounds investigated in this thesis (labial-velar stops, retroflex consonants, interior vowels) as well as on the population history of the region and the languages dealt with in the text; section §1.2 presents the methods adopted in the constituting articles of the thesis; section §1.3 summarises the structure of the thesis.

1.1 State of the art

1.1.1 Phonetic and phonological typology

1.1.1.1 Labial-velar stops

Labial-velar stops (such as those typically transcribed as <kp> and <gb> in the International Phonetic Alphabet) are doubly articulated sounds produced with two closures at the lips and at the velum (see Connell 1994, Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996). These two closures are released almost simultaneously, with the velar one always preceding the labial by a short time (Maddieson 1993); see Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Relative timing of the lower lip and tongue body movements in the articulation of voiceless [kp]; source: Ladefoged & Maddieson (1996: 338)

This asymmetry is primarily due to aerodynamic reasons. Cross-linguistically, labial-velar stops have been observed to occur with three different airstream mechanisms: a simple pulmonic egressive one (with no backward movement of the tongue dorsum

and, therefore, no decrease in pressure between the two closures); a pulmonic egressive one coupled with a velaric ingressive one (the tongue dorsum slides back, causing air to rarefy between the two closures, so that, upon release, air flows into the mouth from the lungs and the atmosphere); or a simple pulmonic egressive one co-occurring with the aforementioned velaric ingressive one and a glottalic ingressive one, i.e., a downward displacement of the partially adducted glottis, generating voicing (Ladefoged 1968; also Bearth & Zemp 1967, Thomas 1978, Mills 1984, Cahill 2018: 152 and the literature cited therein). This means that, in the case of simple pulmonic egressive airstreams, air coming out of the lungs builds up behind the velum and then releases first the closure closer to the source and subsequently the other; and, in the case of velaric ingressive ones, the labial closure has to be maintained longer than the velar one if air suction is to be attained in the oral cavity (Cahill 2018; the labial closure does not, however, necessarily have to be initiated after the velar one, see Connell 1998/99: 18). Additionally, the typological trend for labial occlusions to be longer than velar ones would make it so that, postulating either simultaneous closure events or a preceding velar one, the labial release would still lag slightly. Cahill (2018: 154) mentions other suggestive explanations for velar closure precedence in labial-velars, including one pertaining to the mechanics of the jaw as a hinge, but these appear to fall under the broader umbrella of “ease of articulation” and are therefore to be treated with due caution in the light of such remarks as Ohala (1974: 368) and Simpson (2013: 163). Acoustically, labial-velar stops have been described as characterised by the following properties: steep F2 rise into the following vowel, tendency to display two formant loci, presence of low-frequency energy concentrations throughout the spectrum and of a pre-voiced release, compact concentrations of energy above 3 kHz and in particular around 4 kHz (Ladefoged 1964, Garnes 1975, Connell 1987, 1991a,b, 1994, Dogil 1988). Perceptual studies of labial-velar stops are rare, but the labial element is generally considered to be perceptually more salient in the literature (see Connell 1994: 472 for comments on previous claims by Westermann & Ward 1933; also, Cahill 2018).

In terms of diachronic phonology, labial-velar stops have been interpreted as the outcome of a temporal compression from velar/labial (K/P) + labial-velar approximant (W) + vowel sequences (KWA/PWA) to full-fledged double-articulations (KPA), as reported by Ponelis (1974), based on previous considerations by Westermann (1911, 1927), Doke (1931), Abercrombie (1967), Trubetzkoy (1969), Chomsky & Halle (1968),

and Ladefoged (1971). In plainer terms, the general assumption is that stop + back rounded vowel + vowel sequences (*KUA/*PUA) underwent some degree of labialisation on the *U which would thereafter have been realised as labial-velar *W; following this change, labiovelarisation would have affected *K/*P: *KUA/*PUA > *KWA/*PWA > KPA. Moving from earlier notes by Anderson (1976), who proposed a generative account of labial-velar stop phonology but ignored Ponelis’s contribution, explanations of this phenomenon have been advanced both from a feature-geometrical (Mutaka & Ebobissé 1996/97; see also Sagey 1986, 1988, Clements 1991, 1992) and an articulatory-phonological perspective (Goldstein 1995, Connell 1998/99), with the latter having gained credence over the years as the standard for labial-velar stop internal derivation in the world’s languages (Cahill 2018: 156; however, other possibilities have also been advanced, see Ehret 2001 who reconstructs the following from Proto–Nilo-Saharan to Proto–Central-Sudanic: *gVB > *gbV); see Figure 2. This process of temporal compression, with subsequent loss of the velar element, has been claimed to explain the emergence of labials as reflexes of Proto–Indo-European velar stop + labial-velar approximant sequences in Greek (Szemerényi 1966, Sheets 1975, Stephens & Woodard 1986; for more recent perspectives, see Piwowarczyk 2020, Van Beek 2020) as well as Insular Celtic (Schrijver 1999, Hock 2015), but is most widely reported in Africa. This has led to the common identification of labial-velar stops as “African sounds” (Cahill 2018: 150).

Figure 2 - Temporal compression of *KUA to *KPA in articulatory-phonological terms; source: Connell (1998/99)

As a matter of fact, labial-velar stops seem to occur in roughly one tenth of the world’s languages (Cahill 2008, Maddieson 2013, Eberhard et al. 2024); of these, ~90% are spoken in Africa, with the remaining ~10% distributed across Papua – New Guinea, South America, and Oceania. Within Africa, the vast majority of labial-velar-stop-containing phonological inventories are concentrated in Western and North-Central

Africa (Dalby 1970, Cahill 1999, 2017, Maddieson 2013, Idiatov & Van de Velde 2016, 2021).¹ Because of this peculiar distribution, labial-velar stops have been described as an areal feature of the so-called “Macro-Sudan Belt”. This is a proposed linguistic macro-area going approximately from the Ethiopian escarpment in the east to the western end of the African landmass, in a territory where languages belonging to multiple linguistic families (to wit, Mande, Kru, Gur, Kwa, Benue-Congo excluding most of Narrow Bantu, Adamawa-Ubangi, Sara-Bongo-Bagirmi, and Moru-Mangbetu) are spoken, and where cross-linguistic typological similarities are supposed to be due to contact rather than a shared phylogeny (Güldemann 2003, 2008, 2010, 2018: 479ff, Clements & Rialland 2008, based on earlier research by Greenberg 1959, 1983, Tucker 1967a,b, among others). Languages outside this area which exhibit labial-velar stops in their phonological inventories are said to have borrowed these sounds from neighbouring core Macro-Sudan Belt varieties (Güldemann 2008: 10), and the notion that labial-velar stops spread through contact interference is explicitly stated by Dimmendaal (1995) for Kuku and Alur (Nilotic) and by Bostoen & Donzo (2013) and Donzo (2015) for Ngombe (Bantu; see also Hagège & Haudricourt 1978). Clements & Rialland (2008: 43-44) report labial-velar stops in over half the languages of what they call the “Sudanic belt” (largely corresponding to the Macro-Sudan Belt as defined above). The prevalence of this feature in this macro-area has been explained in several different ways, namely, as retention and spread from Proto-Niger-Congo (Greenberg 1983), as substrate interference from an unknown source (Vogler 2014, cited in Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021: 73), or as transfer from undocumented hunter-gatherer forest languages (Schebesta 1949). Idiatov & Van de Velde (2021) argue that languages in this area differ greatly as to the phonological load of their labial-velar stops, with some presenting them as marginal phonemes and others as fully integrated parts of their phonology. The latter are concentrated primarily around three so-called “hotbeds” of labial-velar lexical frequency (Upper Guinea, Lower Guinea, Ubangi Basin). These, in turn, they consider to be refugial zones where populations speaking varieties without labial-velar stops in their phonology would have migrated in times unknown to history, and where they would have mixed with local groups which they argue served as primary labial-velar stop donors. These primary speech communities

¹ Throughout this thesis, cardinal direction labels such as northern, southern, western, and eastern, are only capitalised in collocations that indicate commonly accepted cultural, historical, or geographic entities, e.g., Central Africa, Eastern Bantu, etc.

would then have shifted to the languages of the newcomers, importing labial-velar stop phonemes into their new phonology (in what they interpret as an instance of shift-induced substrate interference in the sense of Thomason & Kaufman 1988: 110-146, i.e., a case of transfer of grammatical features from one donor language to a target language with the latter still reflecting its genetic background in most respects; see §1.1.2.1).

The relevance of labial-velar stop spread for the identification of a linguistic macro-area in northern sub-Saharan Africa has been called into question by Cahill (2017). According to Cahill, an important part of the reason why labial-velar stops are so frequent in the Macro-Sudan Belt is, quite simply, that this is the area where the most languages are spoken on the African continent, and that the origin of labial-velar stops in this region can be traced back to multiple proto-languages. While Idiatov & Van de Velde's (2021) account addresses the multiple proto-language hypothesis, it does not explicitly deal with the issue of language density as a confounding factor. Furthermore, available overviews of labial-velar stop distribution in Africa (Clements & Rialland 2008, Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021) seem to ignore or downplay the presence of labial-velar stops in the phonological inventories of some languages spoken outside northern sub-Saharan Africa, and generally assume that labial-velar stop spread in Narrow Bantu is limited to the northernmost fringes of the Congo Basin rainforest. Clements & Rialland (2008) do mention that labial-velar stops can be found in a handful of Bantu zone A, C, and D languages spoken within and immediately to the south of the rainforest. They mention Londo A11, Bafo A141, Central Mbo A15C, Duala A21–3, Kpa/Bafia A53, Tuki A64, Ewondo-Fang A70, and Makaa A83 for zone A; Ngundi C10, Bangi-Ntumba C30, Ngombe C41, Beo/Ngelima C45, Topoke/Gesogo C53, and Lombo C54 for zone C; and Mbole-Ena D10, Bira-Huku D30, and Amba D22 for zone D. They also note that “labial-velar stops occur in a few roots in Sakata C34” (p. 44), though their claim that these sounds are particularly marginal in the Sakata lexicon remains unsubstantiated. The authors also concede (same page) that “this list is very likely incomplete, as information for most languages in the area is sparse”. As a matter of fact, their list does not include any Bantu zone B languages of the Lower Kasai, where labial-velar stops have also been reported. This is particularly true of Tiene B81 (Ellington 1977: 28), Nsong B85d (Dibata Mimpiya 1979: 14), Mpur B85e (Kibwenge India'Ane 1985: 39-40), Nsambaan B85F (Katona Makani 2017: 16), Ding B86 (Mula 1977: 7; Munkyen Okab 1990: 208), Ngwi B861 (Nsumuki 1993: 12), Lwel B862 (Khang Levy 1977: 20,

1979: 4), Nzadi B865 (Crane et al. 2011: 21), and Mbuun B87 (Mundeke 2011: 29). Meanwhile, other Bantu zone B languages have also been documented that present labial-velar stops in their phonological inventories, in particular Mbaama B62 as spoken in Sibiti, Kikimi B70r, Teye B73Z, Tyoo B74c, Nginji B76b, and Teke Kenkuu B80x (Kouarata pers. comm., Kouarata et al. 2023; see <https://www.bantufirst.ugent.be/research/west-coastal-bantu-interactive-map/> for information concerning the coding system used in this contribution). These linguistic communities are all located to the far south of the Congo Basin rainforest, near the area where Sakata C34 is spoken.

In sum, there is little agreement to be found concerning the dynamics underpinning the historical spread of labial-velar stops (Dimmendaal 1995, 2001, Grégoire 2003) and their diagnostic power in the identification of linguistic macro-areas (Hyman 2011, Cahill 2017). Moreover, the available phonetic information for languages spoken outside Idiatov & Van de Velde's (2021) three hotbeds of labial-velar stop frequency is scant; a few examples can be found in: Demolin & Teston (1996), who focus on the aerodynamics and articulation of labial-velar stops in Lendu, Mangbetu, and Liko; Demolin & Soquet (1999), who focus on the acoustics and aerodynamics of double articulations (labial-velar stops as well as what they refer to as "labial-uvular" ones) in Mamvu, Efe, and Lese. In particular, the extent to which the articulatory derivation pattern outlined above to account for the internal development of labial-velar stops in individual languages is still productive has not been analysed in the relevant literature. In other words, the issue of whether KW-/PW- sequences can be realised as KP- in free variation in languages that display labial-velar stops in their phonological inventories remains essentially unaddressed. This means that, for the time being, an approach similar to that proposed by Idiatov & Van de Velde (2021) but focussing on the phonetic characteristics of labial-velar stop segments rather than their lexical frequency cannot be attempted. As a consequence, our understanding of labial-velar stop phonetics, phonology, geographical distribution, and historical spread remains limited.

Chapters 2, 3, and 4 tackle the issue of labial-velar stop phonetic typology and diachronic phonology in Lwel and Sakata, two Lower Kasai languages where these sounds have been reported, addressing the first research question mentioned above: what are the synchronic features of labial-velar stops in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai? In this sense, the specific gap in the literature that the contributions

presented in these chapters aim to address has to do with the poor state of documentation of labial-velar stop sounds in the region of interest. Acoustic (Chapters 2 and 3) and aerodynamic (Chapter 4) data are presented for the first time from languages spoken in the southwestern corner of the Congo Basin rainforest. Low-level phonetic information is used to inform phonological considerations about specific instances of sound change in the region (among others: affrication in Kingingele, and the blurring of the voicing contrast between voiced and voiceless labial-velar stops in Lwel).

1.1.1.2 *Retroflex consonants*

Retroflexes (also referred to as “cacuminals” or “cerebrals” in the Indological literature) are a class of coronal consonants traditionally identified by their property of being articulated between the alveolar ridge and the hard palate with the tip of the tongue “curled up to some extent” (and therefore raised) in the direction of the hard palate (Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996: 25; see also Dixit 1990, Trask 1996); see Figure 3. This articulatory property is already present in the etymology of the word “retroflex”, from a Latin form meaning “bent back”. By virtue of their common articulatory trait of being produced with a specific configuration of the active articulator which involves both a raising and a displacement of the tongue tip, retroflex consonants are considered typologically “marked” sounds in the sense of Chomsky & Halle (1968: 300; i.e., markedness as articulatory complexity; see also Hamann 2003: 4).

Figure 3 - X-ray imaging of a retroflex articulation in Tamil (source: Hamann 2003); the tongue is shown to be "curled up" towards the hard palate

Retroflexion is often treated as a place of articulation and is presented as such in the International Phonetic Alphabet; however, part of the literature also refers to retroflexion as a secondary articulation (Bertinetto 2004). Each individual retroflex sound can typically be described more accurately with other place of articulation descriptors: as concerns the active articulator, specific retroflex sounds can be apical, subapical, or occasionally sublaminal; for the passive articulator, they can be described as alveolar, post-alveolar, prepalatal, or palatal. Nevertheless, retroflexion also behaves as a true place of articulation in that it displays the same manner of articulation classes as any other place, i.e., plosives, fricatives, nasals, laterals, etc. (Hamann 2003: 14). Williamson (1977) treats the label “retroflex” as a possible value of “apicality” and Ladefoged & Maddieson (1996) as a specification of “articulatory place”. These definitions are in a sense compatible: retroflexes are generally described as apical or sub-apical articulations targeting the post-alveolar/palatal passive articulator, which offers some grounds for both Ladefoged and Maddieson’s (1996) position (itself in line with IPA 1949, Ladefoged 1971, 1975, Bhat 1974a, Maddieson 1984) and Williamson’s (1977). On the other hand, Laver (1994) uses the term “retroflex” as a mode of articulation descriptor. Similarly to Laver (1994), Hamann (2003) submits that retroflexion “describes an articulatory shape or gesture, rather than a place of articulation” (p. 14) (see also Catford 1977, Ohala 1983). She goes on to explain that significant variation can be found in the realisation of retroflexes, both cross-linguistically and inter-personally (Catford 1970, Hamilton 1996, Dart & Nihalani 1999, Simonsen et al. 2000), depending on a number of factors such as vowel context

(Švarný & Zvelebil 1955, Ladefoged & Bhaskararao 1983, Dixit 1990, Dixit & Flege 1991, Krull et al. 1995), speech rate (Bhat 1974b, Dixit & Flege 1991, Lindblad & Lundqvist 1997), and manner of articulation (Lindblad & Lundqvist 1999). For example, specific classes of retroflex consonants have been described as apical alveolar or post-alveolar in most Indo-Aryan languages as well as in Sino-Tibetan, while retroflexion in Dravidian languages is generally considered to correspond to palatal subapical articulations (Ladefoged & Bhaskararao 1983, Wai-Sum 1999, Arsenault 2017: 7). In Africa, Ladefoged (1968) describes retroflex articulations in Ewe and Central Togo as less curled-up than their counterparts in Indo-Aryan and treats them as apical alveolar. This high degree of variability has been the object of detailed analysis from a quantal theory perspective (Stevens & Blumstein 1975, Ladefoged & Bhaskararao 1983).

Acoustically, retroflex consonants are generally considered to be characterised by lower F3 values on the vowels that precede them than their non-retroflex counterparts (Hamilton 1996, Hamann 2003, Hussain et al. 2017); this is a consequence of the tongue tip rising towards the hard palate / in the post-alveolar region, one of the F3 antinodes or points of maximum velocity (or highest kinetic energy) in the F3 resonance in the vocal tract according to Perturbation Theory (Chiba & Kajiyama 1941). Conversely, no absolute cues to retroflexion have been found on the F2 of vowels preceding a retroflex sound (Hussain et al. 2017). However, acoustic cues to retroflex sounds are as subject to cross-linguistic (and interpersonal) variation as their articulatory properties: in the context of Indian languages, Ohala & Ohala (2001) report F2-F3 convergence in Hindi retroflexes, while Dart & Nihalani (1999) document a general lowering of the F2 in Malayalam; Hamilton (1996) notes that a low F3 is the most consistent cue to retroflexion across Australian languages, while Stevens & Blumstein (1975), in line with Fant (1960), note that it is rather the F4 that lowers towards the F3 (itself lowered, but the main variable is considered to be the clustering of F3 and F4 rather than the lowering of the former by itself).

In terms of diachronic phonology, retroflexes are often the outcome of an articulatory shift in the presence of a rhotic (Bhat 1973, Bertinetto 2004). The phonetic link between rhotics and retroflexes has been explained in several ways. Hall (1997) argues that “since the tongue tip is not inhibited in any way, the curling back of the tongue tip behind the alveolar ridge [...] is a conceivable variant pronunciation for [a rhotic]”. Hamann (2003: 88) maintains instead that “a change from alveolar to retroflex

trill occurs to enhance the perceptual cue of a lowered F3 for the rhotic". This explanation, bearing rather on perception than articulation, is in line with earlier observations by Ohala (1993) on what he calls "false association parsing errors" (i.e., cases in which, given two adjacent sounds, one of the salient acoustic properties of the one is re-analysed as a cue to the other), easing the path to the extension of lower F3 from the rhotic to the adjacent segment. However, rhotic adjacency is not the only context in which retroflexes have been known to emerge. A certain affinity has been documented between retroflexion and back vowels (Bhat 1973, Dixon 1980), claimed by Hamann (2003: 92) to be due to "a coarticulation process of the dental/alveolar towards the tongue body shape of the back vowels". This would be particularly true of back rounded vowels, which display lower F3 values. Other sources have focussed on the link between retroflexion and implosion (Haudricourt 1950, Greenberg 1970, Bhat 1973, Hardcastle & Brasington 1978, Ohala 1983), commonly attributed to the fact that both articulations entail an enlargement of the back cavity compared to their non-retroflex and non-implosive counterparts (Perkell 1969, Bell-Berti 1975, Westbury 1983, Hamann & Fuchs 2008: 100). As a matter of fact, free variation between implosives and retroflexes has been reported in a few Western (Manessy 1979, Stewart 1995, Clements & Rialland 2008: 59) and Eastern African lects (Tse 2013, 2015).

Given the relatively limited set of phonological contexts in which retroflexes have been documented to arise, it should come as no surprise that a) retroflexes only occur in about one tenth of Moran & McCloy's (2019) sample of world languages, and b) their distribution has often been interpreted as an areal feature. This is because retroflexes have long been reported to cluster in specific areas of the world, namely, India, Australia, Southeast Asia, Central Africa, and the Pacific coast of America (Bhat 1973), with secondary hotbeds in Southern Africa, Scandinavia, and the Caucasus. Their presence in specific regions is most likely expressed as spread through contact, since independent internal development is generally excluded given the comparative markedness of these sounds (Hamann 2003, Zhivlov 2016). As a matter of fact, sociolinguistic factors have been claimed to influence the diffusion of retroflexes in neighbouring speech communities (Emeneau 1956, Hamp 1996, Hamann & Fuchs 2010, Tse 2015: 284ff). For example, Hamp (1996: 720) describes the acquisition of retroflexes on the part of Indo-Aryan populations as a process of "acculturation" driven

by contact with Dravidian. In an African context, Tse (2015: 285) attributes the retroflex development of Kizigua implosives to intense contact with Cushitic (Oromo, Somali).

With specific reference to Africa, Bhat (1973) defines his “Central Africa” area of retroflexion diffusion as an east-to-west corridor going from Somalia (and northern Tanzania) to Guinea, a vast territory characterised by the presence of languages from numerous linguistic groups (he names West-Atlantic, Chadic, Nilo-Saharan, Cushitic, Omotic, and Eastern Bantu; p. 14) and covering part of Güldemann’s (2008) Macro-Sudan Belt as defined above. While Güldemann (2008, 2018) does not list retroflexion as an areal feature of the Macro-Sudan Belt, Clements & Rialland (2008) redefine it as a characteristic of eastern Sudan, buttressing previous claims that this particular sub-region within their Sudanic belt should be treated as a separate phonological zone (Schadeberg 1987). Bhat (1973: 14) reports that “retroflexion [...] is not a prominent feature in most of the languages of this area” (see also Meinhof 1932, Tucker & Bryan 1956), describing it as an “optional feature”. According to him, the presence of retroflex phonemes in the area is essentially limited to the sporadic emergence of a retroflex flap.

However, retroflexion, retraction, and implosion have been associated with other typical Macro-Sudan Belt features, including labial-velar stops. In fact, nasalised flaps (or nasal retroflexes, Thayer 1974) have been shown to pattern with labial-velar stops as potential sources of nasality on vowels (Matisoff’s 1975: 265 “rhinoglottophilia”, see also Boyeldieu 2022). Laterals (often in free variation with retroflex flaps) and alveolar implosives have been described as mutual free variants in northeastern Congo (Bokula 1970, Kutsch Lojenga 1991, 1994). Regular correspondences of labial-velar and implosive consonants have been reported in northwestern Congo (Donzo 2015: 351), and a labial-velar origin for implosive/pre-glottalised sounds has been proposed in an extra-African context by Opgenort (2004) (for Kiranti, a Sino-Tibetan language of Nepal; see also Starostin 2009, Michailovsky 1988, 1994). Correspondences between (labial) flaps and voiced labial-velar stops have also been reported in Macro-Sudan Belt languages such as Mbum (Ubangi) by Boyd (1974) and Dii (Bantoid) by Olson & Hajek (2003). This suggests that the cooccurrence of retroflexion, flapping, labial-velar stops, and other typologically unusual sounds in northern sub-Saharan Africa might not be due to chance; rather, it ties in with the observations reported above concerning the presence of labial-velar stops outside Idiatov & Van de Velde’s (2021) three hotbeds of lexical frequency. As it so happens, retroflexes have also been documented

in North Boma B82 (Stappers 1986), in the Lower Kasai, as well as in a handful of hunter-gatherer varieties spoken across the Congo Basin rainforest (Vorbichler 1966/67, Motingea 2010: 205). If indeed retroflexion is to be interpreted as an areal feature of the few regions of the world where it has been reported and independent development in neighbouring languages is to be excluded on the basis of its typological markedness, the emergence of retroflexes in the Lower Kasai might be due to contact interference from no longer extant pre-Bantu languages.

Chapter 5 addresses the issue of retroflexion in North Boma, a Lower Kasai language in which nasal retroflex sounds have been documented by Stappers (1986); nasal retroflexes are analysed in terms of acoustic properties and diachronic phonology, providing an integrated account of their behaviour and development in the language. Chapter 6 provides an overview of the behaviour of rhotic consonants in the languages of Mai-Ndombe, one of the provinces of the Lower Kasai, and represents the first report on the presence of retroflex flaps in the hunter-gatherer languages of the Lower Kasai. In this sense, the two chapters address the second research question mentioned above: what are the synchronic features of retroflex consonants in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai? The specific gap in the literature that the contributions presented in these chapters aim to fill has to do with the poor state of documentation of retroflex sounds in the two Lower Kasai language groups (Lotwa and North Boma) that display them in their inventory. The hypothesis that the emergence of retroflex sounds in North Boma is connected to their presence in the region's hunter-gatherer lects is explored in Chapter 5.

1.1.1.3 Interior vowels

Interiority is defined as the chief quality of non-peripheral vowels, i.e., vowels which present formant values situating them in the central (or “interior”) regions of the vowel space (Parker 2000, Rolle et al. 2017). In this sense, the labels “interior” and “central” are by and large synonymous and will be used as such in this venue unless otherwise specified. Central and back vowels often constitute one natural class in languages in opposition to front vowels. This circumstance has made the study of their contrast particularly difficult from a generative and featural perspective (Chomsky & Halle 1968,

Clements 1985, Sagey 1986, McCarthy 1988, Odden 1991, Halle 1995). Within traditional generative phonology, the possibility of introducing a distinct central category for vowels has often been excluded, opting rather for different specifications of [\pm back] or [\pm round] on peripheral vowels (Kenstowicz 1994). A somewhat different perspective, which relies on the notion of the under-specification of central vowels as opposed to peripheral ones, is the one adopted in Flemming's (2009) account of the phonetics of schwa. Schwa is described as a "weak or reduced vowel" (p. 1) subject to a lot of contextual and interpersonal variability (Lindblom 1963, Van Oostendorp 2000). As a matter of fact, interior vowels are "typically associated with formant frequencies that are less extreme than peripheral vowels" (Rolle et al. 2020: 139), which also entails that peripheral vowels are more perceptually distinct than interior ones. This indirectly reinforces a binary opposition for vowels between front and back (Lindau 1978). However, criticisms of this approach have been proposed since at least Catford (1990) and Clements (1991). Similarly, the proposal to introduce a [\pm peripheral] feature (Stockwell 1966, Harms 1967, 1968, Lindau 1978, Ferrari Disner 1984, Labov 1994) has been rebutted in the general literature for several reasons. First of all, this feature would present a lot of the same characteristics as [\pm ATR] (Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996: 300ff); secondly, it has been said that "it is doubtful that the natural classes which this feature predicts to exist and not to exist are empirically supported" (Parker 2000: 8).

According to Schwartz et al. (1997), vowel systems typically exploit non-peripheral vowels only after having "filled" all the available peripheral positions, from which derives that vowel systems displaying interior vowels generally have a higher number of vowels than those that do not. This is in line with basic notions of Dispersion Theory (Liljencrants & Lindblom 1972, Lindblom 1986, later reformulated as Theory of Adaptive Variability by Lindblom 1990 and subsequently revised by Diehl et al. 2003), which predicts that, in the evolution of a language's acoustic vowel space, vowels will disperse across it to enhance perceptibility. In this sense, peripheral vowels are better suited than interior ones to maximise perceptibility, given their relative distance in the acoustic vowel space. In the world's languages, Schwartz et al. (1997) claim that the most common interior vowels are those closest to the centre of the acoustic vowel space, with schwa being the commonest, followed by front rounded and, finally, back unrounded vowels; high interior vowels are said to be more likely to occur in natural languages than low ones. This hierarchy also influences vowel reduction paths in the

world's sound systems, with (centripetal) vowel reduction typically targeting schwa (Kuznetsova & Anderson 2020: 7).

Interior vowels have occasionally been described as subject to specific phenomena of areal diffusion and particularly so in Africa (Thomas et al. 1973, Rolle et al. 2017, 2020). What is more, their presence in the languages of northern sub-Saharan Africa has been shown to pattern with that of ATR, a feature considered to be highly typical of the Macro-Sudan Belt as defined above (Güldemann 2008, 2018, Clements & Rialland 2008; see also Stewart 1967, Dimmendaal 2001, Casali 2003, 2008, Marchese Zogbo 2019). In fact, it is Rolle et al.'s (2017, 2020) contention that languages displaying ATR harmony and interior vowels in their phonological inventories are complementarily distributed in a few major pockets in the Macro-Sudan Belt, dividing the entire belt into five main zones: a so-called Atlantic ATR zone, a Guinean ATR-deficient zone, a West African ATR zone, a Central African ATR-deficient zone which includes the major hotbed of interior vowel diffusion in the region, i.e., their Central African interior vowel zone, and an Eastern African ATR zone including (but extending well beyond) their Eastern African interior vowel zone. While the Eastern African interior vowel zone is essentially limited to the Nuba Mountains region, the Central African interior vowel zone extends over parts of Chad, Nigeria, and Cameroon.

Given Schwartz et al.'s (1997, 2005) considerations regarding the emergence of interior vowels, namely the fact that they tend to occur in languages with a higher-than-average number of vowels, their presence in the Macro-Sudan Belt (where vowel systems of more than 5 vowels are common) is unsurprising. However, it is remarkable that interiority has been reported in a few Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai, in particular Yans B85 (Swartenbroeckx 1948, Rottland 1977), Nsambaan B85F (Mfum-Ekong 1979), Nsong B85d (Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2019), Ding B86 (Mula 1977, Ebalantshim 1980), Ngwi B861 (Bwantsa Kafungu 1966), and Lwel B862 (Khang Levy 1979). As a matter of fact, with the exception of North-West Bantu (Boyd 2015), Bantu languages typically display vowel systems of 5 or 7 peripheral vowels (Hyman 1999, Maddieson & Sands 2019). In this sense, the Lower Kasai constitutes another exception to this general pattern. As seen above, this is an area where other typical Macro-Sudan Belt features have been documented to occur, including labial-velar stops. Notably, the Central African interior vowel zone described above covers an ample portion of Idiatov & Van de Velde's (2021) Cameroon Gap of labial-velar stop diffusion. Still, reports of labialisation on velar consonants influencing the emergence

of interior vowels are present in the literature (see in particular Krauss 1964: 122-123), suggesting a connection between the two phenomena possibly due to the accessory specification of [+ round] on labialised sounds as confirmed by the notion that non-central interior vowels in the world's languages are predominantly front rounded (Schwartz et al. 1997). In this sense, the presence of interior vowels might be connected to the spread of other Macro-Sudan Belt features in the Lower Kasai.

Chapter 7 addresses the issue of the emergence of central vowels in Ngwi, a Bantu language of the Lower Kasai presenting two contrastive interior vowel phonemes. Interior vowel emergence in Ngwi has been addressed from a Dispersion Theory perspective, evaluating the two phonemes attested in Ngwi against competing interior vowel candidates. In this sense, Chapter 7 addresses the third research question presented above: what are the synchronic features of interior vowels in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai?

1.1.2 Language and population history

1.1.2.1 Diachronic phonology and language contact

The comparative method is a technique used in historical linguistics to reconstruct aspects of ancient languages (Campbell 2021). This reconstruction is operated by comparing cognate reflexes in related daughter languages. The comparative method has been a crucial aspect of the study of linguistic prehistory since at least Schleicher (1848), allowing for the reconstruction of languages thousands of years before written records, which only date back to about 5,000 years ago (Weiss 2015). The fundamental idea informing this method is that by systematically comparing linguistic (chiefly phonetic and phonological, see Harrison 2003, Bostoen 2019; syntactic and morphological reconstruction is founded in partially different principles, see Hoenigswald 1991, Koch 1996, 2015, Barðdal et al. 2020, Bostoen 2022) features across languages, linguists can infer properties of their common ancestors. This method involves identifying cognates – words in different languages that have a common etymological origin – and establishing systematic sound correspondences.

Through this process, linguists can reconstruct proto-forms (hypothetical lexical items from which different cognates have emerged in related languages), proto-sounds (hypothetical phonological units from which different reflexes have emerged in related languages), and proto-languages (hypothetical ancestral languages from which current languages have evolved, a concept present for the first time in Schlegel 1808 based on William Jones's 1786 pronouncements on the structural affinities of Latin, Greek, and Sanskrit; see Fanciullo 2013: 159) and trace the development of language families. The comparative method also helps in classifying languages into families based on shared innovations that are unlikely to have arisen independently.

A general standard for the application of the comparative method can be found in Campbell (2021). In practice, cognate words are compared in different languages to identify correspondence sets (Campbell 2021: 143). Subsequently, a hypothesis regarding the proto-form and proto-sounds at the origin of the correspondence set is formulated, and this hypothetical form is known as a reconstruction (Campbell 2021: 146). In the reconstruction of proto-sounds, the notion of directionality plays an important role. Directionality indicates, given two (or more) sounds, let us call them A and B, whether A derives from B or B derives from A. Typological considerations contribute to the resolution of this issue, and can inform the decision of which sound is the likelier proto-sound candidate, or whether a third C sound should be hypothesised to account for the development of both A and B (Campbell 2021: 147; see also Ohala 1978, 1984). Other criteria that contribute to the reconstruction of proto-forms and proto-sounds are that of economy, whereby "when multiple alternatives are available, the one which requires the fewest independent changes is most likely to be right" (Campbell 2021: 148), and majority, which states that "unless there is evidence to the contrary, we tend to pick for our reconstructed proto-sound the particular sound in the correspondence set which shows up in the greatest number of daughter languages" (Campbell 2021: 148). Hypotheses drawn from one correspondence set are then compared with other lexical series to see how pervasive and regular the sound change (see below) at hand really is in the lexicon of the language under investigation (Campbell 2021: 152). Finally, reconstructions have to be evaluated from the point of view of our general typological understanding of the sound of interest (in the sense that forms that are typologically more common or deemed less marked in terms of phonetic substance are to be preferred).

In dealing with the reconstruction of proto-forms and proto-sounds in the context of the comparative method, the notion of “sound change” is crucial (Garrett 2015). Sound change refers to all alterations in pronunciation patterns occurring over time within a given language. This includes phonologisation, where phonetic properties become specific phonological features (Jakobson 1931, Hyman 1977, 2012), as well as changes stemming from dialect contact, paradigm regularisation, or structural simplification (Garrett 2015: 227).

One of the foundational ideas of the comparative method regarding sound change is the so-called Neogrammarian Hypothesis (Osthoff and Brugman 1878, Paul 1880, Sievers 1901; see also Bloomfield 1933), which posits that sounds change in an absolutely regular and exceptionless fashion in natural languages, and that they do so below the level of awareness of individual speakers (Weiss 2015): a certain sound change will always be triggered within the same phonological system given the right phonological context, and the speakers will not be able to influence its outcome. In Neogrammarian terms, the focus of sound change was solely on language-internal factors (Bowerman & Evans 2015: 20), as no social or individual variables were said to influence the regularity of change in a given sound system. Analogy and borrowing were considered to exceed the scope of sound change proper and rather constitute extra-linguistic variables, a position which in turn determined a sharp dichotomy between internal and external motivations for sound change (see Gerritsen and Stein 1992, Farrar 1996, Yang 2000, Croft 2000, Pargman 2002, Jones and Esch 2002, Torgersen and Kerswill 2004, Hickey 2012). However, since at least Kiparsky (1988, 1995), Labov (1981, 1994, 2001, 2010), Lindblom (1990), and Lindblom et al. (1995), largely based on previous work by Weinreich (1953), the complex interplay of phonetic, phonological, morphological, lexical, individual, and social factors in determining the outcomes of sound change has been brought to the fore in historico-linguistic research. Other contributions have tried to ground sound change in articulatory detail and perceptual processes (Blevins & Garrett 1998, 2004, Blevins 2004, 2006, Ohala 1974, 1981, 1983, 1993). In other words, seminal works in the field of diachronic phonology have emphasised the fact that understanding sound change requires interdisciplinary research, as its actuation presents both a psychological (with a focus on individuals and their articulatory and perceptual idiosyncrasies) and a social component (which has to do with how changes acquire value within speech communities, often under the influence of sociohistorical factors).

As a consequence of this shift in the theoretical frame of reference, corrections to the Neogrammarian Hypothesis have been proposed in the literature for quite some time (since at least Wang 1969). Language contact has been shown to influence the outcomes of sound change in ways that are less predictable than would be admitted by strict adherence to the Neogrammarian Hypothesis. By distinguishing between “language shift” (i.e., what happens when a speech community ceases to use one language and instead switches to another) and “bilingualism” (i.e., the modifications brought about in one language system by speakers of another who use both over a long time span), Thomason & Kaufman (1988: 50) laid the groundwork for a comprehensive typology of contact-induced language change, arguing that “it is the sociolinguistic history of the speakers, and not the structure of their language, that is the primary determinant of the linguistic outcome of language contact”. Van Coetsem (1988, 2000; see also Winford 2003, 2005, 2007, 2013) stressed the importance of bi- (and multi-)lingualism for the study of sound change, arguing against the traditional marginalisation of loan phonology in historical linguistics and for its re-evaluation as an integral component of language change and shift. Van Coetsem (1988) also stressed the importance of the distinction between two types of phonological transfer, i.e., borrowing and imposition, based on the directionality of the transfer and the agent/s involved. In this sense, the role of individual speakers is considered of crucial importance, and language (sound) change is reclassified as an event occurring at an individual/psychological level in a given social context rather than a purely language-internal one. Moving from this premise, borrowing is defined as the transfer of material (including structure) from a source language to a recipient language by a speaker of the latter (“recipient language agentivity”). Imposition, on the other hand, refers to the transfer instigated by the source language speaker, imposing elements of their first phonological system onto the recipient language (“source language agentivity”). This approach underscores the relevance of psychological (psycholinguistic) variables for the study of language change: contact-induced language change encompasses all modifications arising from multilingualism within a community (Lucas 2015).

The centrality of individual speakers in the actuation of sound and language change also raises the question of “intentionality”, i.e., that of to what extent the implementation of modifications to an individual’s or a community’s “way of talking” (Simpson 2015) can be controlled or perceived by its agent/s. Thomason (2006a,b, 2007, 2008) discusses instances of what she considers intentional language change

resulting from language contact, where speakers modify their language to emphasise group identity and cohesion; according to her, while the comparative method retains its validity as a robust tool for historico-linguistic reconstruction, deliberate linguistic manipulation can compromise its effectiveness, violating the key requirement that sound change be exceptionless and imperceptible for individual speakers. Thomason presents cases of explicit language manipulation on the part of speakers and communities: she mentions that multilingual speakers apply known phonological correspondences to adapt loanwords, illustrating conscious language manipulation (Thomason 2007: 45-46); that communities sometimes resist lexical or structural borrowing to maintain linguistic purity or identity, showing that not all changes are passively accepted (Thomason 2007: 48); and that changes can be found across all grammatical subsystems, often motivated by social factors such as hyperdialectism or the desire to enhance group identity (Trudgill 1986). Thomason (2008) argues against the existence of absolute linguistic constraints on contact-induced change, a theoretical position clearly at variance with the regularity postulate of the Neogrammarian Hypothesis.

Possible typologies of the results of contact-induced language change have been proposed, most notably by Ross (2003, 2013). Building on Thomason & Kaufman (1988), the core of Ross's investigation is to discern whether changes brought about by multilingualism (where individuals are fluent in more languages) lead to different linguistic outcomes compared to language shifts (where a community transitions from one language to another). In so doing, Ross (2003: 177-182) delves into various types of contact-induced change, distinguishing between catastrophic and non-catastrophic changes. Catastrophic changes involve abrupt community reformation or creation, often leading to new linguistic forms or pidgins. Non-catastrophic changes, which are said to be typologically more common, include processes such as metatypy, where a community's primary language changes its typological characteristics under the influence of a secondary language, often without direct borrowing of lexical items. Ross (2003: 182-192) further categorises speech communities based on their openness (open vs. closed) and cohesion (tightknit vs. looseknit), submitting that these social configurations influence the kind of linguistic changes that occur. According to him, these (idealised) sharp distinctions represent the basic cinder blocks upon which to build a full-fledged typology of contact-induced language change and, ultimately, diagnose prehistoric language contact.

All these considerations have resulted in a more gradient application of the Neogrammarian Hypothesis in the recent developments of historical linguistics. For example, it has been observed that specific sound changes can be implemented gradually in a given language, a phenomenon known as “lexical diffusion” (Cheng & Wang 1977). Instances of gradual or incomplete diffusion can result in irregular sound change (Wang 1969, Labov 1981, Durie and Ross 1996, Harrison 2003). A case of specific interest in this regard is Bantu, which poses significant challenges to historico-linguistic reconstruction: intense language contact and multilingualism across the Bantu domain have resulted in shared phonological innovations that do not align neatly with genealogical subgroupings (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2022). Möhlig's (1977, 1981) notion of “hybrid sound shifts” (i.e., changes influenced by contact, or “hybridisation”), as opposed to “linear sound shifts” (i.e., outputs of traditional sound change rules), challenges the idea that present-day Bantu phonologies evolved linearly from a single ancestral language. Irregular sound change is a pervasive circumstance in West-Coastal Bantu (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020, 2022), and can be indicative of situations of intense multilingualism where the boundaries between languages are blurred (Blust 1996, Ross 1996). In particular, Pacchiarotti & Bostoen (2022) show that the reflexes of Proto-Bantu *k and *g in West-Coastal Bantu are not uniformly predictable, resulting in cases where a single proto-sound yields multiple, seemingly unconditioned outcomes within individual languages. This irregularity suggests that sociolinguistic and environmental factors may have complicated linear sound change in the region's languages (see below, §1.1.2.2). One possible explanation for irregular sound change in West-Coastal Bantu is substrate interference from extinct languages spoken by autochthonous hunter-gatherer groups with whom Bantu-speaking settlers intermingled. For example, the presence of fricative reflexes of Proto-Bantu *k and *g, uncommon in broader Bantu but not infrequent in the West-Coastal branch, might reflect remnants of these lost languages' phonologies, integrated into present-day speech communities through extensive language shift and cultural assimilation. Another possibility is that subsequent spreads of Bantu settlers may have blurred original isoglosses and complicated linear sound change outcomes. This “spread-over-spread” model (see below, §1.1.2.2) suggests that contemporary Bantu languages are products of layered historical interactions, incorporating elements from various languages over time through processes of migration, language shift, and

cultural integration. Ultimately, irregular sound change may be the product of both scenarios, calling for different interpretations for different instances of sound change.

One of the most important corollaries of this rethinking of sound change as the result of complex sociohistorical interactions is that linguistic evidence, including lexicon and grammar, can offer unique insights into the past, complementing archaeological and genetic findings (Epps 2015). This intuition, already embryonically present in Grimm (1822) and later turned into one of the core tenets of a philological school of thought known as “Wörter und Sachen”, or “words and things” (Meringer 1904/05), has received numerous labels over the years, including “linguistic paleontology” and “cultural reconstruction” (Hock 1991: 573–578, Campbell 2004, Southworth 2005, Crowley & Bowerman 2010). A notable case of linguistic reconstruction used for the purposes of socio-cultural inference is that of Indo-European (Epps 2015: 581 and references): reconstructed vocabulary has allowed us to infer important aspects of the Proto–Indo-European lifestyle, from the practice of agriculture to the domestication of cattle and so forth. Epps (2015) also discusses how grammatical features and discourse patterns (i.e., linguistic elements beyond lexicon) can provide insights into past cultural practices and social interactions. She mentions specific instances of grammaticalisation, i.e., the process by which lexical items evolve into grammatical elements, as phenomena that can be culturally motivated. Examples include the development of future tense markers or honorific systems, which can reflect social hierarchies or specific cultural values.

In the context of this thesis, notions from contact linguistics have been used to explain instances of sound change and shed some light on the possible sociohistorical dynamics underpinning the spread of labial-velar stops, retroflex consonants, and interior vowels in the Lower Kasai. However, the specific contribution of the works presented here lies in the integration of diachronic-phonological analyses with low-level phonetic studies. There are several reasons why detailed phonetic information is desirable even for the purposes of phonological and historical analysis. First, not all phonemes have the same functional load in a given language system, and while two sounds may behave contrastively in a certain context, they may also emerge as allophones in others, making them effectively marginal in the language (Hall 2013). Marginal phonetic features can be used for the implementation of marginal phonemes in a language and can be connected to different symbolic or affective purposes (Matisoff 1994). Second, marginal phonemes are often imported into a recipient

language from a source language with which the former has come into contact (Rueter & Fejes 2024). Van Coetsem (1988: 7-9) distinguishes between two primary mechanisms involved in language transfer: imitation and adaptation, which are linked to two main types of transfer. In borrowing, imitation precedes adaptation, meaning that borrowed elements initially mimic the source language and may only resemble it approximately. This imitation might occasionally lead to deviations in the recipient language, such as adopting new sounds, but these cases are infrequent and usually do not significantly alter the recipient language. On the contrary, adaptation in borrowing aims to adjust the borrowed element to fit the recipient language's phonology. In the process of imposition, adaptation takes precedence, often resulting in substantial modifications as the recipient phonological system incorporates elements from the source language (Winford 2005: 381).

In this sense, the low-level study of sound patterns in a given language can illuminate contact dynamics as well as aspects of the phonology of a language. Numerous phenomena considered highly atypical in Bantu and which can be found in some of the West-Coastal Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai seem to behave as marginal phonemes, occurring only in sparse lexical roots or in restricted phonological contexts (Stappers 1986, Clements & Rialland 2008; see also the sources mentioned above for labial-velar stops, retroflexes, and interior vowels in the Lower Kasai in the §1.1.1). Their specific level of phonological integration, as well as other measurable aspects of their phonetic salience in different language systems, could point in the direction of different contact scenarios. In the articles presented in this thesis, diachronic-phonological and phonetic accounts of the sounds of interest are therefore combined.

1.1.2.2 Population dynamics in the Bantu domain and the Lower Kasai

The so-called “Bantu Expansion” refers to the east- and southbound dispersal, between 5,000 and 1,500 years ago, of Bantu languages and Bantu-speaking people from their ancestral homeland in the Grassfields region of present-day Nigeria and Cameroon (Vansina 1995, Blench 2006, Bostoen 2018, Grollemund et al. 2023); it is

considered to be one of the key factors in the definition of the current linguistic landscape of sub-Saharan Africa, as, to this day, hundreds of Bantu languages are spoken in over twenty countries on the African continent (recent estimates range from 472 to 555 individual lects; Hammarström 2019, Bostoen & Van de Velde 2019). The notion of a Bantu Expansion, as proposed by Oliver (1966), who believed that the event was principally prompted by parallel developments in agriculture, pottery-making, and the use of iron, which allowed settlers to exploit new ecological zones such as the Congo Basin rainforest, has garnered considerable attention over the decades in linguistics, genetics, and archaeology. Over the next few paragraphs, I will outline the importance of considering evidence from different disciplines, drawing on examples from within and without the specific area of interest.

Linguistically, the genealogical unity of Bantu has been established since at least Bleek (1851). Subsequently, extensions of the comparative method as developed for Germanic (and Indo-European more generally) in the first half of the nineteenth century (Schlegel 1808, Schleicher 1848; see above, §1.1.2.1) confirmed this unity (Meinhof 1899). More recent approaches, founded on lexicostatistics (i.e., the comparison of the percentage of shared lexical cognates in languages to determine their relationship), can be found in Vansina (1995), Nurse (1996), Piron (1997), and Bastin et al. (1999); phylogenetic classifications are also available (Holden 2002, Holden & Gray 2006, Rexová et al. 2006, de Filippo et al. 2012, Grollemund et al. 2015, Koile et al. 2022); this approach is qualified by Holden & Gray (2006: 19) as follows: “[phylogenetic tree-building methods] use only innovations to define subgroups. [...] Unlike the comparative method, however, phylogenetic methods use an explicit optimality criterion, such as maximum parsimony or likelihood, to choose among possible trees”. The analysis of internal linguistic variation among different areas of the Bantu domain has contributed to the study of the socio-historical dynamics underpinning the Bantu Expansion. For example, it has been observed that North-West Bantu varieties are subject to a lot more variation than Eastern Bantu, suggesting a later split for the latter group (Vansina 1995, Grollemund et al. 2015, Bostoen et al. 2015).

Archaeologically, the transition from pre-extant Stone Age industries to Neolithic and early Iron Age assemblages, and the emergence of distinct pottery styles, has been considered the key aspect of the southward expansion of Bantu (de Maret 2013). In this sense, pottery emerges as a primary marker of early Bantu-speaking cultures,

with significant archaeological sites such as the Shum Laka rock-shelter in Cameroon providing evidence of technological innovations ~7,000 to 6,000 years ago (Lavachery 2001). The advent of iron metallurgy has also been considered a crucial, albeit later, innovation connected to the expansion of Bantu-speaking settlers south and east of their homeland (Clist 2012). However, the evidence for plant cultivation and domestication appears to be more recent than the start of the Bantu Expansion, challenging the notion of this migration being primarily driven by farming (Kahlheber et al. 2009, Neumann 2003, 2005, Neumann et al. 2012, Bostoen 2018).

Finally, genetic evidence has complemented the information derived from linguistics and archaeology, indicating that the Bantu Expansion was marked by a significant demic diffusion. Genetic studies of single locus mitochondrial DNA (or mtDNA, Pereira et al. 2001, Salas et al. 2002, Belezza et al. 2005, Castrì et al. 2009, Schlebusch et al. 2013) and Y-chromosome markers (Coelho et al. 2009, Berniell-Lee et al. 2009, de Filippo et al. 2011, Ansari Pour et al. 2013) have shown that Bantu-speaking people are characterised by specific haplogroups (i.e., groups of related haplotypes – or collections of alleles within an organism that are passed down collectively from one parent – which descend from a common forebear, see Barry et al. 2016). This evidence supports the notion that the Bantu Expansion was more than a phenomenon of cultural and technological spread, and that it entailed the actual displacement of Bantu-speaking people out of West Africa and across sub-Saharan Africa (Tishkoff et al. 2009, Li et al. 2014, Gurdasani et al. 2015, Patin et al. 2017, Schlebusch & Jakobsson 2018, Semo et al. 2020, Sengupta et al. 2021, Fortes-Lima et al. 2024).

However, information coming from the three different disciplines does not always match. Genetic evidence suggests that there might have occurred successive migratory waves of Bantu settlement, which in turn entails that the present distribution of Bantu languages might be the outcome of a later spread (Coelho et al. 2009, Castrì et al. 2009, de Filippo et al. 2011, Ansari Pour et al. 2013). On the basis of archaeological evidence, Seidensticker et al. (2021) have further questioned the description of the Bantu Expansion as a single macro-event (Vansina 1990, Wotzka 1995, Currie et al. 2013, Grollemund et al. 2015), proposing rather a spread-over-spread model whereby an “initial wave of putative Bantu-speaking Early Iron Age communities largely vanished from the entire Congo rainforest region by ~600 CE [...] The population decline was rapid between ~400 and 600 CE and then continued at a slower pace to eventually result in about 400 years of very limited sedentary activity

(~600 to 1000 CE) before a second wave of immigration and new settlements developed into the Late Iron Age” (pp. 6-7). Further evidence in support of a spread-over-spread explanation has been presented by Fortes-Lima et al. (2024), who claim that successive migrations replaced earlier settlers and their languages throughout the Bantu domain (see also Gunnink et al. 2022, Bostoen et al. 2023). All this body of evidence suggests that the distribution of present-day Bantu languages might be more indicative of multiple spreads than just one Bantu Expansion macro-event.

With specific reference to the Lower Kasai, recent evidence also suggests that the penetration of the rainforest may have occurred in successive waves. Linguistically, the genealogical validity of West-Coastal Bantu (to which the languages analysed in this dissertation predominantly belong) as a major subgroup of Bantu has been recently assessed by Pacchiarotti et al. (2019) and Pacchiarotti & Bostoen (2020) based on a wealth of literature dealing with sound change in the branch (Daeleman 1977, Rottland 1977, Koni Muluwa 2010: 117-161, Bostoen and Koni Muluwa 2011, Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020, 2021). All West-Coastal Bantu varieties share minimally one sound change, the so-called “Proto–West-Coastal Bantu velar merger”, whereby Proto-Bantu *k and *g both merged to *k in Proto–West-Coastal Bantu. In comparative terms, this is known as a “common innovation”, i.e., a diachronic change which is more likely to have originated in one common source (the proto-language) than in different varieties independently of each other. The putative West-Coastal Bantu homeland, previously situated between the Bateke Plateau and greater Bandundu (de Schryver et al. 2015, Bostoen et al. 2015), has also recently been identified by Pacchiarotti et al. (2019) in the wide swath of terrain between the Kamtsha and Kasai Rivers, i.e., a lot further east than previously supposed, in the Lower Kasai. On top of being the region of maximum internal differentiation within West-Coastal Bantu, the newly identified homeland area is a hot spot of phonological diversity unlike any other in the branch. Atypical phonological features transcend phylogenetic subgroups and include: umlaut (Bostoen & Koni Muluwa 2014), phonologically unconditioned final vowel loss (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2021), dorsal fricatives (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2022), heterosyllabic vowel sequences of mid and low vowels (Daeleman 1977, Rottland 1977, Bostoen & Mundeke 2011a,b), but also large vowel systems with up to 13 vowel phonemes including interior vowels (see above, &1.1.1.3; Ebalantshim Masuwan 1980, Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2019, Mfum-Ekong 1979) and labial-velar consonants (see above, §1.1.1.1; Khang Levy 1977, 1979, Crane et al. 2011, Mundeke 2011).

According to Vansina (1973/74), this high degree of internal diversity arose due to the relative isolation of these languages between the Congo Basin rainforest to the north and the savannahs to the south. With reference to the languages of southern Mai-Ndombe, Motingea (2009) interpreted their high degree of internal diversity as an indicator of population dynamics, pointing to possible migrations from areas further to the north; in his words, “the languages of the region around Lake Mai-Ndombe and those spoken in the Lukenye Basin are characterised by a high number of archaisms, Proto-Bantu retentions, and a set of traits reminiscent, at times, of the languages of south Cameroon. However, they present even more remarkable affinities with the languages spoken in the Bantu-Ubangi borderland” (p. 868; notably, the Bantu-Ubangi borderland is part of the Macro-Sudan Belt, see above). As a matter of fact, it is Motingea’s (2009) contention that population movements in the region, tied, as they were, to cultural and linguistic changes, only stopped due to European penetration around the year 1880 AD.

Another remarkable aspect of the Lower Kasai area is the widespread presence of hunter-gatherer “Pygmy” groups, collectively known as Twa (pl. Batwa) throughout most of the Congo Basin (Van Everbroeck 1961, Vansina 1966, 1991, Bahuchet 2006, 2012, Chabiron et al. 2013, Omasombo Tshonda 2019; see Map 2). These groups are generally referred to in the genetic literature as “Central African hunter-gatherers” (Padilla-Iglesias et al. 2022 and the literature cited therein). The interaction between Bantu-speaking newcomers and pre-existing local communities is at the centre of a

Map 2 - Hunter-gatherer groups in the Congo Basin rainforest (source: Bahuchet 2012)

long-standing debate. Genetic studies indicate a significant divergence between the ancestors of Central African hunter-gatherers and modern agriculturalists dating back approximately 60,000 to 70,000 years (Quintana-Murci et al. 2008, Patin et al. 2009, Batini et al. 2011). According to Padilla-Iglesias et al. (2022), the present-day distribution of hunter-gatherers in the Congo Basin rainforest reflects long-term ecological adaptation rather than a more recent Bantu Expansion, contrary to previous historical assumptions (Van der Kerken 1944: 349, 397, 400, Elshout 1963, Hulstaert 1972, 1984); it is their opinion that hunter-gatherer populations have remained stable or even increased during and since the expansion, indicating resilience and adaptability to environmental changes and human activities, as confirmed by the archaeological evidence: “the location of archaeological sites is not only determined by time-invariant geographic or topographic features but by how suitable such locations would have been for hosting hunter-gatherer populations at different points in time. [...] CAHG [Central African hunter-gatherers] have long been adapted to life in tropical environments, and expansions and contractions of suitable ranges have

influenced the demography of CAHG” (Padilla-Iglesias et al. 2022: 3). This means that, in their successive expansive waves, Bantu settlers would have encountered hunter-gatherer dwellers, though the exact dynamics and extent of their admixture remain unclear (Turbón et al. 2021, Lipson et al. 2022 and literature cited therein).

Linguistically, these communities have transitioned from their ancestral languages to those of migrant groups within the Congo Basin (Bahuchet 2012), with the majority now speaking Bantu languages generally referred to by a variety of exonyms such as “Lotwa” (see below, §1.1.2.3). The notion that certain Central African pre-Bantu groups might have shared common linguistic features before switching to the languages of the Bantu newcomers is corroborated by evidence of shared ancestral vocabulary among a few hunter-gatherer languages (in particular, Bantu Aka and Ubangi Baka; see Bahuchet 1993, 2006, 2012), pointing to a common linguistic substrate despite current diversity.

Within linguistics, phonetics and phonology have also contributed to the debate surrounding this alleged pre-Bantu substrate. This approach was modelled after similar lines of reasoning applied to Southern Bantu, where contact with pre-Bantu “Khoisan” hunter-gatherers is easier to reconstruct due, among other aspects, to the fact that a few pre-Bantu languages have survived to this day, and to the particularly salient presence of click sounds in several of the region’s languages (Bourquin 1951, Doke & Mofokeng 1957, Meeussen 1967, Seidel 2005, Güldemann & Stoneking 2008, Gunnink et al. 2015, Pakendorf et al. 2017). Given the nature of the influence Khoisan has exerted on Bantu in Southern Africa, Bostoen & Gunnink (2019: 17-18; see also Gunnink 2022) were able to describe the historical situation in which language contact took place as either one of borrowing, without language shift, or one of full-fledged language shift (Van Coetsem 1988, 2000, Winford 2005, 2007, 2013). The identification of similar “hallmark” features in the phonology of the languages of Central Africa has proved a lot more arduous. Efforts to find unique sounds in these languages have focussed on the presence of labial flaps (Trilles 1932, Olson & Hajek 2003), labial-velar stops (Schebesta 1949), and retroflex flaps (Vorbichler 1966/67, Motingea 2010). However, none of these phenomena appear to be unequivocally pre-Bantu, and they in fact do occur more frequently in non–hunter-gatherer than hunter-gatherer languages (Demolin & Teston 1997). As a consequence, Bostoen & Gunnink (2019) propose a different approach, centred around the examination of Bantu languages spoken by agriculturalist communities with significant genetic admixture with Twa

populations. They suggest that linguistic features that are unusual in the Bantu family, possibly reflecting Twa influence, may have been preserved in these languages due to the social and genetic integration of Twa individuals into Bantu-speaking societies. Ultimately, the two approaches need not mutually exclude each other. As presented above, the emergence of retroflexion, labial-velar stops, and other connected phenomena has also been described as an areal feature of the Macro-Sudan Belt. While labial-velar stops have not been reported in any Lower Kasai Lotwa varieties, flapping (connected to retroflexion) has been documented as a characteristic of multiple Lotwa lects, including those of the Lake Tumba area of the Équateur province of the Democratic Republic of Congo (Motingea 2010), part of the greater Equatorial Lakes zone which extends immediately to the north of the Lower Kasai and partly overlaps with this dissertation's study area. In this sense, different phenomena may be due to different contact scenarios, with the diffusion of labial-velar stops possibly bespeaking a later spread from northern speech groups into the region of interest, and the emergence of retroflexion indicating substrate from pre-Bantu languages (a shift-induced transfer of phonological traits of the kind described by Ross 2013).

The contributions presented in this thesis aim to describe these comparatively uncommon phonetic and phonological phenomena in the languages of the Lower Kasai that display them in their phonological inventories. Additionally, they aim to integrate insights about their synchronic typology with diachronic-phonological considerations, to appraise which of the two contact scenarios outlined above better matches the data. This is informed by the notion that speech sound distribution and frequency can shed light on the history of the area's languages, which in turn can broaden our understanding of the Lower Kasai's population history (see above, §1.1.2.1). This is of interest to linguistic typology proper, given the relative markedness of the features documented in the languages of the region, and to historical reconstruction, given the fact that the West-Coastal Bantu homeland has been recently identified precisely in the Lower Kasai and that some of these phonetic and phonological features (notably, labial-velar stops and interior vowels, but retroflex consonants too; Bhat 1973) have already been interpreted as areal markers indicating prehistoric language contact in other areas of Africa. While the contributions presented here do not offer new archaeological or genetic information, they do complement the available linguistic literature and show to what extent low-level phonetic research can contribute to the debate about the peopling dynamics of the region.

1.1.2.3 Study languages

This dissertation summarises the results of recent phonetic/phonological description and analysis on a group of Bantu varieties of the Lower Kasai, namely, Lwel, Ngwi, Sakata, North Boma, Nunu, Lotwa Lokonda, Lotwa Lolia, and Lotwa Losenge. These specific languages have been selected for two, key reasons: a) they are the ones in which the three phenomena of interest described in §1.1.1 are most widely documented – this is especially true of labial-velar stops and retroflexion, for which (respectively) Sakata and North Boma represent the most interesting cases in the region (with the former displaying the widest array of labial-velar stops of all the languages of the Lower Kasai and the latter the most abundant instances of retroflex consonants); b) they are the ones from which the most (and the most reliable) data are available to us, in terms of the acoustic quality of the available recordings and the extension of their lexical documentation in our datasets. An overview of the available literature on these varieties is presented below:

- Lwel (Bantu B862, glottocode [lwel1234] and ISO 639-3: [lwl]), also known as Kelwer, Kilori, is a West-Coastal Bantu language spoken in the Idiofa territory of the Kwilu province (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019), and in particular in the municipalities of Sedzo and Mateko (Boone 1973; the two varieties are reported to differ to a certain extent but no documentation is available for the Mateko lect). Along with Ding B86, Ngwi B861, and Nzadi B865, Lwel represents one of the first paraphyletic offshoots of West-Coastal Bantu; this means that Lwel does not share any more recent ancestor with any other West-Coastal Bantu variety than the one at the origin of the whole branch (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019). The available literature on Lwel is scant, with the first mentions of the language dating back to Maes (1934), Maes & Boone (1935), and subsequently Vansina (1966). More targeted studies can be found in Khang Levy (1979, 1986, 1987). More recent surveys of the area's languages that include Lwel can be found in Kalunga Mwela-Ubi (1999), Kadima et al. (2008), Bostoen & Koni Muluwa (2014), Koni Muluwa & Bostoen (2015). According to Eberhard et al. (2024), the vitality of Lwel is “stable” (this statement, along with the ones reported for

the other languages presented here, is, however, dubious: what we actually observe is that children are often raised in Lingala or Kongo ya Leta if their parents speak different languages and sometimes even if they speak the same language);

- Ngwi (Bantu B861, glottocode: [ngul1247] and ISO 639-3: [nlo]), also known as Engwíí, Ngwí, Ngul, Nguli, Ngoli, Kingoli, is a West-Coastal Bantu language spoken in the Idiofa territory of the Kwilu province (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019), and in particular in Mangai and Mateko, in close proximity to Lwel (Khang Levy 1979: X). As mentioned above, Ngwi, like Lwel, represents one of the first paraphyletic offshoots of West-Coastal Bantu. The available literature on Ngwi is somewhat more extensive than that on Lwel, with linguistic (Bwantsa-Kafungu 1966, Kumpel Wossey 1980, 2001, Kalunga-Mwela Ubi 1999, Mulumba 2008, Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2021) as well as socio-cultural information having been made available over the years (Nziem 1973, Alengila 1978, Katesi 1986, 1994a,b, Matangila Musadila & Lapika 2007). According to Eberhard et al. (2024), the vitality of Ngwi is “stable”;
- Sakata (Bantu C34, glottocode: [saka1287] and ISO 639-3: [skt]), also known as Kesaa, is a language cluster spoken in the Kutu territory of the Mai-Ndombe province. It displays a lot of regiolectal variation (some of its dialects include Kibayi, Kitere, Kinzinzale, Kingingele, Kingingia; the degree of mutual intelligibility among these different varieties is, however, quite high). Sakata has been alternatively classified as West-Coastal Bantu (Grollemund et al. 2015, Pacchiarotti et al. 2019) or Central-Western Bantu (Koile et al. 2022; the authors classify Sakata as Central-Western in the trees built exclusively on lexical material, and as West-Coastal Bantu in their phylogeographic ones, see Lemey et al. 2010). Sakata is one of the most important vehicular languages in the Kutu territory, as it is spoken in the territorial capital Kutu as well as in Nioki, the province’s unofficial economic capital (Omasombo Tshonda et al. 2019). Numerous sources mention the Sakata language and people, with early mentions in Fievez (1897) and Borms (1905) and the first full-fledged studies of Sakata as a unitary group presented in Baudhuin (1909, 1910), Viaene & Bernard (1909-1910), and Baeyens (1913). Grammar sketches of one or more Sakata varieties can be found in Sundberg (1930), Verdcourt (1935), de Witte (1955), Ikamba (1983, 1987), Matshan-Mamena (1984), and Intiomale Mbonino

(1986, 2018). Phonological information has been made available by Matabisi (1979), Ntuaremba (1986), Tylleskär (1987), and Bontenge (1995). According to Eberhard et al. (2024), the vitality of Sakata is “stable”;

- North Boma (Bantu B82, glottocode: [boma1251] and ISO 639-3: [boh]) is a West-Coastal Bantu language spoken in the Mushie territory of the Mai-Ndombe province. A lot of confusion is present in the literature surrounding the label “Boma”, as it has variously been used to refer to four different languages spoken in relatively close quarters north and south of the Kwa River; the denomination “North Boma” is used here in the sense of Pacchiarotti et al. (2019: 163ff). Along with Tiene (B81), Mpe (B821), and Nunu (B822), North Boma belongs to the Kwa-Kasai North subclade of Kwilu-Ngounie Extended (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019: 167). Early references to the language can be found in Vossius (1666), with subsequent mentions in Johnston (1884, 1908, 1919, 1922), Maes & Boone (1935), Verhulpen (1936), Tonnoir (1939, 1970), Sulzmann (1983) among others. The most comprehensive resource on North Boma grammar (including phonology) is Stappers (1986). According to Eberhard et al. (2024), the vitality of North Boma is “stable”;
- Nunu (Bantu B822, no glottocode or ISO 639-3 available) is a little-documented West-Coastal Bantu variety spoken around Letomo, in the Mushie territory of the Mai-Ndombe province and in the general area where North Boma is spoken. Along with North Boma, Nunu is part of the Kwa-Kasai North subclade of Kwilu-Ngounie Extended. Nunu is not reported in Guthrie (1948, 1953, 1970) and is first mentioned in Bastin et al. (1999) and subsequently in Maho (2009);
- The three Lotwa varieties reported in this venue have been the object of no linguistic description; they are identified as Lotwa Lokonda, Lotwa Losenge, and Lotwa Lolia based on the names of their supposed closest non-Twa Bantu relatives, respectively Lokonda, Lolendo (or Losenge), and Lolia. These are all Central-Western Bantu languages belonging to the so-called “Mongo” (Van der Kerken 1944) group, a proposed ethnolinguistic cluster assigned the alphanumeric code Bantu C60 by Guthrie (1970). As a matter of fact, Lokonda (glottocode: [ekon1238] and ISO 639-3: [lol], also known as Konda, Ekonda) is inventoried as C61E by Maho (2009) and Lolia (glottocode: [boli1255] and ISO 639-3: [bli], or Lalia, Bolia) as C62. No reference is made in either Eberhard et al. (2024) or Hammarström et al. (2014) to Lolendo, and the language is not

inventoried in Maho (2009); it is, however, mentioned in Motingea (2009: 868), who says that Lolendo ought to be “grouped with Lombole and the Nkutsu tongues of the Loβilaka-Tshuapa”, connecting it to what he considers to be a “fairly ancient Mongo population” (my translation). Hammarström et al. (2014) do list a variety they call “Batswa of Nkundo-Ntomba-Ekonda” which they assign the glottocode [bats1244], but it remains unclear whether this label refers to Lotwa Lokonda as reported in the present venue (see also Chabiron et al. 2013: 127-128).

1.2 Methods

1.2.1 Data collection

1.2.1.1 *Fieldwork*

Descriptive linguistics has received considerable impetus in recent years due, among other factors, to the rapid decline in the absolute number of languages spoken and signed in the world (McWhorter 2003, Whalen et al. 2020, Koffi 2021). Phonetic and phonological description, i.e., the collection, classification, and analysis of the sounds of a language (Bhaskararao 2004), is part and parcel of that endeavour. However, this specific aspect of language documentation has benefitted from comparatively little attention in the relevant literature (Whalen et al. 2020: 2). While part of this state of minority can be attributed to the long-standing debate over what is systemic versus what is epiphenomenal in language (Hockett 1958, Fant 1960, Chomsky & Halle 1968, Stevens 1971, Ohala 1971, 2005), with phonetics almost always treated as an ancillary discipline to linguistics proper, a lot of it is more simply due to the very structure of the fields involved. The experimental and quantitative drive that has marked phonetic inquiry since at least Öhman (1966) is not easy to reconcile with the intrinsically exploratory nature of primary documentation. The result of this is that there remains, to this day, little agreement as to what constitutes a minimal set of properties

that ought to be recorded and documented for the purposes of cross-linguistic comparability. In their survey of phonetic documentation across scientific publications in the field, Whalen et al. (2020) conclude that efforts to find wider consensus among phoneticians about the basic categories to document for successful sound analysis should not be spared in the future, but that, for the time being, a lot of variability can be found in data collection and analyses made available in the three main English-language outlets of phonetic descriptive research (the Journal of the International Phonetic Association, the Journal of Phonetics, and the body of research produced by Peter Ladefoged and colleagues within the framework of the NSF-funded “Sounds of the World’s Languages” project).

An attempt at providing overarching guidelines can be found in Chelliah & de Reuse (2011). The authors identify fieldwork as the main method of language documentation and description, and propose the following steps as the basics of phonetic and phonological fieldwork:

- Literature review (prior to fieldwork proper): this entails the collection of all available accounts, descriptions, recordings, and more generally attestations of the language/s one is interested in documenting (Ladefoged 2003, Gordon 2003). Having some idea of the language’s phonology prior to transcription can make the task of identifying the relevant units of speech easier (Gleason 1961);
- Organisation of the relevant word lists (prior to fieldwork proper): in their words, “The challenges of using word lists in phonetic work are: (1) to get the most natural pronunciation possible for acoustic analysis; (2) to record a number of words so that they are conveniently organised for instrumental analysis; and (3) to create data sets that position target sounds in a variety of phonetic environments” (p. 252). Words should be recorded both in isolation and with a carrier sentence and their order of presentation should be manipulated to minimise list intonation effects (Ladefoged 2003, Hildebrandt 2005);
- Consultant selection (in the field): consultants should be fluent speakers of the language, they should not exhibit any speech impediments, and they should not have hearing problems (Ballmer 1981). Older speakers are often suboptimal candidates as they tend to display less articulatory control than younger speakers, but they may be the only ones to retain specific phonological oppositions or sounds in cases of intense language change (Abbi 2001); in this sense, recording both younger and older speakers can paint a clearer picture

of the language's evolution across generations. Metadata spreadsheets should be kept and updated after each recording session. As for the number of speakers, phonological analysis generally requires fewer than does the study of sound-specific phonetic properties, as low-level phonetic details tend to vary more significantly from individual to individual (Ladefoged 2003, Gordon 2003, Hildebrandt 2007). Psychological aspects need be considered: excessive repetitions can tire the speaker and result in less natural speech samples, so that "the fieldworker might limit requests for repetition to three or four tokens. If a particular phoneme or allophone is problematic, this can be checked over a period of time rather than cramming questions into a single session" (p. 255; see also Healey 1964);

- Recording (in the field): the authors emphasise the importance of controlling the recording environment and using equipment that does not pick up background noise (p. 253). Following Austin (2006), they recommend using headphones to monitor what is being recorded, opting for a unidirectional microphone, using a microphone shield, moving the microphone as close to the speaker's mouth as possible without compromising recording quality, and restricting unnecessary movement of people and objects in the vicinity of the place where recording sessions take place;

Specific fieldwork (funded primarily through a Consolidator Grant, n°724275, of the European Research Council under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme granted to Prof. Dr. Bostoen) was carried out as part of my doctoral activities between May and July 2021. Fieldwork was conducted in Mai-Ndombe, within and immediately to the north of the Lower Kasai area. Linguistic data were collected by myself and Prof. Jean-Pierre Donzo (Institut Supérieur Pédagogique de la Gombe, Kinshasa) in Inongo (S 01° 55' 31.6", E 018° 16' 45.5"), Mai-Ndombe's provincial capital and most multilingual centre where a number of Lower Kasai languages are spoken by local residents coming from further south, and Nioki (S 02° 42' 51", E 017° 41' 57.7"), the province's unofficial economic capital as well as one of the most multilingual centres of the Mai-Ndombe sector of the Lower Kasai. The general aim of this fieldwork mission was to collect acoustic and lexical data from as many Mai-Ndombe varieties as possible, both hunter-gatherer Twa lects and settler Bantu tongues from inside and outside the Lower Kasai. Over 42 GB of video data were also collected, documenting traditional hunting dances, rituals, and calls of the

Batwa of the Mai-Ndombe forests. To the best of my knowledge, this is the first time that Mai-Ndombe Batwa receive video documentation. Additionally, genetic data (saliva samples) were also collected in the aforementioned townships and in the hunter-gatherer villages of Bobangi-Sept (S 1° 53' 59", E 18° 19' 0"), Douze (S 1° 51' 0", E 18° 21' 0"), Quinze (S 01° 50' 42.6", E 018° 21' 26.4"), and Bolingo-Trentesept (S 1° 48' 0", E 18° 25' 59"); see Map 3.

Map 3 - 2021 fieldwork mission locations

With reference to Chelliah & de Reuse's (2011) guidelines, fieldwork was organised as follows:

- Literature review: the available literature on the varieties of Mai-Ndombe (Omasombo Tshonda et al. 2019 and references cited therein; see also above, "Study languages") was reviewed; in the field, Prof. Donzo and I requested and obtained access to the academic libraries of the Instituts Supérieurs Pédagogiques of Inongo and Nioki. This allowed us to collect, scan, and analyse a wealth of literature unavailable to European academia (Tataa 1996,

Nkiere 1998, Bimy-Bienge Ngamokuba 2001, Kiekie Mayelebo 2016, among others);

- Organisation of the relevant word lists: lists of 800 lexical items were prepared in consultation with Prof. Donzo; these contained the Swadesh-100 basic vocabulary list. Speakers were shown the lists ahead of the recording sessions, so they could familiarise themselves with the dataset. No specific carrier sentences were used, as recording sessions were only partially directed by us fieldworkers, and consultants were allowed to expand on specific lexical items as they saw fit. The result is that words were often recorded both in isolation and in free connected speech. On top of word lists, morphological questionnaires were also prepared by Prof. Donzo, consisting primarily in longer sentences that the speakers were asked to translate from French into their languages. Thematic word lists for numerals, free connected speech (short stories), songs, and hunting calls were also recorded;
- Consultant selection: consultants were selected following the criteria presented above; older speakers were consulted when the specific demographics of the speech community at hand warranted it (e.g., no younger speakers were available). We managed to interview more than one speaker for larger linguistic groups such as Sakata and North Boma, but in most other cases we limited data collection to one speaker if no others could be found. A metadata spreadsheet containing information about speakers (name, surname, age, sex, origin, origin of the parents, languages spoken) and recording sessions (number of recording session, primary interviewer, microphones used, notes about the relevant environmental variables) was updated after each session (and is now made available in Appendix 2);
- Recording: sessions took place in relatively quiet environments with no echo discernible in the background. In Inongo and the Twa villages of the Inongo area, recording sessions took place outdoors, whereas in Nioki we had access to a relatively quiet space indoors (a room with rugged enough walls to minimise echo effects). Part of the data was recorded on Roland R-26 and Zoom H-5 devices with their built-in unidirectional microphones, and the rest on the same Roland R-26 device with an external plug-in omnidirectional microphone (Saramonic Lavalier Microphone SR-XLM1) clipped onto the speakers' clothes (sideways from the mouth). The sampling rate was kept at 44.1 kHz; maximum

input, whenever verifiable, was set at 75% to minimise clipping; depth was set at 24 bits. Audio files were consistently named as follows: spe_IN_20210530_LOC_01 (speaker, investigator, date, location, and serial number to disambiguate otherwise identical filenames);

Over 137 GB of audio data were collected with speakers of nineteen different varieties, as shown below, Table 1; of these, 84 GB have been transcribed.

Table 1 - Languages documented in 2021

LANGUAGES	DOCUMENTED IN	SPOKEN IN	NUMBER OF CONSULTANTS	TYPE OF DATA
SAKATA (MBANTIN)	Inongo	Kutu territory	1	word lists
SAKATA (MBAMUSHIE)	Inongo	Kutu territory	1	word lists, sentences, free connected speech
SAKATA (KIBAYI)	Nioki	Kutu territory	1	word lists, sentences, free connected speech
SAKATA (KINZINZALE)	Nioki	Kutu territory	1	word lists, sentences, free connected speech
SAKATA (KINGINGIA)	Nioki	Kutu territory	1	word lists, sentences, free connected speech
SAKATA (KINGINGELE)	Nioki	Kutu territory	1	word lists, sentences, free connected speech
SAKATA (KITERE)	Nioki	Kutu territory	1	word lists, sentences, free connected speech
NUNU (BOBANGI)	Inongo	Yumbi territory, Bolobo territory	7	word lists, sentences
NTOMBA	Inongo	Inongo territory	1	word lists
SENGELE	Inongo	Inongo territory	1	word lists
LENDO	Inongo	Oshwe territory	1	word lists, sentences
MPE	Nioki	Mushie territory	1	word lists, sentences, free connected speech
NORTH BOMA	Nioki	Mushie territory	3	word lists, sentences, free connected speech
NUNU	Nioki	Mushie territory	1	word lists, sentences, free connected speech
TIENE	Nioki	Mushie territory	1	word lists, sentences, free connected speech
LOTWA (LOLIA)	Inongo	Inongo territory	1	word lists
LOTWA (LONTOMBA)	Inongo, Quinze (15 km NE of Inongo)	Inongo territory	N/A (the people of Quinze took part collectively)	word lists, songs
LOTWA (LOKONDA)	Inongo	Kiri territory	3	word lists, free connected speech, songs
LOTWA (LOSENGE)	Inongo	Oshwe territory	N/A (group of people took part collectively)	free connected speech, songs, word lists, sentences

Not all chapters presented in this thesis deal with data collected within the framework of this fieldwork mission. Data for the articles presented in Chapters 2 and 7 were collected by co-authors Koen Bostoën and Sara Pacchiarotti in August – September 2019 in Idiofa (Kwilu province, S 4° 96' 59", E 19° 59' 15") during a fieldwork mission within the framework of the BantuFirst project (<https://www.bantufirst.ugent.be/>). Roughly one fifth of the data used in Chapter 5 were collected by co-authors Jean-Pierre Donzo, Sara Pacchiarotti, and Koen Bostoën in Kinshasa in August 2022. Aerodynamic data presented in Chapter 6 were collected by Véronique Delvaux (co-author) and myself in Mons (Hainaut, Belgium) in March 2023 (see below, §1.2.1.2).

1.2.1.2 Laboratory studies

Most of the data analysed in the contributions presented in this thesis were collected in the field, between 2019 and 2022; however, aerodynamic data collection for Chapter 4 was conducted in a laboratory setting. Aerodynamic data collection is the collection of data relative to airflow and pressure in the vocal tract, and is particularly indicated, among other circumstances, in cases of double articulations (such as labial-velar stops) where the acoustic trace does not always allow for detailed analysis of the relative timing of the two closures and releases; as Demolin (2011: 1) puts it: “this technique allows for the induction of articulatory movements in the vocal tract with great precision. Acoustic cues and features may also be deduced on changes of flow and pressure in the vocal tract. Despite the fact that measuring intraoral pressure can be invasive at times, this is one of the most reliable and powerful techniques phoneticians have to understand the behaviour and the production of speech sounds”. The data presented in Chapter 4 were collected at the phonetics laboratory of the University of Mons in March 2023 with three Sakata speakers, all residents of Belgium at the time of data collection. Aerodynamic and acoustic traces were taken jointly with the PCquirer (Scicon) data acquisition system. The audio signal was digitised and sampled at 12 kHz. Oral pressure measurements were obtained with a catheter introduced at the side of the speakers’ mouth, bent behind the rear molars, and connected to a pressure transducer. The volume flow of air from the mouth was collected simultaneously with

a Rothenberg mask, using one of the outlet holes in the mask for the pressure tube. The pressure and airflow signals were low-pass filtered at 50 Hz. Figures 4 illustrates laboratory data collection for the research presented in Chapter 4.

Figure 4 - Aerodynamic data collection with one of the three Sakata speakers who collaborated on the study presented in Chapter 4

445,8 MB of data were collected, including audio, mouth pressure traces, and oral airflow traces; nasal airflow data were collected but have not been analysed for the study presented in Chapter 4.

1.2.2 Archiving and publishing

As for storage and backup, I followed the LOCKSS (“Lots Of Copies Keep Stuff Safe”) principle popularised by the “LOCKSS Program” at Stanford University

(<https://www.lockss.org/about>). Data were stored physically on a personal external drive and on another one currently deposited at the African Studies Department of Ghent University, and online on the BantUGent shared drive (online domain of Ghent University).

Data used in specific articles (for Chapters 2-6) were made public on the Online Science Foundation's platform (OSF) and stored in Europe (Germany). Information about the data used for the specific articles can be found at the following links:

- Chapter 2: <https://osf.io/wbaq5/>; all relevant audio files (labial-velar stops in Lwel) have been made available;
- Chapter 3: https://osf.io/vz8ne/?view_only=7c1ef734f17e45a4ae3848439ee6313d; all relevant audio files (labial-velar stops and fricatives in Kibayi, Kitere, Kingingia, Kingingele, and Kinzinzale) have been made available along with a spreadsheet summarising the entire Sakata labial-velar dataset;
- Chapter 4: https://osf.io/cdfk8/?view_only=%201bd311ad49cd4125a64c4c0913fb6658; the dataset (aerodynamic and duration values associated with labial-velar oral stops in Kingingia and Kimbantín) and statistical procedure used in the article have been made available;
- Chapter 5: https://osf.io/cmezd/?view_only=a0465124c79a4782bad819a830d21f0e; all data (.zip), datasets, and information relative to the statistical procedure used in the article have been made available along with the individual audio files associated with the specific figures used as illustrations in the prose;
- Chapter 6: https://osf.io/hs85b/?view_only=8c1b5e1ab3e541bb8e8d6be45e8648b3; audio files associated with the specific figures presented in the article have been made available along with the relevant TextGrids.
- Appendix 1: https://osf.io/fxdmb/?view_only=204483df54704ed3969361e578b25f02; audio files and .eaf documents associated with the comparative Lotwa lexicon presented in the appendix.

1.2.3 Data analysis

1.2.3.1 Phonetics

Phonetic data analysis was conducted in two successive steps, i.e., phonetic transcription and signal analysis. Statistical analysis was performed for the studies presented in Chapters 3 and 4. Statistical analysis was also conducted in two successive steps, i.e., descriptive and inferential (exploratory) statistics; for the latter, different methods were adopted in Chapter 3 and in Chapter 4. I will break down these different components as follows:

- Phonetic transcription: high-quality transcription is essential and requires training on the part of the fieldworker, who ought to familiarise themselves with the typology and variation of the sounds they intend to transcribe (Redden 1982, Ladefoged 2005a,b). Different levels of transcription, ranging from more phonological or "broad" to strictly phonetic or "narrow", can be adopted depending on the degree of documentation of the language (Laver 1994). For the purposes of the data presented in Chapters 2-7 and in Appendix 1, transcription was carried out manually on Praat (Boersma 2001; all varieties documented) and ELAN (Lausberg & Sloetjes 2009; Lotwa data). Narrow phonetic transcription was preferred (Lotwa), though a broader, phonological transcription style was adopted in the case of most non-labial-velar-containing lexical items in Sakata. This disparity was due to the fact that the Sakata data transcribed for the purposes of acoustic analysis were limited to recordings of lexical items containing labial-velar stops (see Chapters 2 and 3), while Lotwa transcriptions were carried out to provide a more general lexical database that could be used in future research for both lexical comparison and lower-level phonetic analysis;
- Signal analysis: based on the transcriptions and segmentations operated during the phonetic transcription phase of phonetic data analysis, acoustic (Chapters 2-6) and aerodynamic (Chapter 4) traces were first inspected manually to provide preliminary spectral descriptions (see Catford 1977, Johnson 2012), then all relevant variables were extracted from Praat by dint of

specially written scripts for further statistical processing (Chapter 3, 4, and 7). The specific variables to extract were chosen based on the available literature on the different sounds analysed in each contribution, but minimally included duration values (i.e., the duration in ms of the individual segments and words) and formant values (for vowels and sonorants, including F1-4 values as well as bandwidth values for F1-4 and whole sounds); other values include oral airflow and pressure (Chapter 3; see Demolin & Teston 1996, Demolin & Soquet 1999, Demolin 2011) and spectral moments (Chapter 4; see Li et al. 2009, Tabain et al. 2016, 2020). Chapter 7 constitutes an exception in that no spectral analysis is provided of the segments at hand but formant values of Ngwi vowels are extracted from Praat;

- Descriptive statistics: the relevant datasets extracted from Praat were handled in RStudio and Microsoft Excel to provide summaries of the values. Typically, bar graphs of duration and formant values are presented. Scatter-plots are presented in Chapter 4 (oral airflow and pressure values) and 7 (formant values);
- Inferential statistics: Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA; Tabachnick et al. 2013) was used in Chapter 4. MANOVA is a statistical tool used to analyse the differences in the mean vectors of two or more groups, considering multiple dependent variables simultaneously. Unlike Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), which examines one dependent variable, MANOVA assesses the impact of one or more independent variables on a set of two or more dependent variables, allowing for the investigation of complex patterns in multivariate data and the control of Type I error rate when testing multiple hypotheses. This technique is particularly useful in studies where dependent variables are likely to be correlated and the effect of independent variables on the entire set of dependent variables is of interest. MANOVA was utilised to explore the effects of “segment type” (the independent variable in the dataset presented in Chapter 4) on the multiple dependent quantitative variables extracted from Praat. These variables were categorised into three groups, i.e., “duration values”, “oral airflow”, and “mouth pressure”, and MANOVAs were run on two datasets with different “segment type” and dependent variable compositions. Due to the multidimensional nature of the “duration values” group, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA; see Jolliffe & Cadima 2016) was performed to reduce

dimensionality and extract meaningful patterns from the data. PCA is a statistical tool used for dimensionality reduction, which simplifies complexity in high-dimensional data while retaining trends and patterns. PCA transforms the original variables of a dataset into principal components, which are orthogonal (uncorrelated) and maximise the variance. The first principal component accounts for the largest possible variance, with each subsequent component having the highest variance possible under the constraint that it is orthogonal to the preceding components. This method is widely used in exploratory data analysis and in making predictive models, enabling visualisation of the structure of the data and identifying underlying relationships between variables. As for Chapter 5, Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA; see Abdi & Valentin 2007, Abdi et al. 2013) was used to substantiate differences between retroflex and non-retroflex segments in North Boma. MFA is a statistical tool used to analyse datasets where multiple sets of variables are observed on the same set of individuals. It extends PCA to accommodate more than one group of variables, allowing for the examination and comparison of the structure of these groups. MFA works by performing PCA on each group of variables to standardise variance and then combines these groups into one global analysis, summarising inter-group similarities and differences. This technique is particularly useful in studies that involve multidimensional data, enabling researchers to explore relationships between sets of variables and to identify underlying patterns across different types of data.

1.2.3.2 Diachronic phonology

Diachronic-phonological analysis was performed in three successive steps, i.e., lexical transcription, comparative reconstruction, and study of phonetic grounding. I will break down these different components as follows:

- Lexical transcription: extensive word lists were transcribed manually, preferring “broader” phonological transcriptions (except in cases in which higher levels of phonetic detail were required by the nature of the study, in which cases the “phonetic transcription” phase of phonetic data analysis and the “lexical

transcription” phase of diachronic-phonological analysis often coincided). Transcriptions were performed largely by ear and were checked by more than one co-author for each individual contribution to minimise the effect of individual biases on their overall reliability. Whenever possible, transcriptions were also checked against previous reports in the literature (this was, for example, the case of North Boma, where words already reported in Stappers 1986 were explicitly elicited to verify specific phonetic claims by the author). Lexical datasets were produced in Microsoft Excel;

- Comparative reconstruction: cognacy judgments (see §1.1.2.1 for general remarks on the comparative method) were performed on the lexical items summarised in the relevant datasets produced after lexical transcription. Lexical data collected in the field was contrasted with the available Bantu lexical reconstruction set (Bastin et al. 1999) to investigate in what phonological contexts retroflexes, interior vowels, and labial-velar stops emerged in the languages of interest. More extensive applications of the comparative method are presented in Chapters 5 (nasal retroflexes in North Boma) and 7 (interior vowels, as well as heterosyllabic vowel sequences, in Ngwi). Smaller-scale case studies are presented in Chapters 2 (labial-velar stops in Lwel), 3 (labial-velar stops and fricatives in Sakata), and 6 (rhotics in Sakata, North Boma, Nunu, and Lotwa);
- Study of phonetic grounding: the directionality of sound change was evaluated, among other principles, with reference to Dispersion Theory (Liljencrants & Lindblom 1972), a model of vowel system analysis that emphasises the role of perception and predicts that natural languages tend to maximise the acoustic space (dispersion) between the individual vowel phonemes constituting their inventories (this model was applied to the Ngwi case in Chapter 7), while notions from Articulatory Phonology (Browman & Goldstein 1992, Goldstein et al. 2006), a theory of phonological production and representation that identifies functional “gestures” (articulatory targets in speech production) as the atomic

unit of phonological analysis, were used to explain specific aspects of Kingingele affricates as labial-velar free variants in Chapter 3.

1.3 Structure of the thesis

Six relevant articles, written between 2020 and 2024 and currently at various stages of publication (information is provided in the prose) are presented here as individual chapters, followed by a general conclusion and two appendices, one containing a comparative lexicon of four Lotwa varieties, and another presenting the metadata spreadsheet for the Mai-Ndombe fieldwork mission described in §1.2.1.1. These articles are presented in a way that deviates from strict chronological order, rather favouring thematic groups in line with the first three research questions reported in §1 (concerning the typology and diachrony of labial-velar stops, retroflex consonants, and interior vowels). In the following, I provide details about each individual section of this thesis:

- Chapter 2: “Labial-velar stops outside the Macro-Sudan Belt: New evidence from Lwel (West-Coastal Bantu, B862)” – My specific contribution lies in the phonetic annotation and spectrographic analysis of Lwel labial-velar stops. I co-presented an introduction to labial-velar consonants (typology, historical phonology) and I discussed their realisation in Lwel. Sara Pacchiarotti and Koen Bostoën collected the relevant data, supervised the research, and contributed to the writing of the main text including the conclusions;
- Chapter 3: “Labial-velar stops in Sakata (Bantu C34): a preliminary phonetic and diachronic phonological account” – I collected the relevant data with co-author Jean-Pierre Donzo, annotated them, provided a spectrographic analysis of labial-velar consonants in Sakata, and discussed the emergence of affricates as substitutes of labial-velar articulations in Kingingele from an articulatory-phonological perspective. Véronique Delvaux, Sara Pacchiarotti, and Koen Bostoën supervised and contributed to the writing of the main text including the conclusions;
- Chapter 4: “Aerodynamics of central Sakata labial-velars” – I collected the relevant data with co-author Véronique Delvaux and annotated them. I provided

preliminary descriptive statistics of the realisation of labial-velar stops in Central Sakata. Véronique Delvaux wrote the script used to extract the relevant values from Praat;

- Chapter 5: “Nasal retroflexes in North Boma (Bantu B82, Mai-Ndombe, Democratic Republic of Congo)” – I collected the relevant data with Jean-Pierre Donzo (except for the data collected by Sara Pacchiarotti and Koen Bostoen in 2022) and annotated them. I provided a spectrographic analysis of nasal retroflexes in North Boma, presented preliminary descriptive statistics, and produced Multiple Factor Analysis maps for the corpus (balanced for duration and spectral moments). Sara Pacchiarotti wrote the section on the historical phonology of nasal retroflexes. Véronique Delvaux helped with the interpretation of the phonetic data and produced the script used to extract the relevant values from Praat. Koen Bostoen supervised the research and contributed to the writing of the main text including the conclusions;
- Chapter 6: “Phonetic and phonological research in the Mai-Ndombe: a few preliminary notes on rhotics and double-articulations” – I collected the relevant data with Jean-Pierre Donzo and annotated them. I provided a preliminary comparative phonological analysis of rhotics and retroflex flaps in the Mai-Ndombe and summarised the main findings reported in Chapter 3;
- Chapter 7: “The emergence of interior vowels and heterosyllabic vowel sequences in Ngwi (Bantu B861, Democratic Republic of Congo)” – Sara Pacchiarotti is the first and main author of this contribution and wrote the main text of the article. My specific contribution lies in the plotting of the vowel space of Ngwi for F1 and F2 values and in the discussion of interior vowel emergence in Ngwi from a Dispersion Theory perspective. Koen Bostoen collected the relevant data together with Sara Pacchiarotti, supervised the research, and contributed to the writing of the main text including the conclusions;
- Conclusions (and a general discussion of the points mentioned in this introduction with reference to the new evidence collected and analysed in Chapters 2-7) are presented in Chapter 8;

- References for all contributions (including this introduction) are presented after the conclusions;
- Appendix 1: Comparative Lotwa lexicon – I collected the relevant data with Jean-Pierre Donzo, transcribed them, and annotated them with ELAN and Praat. These are made public here for the first time in all available formats;
- Appendix 2: Metadata spreadsheet (fieldwork mission to Mai-Ndombe, 2021) – I updated and edited the spreadsheet after each recording session in the field. The resulting document contains all the relevant information about the speakers with whom we worked in the field as well as the recording sessions.

Chapter 2: Labial-velar stops outside the Macro-Sudan Belt – New evidence from Lwel (West-Coastal Bantu, B862)

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Abstract

The Congo Basin rainforest is among the least well-documented linguistic regions in the world. This means that our current understanding of Central African languages presents important research gaps. This is especially true for phonetics, as sound-specific explorations and data collection in the area remain marginal activities within language documentation. This paper offers new phonetic evidence for the presence of labial-velar stops in Lwel (West-Coastal Bantu, B862), a language spoken along the Kasai River in the Kwilu province of the Democratic Republic of Congo. The presence of labial-velar stops in Lwel calls into question their definition as a distinctive areal feature of the so-called Macro-Sudan Belt in northern sub-Saharan Africa. Moreover, Lwel displays an unusual voicing pattern, seemingly at odds with the long-established notion that voiced labial-velar stops are cross-linguistically favoured over their voiceless counterparts. We tentatively propose that substrate influence from now-extinct pre-Bantu forest languages may have contributed to shaping the unusual phonology of Lwel and several other languages spoken in the West-Coastal Bantu homeland area.

Keywords: labial-velar stops, Bantu phonetics, historical phonology, language contact, substrate interference

2.1 Introduction

Labial-velar stops are doubly articulated sounds (see, e.g., Ladefoged 1968a,b, Ponelis 1974, Ohala & Lorentz 1977, Maddieson 1993, Connell 1994, Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996, Ladefoged 2003) produced with simultaneous occlusions at different points of the oral cavity, one around the velum and one in the labial area. These occlusions are released almost simultaneously, but the velar release always seems to occur first (see Painter 1978, Connell 1987, 1991a,b, 1994, Dogil 1988, Maddieson & Ladefoged 1989, Cahill & Hajek 2001, Cahill 2018: 154). Worldwide, labial-velar stops are most common in Africa, especially /kp/ and /gb/ (Cahill 2008, Maddieson 2011). They occur in three of the four main African language phyla, i.e., Afro-Asiatic, Nilo-Saharan, and Niger-Congo, more specifically in the following branches: Chadic (Afro-Asiatic), Moru-Mangbetu, Bongo-Bagirmi, Nilotic (Nilo-Saharan), Adamawa-Ubangi, Benue-Congo, Kwa, Gur, Atlantic, Mande, Ijoid, and Kru (Niger-Congo; Clements & Rialland 2008, Güldemann 2008). Several phonetically oriented accounts of their historical development have been proposed (Ponelis 1974, Zima 1985, Kelly 1974, 1988, Connell 1991a, 1994, 1995, 1998/9, Demolin 1995, Goldstein 1995, Hyman 2011). Labial-velar stops are generally considered the result of a temporal compression phenomenon (Ponelis 1974, Connell 1998/9: 19), whereby $KuV/K\bar{u}V > KwV > KPV$ (where $K = /k/$ and $/g/$, $P = /p/$ and $/b/$, and $V =$ a vowel other than u/\bar{u}). As a matter of fact, in western Congo the sound shifts $C_{[+voice]}wV > gbV$ and $C_{[-voice]}wV > kpV$ are attested in several rainforest Bantu zone C languages spoken between the Congo and Ubangi Rivers (Bostoen & Donzo 2013). An alternative hypothesis suggests that labial-velar stops might have originated from labial velarisation, as in the Cameroonian Grassfields Bantu language Aghem (see Hyman 1979, Cahill 2018: 156-157). Whatever the case might be, this sound change seems to have affected different areas of the continent to different extents.

Within Africa, labial-velar stops are seen as a distinctive feature of the so-called “Macro-Sudan Belt”, a stretch of land spanning contiguously from the western end of the landmass to the Ethiopian escarpment in the east (Clements & Rialland 2008, Güldemann 2008, 2018: 479-486).² This linguistic macroarea in northern sub-Saharan

² As an anonymous reviewer points out, labial-velar stops are at best weak indicators of the Macro-Sudan Belt. As Hyman (2011) puts it: “This fact [i.e., that labial-velar spread is still ongoing], as well as

Africa would have been “shaped by geographical conditions that were fairly stable over a long time span” (Güldemann 2008: 183). As a result, shared linguistic features in this huge zone would be the outcome of shared geography rather than shared genealogy. As for Bantu, labial-velar stops have not been reconstructed to the family’s putative most recent common ancestor (Meeussen 1967). Their presence in some parts of the Bantu-speaking area has been claimed to be contact-induced through intensive interaction with languages from the Macro-Sudan Belt, such as Adamawa-Ubangi languages spoken north of the Congo River (cf. Bostoen & Donzo 2013, Cahill 2018: 156). However, the social-historical dynamics underpinning this transfer have been left mostly undocumented (Dimmendaal 1995, 2001: 377, Grégoire 2003). Labial-velar stops have mainly been reported in languages of the northern Bantu borderland, i.e., in Guthrie’s “zones A, C, and D spoken in the equatorial forest and Congo Basin from the Atlantic in the west to Lake Albert in the east” (Clements & Rialland 2008: 43). The distribution of labial-velar stops in Bantu does not form a continuity zone, but rather a west-east axis where languages with a high concentration of labial-velar stops in their lexicon alternate with languages without such phonemes in a patchwork-like fashion (Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021).

Given that labial-velar stops are considered to be a typical feature of the Macro-Sudan Belt, and of the northern Bantu borderland in particular, it is remarkable that they have also been reported in several languages of Guthrie’s B80 group, such as Tiene B81 (Ellington 1977: 28), Nsong B85d (Dibata Mimpya 1979: 14), Mpur B85e (Kibwenge India’Ane 1985: 39-40), Nsambaan B85F (Katona Makani 2017: 16), Ding B86 (Mula 1977: 7; Munkyen Okab 1990: 208), Ngwi B861 (Nsumuki 1993: 12), Lwel B862 (Khang Levy 1977: 20, 1979: 4), Nzadi B865 (Crane et al. 2011: 21) and Mbuun B87 (Mundeke 2011: 29). All these languages are spoken to the south of the Congo Basin rainforest and are therefore entirely disconnected from the northern Bantu borderland. While northern Bantu languages are thought to have acquired labial-velar stops from languages spoken in the Ubangi Basin hotbed (Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021), the B80 languages listed above are situated hundreds of kilometres to its south, on the southern periphery of the rainforest. Specifically, they are located at the

the fact that these sounds are found in only half of the languages of the MSB [Macro-Sudan Belt], suggests that the presence or absence of labialvelars [*sic*] will not be very useful for the purpose of reconstructing remote protolanguages”. See Cahill (2008: 383) for an overview of the use of labial-velar consonants in protolanguage reconstructions across the world’s language families and Cahill (2017) for a critical take on the diagnostic value of labial-velars to delimit linguistic areas.

southern end of the so-called “Sangha River Interval”, a natural corridor that might have facilitated the migration of Bantu-speaking peoples through the forest some 2500 years ago (Bostoen et al. 2015, Grollemund et al. 2015). B80 languages may descend from the language/s spoken by the first Bantu speech communities settling south of the equatorial rainforest (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019).

All B80 languages reported to display labial-velar stops belong to West-Coastal Bantu, also known as West-Western Bantu, a major discrete clade within the Bantu phylogeny (de Schryver et al. 2015, Grollemund et al. 2015, Pacchiarotti et al. 2019), in which labial-velar stops are otherwise uncommon. Moreover, Guthrie’s B80 group is the most heterogeneous within West-Coastal Bantu, at least in terms of basic vocabulary. As shown in Map 4, these varieties are spoken within and around the putative West-Coastal Bantu homeland, i.e., between the Kamtsha and Kasai Rivers southeast of Bandundu City in the present-day Kwilu province of the Democratic Republic of Congo (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019: 157). This is the area of highest diversity within West-Coastal Bantu, with several of the aforementioned B80 languages belonging to distinct, major West-Coastal Bantu subclades that converge there.

Several factors may explain why large-scale surveys of sounds in African languages have not reported labial-velar stops in this specific area of the Bantu domain. To this day, several parts of the Democratic Republic of Congo, including its southern outskirts and the border with Angola, remain among the least well-documented linguistic regions of the world (Hammarström 2016). This suggests that our current understanding of Central African languages is influenced by significant research gaps, affecting both synchronic typology and historical linguistics. It is pertinent to mention what Clements & Rialland (2008) note about their list of Bantu A, C and D languages displaying labial-velar stops in their phonological inventories:

“This list is very likely incomplete, as information for most languages in the area is sparse. The Bantu languages in this broad zone are (or presumably have been in the not distant past) in contact with other Sudanic languages having labial-velar stops: southern Bantoid languages in the west, Adamawa-Ubangi languages in the center, and Central Sudanic languages in the east” (p. 44)

As a matter of fact, Clements & Rialland (2008) do not list any Bantu B languages spoken south of Lake Mai-Ndombe in the Democratic Republic of Congo. This is not surprising considering that: a) the sources describing these languages are generally difficult to access; b) labial-velar stops are often a marginal phenomenon in the languages in question, occurring in only a few lexemes; c) the presence of labial-velar stops in these languages is not well established, either phonologically or phonetically; d) while certain sources on a given language report them, others do not. With respect to this last point, for instance, Dibata Mimpya (1979: 14) reports /kp/ and /gb/ in Nsong B85d but Koni Muluwa & Bostoen (2019: 416) do not. For Ding B86, Mula (1977: 7) reports /kp/ and Munkyen Okab (1990: 208) /kp/, /ŋkp/, and /ŋgb/,³ but Mertens (1938: 14) and Mwan Mesongolo (1984: 17) do not list any of these phonemes. It is not clear whether these disparities are to be ascribed to regiolectal variation, differences in documentation methods, or simply divergent analyses of similar data. In other words, the presence and behaviour of labial-velar stops in the West-Coastal Bantu languages of Guthrie's B80 group are still shrouded in doubt.

In an attempt to start resolving this uncertainty, we offer here a preliminary phonetic and phonological assessment of labial-velar stops in Lwel B862. Based on the grammar sketch by Khang Levy (1979), the second and last authors recorded words containing these sounds in August 2019 in Idiofa (Kwilu province, S 4° 96' 589", E 19° 59' 151") during a fieldwork mission within the framework of BantuFirst (<https://www.bantufirst.ugent.be/>). Unfortunately, they could only elicit reliable data from one male native speaker, Mazola Kalakwan Yolo, a 62-year-old civil servant originally from Sedzo who has lived in Idiofa since the 1980s. Mazola Kalakwan Yolo speaks Lwel in informal contexts with relatives and friends, along with Kikongo ya Leta, Lingala, and French as languages of wider communication.

Lwel is a West-Coastal Bantu language spoken in and around the collectivities of Sedzo (S 4° 04' 187", E 19° 17' 769") and Mateko (S 4° 9' 1", E 19° 5' 23"), in the Idiofa territory of the Kwilu province of the Democratic Republic of Congo (Khang Levy 1979: XI). Like other languages with a Guthrie alphanumeric code of B85 and higher (Guthrie 1971, Maho 2009), Lwel is spoken west of the Loange River, south of the Kasai River and east of the Wamba River and of the lower course of the Kwango River

³ See Cahill (2018: 158-159) and the references cited therein for the problem of labial-velar nasal assimilation.

north of its confluence with the Wamba (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019: 189); see Map 4. Phylogenetically, Lwel is, together with Ding (B86), Ngwi (B861), and Nzadi (B865), part of the paraphyly that is sister to the rest of West-Coastal Bantu. These four languages do not share any more recent common ancestor with each other or with any other West-Coastal Bantu languages than the one at the origin of the entire branch (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019: 189-190). The specific variety of Lwel described in this study is spoken around Sedzo (indicated by a red arrow in Map 4) and has been documented by Khang Levy (1977, 1979). Pacchiarotti et al. (2019) refer to it as East Lwel B862X to differentiate it from the western variety spoken around Mateko (see map in Boone 1973 and Khang Levy 1979: X based on Boone 1973: 244). As far as we know, the western variety of Lwel is still undocumented. Lwel (no ISO code assigned as of 2021, see Map 4) is not inventoried in Eberhard et al. 2021. Glottolog 4.4 does include it and categorises it as not endangered (Hammarström et al. 2021). The limited sociolinguistic data we collected in Idiofa in 2019 suggest that Lwel is indeed not endangered, as there are still fluent speakers ranging in age from 20 to 70 years. However, the transmission of Lwel to newer generations appears uncertain, particularly in cases of mixed marriages. In the area where Lwel is spoken, children born of parents speaking different West-Coastal Bantu varieties are often raised in the main vehicular languages, namely Lingala and/or Kikongo ya Leta.

This article is structured as follows. In §2.2, we provide a concise phonetic description of labial-velar stops in Lwel pending a full-fledged acoustic and articulatory analysis for which our current data are insufficient. In §2.3, we consider labial-velar stops in Lwel from the broader perspective of phonological typology and historical linguistics. We conclude in §2.4 by reasserting the necessity for further data collection in the region, as it is only through the analysis of all relevant variables that the exact nature of these sounds and their relevance for historical research can be satisfactorily ascertained.

⁴ The absence of an ISO code next to a language name in Map 4 indicates that the variety does not have one. ISO codes next to language names in Map 1 were obtained from the Glottolog 4.4 (Hammarström et al. 2021). For a discussion of confusion and problems around language names, alphanumeric codes (Guthrie 1971, Maho 2009), and ISO codes for some of the varieties in Map 4, see Pacchiarotti et al. (2019: 163-174).

2.2 Labial-velar stops in Lwel and their realisations

The dissertations by Khang Levy (1977, 1979) are the only descriptive studies of Lwel available to us. In these works, labial-velar stops /kp/ and /gb/ are listed as part of the language's consonantal inventory, reported in Table 2.

Table 2 - Lwel consonant phonemes

	BILABIALS	LABIODENTALS	ALVEOLARS	PALATALS	VELARS	LABIAL-VELARS
ORAL STOPS	p / b		t / d		k	kp / gb
NASALS	m		n	ɲ	ŋ	
FRICATIVES		f / v	s / z			
AFFRICATES		pf / bv				
LATERALS			l			
TRILLS			r			
APPROXIMANTS				j		w

Labial-velar stops are reported in the words in (1) and (2) respectively, to which we added the notation of low tones and noun prefixes where missing. If a word can be considered as a reflex of a specific Bantu Lexical Reconstruction (BLR) (Bastin et al. 2002), we have also added that etymon for further historical considerations below.

(1) /kp/ in Lwel (Khang Levy 1977, 1979)

ò-kpé (cl. 15)	'to die'	*kú	(BLR 2089)
Ø-kpé (cl. 5/6)	'death'	*kúà	(BLR 2069)
kè-kpé (cl. 7/8)	'yam, potato'	*kùá	(BLR 1968)
ṅ-kpé (cl. 3/4)	'salt'	*gúá	(BLR 1521)
ì-kpé (cl. 19)	'a bit of salt'	*gúá	(BLR 1521)

kpè?	‘how much?’ *kua ⁵
kpé	‘despite’

As can be seen in (2), all instances of /gb/ inventoried by Khang Levy (1977, 1979) are prenasalised and the nouns in which they are found are reported as belonging to noun class pairing 9/10. We therefore mark the initial nasal as a noun class prefix, even though it might be synchronically analysable as part of the stem.

(2) /gb/ in Lwel (Khang Levy 1977, 1979)

ḡ-gbú	(cl. 9/10)	‘your mother’	*gúkù ⁶
ḡ-gbáán	(cl. 9/10)	‘his/her mother’	*gúkù + *andɪ ‘his, her’ ⁷
ḡ-gbè	(cl. 9/10)	‘back (body part)’	
ḡ-gbèl	(cl. 9/10)	‘pork’	*gùdú (BLR 1493)

Our recordings (freely available on OSF: <https://osf.io/wbaq5/>) were specifically made to ascertain the occurrence of labial-velar stops in examples (1) and (2) and to assess the potential need for further sound-specific phonetic research in the region. Based on approximately two hours of elicited data, we can unequivocally confirm only the presence of the voiceless /kp/. This sound is observable in the spectrogram in Figure 5 for ḡkpé ‘salt’ (from sound file nekpa.kp_labvel.1.0819_171630_1.666,49366,105.wav on OSF; dynamic range: 50 dB), where one can notice a cross-frequency concentration of energy most likely associated with the bilabial burst of /kp/, corresponding to the more salient of the two closures (Cahill

⁵ This reconstruction is not present in BLR 3 (Bastin et al. 2002). However, the question word kwa is widespread in the Kikongo Language Cluster, a discrete branch of West-Coastal Bantu (de Schryver et al. 2015; Pacchiarotti et al. 2019) and seems cognate to Lwel kpè suggesting that *kua could be reconstructed to Proto–West-Coastal Bantu.

⁶ This specific reconstruction is not found in BLR 3 (Bastin et al. 2002). However, it is present in several West-Coastal Bantu languages and could go as far back as Proto–West-Coastal Bantu. It is not only recurrent in the Kwilu-Ngounie branch of West-Coastal Bantu, but it is also attested in paraphyletic languages at the top of the West-Coastal Bantu tree, such as Ding B86, i.e., in nywa (Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2015), and Lwel B862. Based on reflexes like Laali B73b ngúhò (Bissila 1991) and Kukwa B77a ngúkù (Paulian 1975), we propose a CVCV reconstruction with a prenasalised *g in C₁ (the nasal being a cl 9/10 prefix) and Proto–West-Coastal Bantu *k in C₂, which is the merged reflex of Proto-Bantu *k and *g (when not preceded by a nasal; Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020).

⁷ Guthrie (1970: 141, 151) lists *-nde ‘him, her’ (C.S 509) and *ndi ‘him, her’ (C.S 549) as two proto-items whose reflexes are commonly attested in possessive stems. Kamba Muzenga (2003: 256) reconstructs the form *ɪ/i-ndɪ-e for a 3SG possessive stem of class 1, which is widespread in Western Bantu. We believe it to originate in, or at least to be related to, the root *ndɪ ‘other’ (BLR 942 with attested reflexes in zones F and J; Bastin et al. 2002).

2018: 152). In the spectrogram in Figure 5, the burst (energy concentration circled in red) is preceded by a few milliseconds of prevoicing and a steep F2 rise into the following vowel.⁸

Figure 5 - [kp] in Lwel

The presence of /kp/ was also confirmed in the words in (3).

- (3) Recorded instances of /kp/ in Lwel (BantuFirst fieldwork 2019)
- | | | |
|---------------------|------------------------------------|-----------------|
| ɲè-kpé | ‘salt’ | *gúá (BLR 1521) |
| ò-kpé | ‘die’ | *kú (BLR 2089) |
| ɲ-kpé (maybe ɲ-gbé) | ‘person who eats after the others’ | |

On the other hand, the existence of /gb/ is not unequivocal based on the available data. As shown in (4), the sound reported as /gb/ in Khang Levy (1979) has alternative realisations across repetitions: /gb/ can sound as [kp], as a plain voiced bilabial plosive [b] or as a bilabial voiced implosive [ɓ].

⁸ As Connell (1994: 459) argues about burst spectra: “[...] the energy in the spectrum at release appears primarily in two areas in the lower frequency range, i.e., below 1.2 kHz, and in the midrange, from 24 kHz. The lower concentration could indeed be a reflection of a labial release, and this would not be unexpected [...]; on the other hand the lower end of this energy concentration is almost certainly to be associated with the strong prevoicing of the release. [...] on occasion there was energy present throughout the spectrum, extending quite high in the frequency range.” See Ladefoged (1968a: 12-13) and Cahill (2018: 153) for a more detailed discussion of the spectral qualities of labial-velar stops in general.

(1) Possible recorded instances of /gb/ in Lwel (BantuFirst fieldwork 2019)

- | | | |
|---------------------|---------------|-----------------|
| gbé (/kpé) | ‘how much’ | *kɯa |
| kè-gbà (/bà/bà/kpà) | ‘yam; potato’ | *kùá (BLR 1968) |

Instances of the voiced labial-velar stop /gb/ are harder to identify than their voiceless counterparts for two related reasons. Acoustically, they tend to display less spectrally salient cues to the velar or labial release, as can be seen in Figure 6 for kègbà ‘yam, potato’ (from the sound file gba.gb_labvel.9.0819_181438_1.5,8606,251.wav on OSF; dynamic range: 50 dB).

Figure 6 - [gb] in Lwel

The rather blurry left edge of the spectrogram for gbà ‘yam, potato’ clearly displays the abrupt start of the vowel (stricken through in red) but shows neither a clear concentration of energy across frequencies nor a visible transition signalling the presence of a consonant; additionally, F2 does not exhibit the typical steep rise into the following vowel which we would expect in the presence of a labial-velar stop. Auditorily, the spectral blurriness of the left edge makes voiced labial-velar stops sound more like sonorants than stops.⁹ These observations suggest that the original

⁹ This is chiefly due to the fact that stops are typically associated with sharp left edges, while [+ continuous] sounds, such as sonorants, are not. This may also explain why geminate/singleton

voicing contrast between /kp/ and /gb/ in Lwel was (/is being) reorganised, making it hard to classify /gb/ as a fully (doubly articulated) stop; in other words, /kp/ behaves more like a stop and /gb/ behaves less like one.

Articulatory factors may also contribute to the apparent difficulty in identifying voiced labial-velar stops in Lwel. As is generally the case for labial-velar stops, even in languages that tend to prefer [± spread glottis] over [± voice] as a correlate for voicing (see Iverson & Salmons 2007 for further references on laryngeal realism), aspiration does not seem to play a relevant role in teasing /kp/ and /gb/ apart. This is in line with what we know about labial-velar stops in Bantu, as they do not typically display voicing oppositions based on aspiration (Cahill 2008: 389; however, see Mathangwane 1996 for an account of aspirated doubly-articulated stops in Kalanga S16, Zimbabwe).¹⁰ It is well known that labial-velar stops tend to deploy both ingressive and egressive airstream mechanisms (Ladefoged 1968a,b, Mills 1984, Vogler 1987, Demolin 1991, Connell 1995, Cahill 2008, among others). It is also known that ingressive airstreams make stops behave more like implosives than plain consonants (Simpson 2007). In turn, the necessary ingressive airstream for the production of an implosive is most commonly associated with a lowering of the larynx, in itself a glottalisation phenomenon. Since the most common setting in moving downwards is for the glottis not to be completely closed, the glottalic ingressive airstream is frequently combined with a pulmonic egressive one, resulting in the production of voicing, which is why implosives are typically voiced (see Ladefoged 1968a: 6, Catford 1977: 75, McLaughlin 2005, Demolin & Vuillermet 2006). Consequently, an ingressive airstream mechanism might introduce some degree of glottalisation in the production of Lwel labial-velar stops, where not disfavoured by the phonological specification [– voice] on the voiceless stop /kp/.¹¹ This observation does not necessarily mean that voiced

asymmetries in the world's languages tend to favour realisation of the contrast on stops rather than sonorants (Kawahara & Pangilinan 2017; Lorin & Maselli et al. 2020).

¹⁰ Following Mathangwane (1996), these sounds are not labial-velar stops as we have described them, but rather double articulations in which the release of the labial occlusion comes first; they are therefore transcribed as /bg/ and /pk^h/. No explanation is given about the airstream mechanisms deployed when producing these sounds. Similar sounds are also reported by Poneis (1974) for Zezuru S12, but voicing is unspecified in the author's account.

¹¹ As an anonymous reviewer points out, the ingressive nature of the airstream mechanism at play here should affect both voiceless and voiced labial-velar stops, as is generally the case in the world's languages. However, this does not seem to be the case in Lwel, or at least not to the extent one would expect. Since categorical specifications can influence the (scalar) phonetic realisation of a sound (see e.g. Flemming 2001), it seems reasonable to hypothesise that /kp/, unlike /gb/, is somehow "prevented" from becoming an implosive-like sound. While we have not approached this problem from the viewpoint

labial-velar stops should be classified as full implosives; rather, phonetically, they do not act as true voiced (doubly articulated) stops. Following Ladefoged (1973: 78), glottalisation phenomena might best be described as gradual (scalar) variations along a continuum, with ingressive elements playing a significant role (weakly implosive - strongly implosive).

2.3 Lwel labial-velar stops from a typological and historical perspective

The labial-velar voicing contrast in Lwel is blurred. While realisations of voiceless /kp/ display some salient spectral features, such as the presence of a clear concentration of energy associated with the burst (see Fig. 5), those of its voiced counterpart /gb/ tend to behave more like sonorants (see Fig. 6), much like implosives do (Kaye 1981, Clements 2000, Botma 2011).¹² As such, the contrast might be lost altogether. This is in line with the cross-linguistic preference for segmental contrasts to be licensed and maintained where they are most perceptible, i.e., where more perceptual cues to the contrast are available at the segments' edges (Flemming 1995, 1996, Steriade 1997, Lorin & Maselli et al. 2020).

At the same time, a pattern where /kp/ is clearly present but the existence of /gb/ is dubious is at odds with the typology of labial-velar stops in world's languages. Phonological inventories with phonemic labial-velar stops tend to have both /kp/ and /gb/. If only one of the two labial-velar stops is attested, it is usually /gb/. This is phonetically motivated by the fact that /kp/ is already partly in the "voiced camp" (Cahill 2008). This is because labial-velar stops often deploy an ingressive airstream mechanism in addition to the pulmonic egressive one, so that their voicing opposition is seldom (if ever) based on [\pm spread glottis]. Additionally, they tend to display some negative VOT even when they are phonologically voiceless (see also Ohala 1979). A preference for /gb/ is documented across various language groups worldwide. For

of Optimality Theory, we suppose that an adequate constraint ranking might shed some light on the issue.

¹² In particular, Botma (2011: 19) argues: "labialvelars are sometimes produced with an ingressive airstream mechanism [...]. This makes them similar to implosives, which frequently pattern as sonorants".

instance, in Senufo (Niger-Congo, North Ivory Coast) *kp and *gb merged into /gb/ (Garber 1987); in North Mande (disputably Niger-Congo, throughout West Africa) *gb evolved into /b/ and *kp into /gb/ (Long 1971); in Ono (Trans-New Guinea, Huon peninsula) *kp and *gb merged into /gb/ (Phinnemore 1985). Cahill (2008) reports similar mergers elsewhere in the Pacific, e.g., in Vanuatu. The few languages that favour /kp/ over /gb/ tend to have other phonological gaps in their sound systems (Cahill 2008). This is certainly the case for West-Coastal Bantu. Due to the merger of Proto-Bantu *k and *g into /k/ at the Proto–West-Coastal Bantu level (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020), all West-Coastal Bantu languages lack /g/, except postnasally.

This apparent eccentricity raises the point of whether substrate interference played any role in shaping the phonology of the languages at hand. To this day, a number of hunter-gatherer relic groups still live scattered in small pockets across the Congo Basin rainforest. These communities, often referred to as “Pygmies” – a term not devoid of pejorative connotations, but which lacks a widely accepted alternative¹³ –, are generally believed to be the descendants of the region’s first modern human inhabitants. These people have a distinct ethnic identity and way of life, which usually focusses on hunting and gathering or, less commonly, on a craft, such as potmaking or blacksmithing (Schebesta 1952, Seitz 1970, Biebuyck 1973, Joiris 1994, 1996, Hewlett 1996, 2014, Mukwiza Ndahinda 2011). Linguistically, however, these groups are assumed to have abandoned, in times unknown to history, their ancestral languages for one of those of the many newcomer groups (Bahuchet 2012). Many hypotheses have been formulated regarding the possible influence of a “Pygmy” substrate on Bantu languages. However, any suchlike influence can only be observed indirectly, as no original pre-Bantu hunter-gatherer languages have survived the ravages of time in Central Africa. This situation is different from the one found in Southern Africa, where several present-day Bantu languages manifest traces of past exchanges with severely endangered, but still extant, “Khoisan” languages (Herbert 1990, Güldemann & Stoneking 2008, Bostoen & Sands 2012, Gunnink 2015, Pakendorf et al. 2017). In Central Africa, the quest for traces of ancient hunter-gatherer languages has mainly focussed on lexical data (Bahuchet 1993, 2006, 2012), but there

¹³ Some of these hunter-gatherer communities, and in particular those closest to the Lwel area, are also known as “Batwa”. This term is an exonym, which Bantu speakers across the continent commonly use to refer to what they consider to be autochthonous groups, not only in Central Africa, but also in Southern Africa (Schadeberg 1999). Just like “Pygmy/Pygmies”, “Twa” is not entirely devoid of negative connotations (Lewis 2006, Woodburn 1997).

might be phonetic/phonological leads worth pursuing. As suggested in Pacchiarotti & Bostoen (2020: 152, 162-166), the fortition of Proto-Bantu *g to /k/ and its merger with the pre-existing Proto-Bantu *k in Proto–West-Coastal Bantu could indicate the presence of a substrate reflecting the articulatory habits of ancestral speaker populations, because this velar merger happened both in C₂ and C₁ position, while there is a strong statistical universal for phonological neutralisation to target word ends over beginnings (Wedel et al. 2019). Though highly speculative, this hypothesis was already advanced by Möhlig (1981: 270), cited in Pacchiarotti & Bostoen (2020: 26), who referred to this putative ancestral substrate as a “Rain-Forest Pre-Bantu stratum”:

“In most of the Forest languages, the sound shift *g → [– voice] (g → k) did not cause merger between *g and *k, because, at the time when *g became *k, the original *k had already shifted via the intermediate stages of [x] and [h] towards complete deletion. So, the sound shift *g → [– voice] re-introduced a sound which had previously disappeared in the phonological systems concerned. Such reversion of an inherent trend of sound shift (elimination of a voiceless velar plosive) generally indicates that language shift between nonrelated or only loosely related languages must have taken place”.

While Möhlig (1981) mistakenly assumes that the devoicing of *g did not cause the velar merger in the first place (see Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020), his hypothesis that the merger itself, possibly along with the numerous, unusual vowel systems reported in the region, might betray substrate interference from no longer extant “forest” languages retains its appeal. As shown in this article, Lwel also exhibits a similar devoicing tendency with labial-velar stops.

In the search for phonological and morphosyntactic indicators of possible substrate influence from extinct autochthonous hunter-gatherer languages, the Bantu languages spoken in the West-Coastal Bantu homeland area may prove particularly promising. These languages display features that are atypical from a “typical” Bantu point of view: rare vowel harmonies, umlaut effects, final vowel loss, systems of 9+ vowels, fusion of verb suffixes producing abnormal verbal bases and rare polysemies such as causative/applicative syncretism, absence of passive morphology, etc. (Daeleman

1977, Rottland 1977, Bostoen & Mundeke 2011a, b, Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2011, 2012, Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2021, 2022). Substrate influence from non-Bantu languages is certainly a factor to be considered when trying to account for the development of the distinctive linguistic profile of these languages, which are relatively isolated in the transition zone between the equatorial rainforest and the southern savannas (in the ecoregion known as the southern Congolian forest-savanna mosaic; see White 1983). If the merger of Proto-Bantu *k and *g in Proto–West-Coastal Bantu is indeed diagnostic of a “Rain Forest Pre-Bantu stratum”, the impact of autochthonous hunter-gatherer languages on West-Coastal Bantu may be as old as the first Bantu speech communities south of the forest. Furthermore, if the presence of velar and uvular fricatives as reflexes of Proto–West-Coastal Bantu *k is also the result of substrate interference, as Pacchiarotti & Bostoen (2022) moot, linguistic interaction with local hunter-gatherer communities in the West-Coastal Bantu homeland area may have happened repeatedly at distinct stages in the region’s past.

As discussed in §2.1, Lwel is not an isolated instance of a language with labial-velar stops south of the west-east demarcation line of labial-velar stop frequency. In the Lower Kasai region, several languages near the West-Coastal Bantu homeland exhibit labial-velar stops as free variants of velar stop + labial-velar glide sequences, in line with the general historical evolution pattern of labial-velar stops (see §2.1). For instance, in certain varieties of Ngwi B861, /kw/ has [kp] as a free variant (see Nsumuki 1993: 12 as opposed to the idelect of Frédéric Empenge Itobola living in Idiofa, the main Ngwi consultant of the BantuFirst project team which displays /kw/). In the Idiofa variety of Mbuun B87, [gb] and [kp] are reported as free variants of /gw/ and /kw/ respectively (Mundeke 2011: 29). As the Bantu reconstructions linked to Lwel words containing labial-velar stops in (1) suggest, /kp/ in Lwel may also have originated as a sequence of *k/*g followed by the labial-velar glide *w, the reflex of either *u or *ɔ when followed by another vowel.¹⁴

As mentioned in §2.1, the presence of labial-velar stops in the Bantu languages of the northern Democratic Republic of Congo has been ascribed to long-lasting exchanges (and a high degree of admixture) with speakers of Ubangi languages on

¹⁴ As shown in (2), however, this is less straightforward for /(n)gb/, which seems to be a reflex of *gu preceded by a homorganic nasal but with no vowel following.

both sides of the Ubangi River (Bostoen & Donzo 2013).¹⁵ This far south, the presence of labial-velar stops cannot be attributed to Ubangi interference or be seen as a geographic feature of the Macro-Sudan Belt. In a recent study on the lexical distribution of labial-velar stops in northern sub-Saharan Africa, Idiatov & Van de Velde (2021) claim that the presence of these sounds in Niger-Congo and Central-Sudanic languages is attributable to shift-induced substrate interference from now extinct languages. As for West-Coastal Bantu, Idiatov & Van de Velde (2021: 100-101) argue that labial-velar stops in this Bantu branch were brought by speakers of ancestral North-Western Bantu A80 and A90 languages already having labial-velar stops as the result of substrate interference. These groups are thought to have migrated southwards into the rainforest, subsequently adopting one or more West-Coastal Bantu languages. While this hypothesis seems plausible, we believe it is also possible that West-Coastal Bantu varieties currently found in the homeland area developed labial-velar stops via independent contact with autochthonous hunter-gatherers present in the area at some point in history. Given the absence of labial-velar stops in many lower-node West-Coastal Bantu subgroups (e.g., the KLC), this contact is likely to have occurred in the Lower Kasai region after the initial dispersal of West-Coastal Bantu speakers from their homeland area.

Further documentation and dedicated studies are necessary to make sense of the phonological inventory of West-Coastal Bantu varieties. For example, the possibility that Lwel /gb/ exhibits some degree of implosivity might call for a more comprehensive review of similarly glottalised sounds in the area. Their presence in the wider region is not entirely atypical (Clements & Rialland 2008) and has been recently reported in Gyeli (A801), a Bantu language spoken by hunter-gatherers in southern Cameroon (Grimm 2019). What is more, the role of glottalised sounds as free variants or phonetic manifestations of labial-velar stops remains unexplored in languages reported to exhibit both /kp/ and /gb/. The question is whether an implosive-like realisation of /gb/ could further point in the direction of a merger of /kp/ and /gb/, or rather signal a general reorganisation of voicing (a)symmetries in the Lwel phonological inventory. However, phonetic analyses of implosives in the southern Congo Basin are exceedingly scarce,

¹⁵ A similar contact-based account is reported by Andreas et al. (2009: 25) for Nyam, Chadic, spoken in Nigeria. This explanation should not be taken as an alternative to the phonetically grounded account outlined in §2.1, whereby Ku/ɔV > KwV > KPv. Contact patterns may have played a role in spreading this sound change, which is not always regular in every language with labial-velar stops (e.g., it is not in Lwel), see Cahill (2018: 156).

the one notable exception being Nagano-Madsen & Thornell (2012) for Mpiemo (A86c).¹⁶

2.4 Conclusions

In this paper, we have shown that labial-velar stops are part of the phonological inventory of Lwel B862. This calls into question the earlier areal definition of these sounds as a distinctive feature of the Macro-Sudan Belt in northern Sub-Saharan Africa (Clements & Rialland 2008, Güldemann 2008, 2018). Lwel exhibits an uncommon crosslinguistic pattern for labial-velar stops, where voiceless /kp/ is favoured over voiced /gb/. This situation could evolve into a merger of /kp/ and /gb/ into /kp/ (a merger which, cross-linguistically, tends to favour /gb/), or a neutralisation, with /kp/ being the only labial-velar stop in the language and /gb/ being realised as either a regular plosive or an implosive, given the well-attested tendency for labial-velar stops to be produced with an at least partly ingressive airstream mechanism. In support of the neutralisation scenario, our preliminary exploration of the data collected in 2019 indeed suggests that some degree of glottalisation may be detected on some of the allegedly voiced labial-velar stops in Lwel. While more data are needed to make any further claims, this possibility makes Lwel and other West-Coastal Bantu languages with labial-velar stops a valuable case study for both historical phonology and phonetic typology.

Of course, the hypotheses presented in this contribution require further phonetic evidence from the Lower Kasai. We still know very little about the phonetic characteristics of the languages of the southern Congo Basin. This underscores their significant potential for linguistic research. For one thing, cross-linguistically rare sounds are often found in underdescribed languages, and this is particularly true in Africa (Miyaoaka 2001, Bhaskararao 2004, Maddieson 2018). What is more, some of these sounds seem to correlate strongly with several environmental variables. For instance, the distribution of implosives in the world's languages seems to be linked to

¹⁶ An anonymous reviewer suggests it would be worthwhile to investigate whether bilabial implosives are found in cognate forms of neighbouring languages. The reviewer reports that such an alternation is found in Igbo, where some dialects have a labial-velar stop corresponding to velarised implosive bilabial stops in others.

their proximity to the equator. This outstanding relation has been neglected in the literature compared to other linguistic variables (Axelsen & Manrubia 2014, Gavin & Stepp 2014). Phonetic research in this area could shed light both on the diachrony of language change and contact in Africa and on linguistic evolution in broader terms. Additionally, it could help us better integrate phonetic knowledge and linguistic typology in a very poorly studied area of the world. The result will be a clearer picture of a region that is all too often underrepresented in cross-linguistic surveys.

Chapter 3: Labial-velar stops in Sakata (Bantu C34) – A preliminary phonetic and diachronic phonological account

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Abstract

The present contribution bears on the documentation and description of double labial-velar articulations in a few varieties of Sakata (Bantu C34) spoken in southwestern Democratic Republic of Congo. These phonemes, often considered typical of a linguistic area known as the Macro-Sudan Belt, are considerably more common in southern Central Africa than previously thought. The case of Sakata is particularly interesting due to the wide array of labial-velar articulations its varieties present. First, we provide a spectral analysis of the available data and discuss whether some of the sounds documented here should be described as labial-velar fricatives. Second, we review well-established models of sound change to test them against the newly collected data, with special focus on the Kingingele variety. We conclude by proposing that the presence of labial-velar stops in Sakata is part of a broader set of atypical (in Bantu) features present in this specific area. This might indicate that this region once hosted great linguistic diversity of which Sakata labial-velar stops may be one phonological trace.

Keywords: phonetic documentation, articulatory phonology, Bantu languages, acoustics, sound change

3.1 Introduction

This article is a preliminary phonetic and diachronic phonological study of newly collected fieldwork data on labial-velar consonants in a poorly known cluster of closely related Bantu language varieties from the Lower Kasai region in the Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo, known as “Sakata” (Bantu C34).

Labial-velar consonants, such as those transcribed as <kp> and <gb>¹⁷ in the International Phonetic Alphabet, are doubly articulated sounds produced with simultaneous occlusions at the lips and at the velum (see Connell 1994, Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996, and references cited therein). These closures are released almost simultaneously, but the velar release always seems to occur first (see Painter 1978, Connell 1987, 1991a,b, 1994, Dogil 1988, Maddieson & Ladefoged 1989, Cahill & Hajek 2001, Cahill 2018: 154). Instances of alleged labial-velar articulations with reversed release precedence in Kalanga S16, Zimbabwe, are reported in Mathangwane (1996); see also Ponelis (1974) for Zezuru S12 and Maddieson & Sands (2019: 92ff) for a counterargument; see Maselli et al. (2021: 10ff) for a more comprehensive review.

The presence of labial-velar stops in the phonological inventory of Sakata is striking for several reasons. First, labial-velar stops are rare in the world’s languages, occurring in but 45 of the 567 languages present in Maddieson’s (2018) sample (i.e., 8% of the total). Cahill (2008) reports that over 700 languages exhibit labial-velar stops, i.e., approximately 10% of the world’s ~7000 languages (7151 according to the Ethnologue; Eberhard et al. 2022). The PHOIBLE repository of cross-linguistic phonological inventory data (Moran & McCloy 2019) reports 373 languages with /kp/ and 374 with /gb/ (around 12% of their total). However, their distribution is far from even across linguistic families. According to Cahill’s (2017) updated database of 848 languages with phonemic labial-velar stops, only 66 (8%) of these are spoken outside Africa (mostly in Papua-New Guinea, Oceania, South America). Within Africa, virtually all are from West Africa and northern Central Africa, i.e., north of the Congo Basin rainforest. This is far to the north of the area where Sakata is spoken.

¹⁷ Doubly articulated sounds are better transcribed with an overarching tie bar (k[̄]p, g[̄]b, ŋ[̄]m). However, as no (timing) oppositions between double articulations and clusters of individually articulated consonants are discussed in this paper, they will be consistently transcribed without a tie bar (kp, gb, ŋm) for practicality reasons.

Second, in terms of historical development, some scholars have interpreted the peculiar distribution of labial-velar stops as an areal feature – though possibly one with little diagnostic power (see Hyman 2011, Cahill 2017) – typical of an alleged macro-area known as the Macro-Sudan Belt, a stretch of land extending contiguously from the western end of the African landmass to the Ethiopian escarpment in the east (Clements & Rialland 2008; Güdemann 2008, 2018: 479-486, Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021). This linguistic macro-area would have been “shaped by geographical conditions that were fairly stable over a long time span” (Güdemann 2008: 183). As a result, shared linguistic features in this zone would be the outcome of geography rather than genealogy. Labial-velar stops have not been reconstructed to the Bantu family’s putative most recent common ancestor (Meeussen 1967). Therefore, their presence in some parts of the Bantu-speaking area, especially in between the Congo and Ubangi Rivers, has been claimed to be contact-induced (see Bostoen & Donzo 2013; Cahill 2018: 156), but the exact socio-historical dynamics underpinning this transfer are still a matter of debate (Dimmendaal 1995, 2001: 377; Grégoire 2003). Their presence in Sakata, so far to the south of the major hot spots of labial-velar stops in Africa, is all the more remarkable, though not entirely unprecedented. As a matter of fact, these sounds also occur in other languages of the Lower Kasai area, most of which belong to Guthrie’s Bantu B80 group (see Maselli et al. 2021: 3 for a recent overview); see Map 5. What is more, Sakata stands out amongst these other Bantu languages on the southern margin of the Congo rainforest: besides exhibiting the voiced/voiceless labial-velar oral stop pair /gb/ and /kp/ in its phonological inventory, as do the aforementioned Lower Kasai languages, it also has the labial-velar nasal stop /ŋm/.

Given the documentation state of Sakata labial-velar stops in recent surveys of these sounds which include languages of the Democratic Republic of Congo (Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021), we deemed it useful to present this exploratory phonetic and diachronic-phonological study based on new fieldwork data. In section 3.2, we discuss the Sakata language and people. In section 3.3, we present the methodology and process of data collection. In section 3.4, we provide as complete a spectrographic description of Sakata labial-velar stops as possible, despite some important biases, notably the limited number of consultants, the scarcity of the available data, and the lack of balance in our small corpus. In spite of these issues, the present contribution represents the first phonetically grounded report and analysis of labial-velar stops in

this severely under-documented area of the African continent, arguably one of the least well-surveyed linguistic areas of the planet (Hammarström 2016). In section 3.5, we offer a few articulatory-phonological considerations on affricates as a substitute for labial-velar stops in Kingingele, showing how a theoretical model that has proved useful in explaining the emergence of labial-velar stops in other languages falls short of its goal in the case of this particular variety. In section 3.6, we set forth some historical considerations on the diagnostic power of labial-velar stops as a tool to reconstruct the heterogeneous linguistic past of the Lower Kasai region. Conclusions are in section 3.7.

3.2 Sakata people and language

The word “Sakata”¹⁸ or “Saa” designates a people from the Lower Kasai area of the Democratic Republic of Congo. “Sakata”, ISO 639-3 [skt], is also the most commonly used glossonym to refer to the Bantu varieties spoken by the Sakata people (see van Bulck 1940, de Witte 1955, Matabisi 1979, Intiomale Mbonino 1986, Ikamba 1987, Mundeke 1994). In the referential classification of Bantu languages provided by Guthrie (1971), the language is inventoried with the alphanumeric code C34. In the Bantu phylogeny of Grollemund et al. (2015), Sakata is part of the West-Western clade, also known as West-Coastal Bantu (see Pacchiarotti et al. 2019). Interestingly, in the phylogeographic analysis of the Bantu family presented in Koile et al. (2022), Sakata is assigned to the same clade, i.e., what they identify as clade 5 (Njebe-Mbete-Teke), in the trees built solely on lexical material. However, in trees combining lexical and geographical data, Sakata is reclassified into their clade 9 (Kela-Ntomba), which is part of Central-Western Bantu. This might corroborate origin traditions pointing to a relatively recent migration into the region.

According to Vansina (1965: 129), the Sakata are part of a broader cultural and linguistic group known as Boma-Sakata which also includes South-Nunu B822, (North) Boma B82, (Boma) Nku B80x, and Mpe B821 on the one hand, and the Sakata

¹⁸ The prefixed form “Basakata”, plural for “Sakata person”, is how Sakata people refer to themselves in all the Sakata varieties reviewed in this article. In this article, we refer to both the people and their language as “Sakata”.

varieties known as Saa (Sakata proper), Dza (Dia), Tow, Bai (Bayi), Tere (Eastern Saa) on the other. Similarly, Omasombo Tshonda et al. (2019) view the Sakata people as being most closely related to the Teke, Boma, and Tiene communities of Mai-Ndombe. Omasombo Tshonda et al. (2019) situate their origins further north, in the Ubangi region:

“The Sakata, to whom one might associate the Dia, the Tere and the Tow, came from the Ubangi region. They subsequently advanced along the Congo River down to Kwamouth before taking the Kasai upstream, in relatively ancient times. The migrations of the Sakata would have reached the Mfimi and Lower Lukenye around the 11th or 12th century CE. Their march would have been stopped by the advance of the Mongo” [114; our translation from the French original].

Van der Kerken (1944: 240-241) also traces their origin outside the Lower Kasai region, further west. According to him, the Sakata would have migrated in different waves, the first dating back to the 11th-12th century CE and the last to the 16th-17th century CE. He therefore considers them to be, in his words, a “complex”. This tallies with how Van Bulck (1948: 474) classifies the Sakata people, i.e., within what he calls “Western Bantu”, more specifically the so-called “Old Bantu” (i.e., “Vieux-Bantous”), or peoples with distinctive languages and origin traditions that can be traced back west of the Congo Basin. He clusters Sakata in a “Lake Leopold II” (today “Lake Mai-Ndombe”) subgroup together with other communities such as the Boma, Mpe, Nunu, and Tiene. Motingea (2009: 868) also considers the languages of the Sakata and Boma as the most ancient layers of western Bantu in the area which managed to preserve their cultural and linguistic autonomy in the face of external pressure from neighbouring groups.

In sum, according to the existing literature, the label “Sakata” seems to encompass considerable cultural and linguistic diversity. Based on our own fieldwork experience, Sakata is best understood as a continuum of closely related varieties spanning most of the southern borderland of the Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo, between the Mfimi and Kasai Rivers, and further north, around the southernmost tip of Lake Mai-Ndombe, i.e., over a large portion of the Kutu territory (see Map 5) of the Mai-Ndombe province. According to the speakers, different Sakata varieties are largely mutually intelligible. Our consultants never referred to each other

as speakers of different languages but rather as Sakata speakers from different regiolectal areas. Even speakers from certain peripheral Sakata varieties, such as the Dia, Bayi, and Tere on the right bank of the Mfimi and Lukenye Rivers, often considered to be culturally and linguistically distinct from “core” Sakata (see Vansina 1965), still identify as Sakata. However, perceived shared ethnic affiliation may lead to an underestimation of actual linguistic heterogeneity and time depth of language divergence (see, for example, Bostoen & de Schryver 2018 with reference to the Kikongo Language Cluster further west).

Map 5 – Location of the six Sakata language varieties (adapted from Bokwankon Bosonkie 1997) and neighbouring languages mentioned in Chapter 3¹⁹

Geographically speaking, the Sakata primarily inhabit the Kutu territory of the Mai-Ndombe province. This territory is subdivided into five groupings (*groupements*), broadly corresponding to traditional Sakata chiefdoms as shown in Table 3.

¹⁹ We asked our Sakata consultants to situate on a map where their different varieties were spoken. The geographical distribution obtained in this way overlaps with that in Bokwankon Bosonkie (1997).

Table 3 – Groupings, chiefdoms, and Sakata varieties in the Kutu territory

GROUPING	CHIEFDOM	SAKATA VARIETY
BADIA	Iʒú baDia	Kinzinzale
BATERE	Idju baTere	Kitere
KEMBA	Iʒú Duele	Kimbantin
LWABO	Iʒú baBayi	Kibayi
	Iʒú Mbelo	-
MFIMI	Iʒú Lemvia-Nord	Kingingia, Kimbantin
	Iʒú Lemvia-Sud	Kimbantin
	Iʒú Mabie	Kingingele
	Iʒú Mbamushie	Kəmbamushie

To this day, the available linguistic literature on Sakata remains scarce and the little that exists is by and large unavailable to international academia (Sundberg 1930, van der Kerken 1936, de Witte 1950, 1955, Ikamba 1987, Mpia Lefutu 1993, Mundeke 1994, Bontenge 1995, Tataa Itsutsele 1996, Nkey Iziasuma 2004, Iyekima Bonghe 2004). A small number of sources have focussed specifically on the phonology of Sakata (Matabisi 1979, Tylleskär 1987, Bokwankon Bosonkie 1997). Tables 4 and 5 present Sakata consonant and vowel inventories as described by Bokwankon Bosonkie (1997, focussing primarily on central Sakata), which we take as a reference here. It is important to note, however, as mentioned above, that significant regiolectal variation exists within the Sakata domain. Our fieldwork data show, for example, that the realisation of nasality on vowels differs considerably across Sakata varieties.

Table 4 - Sakata consonant phonemes (adapted from Bokwankon Bosonkie 1997: 20)

	BILABIAL	LABIO-DENTAL	DENTAL/ALVEOLAR	PALATAL	VELAR	LABIAL-VELAR
STOPS	p b		t d		k ^(ŋ) g	kp gb
AFFRICATES			ts dz			
FRICATIVES		f v	s z	ʃ ʒ		
NASALS	m		n	ɲ	ŋ	ŋm
LATERALS			l			
TRILLS			r			
APPROXIMANTS				j		w

Table 5 - Sakata vowel phonemes (adapted from Bokwankon Bosonkie 1997: 20)²⁰

	FRONT	BACK
HIGH	i	u
MID-HIGH	e	o
MID-LOW	ɛ	ɔ
LOW	a	

While some phonological information on Sakata can be found in the literature, to the best of our knowledge no reliable phonetic data have ever been made available.

3.3 Methodology and data collection

As part of the first author’s doctoral research project, the first and third authors conducted fieldwork in the Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo between May and July 2021.²¹ We collected data in the Inongo and Kutu territories, more specifically in the cities of Inongo and Nioki. Inongo is the provincial capital and the province’s most multilingual city. Nioki is the province’s unofficial economic capital and its second most multilingual city. Within the Sakata area, it is the most populous municipality. In Nioki, we could document six different Sakata varieties:²² Kinzinzale

²⁰ Some Sakata varieties, such as Kingingia, display phonological nasal vowels in their inventories.

²¹ For more background, see <https://www.bantufirst.ugent.be/lorenzo-maselli-and-jean-pierre-donzos-bantufirst-fieldwork-mission-in-mai-ndombe-province-drc/>.

²² What we documented is actually more akin to a set of “idiolects”, given the limited number of speakers with whom we managed to work. This necessarily restricts the possibility of inferring broad, cross-variety

(also known as Djia, Dia, Dza, or Wadia) C34B, Kibayi C34C, Kingingia C34X, Kingingele C34Y, Kitere C34W, Kimbantin C34Z. Of these, only C34B and C34C are inventoried in Maho (2009), who also lists Sakata proper as C34A and Tuku, Ketu, Batow as C34D.²³ We interviewed one speaker for each variety, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6 - Basic information about the six Sakata consultants interviewed for the study presented in Chapter 3

VARIETY	CONSULTANT	SEX & AGE	PLACE OF ORIGIN	GEOCOORDINATES
KINZINZALE	Frédy Bopila Mbakela	male, 52	Nioki	-2.72, 17.69
KIBAYI	Rocky Besevuku Monkaja Ila	male, 49	Tolo	-2.95, 18.57
KINGINGIA	Darius Moja Mayo Kemay	male, 52	Nioki	-2.72, 17.69
KINGINGELE	Guillaume Moke Mubata	male, 52	Mongobebe	-2.79, 17.87
KITERE	Jean-Pierre Kemay	male, 58	Kilima	-3.58, 18.54
KIMBANTIN	Manuel Isee	male, 43	Motangili	-2.72, 17.69

Speakers were asked to translate a word list of around 800 items. Several questions were asked by the two interviewers to assess the sociolinguistic status of Sakata. The nature of these latter exchanges was informal and consisted in guided elaboration on present-day Sakata and on the oral traditions concerning the history of the Sakata people. The labial-velar stop dataset (i.e., all words containing labial-velar stops present in the elicited data) for each of the varieties we documented during our fieldwork mission is listed in Table 7. Lexical items with a labial-velar stop are reported for each variety with their equivalent in all other varieties (whenever available). A question mark means lack of data.

generalisations based solely on the data presented here. Nonetheless, it is worth mentioning that more data collection is currently underway with several speakers of Central Sakata varieties close to what is referred to here as Kingingia, and that these additional sources seem to buttress the findings reported in this preliminary venue.

²³ During fieldwork in Nioki and Inongo, we could identify no specific variety as “Sakata proper”, nor did we find any speakers of “Tow”, a variety also not mentioned by our consultants. For the conventions used in the assignment of alphanumeric codes to Bantu varieties of the region not inventoried in Guthrie (1970) and/or Maho (2009), see Pacchiarotti et al. (2019: 159-160).

Table 7 - Labial-velar dataset for six different varieties of Sakata (Kibayi, Kinzinzale, Kingingia, Kingingele, Kitere, Kimbantín)

	KIBAYI	KINZINZALE	KINGINGIA	KINGINGELE	KITERE	KIMBANTIN
‘(KIND OF) STONE’	ɲkú	nmú:	nmú:	nmú:	?	?
‘BACK’	?	?	?	?	nmwá	?
‘BROOM’	lèkwámò	lè:χwómò	lèmó	lèmó	lèmó	?
‘CLOSE’	?	lèkpílèkpì	lèkpílèkpì	lèpfilèpfi	lègbìgbì	ò:kpókpè
‘DEATH’	?	ì:kpá	ì:kpá	ì:kpá/ì:pfá	?	ì:kpá
‘DEATH SPIRIT’	mùkff	mùkífú	ùpfi	ùpfi	?	?
‘DISABLED PERSON’	ɲgbákàrà	?	ɲkpákàrà	ɲgbákà:	ɲgbá	?
‘FLEA’	í:ɲmè	í:kpà	í:ɲmà	í:kpà	í:ɲmà/í:kpà	?
‘HOW MUCH/MANY’	kpé	kpé	kpí	kfi	gbí	?
‘LAUGH’	?	?	?	?	?	kpánkié
‘LEG’	lè:kólò	lè:mélè	lè:kwí	lè:kwí	?	?
‘MOURNING’	ì:kpá	N/A	ɲkpá	mpfi	ì:kpí	ì:kpá
‘MYSELF’	múɲgbà	múɲgbà	múɲgbà	múndzà	múɲgbà	?
‘NAVEL’	mò:túò	mù:χúmá	ù:múá	ù:kfúá	?	?
‘OWNER’	múɲgbà	múɲgbà	úɲgbà	úndzà	úɲgbà	?
‘PELLET’	kèrikpá	kèrikpá	kèrèkpá	kèrèkpá	?	?
‘SALT’	mùɲkpá	mùkpá	ù:kpá	ù:pfí	ùɲkpá	ɲkpá
‘SHORT’	bò:gbé	bò:gbé	ò:kpé	ò:fí	ò:gbí	lè:kwúkpè
‘TERMITE HILL’	éɲkóló	kénmèlé	kéɲkúó	kéɲkúó	?	?
‘TO DIE’	òkpá	òkpá	òkpá	òpfá	ì:kpá	?
‘WRECK’	?	kíɲgbàɲgbà	kíɲgbàɲgbà	kíɲgbàɲgbà	?	?
‘YAM’	è:kpá	kè:kpá	kè:kpá	kèpfi	è:gbá	kè:kpá

The data were recorded indoors, in a relatively quiet environment with no echo discernible in the background; recording conditions, while sub-optimal (i.e., not fully controlled for), remain the best available to us in the field. Recording sessions were interrupted during the hours of maximum traffic in the vicinity of the building. Some of the data were recorded on Roland R-26 and Zoom H-5 devices with their built-in directional microphones, and the rest on the same Roland R-26 device with an

external plug-in omnidirectional microphone (Saramonic Lavalier Microphone SR-XLM1) clipped onto the speakers' clothes (sideways from the mouth). The sampling rate was kept at 44.1 kHz/s; maximum input, whenever verifiable, was set at 75%; depth was set at 24 bits; the signal is stereo, and the resulting file format is .wav. The data were then imported into Praat (Boersma & Weenink 2020) for annotation and analysis.

3.4 Sakata labial-velars

Table 7 shows that all surveyed Sakata varieties minimally contain the voiceless labial-velar stop /kp/, with five out of six also exhibiting its voiced counterpart /gb/.²⁴ It is important to note, though, that the distribution of these sounds is not even across varieties. Out of 95 identified words with labial-velar stops in our dataset, 38 display voiceless /kp/, and only 20 its voiced counterpart /gb/. If we consider possibly reduplicated lexical items (e.g., *lèkpílèkpì* 'close by', *kíngbàngbà* 'abandoned object') presenting more than one labial-velar stop, this gives us a total of 40 /kp/ and 24 /gb/ tokens in our corpus. Audio files for these items have been made public on OSF.²⁵

Although the auditory difference between /kp/ and /gb/ is clear to the linguist's ear, spectral cues to a voicing distinction are scarce, as shown with the Kinzinzale examples in Figure 7.

²⁴ We do not have evidence of /gb/ in Kimbantin. However, our Kimbantin data are significantly less comprehensive than for the other varieties. Lack of evidence is therefore not necessarily evidence of absence.

²⁵ https://osf.io/vz8ne/?view_only=7c1ef734f17e45a4ae3848439ee6313d.

Figure 7 - Realisations of *Kitere gbí* (left) and *Kinzinzale kpé* (right) 'how much/many'²⁶

F2 transitions are marked by a steep rise into the following vowel (light green line in the spectrogram), though no specific tendency for double formant loci can be identified (Ladefoged 1968a, Garnes 1975, Connell 1994). The characteristic presence of a voicing bar in the lower regions of the spectrum (see infra Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996, among others) is more clearly visible on the voiced than the voiceless counterpart (circled in red), but it does not seem to distinguish the two as neatly as one might expect. This is not surprising, as labial-velar stops, regardless of their phonological specification for voicing, tend to merge (however completely) to [+ voice]. This is known to happen for several phonetic reasons (see Cahill 2008). First, voiceless labial-velar stops typically lack aspiration, even in languages that tend to prefer [\pm spread glottis] over [\pm voice] as a correlate for voicing (see Iverson & Salmons 2007). This suggests that, all other factors being equal, labial-velar stops are more easily interpreted as [+ voice] rather than [- voice], leading voiceless labial-velar stops to behave acoustically more like voiced ones. Second, labial-velar stops typically display some degree of implosivity (see Siertsema 1958, Ladefoged 1968b, Demolin 1991, 1995). Since the most common setting in larynx lowering is for the glottis not to be completely closed, the glottalic ingressive airstream is often coupled with a pulmonic egressive one. This in turn may generate voicing on both voiceless and

²⁶ Audio files on OSF: [kpé] Kinzinzale-combien_sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_03, [gbí] Kitere-combien_sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_03

voiced labial-velar stops (see Ladefoged 1968b: 6, Catford 1977: 75, McLaughlin 2005, Demolin & Vuillermet 2006).

This situation matches that found in the other varieties surveyed, as can be seen in Figure 8 (voiceless labial-velar stops). Different pre-voicing spans (circled in red) can be observed during the release phase.

Figure 8 - Realisations of *(kèrè)kpá* 'pallet' in Kibayi (top left), Kingingele (top right) and Kingingia (bottom)²⁷

If we compare Figure 8 with Figure 9, we can observe that prevoicing (red circle) is clearer for [gb] than for [kp]. F2 rise (green line) is particularly steep.

²⁷ Audio files on OSF: Kibayi Kibayi-grabat_sak_LM_20210622_NIO_15_copy, Kingingele Kingingele-grabat_sak_LM_20210622_NIO_15_copy, Kingingia Kingingia-grabat_sak_LM_20210622_NIO_15_copy.

Figure 9 - Realisation of (b̀)gbé 'short' in Kibayi²⁸

As mentioned above, some varieties of Sakata (Kibayi, Kingingia, Kitere) also exhibit labial-velar nasals.²⁹ To the best of our knowledge, labial-velar nasals have not been reported anywhere else in the region. However, they are quite common further north, in the Macro-Sudan Belt (see Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021). A few exemplary spectrograms can be seen in Figure 10.

²⁸ Audio file on OSF: Kibayi-court_sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_03.

²⁹ Other examples of labial-velar nasals were found in our impressionistic survey of another variety of Sakata, i.e., Kimbamushie, but we do not have recordings of those.

Figure 10 - Realisations of (i)ηmÉ/(i)ηmá 'flea' in Kibayi (top left), Kitere (top right) and Kingingia (bottom)³⁰

As can be seen in Figure 10, labial-velar nasals predictably differ from their oral counterparts for the lack of a visible burst, but, to varying degrees, they all display the characteristically steep F2 rise that was observed for labial-velar oral stops (green line; more so in Kibayi, given the higher F2 of the following vowel). Effects of a nasal murmur are discernible throughout the consonant, but no spectral cues such as higher frequency damping unequivocally indicate the transition from a velar to a labial articulation.

Finally, the presence of voiceless labialised velar fricatives deserves a mention. While the very possibility of double, synchronous sources of turbulent noise in the

³⁰ Audio files on OSF : Kibayi Kibayi-puce_sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_13_copy, Kitere Kitere-puce_kit_LM_20210626_NIO_01, Kingingia Kingingia-puce_sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_13_copy.

vocal tract has long been the object of debate (Cahill 2018: 150), the notion of a voiceless labialised velar fricative / voiceless labial-velar approximant (Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996: 326) is common in the field of English dialectology, especially in reference to Scottish and American English (a few recent case studies: Schützler 2010, Bridwell 2019, Li & Gut 2022). At the moment, we lack the appropriate data to analyse the articulation of what we have transcribed as <ɱ> in Sakata. Whatever its exact phonetic nature might be, it is interesting to note that within the Sakata domain cognates appear to a) present /ɱ/ (and /χw/) in phonological contexts in which one would expect a labial-velar stop to arise historically (KW- > KP-, see *infra*), and b) differ as to the degree of labialisation of some of their fricatives as can be seen in the following examples: (i) BLR 1927 *kómbó ‘broom’> Kibayi: *lèkwámò*; Kinzinzale: *lè:χwómò*; Kingingele / Kingingia / Kitere: *lèṃǒ(m)*; (ii) *kúmbá ‘navel’³¹ > Kinzinzale: *mù:χúmá*; Kingingia: *ù:múá*; Kingingele: *ù:kfúá*.³²

In the case of the reflexes of BLR 1927 *kómbó ‘broom’, the Sakata varieties surveyed here are the only ones in West-Coastal Bantu to display fricativisation in root-initial position without additional voicing³³ (/k/ > /χ/ in Kinzinzale).³⁴ In turn, the back fricative + labial-velar approximant sequence appears to be subject to varying degrees of temporal compression in Kinzinzale and in Kingingele, Kingingia, and Kitere, as can be observed in Figure 11.

³¹ This root is absent from the BLR3 database (Bastin *et al.* 2002) but widely attested in West-Coastal Bantu and beyond.

³² BLR stands for Bantu Lexical Reconstructions 3 (Bastin *et al.* 2002), a database of nearly 10.000 Bantu lexical protoforms with variable time depth. but widely attested in West-Coastal Bantu and beyond. The number following the BLR abbreviation refers to the unique index number of a given reconstruction in the dataset. Reconstructions without a number are not present in BLR but are posited on the basis of research on West-Coastal and Central Western Bantu languages carried out at BantUGent. For example, the root *kúmbá ‘navel’ is absent from BLR but widely attested in West-Coastal Bantu and beyond.

³³ Bantu B40 languages of the Kikongo Language Cluster are the only West-Coastal Bantu languages to have voiced fricative velar reflexes of Proto-West-Coastal Bantu *k, which results from the merger of Proto-Bantu *g and *k (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020), in root-initial position, i.e., *k > γ. Fricative reflexes of Proto-West-Coastal Bantu *k in root-final position are more common though not widespread (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2022).

³⁴ In other contexts, /k/ is the regular reflex of Proto-Bantu *k in Kinzinzale; see, e.g., *ok:ára* ‘to bite’ < *kag, *mukía* ‘tail’ < *kídà BLR 1793, *le:ké:* ‘leaf’ < *kájá BLR 1736.

Figure 11 - Realisations of Kitere (lè:)mó (left) and Kinzinzale (lè:)χwómò (right), 'broom'³⁵

In the case of [lè:χwómò], a clear F2 slope marking the passage from [w] to [o] is visible (line in light green), alongside a mid-to-high frequency region of lesser energy after the fricative (circled in light red); in the case of [lè:mó], none of this is visible, and while the effects of possible lip-rounding are not easily identifiable without a reliable formant contour, they are unmistakable to the trained ear. Regardless of the exact phonetic nature of this sound, the reflexes of *kúmbà 'navel' represent one step further in terms of phonological patterning, possibly indicating that both labial-velar stops and these newly documented fricatives constitute one sound class in Sakata (both are only to be found in Sakata varieties and in contexts deriving from *KW- sequences). The case of Kingingele (see §3.5) is of particular interest: the voiceless labiodentalised velar stop /kf/, which is often present alongside affricates like /pf/ where a voiceless labial-velar stop can be found in most other Sakata varieties, is also found in this variety whenever [m] is present in a cognate word in Kingingia. This suggests that affrication might intervene in Kingingele as a substitute of both labial-velar stops and labialised velar fricatives.

It is essential to remember that our data, and possibly the very number of lexical items with labial-velar sounds in Sakata, are too limited for conclusive phonological generalisations. This being said, it is also important to highlight that Sakata speakers consider the relatively extended presence of labial-velar consonants in their language

³⁵ Audio files on OSF: Kinzinzale Kinzinzale-balai_sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_11, Kitere Kitere-balai_sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_11.

as an identity marker distinguishing them from other Bantu speech communities of the area. Complementarily, their neighbours commonly identify Sakata speakers by their extensive use of labial-velar consonants, thereby rendering this sound class a defining linguistic mark.³⁶ Based on our own fieldwork experience, the fricatives described above align with labial-velar stops when it comes to distinctive sociolinguistic identity. In fact, to our knowledge, no other Mai-Ndombe languages display a labial-velar fricative like the one described above.³⁷

3.5 Affricates as a substitute for labial-velar stops in Kingingele

Following the analysis of Ponelis (1974) and Connell (1998/1999: 19) as discussed in Cahill (1999), labial-velar stops are likely the outcome of a temporal compression phenomenon of the following type: $KuV/K\upsilon V > KwV > KPV$; $PuV/P\upsilon V > PwV > KPV$.

Connell's (1998/1999) approach moves from the premises of Articulatory Phonology (Browman & Goldstein 1989, 1990; Recasens et al. 1997; Goldstein, Byrd & Saltzman 2006; Hall 2018), in that it challenges Mutaka & Ebobissé's (1996/1997) feature-geometrical account of the evolution of labial-velar double articulations based on data from West and East Sawabantu. According to Connell (1998/1999), the progressive overlap of the TONGUE BODY (TB) and LIPS gestures to the point of near synchrony results in a reassignment of constriction specifications (whichever articulator targets {close} spreads this specification to the other). The gestural scores for the chains of changes $KuV/K\upsilon V > KwV > KPV$ and $PuV/P\upsilon V > PwV > KPV$ presented by Connell (1998/1999) are reproduced in Figure 12.

³⁶ See the notion of *blasone linguistico* in Italian dialectology (e.g., Gally 2015); for comparable issues in African linguistics, see Thomason (2007), Storch (2011), Bostoën & Donzo (2013), Gunnink et al. (2015), Dimmendaal & Storch (2016: 28).

³⁷ Other languages to display labial-velar stops in the Mai-Ndombe province are Tiene B81 (see Ellington 1977), the Teke variety known as Kenkuu (recently studied by Guy Kouarata in 2021, pers. comm.) or Boma Nkuu (Nsuka Nkutsi 1990, Pacchiarotti et al. 2019), and the neighbouring varieties Nunu B822 and North Boma B82 (to varying degrees; pers. data).

Figure 12 – Gestural score for the evolution of labial-velar stops (adapted from Connell 1998/99)

The applicability of this model is a matter of particular interest in Sakata. As mentioned above, out of 95 identified words containing labial-velar oral stops, nasal stops, or labialised velar fricatives in our set, 58 display labial-velar oral stops, of which 38 /kp/ and only 20 /gb/. Accounting for possibly reduplicated lexical items containing more than one labial-velar oral stop, this gives us a total of 40 /kp/ and 24 /gb/ tokens. For each voicing type, only 3 items could be found in Kingingele (see Table 7). In this variety, labial-velar oral stops appear to undergo a more or less regular process of affrication, as in the examples below.³⁸

1. ‘myself’: Kibayi, Kinzinzale, Kingingia, Kitere: *múŋgbà* vs. Kingingele: *múndzà*
2. BLR 2096*kúà ‘death’ > Kibayi, Kinzinzale, Kingingia: *òkpá*; Kitere: *ì:kpá*; Kingingele: *òpfá*
3. *kuai ‘how many’³⁹ > Kibayi, Kinzinzale: *kpé*; Kingingia: *kpí*; Kitere: *gbí*; Kingingele: *kff*⁴⁰

Numerous questions can be raised concerning the Kingingele case: a) did Kingingele not develop labial-velar oral stops in the first place, or did it substitute them with affricate variants?; b) what are the underlying reasons for the sound changes leading to the development of affricates as substitutes of labial-velar consonants in

³⁸ But Kingingele *kèràkpá* ‘pallet’ and *ŋbákàà* ‘disabled person’.

³⁹ This root does not occur in BLR3 (Bastin *et al.* 2002) but is widespread within West-Coastal Bantu, where languages generally feature *kwa* (mostly in the Kikongo Language Cluster) or *kwe* (mostly elsewhere). If one hypothesises the presence of a final interrogative *-í (see Meeussen 1967: 103, Idiatov 2022), *kuai seems the only possible reconstruction accounting for both present-day forms.

⁴⁰ As an anonymous reviewer notes, /kf/ is better defined as a labiodentalised velar stop; it does, however, appear to occur in free variation with /pf/ (an affricate proper) in most contexts in Kingingele.

Kingingele?; c) why does Kingingele specifically differ from other Sakata varieties? Of course, our data do not permit a comprehensive analysis of the (extra)linguistic factors at play here, but a few hypotheses can be formulated nonetheless.

Assuming that the affricate reflex in Kingingele followed directly from a Proto-Bantu form like the one described in the early stages of the change summarised above, one would probably have to imagine a sound change trajectory along the following lines: KuV/KɔV > KwV > KvV (> KfV/PvV) > PfV. In other words, a partial reassignment of constriction specifications, such that the LIPS' degree of constriction be specified as {critical} rather than {close}, i.e., enough for turbulent noise to be produced. It is a well-established fact in Articulatory Phonology that coarticulation can lead to sound change in a gradient way; see, among others, Browman & Goldstein (1992), Romero & Martín (2003). Devoicing is unsurprising, as it is also attested in Connell (1998/1999). As for the (non-systematic) velar-to-labial shift, a featural explanation might account for it in terms of assimilation ([+ velar] > [+ labial]/__[+ labial]); an articulatory perspective, on the other hand, might build on the timing of the gestures involved: the anticipated activation of the LIPS articulator covered the preceding movement of the TB, assuming its {close} specification and yielding the output below with only one articulator changing specifications (LIPS {close} to {critical}; see Browman & Goldstein 1991: 322); see the gestural score in Figure 13.⁴¹

Figure 13 - Proposed gestural score for the evolution of voiceless affricates from KUV sequences in Kingingele

This possibility supersedes all problems linked to the synchronisation of multiple articulations, effectively producing a stop with a more or less prolonged moment of turbulence after the burst (i.e., an affricate; see Berns 2014: 370). In other cases, such as *ò:f:f* ‘short’, it appears that the stop element of the affricate is lost altogether. It can

⁴¹ The contribution of the teeth is left aside here; it is worth mentioning that none of the languages reported in the UPSID database have purely bilabial affricates in their inventory.

be hypothesised that this is either a subsequent specification or an alternative development, where the {bilabial critical} specification of the LIPS simply extends backwards without assuming the {velar close} one of the TB. Now, these reflexes are by no means rare in the languages of the region: a labiodental/bilabial fricative element is found in numerous forms deriving from Proto-Bantu proto-forms structured like those visible in the early stages of the sound change in $KuV/K\bar{u}V > KwV > KvV (> KfV/PvV) > PfV$; see, e.g., *kúà ‘death’ (BLR 2096), which exhibits reductions to [f(w)]/[pf] in 37 cases out of 47 West-Coastal Bantu attestations in our team’s comparative lexical database.

The situation for the voiced counterpart is, however, more complicated. Where the other Sakata varieties surveyed here seem to have developed the voiced labial-velar stop /gb/, Kingingele mostly exhibits the alveolar affricate /dz/; see (1). One possibility would be to hypothesise a sound change like $GuV/G\bar{u}V > GwV > GvV (> BvV) > DzV$. However, the reasons why DzV should be the result of articulatory restructuring from BvV are unclear, as Articulatory Phonology disfavours gestural addition as a source of sound change (in this case, the activation of the TONGUE TIP; see Goldstein 1995). There is reason to believe /dz/ may have been favoured over /bv/ for considerations other than articulation. Acoustically, a key difference between [dz] and [bv] lies in the fact that the latter is more diffuse, having no anterior resonating chamber, which makes it less perceptible. This is in line with the PHOIBLE ranking according to which occurrences of /dz/ outnumber those of /bv/ by a factor of ten in the world’s languages. This ranking does not, however, explain by itself the sound change in question, as /ts/ is also considerably more common than /pf/ (coronal affricates are generally preferred cross-linguistically; see also Berns 2014).

Therefore, a purely articulatory explanation does not appear to fully capture the sound change at play in Kingingele. This may necessitate a different explanation, bearing rather on sociophonetics. As noted above, the presence of labial-velar stops is treated as a linguistic identifier by Sakata speakers, and, within the Sakata domain, the presence of affricate allophones is clearly identified as a hallmark Kingingele feature. Building on Labov’s (1994) remarks on sociolinguistic “change from below” (i.e., community-driven linguistic innovations that originate below the level of explicit social awareness), Thomason (2007: 45) goes on to contest the widely held assumption that deliberate linguistic manipulation should only affect minor or trivial aspects of the grammar. In this sense, affrication can be used as a deliberate (and

non-systematic, as attested by the presence of sporadic labial-velar stops in Kingingele too) tool on the part of Kingingele speakers to distance themselves from the other Sakata. Should this explanation prove valid, the reasons for this explicit distancing would need to be identified. Based on our personal fieldwork experience, the Sakata consider themselves distant descendants of peoples from further north. It is perhaps imaginable that different integration strategies were implemented by different Sakata groups when they immigrated into the Lower Kasai region. This, in turn, would indicate that Kingingele speakers might have adopted /pf/ to sound more like those around them who did (and do) have /pf/ as an articulatorily-grounded allophone of /kp/, and they may have opted for /dz/ in the case of /gb/ simply because it is more accessible than /bv/ (as evidenced by the fact that /dz/ is a lot more common/unmarked typologically than /bv/). In the case of the West-Coastal Bantu language Lwel B862, Maselli et al. 2021 observed that voiceless labial-velar stops are more stable than their voiced counterparts, which, on the other hand, tend to be realised as plain [b] (or slightly implosive versions of [b]). If that pattern were to hold true for other languages of the region, it could indicate that the Kingingele speakers might not even have “looked for” other regular reflexes of *gw- in the region, thus buttressing the notion that no articulatory variables came into play in the identification of their affricate allophone. More data on the acoustics and articulation of Sakata labial-velar sounds are needed to test these hypotheses. Evidence from other fields, including sociolinguistics, should also be considered.

3.6 Historical implications

We conclude this contribution with a few considerations on the phonetic and phonological uniqueness of the West-Coastal Bantu languages spoken in the Mai-Ndombe province. Besides the existence of a full-fledged inventory of labial-velar stops including nasals in the Sakata varieties phonetically documented here for the first time, neighbouring languages such as North Boma B82 and Nunu B822 display phonemic nasal retroflexes (Stappers 1986, Maselli et al.: forthcoming). What is more, they probably also have similar maximality constraints on the verb stems to those described for Tiene (Ellington 1977, Hyman 2010), where restrictions can be found on

the place of articulation and nasality of consonants in different phonotactic positions within the verb stem. Maximality constraints and the sporadic presence of labial-velar stops are found elsewhere in the West-Coastal Bantu languages spoken in the homeland area (see, e.g., relevant Ding data in Ebalantshim Masuwan 1980, Maselli et al. 2021). On the contrary, the comprehensive inventory of labial-velar stops found in some Sakata varieties, along with the nasal retroflexes of North Boma, are, to our knowledge, unique within West-Coastal Bantu. This means that they are unique to the Mai-Ndombe area. At the same time, the West-Coastal Bantu homeland region (see Pacchiarotti et al. 2019) is also a hot spot of phonological diversity unlike any other in West-Coastal Bantu. Languages from this area all belong to Guthrie's B80 group, which is the most diverse within West-Coastal Bantu in terms of basic vocabulary. Atypical phonological features crosscut phylogenetic subgroups and include: large vowel systems with up to 13 vowel phonemes (Ebalantshim Masuwan 1980, Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2019, Mfum-Ekong 1979), diphthongisation, umlaut (Bostoen & Koni Muluwa 2014), phonologically unconditioned final vowel loss (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2021), dorsal fricatives (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2022), and heterosyllabic sequences of mid and low vowels (Pacchiarotti et al. 2021; see also Daeleman 1977, Rottland 1977, Bostoen & Mundeke 2011a,b).

These facts invite consideration about the origins and the sociolinguistic dynamics underpinning this synchronic diversity. In terms of origin, today's scenario suggests that the relevant languages spoken in the Mai-Ndombe and Bandundu regions where the West-Coastal Bantu homeland area is located display traces of archaic heterogeneity (Hetzron 1976) and are therefore "fossils" of erstwhile greater linguistic diversity in the area. As argued by Nettle (1996), the social isolation model of physical barriers to explain language diversification seems to be inappropriate for West Africa and, in all likelihood, for Central Africa as well. Although precise sociolinguistic data are unavailable, the speech communities displaying the phonological inventories and features described above have a relatively small number of speakers, in the range of 2,000 to 20,000 individuals, and are in close contact with other speech communities with which they usually interact in a language of wider communication such as Lingala or Kongo ya Leta. Nevertheless, this situation of contact has not led to language convergence or the loss of distinctive phonetic/phonological features such as a full set of labial-velar stops (in Sakata) and nasal retroflexes (North Boma, Nunu). Possibly, these features are attributable to conscious language manipulation as a way to create

group identity (Dimmendaal & Storch 2016). At the same time, it is possible that some of these features are the result of speakers shifting to another language while preserving some phonological aspects of their original tongues. A combination of these factors cannot be excluded either. As a matter of fact, labial-velar stops are a trait of particular interest in historical terms. Unlike other distinctive phonetic features of African languages, such as clicks in southern African Khoisan and Bantu, labial-velar stops are acoustically less marked, as attested by the fact that they are known to converge to plain labial realisations in numerous languages (see Cahill 2008, Maselli et al. 2021: 152, and the literature cited therein). In this sense, while more acoustically marked sounds, e.g. clicks, are hardly ever transferred in situations of superficial interlinguistic contact (Gunnink et al. 2015, Pakendorf et al. 2017), labial-velar stops may have spread more easily through deliberate acquisition on the part of Bantu speakers in several areas of the Congo Basin, including southern Mai-Ndombe, possibly as a way for them to distance themselves from the neighbouring Mongo (as has been claimed to be the case for several Bantu languages spoken between the Congo and Ubangi Rivers; see Bostoen & Donzo 2013). In fact, while the phonological load of labial-velar stops appears to be established in Sakata, numerous other languages spoken in the immediate vicinity of Sakata (North Boma, Nunu) or in the wider region (e.g., Lwel B862, B82, Western Ngwi B861Y) present labial-velar stops as free variants of /kw/ and /gw/ sequences (especially in fast, connected speech; pers. data).⁴² This might indicate that some speech communities of the Lower Kasai area present labial-velar stops in their shared “phonetic” inventory (i.e., as a commonly accepted variant of /kw/ and /gw/, to varying degrees) before they do, individually, as full phonemes in their phonological ones. In this sense the functional load of labial-velar stops in the Bantu languages of the region may be said to range from cases of major (Sakata) to minor (Nunu, North Boma) phonologisation. If so, a typology of labial-velar-containing inventories in southwestern Congo, after the model of Güldemann & Stoneking’s (2008) work on southern African clicks, would prove greatly beneficial in backstopping our understanding of the situation. Clearly, the unique

⁴² While the North Boma speech varieties documented by the first and third author in 2021 feature labial-velar stops, the North Boma variety of Bopaka-Pentana (-2.49, 17.36) documented in August 2022 by the second, third and last authors has [kf] and [tf] in words where other North Boma varieties might have labial-velar stops.

phonological diversity of the Mai-Ndombe province and the West-Coastal Bantu homeland area presents a promising avenue for dedicated phonetic documentation.

3.7 Conclusions

Labial-velar stops, a class of typologically rare sounds, occur in the consonant inventory of Sakata (Bantu C34), a cluster of closely related varieties spoken in the Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo. This linguistic area, one of the world's least well-surveyed ones, is situated significantly to the south of Africa's major hot spot of labial-velar stops, i.e., the so-called Macro-Sudan Belt. Following our inventory of labial-velar stops in Lwel, a closely related language from the West-Coastal Bantu homeland in Kwilu (Maselli et al. 2021), we have provided here the first detailed spectrographic description of this category of double articulated consonants in the region, establishing the existence of both voiceless and voiced labial-velar stops and of their nasal counterparts in Sakata. While some Sakata varieties have labialised velar fricatives correspond to labial-velar stops in terms both of historical phonology and sociophonetics, Kingingele substitutes them with affricates. Unlike what happens in other African languages, the emergence of voiced affricates as a substitute for /gb/ in Kingingele eludes explanation through Articulatory Phonology. Therefore, we contend that Kingingele speakers may have adopted a phonetically ungrounded variant to distance themselves from other Sakata speech communities in the area. Finally, when it comes to the historical-linguistic implications of Lower Kasai's great phonological diversity, labial-velar stops in Sakata may be just one trace of a now submerged past of even greater linguistic differentiation in the region. In this sense, efforts should not be spared in the future to provide a further-reaching typology of labial-velar-containing phonological inventories in southwestern Congo.

Chapter 4: Aerodynamics of Sakata labial-velar oral stops

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Abstract

The present contribution represents the first in-detail exploratory account of the aerodynamics of labial-velar oral stops in Sakata, a Bantu dialect cluster of southwestern Congo. Data collection took place at the phonetics laboratory facilities of the University of Mons with three speakers of central Sakata. Comparative data of labial-velar and plain bilabial oral stops are presented and analysed. Descriptive statistics of the relevant variables are discussed. Given each group of variables, MANOVA results are presented for specially tailored subsets of the whole dataset to investigate variance in the corpus. Sakata labial-velar stops are shown to differ from plain bilabials for duration, airflow, and pressure patterns. Voiceless labial-velar stops exhibit pressure and airflow values consistent with a more prominent lowering of the tongue root / larynx than their voiced counterparts. Matches and mismatches with the available typological literature are also delineated and discussed.

Keywords: aerodynamics, labial-velars, Bantu languages, speech communication, phonetic documentation

4.1 Introduction

Labial-velar consonants are among the commonest double articulations in human speech, attested in around one tenth of the world's sound systems (Maddieson 2018, Moran & McCloy 2019, Cahill 2008); for the most part, they occur in Niger-Congo and Nilo-Saharan lects from northern sub-Saharan Africa, and are more sporadically reported in Papua – New Guinea, Oceania, and South America (Cahill 2017). They are produced with overlapping labial and velar closures released almost simultaneously, with the velar release always preceding the labial (Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996, Maddieson & Ladefoged 1989, Painter 1978, Connell 1987, 1991a,b, 1994, Dogil 1988, Cahill & Hajek 2001, Cahill 2018). Instrumental analyses of labial-velar consonants are scarce, with only a handful of articulatory and aerodynamic descriptions available in the literature (Ladefoged 1968a, Maddieson 1993, Demolin & Teston 1996, Demolin & Soquet 1999, Grawunder et al. 2011). It is generally accepted that, during the articulation of labial-velar stops, a certain degree of air rarefaction is attained between the two closures, causing the co-occurrence of ingressive and egressive airstream mechanisms upon release (Mills 1984, Vogler 1987, Demolin 1991, Ladefoged 1968b). This is most commonly due to a slight backward movement of the tongue root, often accompanied by a lowering of the larynx (Ladefoged 1993).

Labial-velar stops (both oral and nasal) have been reported in Sakata, a dialect cluster of Bantu (Niger-Congo) spoken by around 10-50,000 people in the Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo (Van Bulck 1940, Mundeke 1994). Sakata is traditionally listed as C34 in Guthrie's (1970) alphanumeric classification of Bantu languages. To this day, the available phonological literature on Sakata remains scant (Matabisi 1979, Tylleskär 1987, Bokwankon Bosonkie 1997), with only one source providing detailed acoustic information (Maselli et al. 2023). This gap is particularly severe in that Sakata is spoken far to the south of the so-called "Macro- Sudan Belt", a vast linguistic macro-area of which labial-velar stops have been considered a diagnostic feature (Clements & Rialland 2008, Güldemann 2008, Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021). Interestingly, labial-velar stops have also been reported in other southwestern Congo lects, though their phonological status appears to be less well-established in those than in Sakata (Maselli et al. 2021). The phonological inventory

of Sakata (adapted from Bokwankon Bosonkie 1997, Maselli et al. 2023) is reported below, Table 8.

Table 8 – Central Sakata phonology

CONSONANTS	BILABIAL	LABIO-DENTAL	DENTAL/ALVEOLAR	PALATAL	VELAR	LABIAL-VELAR
STOPS	p b		t d		k g	kp gb
AFFRICATES			ts dz			
FRICATIVES		f v	s z	ʃ ʒ		
NASALS	m		n	ɲ	ŋ	ŋm
LATERALS			l			
TRILLS			r			
APPROXIMANTS				j		w
VOWELS		front				back
HIGH		i				u
MID-HIGH		e				o
MID-LOW			ɛ		ɔ	
LOW				a		

The present contribution represents the first empirical aerodynamic study of Sakata labial-velar stops. Aerodynamic traces are essential in the study of labial-velar articulations given their typological characteristics, including the occurrence of specific aerodynamic events such as air rarefaction between the velar and labial closures (see above). This paper is particularly concerned with the production of labial-velar oral stops (as well as plain bilabial stops) in two varieties of central Sakata, i.e., Sakata Mbantín and Sakata Mbamushie. The research made available in this venue is chiefly exploratory and should therefore be intended as primary phonetic documentation.

4.2 Methodology and data

4.2.1 Data collection

Full datasets and metadata have been made available on OSF: https://osf.io/cdfk8/?view_only=1bd311ad49cd4125a64c4c0913fb6658.

Data collection took place in Mons in March 2023. Data were collected with three L1 speakers of Sakata residing in Europe at the time of data collection. All participants are multilingual, fluent in French and Lingala, and highly educated members of their community. They are the only speakers of Sakata we were able to recruit in Belgium and are likely to be among the very few living in Europe. Despite the limited number of participants, this sample is the most representative available as of 2024. Relevant biographical information (pseudonymised) is available below, Table 9.

Table 9 – Sakata speakers interviewed for the study presented in Chapter 4 (metadata)

	SP. A	SP. B	SP. C
AGE	51	63	64
ORIGIN	Bokoro	Mongobebe	Mongobebe
VARIETY	Mbantini	Mbamushie	Mbamushie

A set of labial-velar–containing and bilabial-containing Sakata words was produced in collaboration with the speakers, drawing upon information previously reported in the literature (Maselli et al. 2023). The set includes 22 lexical items, of which 11 contain labial-velar and 11 bilabial stops; one labial-velar–containing word presents two labial-velar segments, and one bilabial-containing word presents 2 bilabial segments. 8 of the 11 labial-velar–containing words display voiceless labial-velars (with their voiced counterparts being regularly preceded by a nasal), while 7 bilabial-containing ones display a voiced bilabial; this lack of balance is largely due to the uneven quality of Sakata lexical documentation at the time of data collection. All segments are word-medial and in intervocalic position, with the exception of one word-initial voiceless labial-velar and the voiced labial-velar stops which are preceded by a nasal and followed by a vowel. A conventional orthography was agreed upon, as well as a carrier sentence. The carrier sentence reads as follows, with hyphens marking the position of the target word: Mantshii - mba isa, - - - (meaning: "I say - three times, - - -"; in practice, we elicited 4 repetitions per word, 1 in the carrier sentence and 3 in isolation). Aerodynamic data were collected with PcQuirer 516 (Scicon R and D Inc.). This allowed us to simultaneously record acoustic traces and three channels of aerodynamic data (mouth pressure, oral airflow, nasal airflow). The audio signal was digitised and sampled at 12 kHz, dc channels were sampled at 1 kHz. Mouth pressure

was obtained by dint of a catheter introduced at the side of the mouth, bent behind the second molars, and connected to a pressure transducer. Volume flow from the mouth was collected with a Rothenberg mask, with a pressure tube inserted in one of the mask's outlet holes. Pressure and airflow signals were low-pass filtered at 50 Hz. The nasal airflow trace has not been analysed for the purposes of this study, as the focus of this paper does not extend to labial-velar nasal stops.

4.2.2 Data analysis

All recordings were annotated with Praat (Boersma & Weenink 2001). Individual tokens deemed unsuitable for phonetic analysis (due to background noise and/or mispronunciations) were manually removed. Based on the acoustic trace, start and end points were identified for the relevant words and segments and marked on two interval tiers; four critical articulatory moments (T1-4) were identified on a third point tier based on the mouth pressure and oral airflow traces. These are described as follows: T1 - initial lowering of the oral airflow trace (associated with the first closure); T2 - initial lowering of mouth pressure (around the velar closure; only for labial-velar); T3 - lowest mouth pressure value (only for labial-velar); T4 - moment of maximum mouth pressure at the labial release. An example of annotated .wav file is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14 - Overview of standard annotation for the study presented in Chapter 4 (labial-velar on top, bilabial at the bottom)

The resulting corpus includes 74 [kp] items, 32 [gb], 73 [p], 82 [b].

Selected variables were extracted from Praat. These include: duration values (entire word, relevant segments, adjacent segments if nasals or vowels, segment boundaries to T1, T2, T3, and T4 for labial-velar and to T1 and T4 for bilabial stops), oral air flow (sampled at T1, T2, T3, and T4 for labial-velar, and at T1 and T4 for bilabial stops), and mouth pressure (sampled at T1, T2, T3, and T4 for labial-velar, and at T1 and T4 for bilabial stops). Duration is expressed in s, oral airflow in l/s, mouth pressure in cmH₂O. The relevant datasets were manually inspected. Outliers were excluded from final analysis; missing values for bilabial stops at T2 and T3 were assigned NAs.

Descriptive statistics summarising the resulting dataset are presented as bar graphs and scatterplots in §4.3.1-4.3.2. Inferential statistics were performed with

RStudio (RStudio Team 2020) for duration, airflow, and pressure values. We employed Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA, Tabachnick et al. 2013) to explore the effects of “segment type” (independent variable) on the multiple dependent quantitative variables extracted from Praat. These variables were categorised into three groups (“duration values”, “oral airflow”, and “mouth pressure”), and MANOVAs were run on two datasets with differing “segment type” and dependent variable compositions. The first dataset includes four “segment type” values (kp, gb, p, b) and was analysed for all three dependent variable groups. Due to the multidimensional nature of the “duration values” group, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed to reduce dimensionality and extract meaningful patterns. This approach allowed us to assess the overall effect of “segment type” on the combined dependent variables within each group. The second dataset is limited to labial-velar values of “segment type” (kp, gb) but expands the number of dependent variables, introducing additional measures taken at T2 and T3. PCA was again utilised for “duration values” to condense the variables into principal components, which were then analysed using MANOVA. The application of PCA prior to MANOVA for “duration values” in both datasets was key in reducing data complexity and highlighting the underlying structure of the data. This step was crucial for handling the high dimensionality and collinearity among variables, thus ensuring a more robust and interpretable analysis. “Oral airflow” and “mouth pressure” were handled without PCA as they did not raise the same collinearity concerns as “duration values”.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Duration

Duration differences are more prominent in the case of labial-velars than bilabials. On average, voiceless [kp] are longer than voiced [gb]; see Figure 15.

Figure 15 – Labial-velar vs. bilabial segment duration values (with standard error bars)

Segments preceding labial-velar stops appear to be longer (for [kp]) or shorter (for [gb]) than those preceding plain bilabials. Following segments are only shorter than preceding ones in the case of [kp]. Absolute highest following-segment duration values are those reported for [b], with all other sound classes behaving similarly in that position. Though absolute highest preceding-segment duration values are reported for [kp], they appear to fall within the same error range as [b]; see Figure 16.

Figure 16 – Labial-velar- and bilabial-adjacent segment duration values (with standard error bars)

MANOVA results for "duration values" reveal a significant effect of "segment type" on the relevant quantitative variable (i.e., the score of the PCA limited to its first two components, which by themselves explain over 89% of the variance in the corpus). This is true of both the four- and the two-level independent variable datasets, as summarised in Table 10.

Table 10 - MANOVA results ("duration values" for [kp], [gb], [p], [b] vs. labial-velar and bilabial stops)

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	DF	APPROX F	P-VALUE
SEGMENT TYPE (4 LVL)	3	115.05	<.001
SEGMENT TYPE (2 LVL)	1	78.017	<.001

4.3.2 Aerodynamics

Considerably more airflow can be detected at T1 and T4 on labial-velar stops than plain bilabials, with the latter displaying some negative flow (air suction) upon release. This is expected right before the typical surge in airflow accompanying explosive

bursts (see Figure 14). Voiceless labial-velar stops exhibit more positive airflow upon release than their voiced counterparts; see Figure 17.

Figure 17 – Labial-velar and bilabial oral airflow at closure and release (with standard error bars)

Mouth pressure values are consistently higher at T4 than T1. Mouth pressure values at T1 are highest for [gb] and lowest for [kp]. However, labial-velar mouth pressure values at T4 are importantly higher for bilabial, and [p] in particular, than labial-velar stops. Standard error indicates that negative mouth pressure can be found at T4 on both labial-velar stops (and at T1 on [kp]); see Figure 18.

Figure 18 – Labial-velar and bilabial mouth pressure at closure and release (with standard error bars)

Scatterplots are presented in Figure 19 that represent labial-velar oral airflow (top) and mouth pressure (bottom) values at the four articulatory moments, over time (0 on the time axis represents the beginning of the relevant segment). For the two aerodynamic measures, voiced and voiceless labial-velar stops display similar trajectories irrespective of voicing, with suction detected at T2 and T3. T3 mouth pressure levels are markedly lower for [kp] than [gb]. As concerns the timing of the four events, the first closure typically occurs before the sound's acoustic trace is audible, though voiceless and voiced labial-velar stops differ in that, on average, voiced–labial-velar T2 also precedes the sound's left edge. Inter T2-T3 time is longer for [kp] than [gb]. T4 immediately follows T3 in both voicing contexts.

Figure 19 - Schematic aerodynamic trajectories of [kp] and [gb] at the four relevant articulatory moments

MANOVA results for "oral airflow" and "mouth pressure" reveal a significant effect of "segment type" on the variables, as can be seen in Table 11.

Table 11 - MANOVA results (aerodynamics, for [kp], [gb], [p], [b] vs. labial-velar and bilabial stops)

QUALITATIVE VARIABLES	DF	APPROX F	P-VALUE
ORAL AIRFLOW (4 LVL)	3	7.4233	<.001
ORAL AIRFLOW (2 LVL)	1	7.2378	<.001
MOUTH PRESSURE (4 LVL)	3	62.191	<.001
MOUTH PRESSURE (2 LVL)	1	10.636	<.001

Across all analyses, significant p -values consistently point to the critical role of "segment type" in explaining corpus variance. The difference in effect sizes between the two variable groups and across the different levels of "segment type" complexity suggests that the impact of "segment pressure" is more pronounced than on "oral airflow". This pattern holds true irrespective of segmentation granularity, albeit with nuanced differences in magnitude between categorisations.

4.4 Discussion

Data from Sakata confirm previous findings in the literature concerning the relative duration of [kp] and [gb] (Demolin 1992, Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996), with the former exhibiting higher values than the latter, but no specific effects of segment type on labial-velar- and bilabial-adjacent segment duration were detected. Differences in duration between [p] and [b] are less marked but in line with common typological differences between voiced and voiceless segments. Oral airflow values differ significantly between labial-velar and bilabial stops, with the former displaying higher volume flow at both first closure and release. Mouth pressure build-up prior to release is higher for bilabials than labial-velars. Air rarefaction after completion of the second closure is more prominent for [kp] than [gb]. Differences in inter T2-T3 time appear best suited to explain the durational difference between [kp] and [gb], indicating a more prolonged period of air rarefaction in the articulation of [kp] than [gb]. This matches

previous findings concerning the relative salience of voiceless and voiced labial-velar stops in other Bantu languages of the region of interest (Maselli et al. 2021, 2023), and is compatible with mouth pressure levels at T3, for which the two segments have been shown to differ significantly (the longer duration of the articulatory event leading to air rarefaction between the two closures causes a more significant drop in mouth pressure). A cursory analysis of spectral differences between [kp] and [gb] does not offer clear-cut cues to differences in low-frequency energy concentrations ("voicing bar") within the labial-velar category. This might indicate the presence of a glottalic airstream mechanism (Siertsema 1958, Ladefoged 1968a), i.e., a lowering of the larynx, in the articulation of the labial-velar stops reported in this corpus. Differences in T1-T2 timing relative to the acoustic left edge of the labial-velar might be attributable to the fact that voiced labial-velar stops are often preceded by nasals, suggesting that the labial closure already occurs during the nasal articulation. While this consideration exceeds the scope of the present contribution, it might indicate that pre-labial-velar nasals in Sakata are also articulated as labial-velars and therefore assimilate to [gb] (Goldie 1862, Welmers 1968, 1973, Ryder 1987, Cahill & Parkinson 1997). T1-T4 timing is comparable across labial-velar types, in spite of general duration differences between voiced and voiceless labial-velar stops. Negative airflow at T2 indicates that larynx, and possibly tongue body, lowering (and, consequently, air rarefaction in the oral cavity) is initiated before the labial closure is complete. Positive oral airflow values at T4 on labial-velars mark the presence of an egressive pulmonic airstream mechanism with a sudden rise in pressure upon release (Demolin 1991, Conell 1994); lack of a similar phenomenon in bilabials is marked by oral airflow values approximating 0 at T4. Higher mouth pressure values at T4 for bilabials also reflect this difference, with pressure building up throughout the articulation (i.e., without the typical dip at T3 that marks their labial-velar counterparts).

Chapter 5: Nasal retroflexes in North Boma (Bantu B82, Mai-Ndombe, Democratic Republic of Congo)

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Abstract

Retroflex consonants represent a major class of language sounds, but our understanding of their phonetic and phonological properties remains limited. From the standpoint of acoustics, recent contributions are largely lacking. Few full-fledged descriptive works have been made available to empirically establish their presence and characteristics in the world's languages (see Hamann 2002, 2003). Within retroflex consonants, liquids are particularly rare, and very little descriptive and/or theoretical and/or historical research has been conducted on them, with a few exceptions for Australian and Indian languages (Kochetov et al. 2018, 2020; Tabain et al. 2016, 2020). Bantu languages are not included in most broader surveys. Recent fieldwork in the Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo confirms the existence of nasal retroflexes in North Boma (B82), as initially reported by Stappers (1986). This paper presents an acoustic description of these segments, which is the first detailed study of this kind for the Bantu languages of Congo. North Boma nasal retroflexes are shown to constitute a discrete class within the language's nasal inventory. Compared to their non-retroflex counterparts, they are significantly shorter, exhibit lower concentrations of energy in the spectrum with more energy concentrated around their centre of gravity (as well as more peaked energy concentrations), show higher values of F1 and F1 bandwidth and lower values of F2 bandwidth. Furthermore, it is hypothesised that retroflexion might be a phonological substrate feature originating from extinct non-Bantu languages once spoken by foraging communities. This contribution also showcases how detailed phonetic documentation and description are an asset for historical research.

Key words: phonetic documentation, acoustics, retroflexion, nasality, Bantu, diachronic phonology, substrate interference

5.1 Introduction

Retroflexes are a class of language sounds often described by their articulatory property of being produced with the tip of the tongue “curled up to some extent” (Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996: 25). The term “retroflex” has long served as a descriptor for this specific tongue gesture (since at least Pike 1943; see also Dixit 1963, 1990: 190, and the literature reviewed therein). While this definition is not circumscribed to any one place of articulation, the observation that a contrast exists in a number of languages between retroflex and non-retroflex apical consonants led to the further specification of retroflexes as apical post-alveolars, thereby effectively treating the label “retroflex” as that of a specific place of articulation (in line with IPA 1949; see Ladefoged 1971, Bhat 1974), albeit one with great cross-linguistic⁴³ variability. This variability is expressed in terms of a) tongue tip position (apical to sub-apical, see *infra* Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996) and b) nature of the gesture employed (Ladefoged & Bhaskararao 1983). The observation that retroflex sounds are subject to considerable cross-linguistic variation dates as far back as Firth (1948), with remarks on Urdu by Qadri (1930) (see also Dixit 1990, Simonsen, Moen & Cowen 2000). In the literature, the link between retroflexion and retraction has been the object of considerable debate: while originally rebutted by Bhat (1973, 1974),⁴⁴ Hamann (2002) formalises it as a monodirectional implication, meaning that all retroflex sounds would necessarily be retracted, but not vice versa. Building on this premise, Hamann (2003) proposes that the actual “curling back” of the tongue tip is not a necessary part of retroflex articulations, which would be better described by the following properties: apicality, posteriority, presence of a sub-lingual cavity throughout the articulation itself, and retraction (Hamann 2003: 32-39; see Flemming 2003, Boersma & Hamann 2005 for further discussion on this point).

The present contribution represents the first in-detail description of nasal retroflex stops (henceforth, nasal retroflexes) in North Boma (Bantu B82),⁴⁵ a West-Coastal Bantu language spoken on the fringes of the Congo Basin rainforest in southwestern Democratic Republic of Congo. Nasal retroflexes were reported in North Boma for the

⁴³ And possibly inter-personal; see Catford (1968: 310).

⁴⁴ Based on observations by Emeneau (1939) on the vowel system of Badaga, a Dravidian language of India.

⁴⁵ Guthrie’s (1970) referential classification, as updated by Maho (2009).

first time by Stappers (1986), and we collected data specifically to test the validity of that report. In the lexicon-based phylogeny of Pacchiarotti et al. (2019: 185-189), North Boma constitutes, along with Tiene (Bantu B81), Mpe (Bantu B821), and Nunu (B822),⁴⁶ a discrete subclade called Kwa-Kasai North within the Kwilu-Ngounie subbranch of West-Coastal Bantu, itself a major branch of the Bantu family also known as West-Western Bantu (Grollemund et al. 2015, Koile et al. 2022). The specific interest of our line of research lies at the intersection of several different issues.

First, North Boma retroflexes are exclusively nasal.⁴⁷ These constitute the rarest class of retroflex consonants in the world's languages (Tabain et al. 2016, 2020). The description provided in this article will help broaden our understanding of their phonetic and phonological behaviour. A detailed study of the acoustic properties of nasal retroflexes will allow us to compare available results in the literature (Hussain et al. 2017, Tabain et al. 2020), mostly drawn from languages outside Africa, with new information from one of the most severely under-documented linguistic areas of the planet (Hammarström 2016), and to formulate preliminary articulatory hypotheses for future empirical research in the field (i.e., lay the groundwork for further articulatory studies to be conducted with the necessary instrumental equipment).

Second, North Boma is spoken in the Mushie territory of the Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo, north of the Kwa and Mfimi Rivers. Interestingly, while retroflexion itself is not documented in the immediate vicinity of the area where North Boma is spoken, retroflex flaps can be found in the Lotwa Bantu languages of eastern Mai-Ndombe's last surviving foraging communities (Motingea 2010, Maselli 2024). These relic groups, also known as "Batwa", are generally considered the descendants of ancestral hunter-gatherers who inhabited the area before the advent of Bantu speakers (Saïdi Hemedi et al. 2012: 3). Nowadays, all Mai-Ndombe Batwa speak Bantu languages; they are presumed to have shifted to Bantu and to have abandoned their own original languages, which supposedly belonged to one or more unrelated and no longer extant language family/ies (Bahuchet 2012). The occurrence of retroflexion in hunter-gatherer languages is consistent with earlier accounts by Vorbichler (1966/67), who reports retroflex flaps in Efe, a Central Sudanic (Nilo-

⁴⁶ Nasal retroflexes were also found in Nunu. However, due to insufficient data, we do not report on their presence in this contribution.

⁴⁷ Stappers (1986) claims retroflex flaps are phonemic in North Boma, but our data do not support their description. Rather, retroflex flaps, whenever (sporadically) present, seem to be free variants of intervocalic laterals and trills. More information is available in §5.4.

Saharan) language spoken by Bambuti foragers in the Ituri forest (northeastern Democratic Republic of Congo). A pre-Bantu “forest substrate” (Möhlig 1981, Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020, Motingea 2021, Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2022) has already been hypothesised to explain specific phonological features of the Bantu languages of West-Central Africa, which are geographically less widespread but linguistically more diverse than their relatives further east and south (Bostoen 2018). The North Boma case is of particular interest as it could provide new information on retroflexion as another possible substrate feature.

Third, out of 399 languages reported to have a nasal retroflex in their phonological inventory by PHOIBLE (Moran & McCloy 2019), only 43 (mostly from northern and western Australia) present inventories without any obstruent retroflexes, and only 2 (namely Syan, or Saya, a Chadic language of Nigeria, see Schneeberg 1971; and Mandara, or Wandala, another Chadic language spoken in Cameroon and Nigeria, see Fluckinger 1981) display a nasal as their sole retroflex phoneme. North Boma also displays only one nasal retroflex phoneme in its inventory, which is an almost unique typological situation; presence of a phonemic retroflex flap is documented by Stappers (1986) but remains dubious based on our own personal data (see below, §5.4).

This chapter aims to offer an exploratory acoustic description of nasal retroflexes in North Boma. More specifically, it provides as complete an exploration of the available data on North Boma nasal retroflexes as possible, given the following limitations: first, the scarcity of the available data, and second, the lack of balance of our small corpus. Despite these issues, the present account represents the most comprehensive phonetic analysis to date of retroflex sounds in southwestern Congo.

The present contribution is organised as follows: in §5.2, we present an overview of documentary efforts on retroflex sounds in the world’s languages; in §5.3, we describe the technical and environmental aspects related to the data collection and processing phase of our research; in §5.4, we discuss the phonology and historical origins of phonemic nasal retroflexes in North Boma; in §5.5, we offer an acoustic analysis of North Boma nasal retroflexes and adjoining vowels, and we discuss it in the context of the relevant literature on the acoustic correlates of nasal retroflexes in the world’s languages; discussion and conclusions are in §5.6 and §5.7 respectively.

5.2 Documentation of retroflex sounds in Africa and beyond

Several phonological accounts of the properties of retroflexes are present in the literature; a few language-specific phonetic studies (acoustics, articulation, etc.) are also available. Firth (1948) presents palatograms from Marathi (Indo-Aryan), while Švarný & Zvelebil (1955) display palatograms, linguograms, and X-rays of retroflex consonants in several Indian languages, with special focus on Tamil. Other contributions are available on a wide array of languages of India (Heegård & Mørch 2004, Arsenault & Kochetov 2011, Kochetov et al. 2020, Hussain & Mielke 2021 on Kalasha, Indo-Aryan; see also Morgenstierne 1973, Ohala 1994, Spajić, Ladefoged & Bhaskararao 1996, Dart & Nihalani 1999, Hussain et al. 2017, Smith et al. 2013a,b, Kochetov, Faytak & Nara 2019), South-East Asian languages (Qiuwu 2001, Michaud 2006, Thurgood 2009 on retroflexion in East Asia), and Norwegian (Simonsen, Mowen & Coen 2008, Stausland Johnsen 2012, 2013). Numerous fine-grained phonetic analyses are available on several Australian languages (Dixit 1990, Butcher 1995, Hamilton 1996, Tabain 2009, Fletcher, Loakes & Butcher 2014, Tabain & Beare 2016, 2017, Tabain et al. 2016, 2020).

However, to this day, comparatively few studies have been conducted on retroflexes in African languages. Bhat (1973) treats what he defines as “Central” Africa as a major retroflex area:

Another major retroflex area is central Africa -- coast to coast from Guinea to Somali Republic, and Tanzania. Languages belonging to different families and stocks spoken in this area such as SHERBRO (WEST ATLANTIC); EWE and BINI (KWA); HAUSA (CHAD); KANURI (SAHARAN); BAGIRMI, MORU, BIRRI, BONGO, LUGBARA and DAIR (SUDANIC); BERTA; BEDAUYE, GOLLA, and SOMALI (CUSHITIC); WELAMO (OMOTIC); KONDE and MOMBASA SWAHILI (BANTU) are reported to have retroflexed sounds. (Bhat 1973: 14; capitals in the original)

The author does, however, go on to specify that retroflexion is “not a prominent feature in most of the languages of this area” (same page; see similar remarks by Ladefoged 1964: 18, Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996: 25f). Within the Niger-Congo phylum, Merrill

(2022) offers a survey of the occurrence of voiceless rhotic/retroflex consonants in Atlantic and posits that a sound similar to [t̪] or [t̪ʂ] likely goes back to the most recent common ancestor of this family. Outside Atlantic, Laver (1994: 222) mentions the presence of “voiced alveolar retroflex flapped stops” in Gbaya (Ubangi, Sudan; see also Lekens 1952, Samarin 1959, Walker & Samarin 1997) and Shona (Bantu S10, Zimbabwe). Tse (2013, 2015) focusses on the diachrony of retroflexes in Kizigua (Bantu G311, Somalia); another relatively well-documented case is that of retroflex/flapped consonants in Kinyarwanda (Bantu JD61, Rwanda), for which acoustic, articulatory, and phonological accounts are available (Sibomana 1974, Kimenyi 1979, Walker & Mpiranya 2006, Walker, Byrd & Mpiranya 2008). In some western and northern Congo Bantu languages of Equateur and greater Bandundu (Motingea 2010: 205, Maselli 2024; earlier accounts of a similar phenomenon in northeast Congo can be found in Vorbichler 1966/7), the flapped/retroflexed realisation of laterals, rhotics, and occasionally alveolar stops has been attributed to the presence of an alleged hunter-gatherer “Pygmy” substrate (Möhlig 1981), but no detailed phonetic studies of this phenomenon are available. To the best of our knowledge, there are no acoustic studies of retroflex sounds in any Bantu language of Congo besides the one presented here, and very few are available from other corners of the Bantu domain (see above).

5.3 Data collection and processing

The data used for the acoustic analysis (available on OSF: https://osf.io/cmezd/?view_only=a0465124c79a4782bad819a830d21f0e) presented in this article were collected by the first and third authors between June and July 2021, on a field mission in the Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo as part of the first author’s doctoral research project. Data collection took place in Nioki (-2.72037, 17.69001), in the southern part of Mai-Ndombe (Map 6).⁴⁸ The authors

⁴⁸ Following the constitutional reform of 2006 (with subsequent modifications, or “repartitioning”, in 2015), Congolese local governance has been organised into a variety of hierarchical levels of administration (province > territory > sector/chiefdom > grouping > village). Despite its relatively low level on the hierarchy above, Nioki (part of the Kutu territory) represents the second-largest economic centre of the province, and by far its second most multilingual municipality (after Inongo, the provincial capital), which is why several North Boma and Nunu speakers could be found and interviewed there.

recorded word lists, including basic Swadesh-100 lexical items, sentences, and free connected speech, with three local consultants. Additional data were collected at a later stage by the last three authors during a fieldwork mission in Kinshasa in August 2022 through elicitation with the late Léon Mabwakha ma Bonkako, whose memory we wish to honour with the present contribution (see acknowledgments). Elicited materials included a list of approximately 800 words. An overview of the relevant information on the four speakers is provided below:

- Subject A: 35 years, male, first language: North Boma, origin: Mbali (a.k.a. Mbali-Iboma, -2.38, 17.29), mother's origin: Mbali, father's origin: Izana (possibly Izono,⁴⁹ -2.60, 17.56);
- Subject B: 37, male, North Boma, origin: Bobala (-2.56, 17.52), mother: Bobala, father: Izono;
- Subject C: 50, male, North Boma, origin: Mushie (-3.02, 16.92), mother: Mushie, father: Mushie;
- Léon Mabwakha ma Bonkako (no pseudonymisation provided): 80, male, North Boma, origin: Bopaka (-2.49, 17.36), mother: Bopaka, father: Bopaka

⁴⁹ Izono is organised into four *de facto* semi-independent villages. No further information could be retrieved from our consultant as to the exact origin of their father.

Map 6 - The Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo (with the locations provided by the speakers interviewed for the study presented in Chapter 5)

Recording sessions took place indoors, in a relatively quiet environment with no echo discernible in the background. Part of the data was recorded on Roland R-26 and Zoom H-5 devices with their built-in directional microphones, and the rest on the same Roland R-26 device with an external plug-in omnidirectional microphone (Saramonic Lavalier Microphone SR-XLM1) clipped onto the speakers' clothes (sideways from the mouth). The sampling rate was kept at 44.1 kHz; maximum input, whenever verifiable, was set at 75% to minimise clipping; depth was set at 24 bits. The data were then imported into Praat (Boersma 2001) for annotation and analysis. Annotation and transcription of the data collected in 2021 were carried out by the first author and checked against the preliminary description of the sounds of interest by Stappers (1986). The transcription of the data collected in 2022 was carried out by the fourth author, and phonetic annotation of the relevant segments was performed by the first author. The relevant acoustic variables (duration, formant, and spectral moment values; see below) were semi-automatically extracted from Praat by dint of a script specially written by the second author.

Formant values were sampled at 10%, 30%, 50%, 70%, and 90% of the duration of the segments of interest (i.e., nasals and adjacent vowels). We extracted F1, F2, F3, and F4 median values with their relative bandwidths, average bandwidth over F1 to F4, as well as F1 and F2 onset and offset slopes (for vowels: offset slopes for pre-consonantal ones, and onset slopes for post-consonantal ones). Onset slopes were calculated as a function of F1/F2 formant values at 50% of the total duration of the sound of interest minus the same value at the 10% temporal mark, divided by 40% of the total duration of the sound. Conversely, offset slopes were calculated as formant value at 90% minus formant value at 50% on 40% of the segment's total duration:

$$\frac{\text{Formant value at 50\% of the total duration of the sound of interest} - \text{Formant value at 10\%}}{\text{Total duration of the sound of interest} * (40/100)}$$

$$\frac{\text{Formant value at 90\% of the total duration of the sound of interest} - \text{Formant value at 50\%}}{\text{Total duration of the sound of interest} * (40/100)}$$

Formant transitions have been the focus of a lot of research on coronal oppositions, especially in relation to retroflexion (Halle, Hughes & Radley 1957, Delattre, Liberman & Cooper 1962, Butcher 1995, Iskarous, Fowler & Whalen 2010, Rhone & Jongman 2012). In particular, a lowered F3 both on the vowel preceding the sound and on the first part of the sound itself is considered an indicator of retroflexion (Steriade 1995, 2001a, Tabain 2009, 2011, 2012). F4 is also to some extent affected by the same phenomenon and a lowered F4 has been associated with retroflex articulations in the world's languages (Hussain et al. 2017). On the other hand, less attention has been paid to spectral moments as cues to articulatory configurations of the vocal tract in the production of retroflexes (Tabain et al. 2016, Themistocleous, Fyndanis & Tsapkini 2021).

Spectral moment values correspond to the sounds' centre of gravity, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis (Forrest et al. 1988, Nittrouer 1995, Tanner et al. 2005, Li, Edwards & Beckman 2009, Schindler & Draxler 2013). In spectral moment analysis, the sound's power spectrum is treated as a probability distribution and its mathematical moments are calculated accordingly (Li et al. 2009: 3), as shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20 – Centre of gravity (μ), standard deviation (σ), skewness, and kurtosis of a probability distribution. A = normal distribution, with corresponding μ and σ ; B = positively skewed distribution and corresponding shift in mean (dotted vertical line); C = peaked distribution with positive kurtosis (source: Tanner et al. 2005)

Spectra displaying a dominant mode tend to exhibit a negative correlation between the first moment (centre of gravity) and the resonating cavity's length, offering a rough indication of constriction position. The second spectral moment (standard deviation) serves the primary purpose of distinguishing between a broad, dispersed spectrum and sharper, more concentrated energy distributions. The third spectral moment (skewness) is correlated to articulation placement. Broadly, a positive value suggests an accumulation of energy in the lower frequencies below the mean. The fourth spectral moment (kurtosis) can help distinguish tongue posture differences, which in turn contribute to alterations in the spectral shape's peak concentration (see Li et al. 2009: 3). Spectral moment analysis has been applied most profitably to the study of noisy spectra such as those of fricatives; in the case of nasals, spectral moment analysis has been used most recently by Tabain et al. (2016). We believe that, given the nature of our corpus and the necessarily suboptimal circumstances of acoustic data collection in field settings, spectral moment analysis is better suited than other, traditional methods of nasal spectrum analysis (Recasens 1983), such as antiformant analysis, to provide a preliminary description of nasal retroflexes in North Boma.

Spectral moments were calculated differently for vowels and consonants. For vowels, the analysis range was set at 0 to 5,000 Hz, and for consonants at 1,000 to 5,000 Hz (in a way similar to Tabain et al. 2016). This is because, in voiced consonants, energy concentrations lower than 1,000 Hz essentially correspond to voicing, and the aim of moment measurements is rather to capture place of articulation (i.e., features

of the supralaryngeal tract). On the other hand, in the case of vowels, information related to F1 is typically located below 1,000 Hz, which justifies the range selection mentioned above. Vowel and consonant values are never compared directly in this paper, which allows for the adoption of two different set ranges.

For the purposes of this study, spectral moment values were sampled at 10%, 50%, and 90% of the duration of the segments of interest. We obtained average formant and spectral-moment values for the whole segment (from 10% to 90% of the duration). Spectral moments were calculated in two separate ways:

- *Over the entire segment.* This method is largely inspired by DiCano's (2021) script, (version n 4.0, updated in 2021; Haskins: https://www.acsu.buffalo.edu/~cdicanio/scripts/Time_averaging_for_fricatives_4.0.praat), based (among others) on Shadle (2012) and Forrest et al. (1988). This method was originally developed for fricatives. It involves a) analysing the central 80% of the consonant by calculating several spectra over consecutive windows within this larger 80%-duration window, and then b) averaging the spectra before measuring the moments: "Within time-averaging, a number of DFTs are taken from across the duration of the fricative. These DFTs are averaged for each token and then the moments are calculated. The analyzed duration of the fricative is always equivalent to the center 80% of the total duration, cutting off the transitions" (DiCano 2021). Analysis parameters were adjusted to account for duration variations across the corpus, which contains very short segments (retroflex: average approx. 50 ms \pm 20) and others over twice as long (other consonants: average approx. 110 ms \pm 55). Thus, the number of windows used to calculate the spectra equals 5 windows of 15 ms each. In practice, if the segment was 110 ms, we discarded the first 11 and the last 11 ms, which results in 5 almost consecutive windows of 15 ms (inter-window signal portions of 3 ms were not analysed). If the segment was shorter, windows could overlap up to a maximum of 50% of their duration (to avoid overanalysing the central portion of the segment), which accounts for segments down to 45 ms;
- *In a single window positioned at specific points of the segment.* This second method is based on Tabain et al. (2016): a 20 ms window centred around the middle portion of the segment, with analysis over a frequency range of 1000 to

5000 Hz (for consonants). The main difference with Tabain et al. (2016), and the previous method, is that we performed the measurement of spectral moments directly via Praat's algorithm. Note that, unlike Tabain et al. (2016), we also adopted the same procedure at 10% and 90% of the segment's total duration, both for vowels and consonants. For segments shorter than 100 ms, this includes a very short portion of the adjacent segment in the relevant window. For example, in the case of a nasal segment of 50 ms, centring our analysis window around 10% of the sound's duration (i.e., at 5 ms from the start of the segment), our analysis would start at -5 ms (5 ms before the segment boundary, or the last 5 ms of the preceding vowel) and end at +15 ms. Given that a) we want to capture transition effects, and b) the values remain very small, roughly overlapping manual segmentation error (5 ms), we hold this is an acceptable trade-off for a method overall better-tailored to our specific needs.

The values measured for "duration" and "spectral moments" risk to obfuscate the effect of place of articulation on the phonetic realisation of the sounds at hand – the former, in that nasal retroflexes and non-retroflexes mostly occur in different contexts where duration differences are expected irrespective of place of articulation, and the latter, because spectral moments are sensitive to lots of different factors, such as background noise and how much vowel is included in the measurement window, which risk to compound the duration issue. In order to address these points, modified versions of the dataset were produced, one balanced for duration (i.e., only including observations with duration values lower than 0.01 s) and one without spectral moment values (see below, §5.5).

The datasets resulting from the extraction of the parameters listed above were then imported into R and RStudio (RStudio Team 2019, R Core Team 2020), for the purposes of statistical analysis, and mined with FactoMineR (Lê et al.2008).

5.4 Synchronic and diachronic phonology of North Boma nasal retroflexes

In this section, we discuss the phonemic status, phonotactic distribution, and historical origins of /ŋ/ in North Boma. First, we present the consonantal inventory of North Boma as presented by Stappers (1986: 1), see Table 12. All consonants in Table 12 are phonemic, according to Stappers. Brackets around /g/ are meant to signal that this phoneme has a very limited distribution and occurs only after /ŋ/. Brackets around /ɾ/ mean that what Stappers describes as a flap would appear to be a sporadic free variant of intervocalic /l/ and /r/ based on our data. Stappers uses the following grapheme/phoneme correspondences: <r> for [r], <j> for [ɟ], and <y> for [j].

Table 12 – North Boma consonant phonemes (Stappers 1986: 1)

	LABIALS		LABIODENTALS		ALVEOLARS		RETROFLEXES	PALATALS		VELARS	UVULARS
NASAL	m				n		ŋ	ɲ		ŋ	
LATERAL					l		(ɾ)				
PLOSIVE	p	b			t			c	ɟ	k	(g)
FRICATIVE			f	v	s	z					ʁ
AFFRICATE					tf	dv		kf		gv	
APPROXIMANT								j		w	

Stappers (1986: 4) offers minimal pairs as evidence for the consonantal inventory in Table 1. As for the nasal retroflex, the minimal pair Stappers (1986: 4) provides contrasts /n/ with /ŋ/ in C₂ position as follows: *ɛkání* ‘we had wished’ vs *ɛkáŋí* ‘we had danced’. Although this pair (as well as all others) has been confirmed by the late Léon Mabwakha ma Bonkako, there are only very few words in the North Boma variety described by Stappers (1986), which appears to be nearly identical to the one spoken

by Léon, where /n/ occurs in C₂ position within a C₁V₁C₂V₂C₃V₃ template (where C stands for consonant and V for vowel). This is because, as we show in this section, most Proto-Bantu *n and *nd in C₂ position became /ŋ/ in North Boma. In our data, /m/, /ŋ/, /ɲ/, /ɓ/, /r/, /l/, /t/, and /n/ are the only consonants which occur in C₂ position in North Boma. Among these, the phonemic status of /ŋ/ is confirmed by additional pairs such as *mwá:ɓà* ‘year’ vs *mwá:ŋà* ‘child’ and near minimal pairs such as *ŋk:áŋà* ‘I dance’ vs *ŋk:ámá* ‘hundred’.

Historically, /ŋ/ is the regular reflex of Proto-Bantu *n and *nd in C₂ position within the root, as can be seen in (1). In (1), slashes separate singular and plural forms of the same noun and hyphens show morphological segmentation of noun class prefixes and noun roots. In North Boma, /ŋ/ never occurs in C₁ position within a C₁V₁C₂V₂C₃V₃ template. Throughout this section, a given North Boma synchronic form is posited as the reflex of a protoform. This protoform, conventionally preceded by an asterisk in historical linguistics, is accompanied by a number which identifies a unique entry in the Bantu Lexical Reconstruction 3 database (BLR) (Bastin et al. 2002). This database contains nearly 10,000 Bantu lexical reconstructions of variable time depth (Bostoen and Bastin 2016).

(1) C ₂ *n	BLR 3203 *jánà ‘child’	>	<i>mw-áŋà/mj-áŋà</i>
	BLR 3472 *jínò ‘tooth’	>	<i>zj-úŋù/mj-úŋù</i>
	BLR 5531 *tíni ‘piece’	>	<i>kè-t:íŋi/bè-t:íŋi</i>
	BLR 1805 *kín ‘to dance’	>	<i>kò-k:áŋ-à⁵⁰</i>
	BLR 2041 *kún ‘to plant’	>	<i>kò-kwán-à</i>
	BLR 661 *còn ‘to write’	>	<i>kò-c:óŋ-ò</i>
C ₂ *nd ⁵¹	BLR 579 *cíndí ‘squirrel’	>	<i>Ø-nsí:ŋí/ Ø-nsí:ŋí</i>
	BLR 1446 *gòndé ‘crocodile’	>	<i>Ø-ŋgò:ŋé/ Ø-ŋgò:ŋé</i>
	BLR 543 *céndé ‘thorn’	>	<i>Ø-nsjéŋé/ Ø-nsjéŋé</i>
	BLR 1628 *jùndò ‘hammer’	>	<i>Ø-ŋjú:ŋù/Ø-ŋjú:ŋù</i>
	BLR 6697 *pònd ‘to rot’	>	<i>kò-pòŋ-ò</i>
	BLR 2044 *kúnd ‘to love’	>	<i>kò-kwán-à</i>

⁵⁰ In North Boma, the onset consonant in a syllable carrying a high tone is phonetically realised as a geminate.

⁵¹ We only have one example out of 130 words with /ŋ/ or /n/ in C₂/C₃ where /ŋ/ is the reflex of *nt but in a reconstruction which is only tentative, namely *tant ‘bite’. Certainly, historical *nt simplified to *n but the evidence is virtually non-existent to claim that this outcome also underwent the shift to /ŋ/.

BLR 2125 *kùnd ‘to bury’ > kò-kfwáṅà

By contrast, /n/ in C₁ is the regular reflex of Proto-Bantu *n as shown in (2). Note that *nd did not occur in C₁ position in Proto-Bantu except across morpheme boundaries, i.e., whenever *d was preceded by a homorganic class 9/10 nasal prefix N-, which was often reanalysed as part of the root as shown in (2), see, e.g., Ø-ndú:ṅú/ Ø-ndú:ṅú, historically *n-dú:ṅú*.

- (2) C₁ *n BLR 5428 *nuku ‘meat’ > mù-n:úḅù/mì-n:úḅù
 BLR 3683 *nàì ‘four’ > nî
 BLR 2286 *nók ‘rain’ > kò-n:óḅ-ò
 BLR 2342 *nú ‘drink’ > kò-nw-á
 BLR 4340 *dùndà ‘fish sp.’ > Ø-ndú:ṅú/Ø-ndú:ṅú ‘electric fish’
 BLR 1561 *jàdí ‘lightning’ > Ø-ndzàlí/Ø-ndzàlí

In North Boma, nasal + plosive sequences in C₂ position underwent reduction in favour of the nasal, i.e., *mb > /m/, e.g. Ø-ndzà:mí ‘God’ (< BLR 3196 *jàmbé), *ṅg > /ŋ/, e.g. è-káṅà/ṅ-káṅà ‘guinea-fowl’ (< BLR 1720 *káṅà).⁵² Given the pervasiveness of /ŋ/ in the lexicon, the most likely scenario is that this sound change occurred only after the simplification of *nd > /n/, once the historical simple nasal C₂ *n had merged with the *n historically originating from the simplification of C₂ *nd. In Bantu languages, the vowel preceding a nasal cluster (nasal + plosive) usually lengthens (Hyman 2019). This can be seen in words such as *n-sí:ṅí/n-sí:ṅí* ‘squirrel’ and *ṅ-gò:ṅé/ṅ-gò:ṅé* ‘crocodile’ in (1). In turn, lengthened vowels are an ideal phonetic environment for the emergence of diphthongs in West-Coastal Bantu languages (Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2012; Pacchiarotti et al. 2021). Indeed, there is evidence that diphthongisation of long vowels also happened in North Boma, as in *n-sjéṅé/n-sjéṅé* ‘thorn’ and *kò-kwáṅ-à* ‘to love’ in (1), but, perhaps by analogy with historically lengthened vowels preceding nasal clusters, diphthongisation is also found in words containing historical short vowels such as *kò-kwáṅ-à* ‘to plant’ in (1), as well as *ì-kjáṅá/mà-kjáṅá* ‘dance’ (< BLR 1807 *kínà) and *kò-mjáṅ-à* ‘to swallow’ (< BLR 2190 *mìn). Similarly, and perhaps also

⁵² /ŋ/ is the only outcome of this cluster reduction process which underwent loss in the vast majority of the relevant lexical items, e.g. e-baa/m-baa ‘jaw, chin’ (< BLR 108 *banga).

due to analogical change, not all vowels historically preceding a nasal cluster were lengthened, see, e.g., *mù-kàṅú/mì-kàṅú* ‘news’ (< BLR 1706 *kàndá ‘letter’).⁵³

Nevertheless, there are a few lexical items which appear to have escaped the change *n/*nd > /ŋ/ in C₂ and rather preserved /n/, giving rise to the minimal pair *εkání* ‘we had wished’ vs *εkáṅí* ‘we had danced’ which Stappers (1986) uses to show that /ŋ/ contrasts with /n/ in C₂. In most instances, we find no readily identifiable conditioning environment that could have blocked this diachronic sound change. Although a lot of the nouns preserving /n/ in C₂ end in /i/ as can be seen in (3), there are just as many cases where a final /i/ is preceded by /ŋ/, as shown in (4). In the same vein, the different vowels preceding C₂ /n/ in (3) cannot be considered as a conditioning environment preventing the sound change *n/*nd > /ŋ/ from occurring because /u/, /ʊ/, and /a/ are also found in lexical items where C₂ *n/*nd did become /ŋ/, see (1).

- | | | | |
|-----|--------------------------------|---|---|
| (3) | BLR 1545 *kùndú ‘stomach’ | > | <i>ì-kfùní/mà-kfùní</i> ‘belly’ |
| | BLR 1627 *jùṅì ‘bird’ | > | <i>Ø-ṅúṅì/Ø-ṅúṅì</i> |
| | BLR 2390 *pándà ‘branch, fork’ | > | <i>Ø-mpání/Ø-mpání</i> ‘branch’ |
| | BLR 8292 *jání ‘sun’ | > | <i>mw-ání/mj-ání</i> ‘light, day’ |
| (4) | BLR 2206 *món ‘see’ | > | <i>kè-m:ón-i/bè-m:ón-i</i> ‘fortune teller’ |
| | BLR 579 *cíndí ‘squirrel’ | > | <i>Ø-nsí:ṅí/Ø-nsí:ṅí</i> |
| | BLR 2577 *pínd ‘(be) black’ | > | <i>m-pìṅ-í</i> |
| | BLR 9667 *jini ‘pubes’ | > | <i>mù-zì:ṅí/mì-zì:ṅí</i> ‘anus’ |

Additionally, three lexical items indicate that some of the few synchronic occurrences of /n/ in C₂ position originate from Proto-Bantu *nj, phonetically probably [ŋ] or [ŋ̃], e.g. *kè-kání/bè-kání* ‘hand’ (< BLR 1329 *gàṅjà), *n-zén:é* ‘cricket’ (< BLR 1583 *njénjé), or Proto-Bantu *ny, phonetically probably [ŋ], e.g. *kò-ṅón-ò* ‘to twist’ (< BLR 1945 *kóny), *kò-ṅán-à* ‘to swim’ (< BLR *nyány). The fact that *n as the reflex of *nj and *ny did not merge with *n originating from either Proto-Bantu *n or *nd in C₂ possibly indicates that the change in *nj/*ny > n occurred after *n/*nd > *n > ŋ. Otherwise, the former nasal would have undergone retroflexion too.

⁵³ *mù-kàṅú/mì-kàṅú* ‘news’ could alternatively be a reflex of BLR 1317 *gano ‘wisdom’ or BLR 1318 *gano ‘tale’, in which case the short vowel would be expected.

Finally, we discuss occurrences of /ŋ/ in C₃ position. In this position, /ŋ/ in North Boma is the reflex of a historical *n in the same phonotactic position, e.g. *mù-sámúŋù* < (BLR 433 *cààmànò), or the outcome of a common Bantu nasal harmony process whereby a stop becomes a nasal (usually maintaining the same place of articulation as the stop), whenever the root contains a nasal consonant, e.g. *è-béméŋé/m-béméŋé* ‘mosquito’ (< BLR 7535 *bémbédé). Nasal harmony also occurred in verb stems with derivational suffixes such as *-ad, *-Id and *-ud as in *kò-zímàŋ-à* ‘to forget’ (< BLR 5716 *dímbad), *kò-sémòŋò* ‘to slip’ (< BLR 509 *cèdɪmɔk, likely to have undergone metathesis to *cèmɪdɔk), *è-ŋ-kfúmèŋé* ‘stuttering’ (< BLR 5379 *kúkumɪd ‘stammer’), *kò-k:ámòŋ-ò* ‘to squeeze’ (< BLR 1691 *kámud), see also *kò-bímàŋ-à* ‘to sleep’ (< BLR 6025 *bítam, likely to have undergone metathesis to *bímat). Yet, there is evidence that in a few cases the nasal harmony process did give rise to /n/ instead of /ŋ/, see, e.g., *kò-zíyìnà* ‘to learn’ (< BLR 3338 *jíg), *kò-závané* ‘to spread out in the sun’ (< BLR 3206 *jánɪk), and *kò-s:íyínè* ‘push back’ (< BLR 2934 *tíndɪk). The last two examples suggest that metathesis might have played a role in these seemingly irregular outcomes, e.g. *jánɪk > *jakɪn* > *jakan* > *závané*; *tíndɪk > *tíkɪnd* > *tíkɪn* > *s:íyínè*.⁵⁴ Metathesis in verb stems is known to be common in one of North Boma’s closest relatives, i.e., Tiene (Ellington 1977, Hyman 2010).

Whatever the case might be, synchronically, the consonantal portion of a typical Proto-Bantu derivational suffix such as applicative *-Id always surfaces as /ŋ/ if the verb stem contains a nasal, see /kò-túm-Id-à/ ‘INF-send-APPL-FV’ > [kòtúmèŋé], /kò-tfúm-Id-a/ ‘INF-sew-APPL-FV’ > [kòtfúmèŋé] but /kò-kàb-Id-a/ ‘INF-offer-APPL-FV’ > [kòkàbéri]. Whenever the verb root contains /ŋ/ in C₂ and is followed by an applicative suffix which is then realised as /ŋ/ due to nasal harmony, the outcome of a sequence of two [ŋ] after vowel apocope yields [n:], as shown in Table 13 with the synchronic derivation of the applicative form *kò-m:án:-è* [kòm:án:è] from its corresponding root *kò-m:áŋ-à* ‘to finish’. For ease of exposition in Table 2 we only show the root plus the final vowel without the infinitive prefix *kò-*.

⁵⁴ With possible spirantisation of /t/ > [s] (see Schadeberg 1995, Bostoen 2008).

Table 13 – Synchronic derivation of the applicative form *kò-m:án-nè* [kòm:án:è] from its corresponding root *kò-m:áŋ-à* ‘to finish’ in North Boma

root-final vowel	<i>m:áŋ-à</i> ‘to finish’
applicative derivation	<i>m:áŋ-ɪd-à</i>
nasal harmony	<i>m:áŋ-ɪŋ-à</i>
final vowel height harmony	<i>m:áŋ-ɪŋ-è</i>
applicative vowel apocope	<i>m:áŋ-ŋ-è</i>
retroflex > alveolar	<i>m:án-n-è</i>

The emergence of [n:] out of a sequence of two [ŋ] is also observed with derivational suffixes other than the applicative. Compare *kò-kfwáŋ-à* ‘to bury’ (< BLR 2125 *kùnd) and *kò-kfún:ò* ‘to dig up’ (< BLR 2126 *kùndɪd). Based on the evidence we have gathered so far, one could imagine a chain of changes like the following: *kùndɪd > *kfúnɪd > *kfúnɪd > *kfúnɪŋ/kfúnɪŋ > *kfúnŋ/kfúnŋ > kfún:.⁵⁵ The verb form *kò-b:ín:ò* ‘to dig up’ (< BLR 209 *b:índ ‘obstruct’) probably underwent a similar chain of changes. Thus, it seems that C₂ [n:] derives from a C₁V₁C₂V₂C₃V₃ template structure where C₂ was /ŋ/ and C₃V₃ is a derivational suffix which underwent nasal harmony and was realised by default as /ŋ/.

In summation, /ŋ/ is a phonotactically restricted phoneme in North Boma B82 which occurs only in C₂/C₃ position within a C₁V₁C₂V₂C₃V₃ template. Historically, /ŋ/ is the reflex of Proto-Bantu *n and *nd. The *nd sequence simplified to *n at some point in the history of this language and merged with Proto-Bantu *n. Etymological *n as well as *n deriving from the cluster reduction of *nd developed into /ŋ/ in C₂/C₃ position. In C₁ position, Proto-Bantu *n and *nd were maintained as such. However, this sound change did not affect all lexical items, so much so that some historical *n (whether from Proto-Bantu *n or *nd) were maintained as alveolar nasals in C₂ instead of undergoing retroflexion. Other synchronic C₂ /n/ in North Boma originate in Proto-Bantu C₂ *nj or *ny.

⁵⁵ In this hypothetical chain, the spirantisation of *k > /kf/ and the tonal dissimilation of *LL to HL (BLR 2125 *kùnd-à > *kfwáŋ-à* ~ *kfún:ò*) are arbitrarily placed at the beginning. We have no evidence for their seriation with respect to other changes.

In §5.8.1, we provide a comparative list of all lexical items we found which contain /ŋ/ or /n/ in C₂ and C₃ positions in the data from our fieldwork missions (2021 and 2022) as well as in the grammar sketch of Stappers (1986).

5.5 Acoustic characteristics of nasal retroflexes in North Boma

5.5.1 Preliminary observations

Broadly speaking, clear spectral cues to tease retroflex and non-retroflex nasal sounds apart in North Boma are scarce. However, a few preliminary observations can be drawn from the comparison of word-internal nasal oppositions as shown in Figure 21 with [inãŋa] ‘eight’.

Figure 21 - Oscillogram, spectrogram, and segmentation of one repetition of the North Boma word [inãŋa] 'eight' as produced by Subject C; audio file available on OSF (name: Figure 2 audio)

The retroflex segment is considerably shorter than the alveolar; this is compatible with our understanding of transient articulations like those of flaps and taps (see Laver 1994: 221-227, Bickford & Floyd 2006: 141-142, Warner et al. 2009, Derrick & Gick 2011).⁵⁶ However, effects of position may also come into play, with consonants in C₂ position undergoing shortening (see below, §5.5.2).

In a handful of interesting cases, a high-frequency spike in intensity (circled in red in Figure 22) can be observed in the spectrogram when a nasal retroflex occurs (especially in the speech of Subject C).

⁵⁶ Following Bickford & Floyd's (2006) indications, the articulatory difference between a nasal retroflex and a nasalised flap ([ŋ]/[ɾ̃]) should be minimal (possibly restricted to segment duration and/or the presence of flicking). It is worth mentioning that a similar problem is tackled tangentially by Thayer (1974: 212) when sketching a comparative phonology of Sara-Bongo-Bagirmi languages from the Central African Republic – Chad – South Sudan border area; see also Bhat (1973: 30), Stevens & Blumstein (1975: 231-232), Harnsberger (1998: 29, 56), Arsenault (2017: 24fn).

Figure 22 – Realisations of North Boma nasals. To the left: spectrogram of [kokfã:ŋa] ‘to bury’; to the right: spectrogram of [mob:ã:ŋo] ‘expensive’; both pronounced by Subject C (audio files available on OSF as Fig 3 – 1 audio and Fig 3 – 2 audio respectively)

At the same time, a sudden increase in energy can be observed on the oscillogram, accompanied by a peak in intensity on the spectrum; see Figure 23.

Figure 23 – Realisation of a North Boma nasal. To the left: spectrogram and oscillogram of the nasal retroflex in [kokfã:ŋa] ‘to bury’ (Subject C, on OSF: Fig 3 – 1 audio); to the right: spectrum of the section indicated on the oscillogram, with spike intensity signalled in red

This very short span of higher-frequency noise might point in the direction of a transient percussion, such as the one effected by the tongue against the palate in some flapped articulations (see also Švarný & Zvelebil 1955: 390). However, we are dealing at best with a weak indicator since it does not occur consistently across realisations.

5.5.2 Descriptive statistics

A series of descriptive statistics were performed to summarise our dataset (which includes [m], allophonic [m] in pre-labiodental position, [n], [ɲ], [ŋ] and [ŋ]).⁵⁷ Full results are displayed in §5.8.2. On average, nasal retroflexes appear to be a lot shorter than their non-retroflex counterparts (their length is roughly half that of the other nasals; see Figure 24). This might be in keeping with our preliminary observation (see above) that nasal retroflexes behave more like flaps than nasal stops.

Figure 24 – Average duration of North Boma nasals

This effect may also be enhanced by blurriness at the relevant segmental edges. Considering that these sounds are particularly subject to internal changes in articulatory targets, it becomes apparent that assigning clear-cut segmental boundaries can be complicated and possibly result in the identification of a core section without its more coarticulated boundaries.

Figure 25 summarises average formant and bandwidth values for the six nasal places of articulation.

⁵⁷ The relevant datasets are available on OSF (Data folder).

Figure 25 – Median formant values (horizontal lines) for six types of North Boma nasals with their relative average bandwidth (bars)

F2-4 values appear to be lower for retroflexes than for their non-retroflex counterparts; contrary to our expectations, this effect appears to be greater for F2 and F4 than for F3. Retroflex consonants' F2 trajectories are expected to be largely language-dependent (Hamann 2003: 59). Since articulatory predictions concerning the acoustics of retroflex sounds suggest that the presence of a posterior articulation would result in raised F2 (via the insertion of a low-frequency resonance between F2 and F3, see, e.g., Stevens 1998: 436ff), it can be hypothesised that nasal retroflexes in North Boma are characterised by tongue retraction, resulting in lower F2 values, more than by other cross-linguistically well-attested retroflexion mechanisms; see Dart & Nihalani's (1999) data on Malayalam. In turn, the inter-F3/4 spectral region in retroflexes has often been claimed to be narrower than in other articulations (Stevens & Blumstein 1975: 219), which would explain why F4 is more significantly lowered than F3.

F1 bandwidth values appear to be greater for nasal retroflexes than for their non-retroflex counterparts, perhaps indicating the presence of a more diffuse murmur, with

more energy concentrated in the lower regions of the spectrum. This could be achieved through lengthening of both the front and back cavity, which is compatible with a more perpendicular position of the tongue against the passive articulator (thereby minimising the tongue-palate contact area); if coupled with the notion that F2 values tend to be lower on retroflexes than on their non-retroflex counterparts, this observation points in the direction of a (sub-)apical alveolar articulation.

Figure 26 summarises spectral moment results in North Boma.

Figure 26 - Average spectral moment values for six types of North Boma nasals (95% confidence interval); centre of gravity and standard deviation are expressed in Hz, while skewness and kurtosis are dimensionless (see Harrington 2010: 41)

Centre of gravity values are lower for retroflexes than non-retroflexes, while the effect of standard deviation is less patent. Skewness and kurtosis values appear to

distinguish nasal retroflexes from their non-retroflex counterparts, in that the former score higher average values than the latter. Tentatively, this could suggest that nasal retroflexes have higher (and more peaked)⁵⁸ concentrations of energy in the spectral area below their centroid frequency.

5.5.3 Multiple Factor Analysis

A Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA) was performed on the dataset. MFA is an extension of Principal Component Analysis (PCA). In order to understand how MFA works, let us first review the fundamentals of PCA. PCA is a dimensionality reduction technique used to simplify complex datasets by transforming them into a new set of variables called “principal components”. These principal components are linear combinations of the original dimensions. They are arranged in order of importance, with the first component explaining the most variation in the data, the second component being the second most indicative, and so on. In PCA terms, “dimension” refers to the original variables or attributes that were used as input data. In this sense, the term “dimension” refers to a variable or feature within a dataset. More specifically, it represents one of the original attributes or measurements that are being analysed. Dimensions are defined as percentages of total inertia (a measure of the points’ weighted spread), and their correlation to specific variables indicates to what extent those variables can explain the percentage(s) of inertia they express. PCA aims to reduce these dimensions into a smaller set of components, i.e., the principal components, that capture the essential information in the data while minimising redundancy. These principal components are the new dimensions explaining the behaviour of the data.

MFA is a factorial method specifically designed to analyse datasets where variables are structured into groups. It is “tailored to handle multiple data tables that measure sets of variables collected on the same observations” (Abdi et al. 2013). In practice,

⁵⁸ Skewness and kurtosis, the way they were defined above, are not entirely independent of one another; see the following passage: “Skewed distributions are always leptokurtic [...]. Among the several alternative measures of kurtosis that have been proposed (none of which has often been employed), is one which adjusts the measurement of kurtosis to remove the effect of skewness [...]. There is much confusion about how kurtosis is related to the shape of distributions. Many authors of textbooks have asserted that kurtosis is a measure of the peakedness of distributions, which is not strictly true. It is easy to confuse low kurtosis with high variance, but distributions with identical kurtosis can differ in variance, and distributions with identical variances can differ in kurtosis” (Wuensch 2005: 3).

MFA takes a set of observations described by a certain number of variables and yields a measure of the degree to which each variable group explains variance in the set (see Abdi & Valentin 2007). Several sets of variables (continuous or categorical) are analysed in two steps: a PCA is run on the quantitative variables (in our case, clustered into the following groups: “duration”, “formant values”, “bandwidth values”, “slope values”, and “spectral moments”), and an estimate and p -value of the correlation between all (supplementary) qualitative variables (in our case, “segment” and “retroflexion”) and the dimensions (principal components) produced by the first PCA are then provided.

MFA is used when more than one set of variables has been measured for the same observations. In our case, several sets of variables (both quantitative and qualitative, see above) have been measured for the same individual observations (in this case, North Boma nasals). Therefore, MFA allows us to see what quantitative variables best explain variance in the corpus, and which of the two qualitative variables (“segment” and “retroflexion”) better describes the North Boma nasal acoustic space – in other words, we expect to see if nasal retroflexes constitute a compact and separate group from the other nasals of North Boma, and what acoustic parameters best explain their difference from those other nasals.

MFA have also been conducted on slightly modified versions of the dataset, one balanced by duration (i.e., only including observations with duration values lower than 0.01 s) and one without spectral moment values.

For the purposes of this presentation, we will only comment on individual factor maps;⁵⁹ these graphically represent each group of observations (average values) with its values for all the sets of variables mentioned above and its barycentre on the plane described by the two top dimensions of the PCA. See, for example, Figure 27.

⁵⁹ Other graphs are made available on OSF, see MFA folder.

Figure 27 - Individual factor map of the entire North Boma nasal dataset

In Figure 27, an individual factor map is presented for the entire dataset (all consonants, all duration values) with all variable groups. Each observation set (labelled in bold in the picture) is connected to coloured squares representing its average value for the five variable group measurements of interest; the label itself is placed at the barycentre of these average values on the plane. The plane is defined by the first two principal components (here, dimensions 1 and 2)⁶⁰ of the PCA. As can be seen, retroflex and non-retroflex segments constitute two separate groups with very distinct acoustic characteristics. Along the dimension 1 axis, which accounts for around one fourth of the dataset's total inertia (in other words, it explains one fourth of the variance, the "behaviour", of the data), retroflex and non-retroflex segments exhibit inverse correlations for almost every variable, except for bandwidth values for the nasal alveolar. Dimension 1 is described by the following characteristics (Table 14):⁶¹

⁶⁰ Let the reader be reminded that, in PCA terms, "dimension" refers to the original variables or attributes that were used as input data, and PCA aims to reduce these dimensions into a smaller set of components that capture the essential information in the data while minimising redundancy. Therefore, on the plane at hand, the variables of interest are plotted against the two principal components of the PCA originally performed on the dataset; these principal components are known as "Dimension 1" and "Dimension 2".

⁶¹ Complete dimension descriptions are available on OSF; only immediately relevant ones will be commented on in the prose.

Table 14 - Top 4 quantitative variables directly and inversely correlated to dimension 1 of the MFA summarised in Figure 27

TOP VARIABLES	CORRELATION	P-VALUE (ALPHA = .05)
DURATION	0.7116837	2.596842e-91
F2 BANDWIDTH	0.6837978	1.056055e-81
CENTRE OF GRAVITY	0.6816888	5.090453e-81
F2 ONSET SLOPE	0.6535843	1.940642e-72
F1	-0.2850274	2.228860e-12
F1 BANDWIDTH	-0.2940985	4.076643e-13
KURTOSIS	-0.5151657	6.712375e-41
SKEWNESS	-0.5346865	1.718151e-44

Retroflexes are significantly shorter than non-retroflexes; they exhibit lower F2 bandwidth values, have a lower centre of gravity, and tend to be characterised by negative F2 onset slopes; at the same time, they show higher spectral tilt (skewness) values, higher kurtosis, and higher F1 and F1 bandwidth values. This suggests that nasal retroflexes show higher concentrations of energy in the lower regions of the spectrum around the centre of gravity; duration values are compatible with the possibility that North Boma retroflexes behave like nasalised flaps.

As mentioned above, MFA were also run on modified versions of the dataset to account for duration biases and other related issues, including the sensitivity of spectral moment values to background noise and vocalic context. Figure 28 presents individual factor maps of a duration-balanced set (restricted to segments shorter than 0.01 s) and of the same set as above (Figure 27) without spectral moment values.

Figure 28 - Individual factor maps of: above, a duration-balanced set of North Boma nasals (restricted to segments shorter than 0.01 s); below, the entire North Boma nasal dataset without spectral moment values

The acoustic distinction between retroflex and non-retroflex segments remains sharp whether the sets are balanced for duration or not. Nasal retroflexes remain negatively correlated to dimension 1, with non-retroflexes on the positive side of the same axis (the only exception being nasal palatal duration values). The main variable groups defining dimension 1 are now “formant values” and “spectral moments”, with retroflexes exhibiting once again lower F2 bandwidth values and higher F1 and F1 bandwidth values than their non-retroflex counterparts, along with higher skewness

and kurtosis and a lower centre of gravity.⁶² When spectral moment values are excluded from the analysis, a newly defined dimension 1 (mostly correlated to duration, slope, and bandwidth) is again inversely correlated to the dataset's retroflexes and directly correlated to their non-retroflex counterparts (except for labiodental and alveolar slope values, as well as alveolar bandwidth values, which tallies with the situation presented in Figure 27). Taken together, these supplementary analyses suggest that duration alone does not account for the retroflex/non-retroflex opposition in North Boma and show how other acoustic variables (chiefly bandwidth and formant values) contribute to informing the distinction.

MFA were also performed on the entire dataset with values measured at 10% and 90% of the sounds' total duration, to account for the flicking hypothesis advanced above in relation to the speech of Subject C; it has been mentioned (see above) that retroflexes can affect different targets throughout their articulation, with the tongue tip "flapping out" of a curled-up position. In their typology of the sounds of the world's languages, Ladefoged & Maddieson (1996) claim that the "tongue tip first bends back into the retroflex position, and then, during the closure phase, straightens out somewhat, so that by the time of the release of the closure it is in a less extreme position" (p. 28). This would not appear to be the case in North Boma; see Figure 29.

⁶² See "ConsMedShortMFALog.docx" on OSF.

Figure 29 - Individual factor maps of: above, the entire North Boma nasal dataset with values measured at 10% of the sounds' total duration; below, the entire North Boma nasal dataset with values measured at 90% of the sounds' total duration

The important similarities between the two planes at 10% and 90% of the sounds' total duration indicate that nasal retroflexes in North Boma behave rather uniformly throughout their articulation, with the exception of slope and formant values (as would be expected in onset vs. offset position). Regardless, "retroflexion" remains the most important variable in the definition of the planes, as was the case in all other MFA performed and shown above.

Based on the results summarised up to this point, North Boma nasal retroflexes constitute a discrete class within the language's nasal inventory. Compared to their non-retroflex counterparts, they are significantly shorter, exhibit lower concentrations of energy in the spectrum with more energy concentrated around their centre of gravity (as well as more peaked energy concentrations), show higher values of F1 and F1 bandwidth and lower values of F2 bandwidth; they are not characterised by different acoustic properties in onset vs. offset position, suggesting that they do not in fact behave like quickly flicking flaps as had been hypothesised based on some features of the speech of Subject C. This, coupled with the phonological information provided above, backstops their characterisation by Stappers (1986).

5.5.4 Vowels

Nasal-adjacent vowels have also been analysed to account for coarticulation effects and to determine whether any effects attributable to proximity to a nasal retroflex can be detected (full results available in §5.8.2). Figure 30 compares duration values for the three cardinal vowels /a/, /i/ and /u/.

Figure 30 - Average duration values for three nasal-adjacent cardinal vowels in North Boma

All three vowels appear to be longer in pre-retroflex position, but only two of them (/a/ and /u/) display similar adjacency effects in post-retroflex position, where they are shorter.

A MFA was performed on the same vowels; the results are shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31 - Individual factor map of the entire nasal-adjacent North Boma cardinal vowel dataset

Retroflex adjacency is positively correlated to dimension 1 of the plane (which alone accounts for around one fourth of the set's total inertia); however, as one can clearly see, the distinction is a lot less sharp than was observed for the consonants, with vowel quality effects (e.g., high vs. low) weighing more in the definition of the plane than vowel position. As a matter of fact, Table 15 clearly shows that of the two qualitative variables at hand, "position" is a lot less significantly correlated to dimension 1 than "segment":

Table 15 - Qualitative variables correlated to dimension 1 of the MFA summarised in Figure 31

QUALITATIVE VARIABLES	CORRELATION	P-VALUE
		(ALPHA = .05)
SEGMENT	0.5383461	1.576257e-91
POSITION	0.1362722	4.599345e-17

In other words, acoustic vowel measurements differ by vowel phoneme considerably more than by context. No specific effects of retroflexion could be detected on the nasal's vocalic environment.

5.6 Discussion

Nasal retroflexes in North Boma have been found to differ significantly from their non-retroflex counterparts. A first visual inspection of the available samples allowed us to identify a tendency for nasal retroflexes to display greater concentrations of energy in the lower regions of the spectrum and fewer / less identifiable higher-frequency intensity peaks (i.e., less clear formant structure throughout the sound). Following this first step, a series of descriptive statistics were run to summarise the dataset. Nasal retroflexes were found to be shorter than their non-retroflex counterparts, and to exhibit lower F2, F3, and F4 average values than all other nasals in the set, while no effect of bandwidth could be identified at this stage, apart from F1 (greater F1 bandwidth values for retroflexes than non-retroflexes, possibly indicating a more diffuse murmur). Nasal retroflexes appear to have the sharpest F1 slopes both in onset and offset position, but no specific effect of retroflexion could be detected on F2 onset and offset slopes. Nasal retroflexes show higher skewness and kurtosis values than their non-retroflex counterparts, suggesting higher / more peaked concentrations of energy in the spectral area below their centroid frequency; lower centre of gravity values also appear to point in the same direction.

In order to substantiate these preliminary findings, a series of MFA were performed on the dataset (quantitative variables grouped as follows: "duration", "formant values", "bandwidth values", "slope values", "spectral moments"; qualitative variables grouped as follows: "segment", "retroflexion"). A first MFA, run on the relevant sounds' median values, showed that the retroflex / non-retroflex opposition is better suited to explain the plane's inertia than the 'segment' variable. Retroflexion was shown to be significantly correlated (inversely) to segment duration, F2 bandwidth, centre of gravity, and F2 offset slope values, and (positively) to skewness, kurtosis, F1 bandwidth, and F1. This indicates that North Boma nasal retroflexes are shorter than their non-retroflex counterparts and exhibit more energy concentrated in the lower regions of

the spectrum, while no specific effect of retroflexion was found on F3. This is interesting as it appears to set the North Boma case apart from others presented in the available typological literature (see Hussain et al. 2017). Perhaps, this might indicate that retroflexes in North Boma have a relatively advanced constriction location. In line with the available acoustic literature (Stevens & Blumstein 1975), an F3-4 pinch was observed, but no effect of F2-3 convergence, which, again, sets the North Boma case apart from other well-documented cases (see Hamann 2002, 2003). Lower centre of gravity and standard deviation on the one hand, and higher skewness and kurtosis on the other, might indicate a position of the tongue perpendicular to the hard palate, which is consistent with the F3 findings (as a less retracted constriction location also requires less “curling” of the tongue tip). MFA were also performed on nasals with values sampled at the 10%- and 90%-duration temporal marks, to test whether retroflexion in North Boma were a dynamic articulation targeting different places at the sound’s onset and offset (Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996). This was not found to be the case, suggesting that nasal retroflexes in North Boma do not behave as quickly flicking flaps as previously hypothesised.

Vowel adjacency effects were also analysed. MFA were performed on three cardinal vowels (/a/, /i/, and /u/). No significant effect of retroflexion was found on nasal-adjacent vowels. This also sets the North Boma case apart from other cases documented in the literature, where adjacency to a retroflex has been linked to lowered F3 values on the vowel.

While no other retroflexion phenomena could be found in the immediate vicinity of the North Boma area, some are detectable in the Bantu Lotwa languages of the last surviving forager groups of the eastern corner of Mai-Ndombe (Maselli 2024), where flapping as a realisation of intervocalic laterals is a common phonetic possibility (as attested in other Congo Basin forager languages too; see Bokula 1970, Kutsch Lojenga 1994, Motingea 2010). Although this is hard to prove given the absence of historical language data, the occurrence of retroflex nasals in North Boma could be diagnostic of substrate influence or shift-induced interference (Thomason 2006) from the non-Bantu tongues of the foragers who once became part of the ancestral North Boma speech communities. In the process of foreign language acquisition, some degree of structural phonological impact of source languages on recipient languages is very common and known as “imposition” under “source language agentivity” (Van Coetsem 1988). If these foreign language speakers shifted in sufficiently large

numbers to ancestral North Boma, the imposition of the phonotactic structure of their non-Bantu source language on their Bantu recipient language would have undergone horizontal (through space) and vertical (through time) transmission along with the language community itself. While the overall rarity of nasal retroflexes in Bantu is a first indication of loan phonology, their positional restrictions are further evidence of the contact-induced intrusion of a phonotactic constraint from a non-Bantu source language, and so is our acoustic finding concerning their apparent saliency within North Boma nasals. As a matter of fact, as Blevins (2017: 12) puts it, “the more salient the phonetic pattern, the more likely it will spread areally” (see also Fleischacker 2000, Kenstowicz 2001, 2003, Steriade 2001a,b, Kang 2002, among others). To what extent retroflexion is stable in the Mai-Ndombe languages which display it is a matter for further research. In fact, while /ŋ/ appears in C₂ (or, less often, C₃) position within a C₁V₁C₂V₂C₃V₃ template, our comparative data suggest that /ŋ/ is not equally frequent in all varieties.

5.7 Conclusions

The present contribution represents the first in-depth analysis of a severely understudied class of sounds, i.e., nasal retroflexes, in a severely understudied Bantu language, i.e., North Boma, spoken in a severely understudied area of the planet, i.e., the Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo. By integrating low-level phonetics and synchronic and diachronic phonology, we have been able to push our analysis of nasal retroflexes beyond the scope of each individual field.

Our original fieldwork with different North Boma speakers has allowed us to document the nasal retroflex /ŋ/, which is rare both in Bantu and in the rest of the world’s languages, and to confirm the phonemic status of this sound as reported by Stappers (1986). Our comparative synchronic study has also shown that this sound is not equally frequent across speakers and varieties of North Boma, suggesting a position of particular volatility in the language’s consonantal inventory. The cross-speaker and cross-variety instability of /ŋ/ in present-day North Boma could suggest that this sound was originally a loan phoneme. In support of this hypothesis, other retroflex sounds such as [ɽ] have been found in Bantu languages spoken by several

foraging communities in the wider area, commonly considered the descendants of populations who already lived in the region before the arrival of Bantu speakers. Hence, substrate interference from shifting non-Bantu speakers could well be the historical source for North Boma /ŋ/.

Even if /ŋ/ was originally a loan phoneme, this does not mean that it is only found in loanwords – quite the opposite. Thanks to our diachronic phonological analysis, we could determine that /ŋ/ is the regular reflex of both Proto-Bantu *n and *nd in word-final position, i.e., C₂ in disyllabic stems or C₃ position in trisyllabic stems. While the regularity of the sound change points towards a firm integration of this alleged loan phoneme into North Boma's sound system, its restriction to word-final position might betray the phonotactics of a non-Bantu substrate language. Additionally, the regular correspondence of /ŋ/ to both Proto-Bantu *n and *nd informs us on the sound shift's relative chronology: this must have happened after the reduction of voiced nasal - voiced oral consonant (NC) clusters such as *nd to simple nasals like *n. This type of consonant cluster simplification is widespread in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai region (Pacchiarotti et al. forthcoming). As this simplification also occurs in North Boma's closest relatives, i.e., Mpe B821, Nunu B822, and Tiene B81, it probably took place in the most recent common ancestor of these four languages. However, /ŋ/ itself is not attested in North Boma's closest relatives except Nunu B822. Consequently, its adoption in the sound inventory of North Boma (and Nunu) must all in all be a relatively recent phenomenon, which reinforces our hypothesis of a contact-induced origin.

By going beyond historical phonology and grounding our findings in acoustics, using, among others, advanced methods of statistical analysis such as MFA (which is a first in the region), we have been able to show that retroflexes in North Boma are a particularly salient class of nasals. The retroflex/non-retroflex opposition is the most significant one in explaining our acoustic dataset's variance regardless of duration and spectral moment values. This reinforces the hypothesis that the nasal retroflex is in fact a loan phoneme integrated into the North Boma inventory through contact, in the light of Blevins's (2017) observations on the impact of acoustic saliency on the ease of spread of phonetic patterns.

Finally, our factorial overview of the main acoustic correlates of retroflexion in North Boma shows that our data both matches and flouts acoustic expectations. These key typological data from a severely under-researched area of the world contribute to the debate on the acoustics of retroflex consonants in the world's languages. Admittedly,

a lot more research still needs to be conducted, specifically aimed at the collection of articulatory data to further ground the acoustic considerations presented here. The possibility of perceptual studies should also be explored if we are to further assess the degree of saliency of retroflexion in North Boma. Additional evidence should be collected on neighbouring Nunu, where a similar phenomenon has been detected in our preliminary fieldwork data.

5.8 Supplementary materials

5.8.1 Words with /ŋ/ or /n/ in C₂ and C₃ position across three North Boma varieties

This appendix presents all lexical items containing either /ŋ/ or /n/ in C₂ and C₃ position across three North Boma varieties, i.e., those documented in Stappers (1986) and our own fieldwork missions of 2021 and 2022. The reader will see that the variety we documented in 2022 is (nearly) identical to the one documented by Stappers (1986). Lexical items in this appendix are ordered alphabetically by concept name. All words are transcribed using the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA), except in Stappers (1986) where <y> = [j], <r> = [r], and <j> [ɟ]. In Stappers (1986) and Fieldwork 2021, low tone is left unmarked. The last column presents the historical form of which lexical items on the same row are likely to be the reflex. All historical forms with an index number are taken from the Bantu Lexical Reconstructions 2/3 database (Bastin et al. 2002). Those without an index number are tentative reconstructions based on comparative evidence from West-Coastal and Central-Western Bantu branches. A blank cell means lack of data. An em-dash — means that in a given variety the concept is expressed by a root which does not contain /ŋ/ or /n/ in C₂ / C₃ position.

As the reader will notice, our comparative data suggest that /ŋ/ is not equally frequent across varieties. We found that, out of 104 lexical items collected in 2022, 82 had /ŋ/ in C₂/C₃ (79%) and 22 had /n/ in C₂/C₃ (21%). Similarly, of the 61 lexical items having /ŋ/ or /n/ in C₂/C₃ in Stappers (1986), 53 have /ŋ/ (87%) and 8 /n/ (13%). By

contrast, out of the 77 lexical items collected in 2021, 40 have /ŋ/ (52%) and 37 have /n/ (48%). North Boma speakers who participated in 2021 are younger than the speaker of 2022 and have lived away from their community and in non-rural environments for longer than he had. It is possible that these younger speakers are losing the nasal retroflex by producing it as an alveolar, possibly under the influence of speakers of other languages of the region which do not have nasal retroflexes in their phonological inventories. It is worth noting that our 2022 speaker never produced /n/ as a free variant of /ŋ/ in C₂ position.

Table 16 - Words with /ŋ/ or /n/ in C₂ and C₃ position across three North Boma varieties

Concept	Stappers 1986	Fieldwork 2021	Fieldwork 2022	BLR index	BLR protoform
1. (red) ant		ikfúni	ikfúni/màkfúni èkámúńú/ ŋkámúńú	BLR	*kúndà
2. anus	muzi:ńí	muʒi:ńí	mùzì:ńí/mìzì:ńí	BLR 9667	*jini 'pubes'
3. bamboo			izá:ńá/màzá:ń á		
4. belly		ipfu:ńí	ikfúni/màkfúni	BLR 1545	*kúndú
5. big	bɔnéŋɛ	bon:é	bòn:éŋɛ ~ bòn:éńɛ	BLR 2252	*nén
6. bird		ńíni	ńúni/ńúni	BLR 1627	*jùni
7. black	mpi:ńí		mpìńí	BLR 2577	*pínd
8. branch		ep:áni	mpáni/mpáni	BLR 2390	*pándà
9. brother	nâ:ńa			BLR	*nándà
10. calabash	mbjá:ńá	mbjána	mbjáná/mbján á	BLR 212	*bíndà
11. chameleon			mbwílùńú/ mbwílùńú		
12. caterpillar		kémbayaní	kèzinà/bèzinà		
13. carved image			ŋkò:ńí		
14. child	mwá:ńa	mwána	mwánà/mjánà	BLR 3203	*jánà
15. cricket		nzén:é	—	BLR 1583	*ńjénjé
16. crocodile	ngɔ:ńé	ŋgóńé	ŋgò:ńé/ŋgò:ńé	BLR 1446	*gòndé

17. deep		nɔja:ɳá	nɔjãɳá	BLR 6275	*dindú
18. dignitary	nju:ɳu				
19. dirt		mbiúɳu	mbjúɳù	BLR 249	*bindò
20. eel		mutfóni	—	BLR 6725	*condi
21. eight	in:áɳà		inâ:ɳa	BLR 6434	*nàinài
22. electric fish		ndú:ɳu	ndú:ɳú/ndú:ɳú	BLR 4340	*dòndà
23. encampment		ɳá:ɳo	ɳgãɳù/ɳgãɳù	BLR 1324	*gàndá
24. family			ikjáɳà/màkjáɳà	BLR 1321	*gàndá
25. fin			mâl:áɳànù		
26. five	ta:ɳu		táɳù/bètáɳù	BLR 2768	*táànò
27. friend	m̀bè:ɳí		mbè:ɳí	BLR 8504	*bandi 'eminent man'
28. full	musia:ɳa	mufjáɳa	mùsáɳà/misáɳà	BLR	*kinà
29. grudge			ɳgwàɳá		
30. hail		éɳgu:nú			
31. hammer			ɳjú:ɳù	BLR 1628	*jùndò
32. (palm of) hand	kani	ké:k:áni	kèkání/bèkání	BLR 1329	*gàɳjà
33. heel		kéb:uɳú			
34. hill	ngina			BLR 5527	*gìnà 'ant-hill'
35. host, stranger	ngje:ɳé	ɳgje:ɳé	ɳgje:ɳé/ɳgje:ɳé	BLR 7614	*gèndi
36. hot		ke:dʒuyún:i	kèjùɳùni/ bèjùɳùni		
37. how		zébúni	mùzá múɳi mùzá:n:à		
38. jigger, louse		nsána	nsáɳà/nsáɳà	BLR	*kínà
39. judge	ɳté:ɳi			BLR 2846	*ténd 'to say, speak'
40. light, day	mwání	mwáɳi ~ m:wání	mwání/mjáɳí		

41. maternal aunt		ηγό zə γαηγάni			
42. moon, month	ḥɔ:ɲɔ	ηόηo	ηγόηò/ηγòηò	BLR 1447	*gòndò
43. mosquito, fly	béméné	eb:émene	èbéμένé/ mbéméné	BLR 7535	*bémbédé
44. mother	nâna:	—	—		
45. mouth	muna/mina			BLR 4709	*nùà
46. name	zá:ηà/mjána	ζάηa	zjá:ηa/mjá:ηa	BLR 3464	*jína
47. news	—	—	mùkànú/mikàn ú	BLR 1706	*kándá 'letter'
48. paternal uncle		ta:rá zi: zéni			
49. pepper		izáni	ìzàni/màzàni		
50. piece		kets:ini	kèt:ìni/bèt:ìni	BLR 5531	*tíni
51. plantation			ηγù:ηú/ηγù:ηú	BLR 1509	*gùndà
52. post in the center of a hut			mwáηù/mjána		
53. pot, pan	εκε:ηε/ηκε:ηε				
54. price	muba:ηu	mob:áηu	mùbáηù	BLR	*bándù
55. pus	tfwá:ηá				
56. rainbow		munjáni	mùηkání/ mìηkání	BLR 1708	*kándá 'strap, belt'
57. raw		kop:jána			
58. savanna, field		ntána	ntána	BLR	*tándù
59. sixty	samuηu		mùsámúηù	BLR 433	*cààmànò
60. skin bag			mpòηí/mpòηí		
61. skinny			itána/màtána		
62. spark	mwa:ηá			BLR 3225	*jànjá 'daylight'
63. spider	sá:ko:ηé	nsáko:ηé ~ nséηko:ηé	nsækò:ηé/nsæ kò:ηé	BLR 6734	*kòndé 'spider net'

64. split post	ik:ún:i				
65. squirrel	sí:ńí	ńjí:ńí	nsí:ńí/nsí:ńí	BLR 579	*cíndí
66. stump, trunk (of tree)		ket:íni (trunk)	nsáńà (stump) mùmbúbúnú/ mìmbúbúnú (trunk)	BLR 2926	*tínà ⁶³
67. stuttering			èńkfúmèńè	BLR 5379	*kúkumíd
68. sun	vwá:ńà	wáńa	vwáńà	BLR 8292	*jání
69. (queen) termite	mutfwána	mutswána			
70. there		kuné	kúnè		
71. this X there			kjákìńè:		
72. thorn		nsjéńe	nsjéńé / nsjéńé	BLR 543	*céńdé
73. to be sideways			kòzímàńà mbîi	BLR 3354	*jímád
74. to be tired		kòkòńò	kokó:ńo	BLR 1934	*kóńd 'to be thin, emaciated'
75. to bite	tána		kot:ána	BLR	*tánt
76. to bury	kòfwá:ńa	kokfwána	kòkfwána	BLR 2125	*kúńd
77. to chat	kòdvwa:ńa	kod:zwána	kòdvwána	BLR	*duánd
78. to dance	ekání [past]	kok:áno	kòk:ána	BLR 1805	*kín
79. to dance > dance		ik:jána	íkjáná/màkján á	BLR 1807	*kína
80. to deny		kozána	kòzána		
81. to desire, love	kwá:ńa		kòkwána	BLR 2044	*kúńd
82. to despise	ńańá!				

⁶³ Although the synchronic roots t:ini and sána look formally different enough that their cognate status might be called into question, they are in all likelihood cognates. In the variety documented in 2022, the historical form tínà first underwent Bantu Spirantisation (Schadeberg 1995; Bostoen 2008), whereby /t/ > [s] when followed by the high vowel /i/, yielding the intermediate form síńà. Then, the second vowel was copied in V1 position so that síńà > sána. The same process happened in kámà 'monkey' (< BLR 1798 *kímà), kò-kán-à 'to dance' (< BLR 1805 *kín), n-sána 'jigger, house' (< BLR *kína) and and mù-sána 'whole' (< *kina).

83. to dig up			kòkfún:ò kòb:ín:ò	BLR 2125 BLR 209	*kùnd *bìnd 'to obstruct'
84. to fight	nwa:ηα			BLR 1151	*dùan
85. to finish	maηά!	kom:ά:na	kòm:άηà	BLR 2148	*màn
86. to forget	zímiηα		kòzímàηà	BLR 5716	*dímbad
87. to hoe			kòn:únò ntòró		
88. to learn	zíβiηα		kòzìγiηà	BLR 3338	*jíg
89. to marry with	láμεηε				
90. to mold a pot			kòbwáηà kèlèè		
91. to munch			kòt:ávàn:ò		
92. to pass by	kócwa:ηα				
93. to pierce		kotfwáηα			
94. to plant	kòkwáηα	kok:wáηα	kòkwáηà	BLR 2041	*kún
95. to plant > fallow land			mùkwáηà/ mìkwáηà	BLR 2041	*kún
96. to plant >seed		bek:úni	bjá bi bà kwáηà	BLR 2041	*kún
97. to push	síβiηε	kos:íγene	kòs:íγiηè	BLR 8076	*cègeni
98. to put away			kot:áyane		
99. to put down	naηά!			BLR 8242	*nàn 'to pull, to spread out'
100. to resemble, be equal	fâ:ηα	kof:άηα	kòfâηà	BLR 2670	*púan
101. to limit oneself	bόμεηε				
102. to rot	pò:ηο	kop:όηο	kòpòηò	BLR 6697	*pònd
103. to run		kol:άγa e nsúno	kòl:ávà ì nsùηù	BLR 9582	*dák 'to walk'

104. to see	mô: [past: móní]	kom:ó	kòmô [past: móní]	BLR 2206	*món
105. to see > to meet	môno		kòm:ón:ò	BLR 2206	*món
106. to see >fortune teller			kèm:óni/ bèm:óni	BLR 2206	*món
107. to see > encounter	kemónú			BLR 2206	*món
108. to send (for)	túmiŋe		kòt:úmèŋè	BLR 3055	*tóm
109. to shout	ŋaŋá	koŋ:ána	kòŋáŋà	BLR 2339	*NàN 'grumble'
110. to sleep	bímiŋa	kob:ímena	kòbímàŋà	BLR 6025	*bítam
111. to slip			kòsé mòŋò	BLR 509	*cèdɪmuk
112. to start		kob:án:e	kòb:ánè	BLR 88	*bánd
113. to swallow	mjaŋa	kom:jána	kòmjàŋà	BLR 2190	*mìn
to swallow >mout h	—	ména	m:énà/m:énà	BLR 2190	*mìn
114. to swell	bímiŋe			BLR 240	*bimb
115. to swim		koŋána	kòŋánà	BLR	*ŋjánj
116. to thank	ŋtó:ŋi [past]				
117. to twist		koŋwána	kòŋónò	BLR 1945	*kónj
118. to write	cónɔ	koŋwána	kòc:ónò	BLR 661	*cón
119. tooth	zjú:ŋu/mjú:ŋu	zónɔ	zjúŋù/mjúŋù	BLR 3472	*jínò
120. torch			mwàŋá/ mjàŋa	BLR 3609	*mùŋì
121. water well		ídzwá:ŋá	ídwàŋá/màdw àŋá		
122. what			kján:à		
123. when	kesie kíŋĩ		lú:nà, kèsínà		
124. where	kúnĩ	váni	kúnì, vání		
125. who	ze búŋĩ	n:á	ɟwán:à		

126. why	ketó:ŋó mbe, nsáŋá mbe		nsáná mbè		
127. wine		máŋa	—	BLR 8255	*jáná
128. worm			mùkènú/mikèn ú		
129. yesterday		mbálitjú:ŋi	—		

5.8.2 Full descriptive statistics results

This appendix contains all descriptive-statistical results for the six nasal places of articulation present in North Boma. All measurements (except slopes) consist of the median of the values calculated over the duration of the consonant (from 10% to 90% of its duration). It also shows results for six nasal-adjacent vowels.

Table 17 - Full descriptive statistics results associated with the North Boma nasal dataset

Average values (consonants)	m	ŋ	n	ɲ	ŋ	ŋ
Duration	0,116958456	0,127085863	0,11377068	0,127098365	0,11669258	0,050177132
F1	330,5065502	367,3	361,0066667	338,2352941	361,2432432	394,2269504
F2	1346,620087	1488,1	1410,306667	1502,294118	1294,027027	1212,929078
F3	2364,580786	2476,6	2369,386667	2481,411765	2387,783784	2314,106383
F4	3501,200873	3633,7	3503,593333	3492,529412	3602,648649	3355,815603
Bandwidth F1	149,0393013	145,8	125,0266667	118,5882353	116,5135135	250,893617
Bandwidth F2	626,7510917	637	559,06	782,1176471	787,7297297	377,1489362
Bandwidth F3	428,4454148	461	359,2	363,2352941	337,6486486	294,7021277
Bandwidth F4	624,9126638	640,1	479,86	409,0588235	688,027027	566,3049645
Bandwidth	457,2576419	471	380,76	418,2352941	482,5405405	372,248227
(general)						
F1 onset slope	- 0,655587309	- 2,192436469	- 0,714114838	- 0,902337255	0,342961736	- 0,601773574
F1 offset slope	0,839046821	- 1,388057592	0,056331044	0,717480221	-1,52208076	0,45866824
F2 onset slope	- 1,746961073	3,486803985	- 0,406675826	- 9,355002127	1,494775355	- 0,012090579

F2 offset slope	-	5,427406633	1,530186927	4,540706462	-	-
	1,055875515				4,768112677	0,137739191
F1 (10%)	342,8777293	400,2	378,72	361	365,972973	422,5673759
F2 (10%)	1388,056769	1428	1405,966667	1627,647059	1318,108108	1228,744681
F3 (10%)	2412,148472	2530,8	2366,733333	2716,058824	2415,324324	2330,411348
F4 (10%)	3510,697368	3546,1	3478,201342	3538,117647	3550,567568	3343,071429
Bandwidth F1 (10%)	196,7510917	174,9	176	145,5294118	135,9189189	289
Bandwidth F2 (10%)	633,2838428	654	617,72	827,4117647	681,6486486	367,5531915
Bandwidth F3 (10%)	622,6593886	442,8	455,6	498,8823529	429,5675676	301,4255319
Bandwidth F4 (10%)	644,8245614	624,5	538,3154362	495,2352941	947,4054054	735,9714286
F1 (30%)	330,4497817	375,6	366,2666667	354,2352941	363,5945946	394,8156028
F2 (30%)	1370,746725	1503,8	1437,826667	1503,588235	1375,081081	1222,58156
F3 (30%)	2395,406114	2540,1	2373,26	2577	2393,108108	2324,460993
F4 (30%)	3523,401747	3603,3	3531,653333	3536,117647	3630,594595	3344,900709
Bandwidth F1 (30%)	163,5458515	125,7	135,74	155,2352941	115,8108108	276,4255319
Bandwidth F2 (30%)	695,0567686	608	650,8733333	1131,411765	885,1621622	456,2978723
Bandwidth F3 (30%)	526,279476	421,9	422,6333333	437,1176471	403,2432432	353,3971631
Bandwidth F4 (30%)	709,1048035	895,6	539,8533333	525,0588235	754	757,4113475
F1 (50%)	327,5327511	368,4	362,0533333	334,5294118	374,8378378	387,8652482
F2 (50%)	1353,41048	1491,3	1391,746667	1467,882353	1356,459459	1224,851064
F3 (50%)	2384,20524	2394,3	2369,986667	2265	2435,648649	2311,262411
F4 (50%)	3528,546256	3604,6	3498,114094	3413	3612,72973	3355,778571
Bandwidth F1 (50%)	165,8815789	141,1	158,9865772	127,3529412	114,5675676	261,0567376

Bandwidth F2 (50%)	754,3799127	817,3	683,9933333	1440,176471	1003,432432	447,3758865
Bandwidth F3 (50%)	485,6200873	549,4	379,5466667	366,4705882	429,3513514	329,4255319
Bandwidth F4 (50%)	707,6828194	776,7	633,4966443	366,5294118	830,2702703	655,4214286
F1 (70%)	331,6973684	360,9	360,1879195	334,3529412	355,7027027	392,0992908
F2 (70%)	1341,065502	1332,7	1427,34	1440,882353	1344,675676	1219,184397
F3 (70%)	2398,772926	2440,5	2387,066667	2442,588235	2376,72973	2315,652482
F4 (70%)	3553,916667	3577	3525,202703	3441	3640,405405	3379,914286
Bandwidth F1 (70%)	185,3406114	149,5	133,6644295	111,1176471	115,6486486	269,177305
Bandwidth F2 (70%)	757,6331878	879,5	586,14	974,3529412	890,0540541	439,1134752
Bandwidth F3 (70%)	470,0917031	570,1	449,9266667	705,3529412	375,2432432	371,5177305
Bandwidth F4 (70%)	754,5657895	667,9	560,1283784	413,4117647	756,9459459	534,3571429
F1 (90%)	348,628821	344,2	364,0134228	349,4117647	341,8108108	414,5815603
F2 (90%)	1335,733624	1498,7	1432,846667	1515,647059	1281,189189	1225,134752
F3 (90%)	2391,349345	2474,8	2378,133333	2563,470588	2397,810811	2324,858156
F4 (90%)	3520,236842	3577,7	3519,067568	3536,764706	3593,432432	3408,321429
Bandwidth F1 (90%)	175,6593886	178,8	133,7919463	135,8823529	130,8108108	285,3642857
Bandwidth F2 (90%)	747,3930131	702,5	613,5066667	907,8823529	793,7297297	377,8014184
Bandwidth F3 (90%)	501,860262	1044,5	442,2666667	449,8235294	497,1081081	397,8439716
Bandwidth F4 (90%)	745,8070175	577,1	557,3378378	424,3529412	793,027027	488,5428571
Centre of gravity	1852,650655	1861,3	1858,154362	2198,352941	1904,864865	1631,921429

Standard deviation	795,9737991	720,9	718,0466667	919,7647059	751,1621622	661,6170213
Skewness	2,450305677	1,946	2,463206667	2,005882353	2,027837838	3,814326241
Kurtosis	20,94873362	10,093	24,74753333	21,74058824	15,38594595	54,13042553
Centre of gravity (10%)	1823,768559	1927,2	1810,633333	2358,941176	1802,72973	1540,141844
Standard deviation (10%)	758,6681223	783,6	667,48	871,5882353	690,4864865	522,4042553
Skewness (10%)	2,807336245	1,419	2,596266667	0,659176471	3,213513514	3,841276596
Kurtosis (10%)	70,03286463	6,839	50,54893333	12,23529412	74,39	120,078227
Centre of gravity (50%)	1847,174672	1838,2	1840,233333	2091,941176	1909,459459	1607,141844
Standard deviation (50%)	759,9737991	760,6	655,34	794,5294118	703,7567568	595,0496454
Skewness (50%)	2,670480349	1,963	2,415666667	2,045294118	2,956216216	3,368439716
Kurtosis (50%)	58,08733974	15,514	44,50086667	45,06235294	84,0127027	89,84085106
Centre of gravity (90%)	1835,9869	1790,5	1878,46	2172,294118	1901,540541	1569,992908
Standard deviation (90%)	747,4759825	789,2	678,3733333	792,5882353	728	554,1985816
Skewness (90%)	2,865502183	2,075	2,310133333	1,287647059	2,979459459	4,046666667
Kurtosis (90%)	55,9339738	18,389	39,522	24,22352941	72,03154054	125,7543972

Average values - [a]	post-non-retroflex	post-retroflex	pre-non-retroflex	pre-retroflex
Duration	0,108469556	0,081152969	0,116328227	0,147629671
F1 slope	2,776231246	0,817906072	-4,405244158	-4,158146853
F2 slope	2,202091175	1,852750049	-0,575651371	-1,367992775
F1 (10%)	536,5465116	469,2413793	583,9215686	575,7530864
F2 (10%)	1256,802326	1116,224138	1287,156863	1253,185185

F3 (10%)	2259,593023	2242,62069	2182,352941	2285,419753
F4 (10%)	3400,151163	3399,758621	3339,980392	3354,45679
Bandwidth F1 (10%)	241,5581395	340,9137931	133,2941176	262,3580247
Bandwidth F2 (10%)	351,9418605	223,6724138	290,2745098	264,9506173
Bandwidth F3 (10%)	593,9302326	464,1896552	448,1568627	483,6419753
Bandwidth F4 (10%)	538,9186047	446,0517241	359,4705882	349,691358
F1 (90%)	524,3176471	454,1206897	567,76	543,382716
F2 (90%)	1335,918605	1182,258621	1301,058824	1170,259259
F3 (90%)	2369,906977	2261,844828	2333,705882	2336,839506
F4 (90%)	3444,883721	3362,310345	3438,039216	3298,17284
Bandwidth F1 (90%)	288,4302326	356,2241379	229,0392157	306,691358
Bandwidth F2 (90%)	367,3604651	250,9310345	367	224,4938272
Bandwidth F3 (90%)	637,0116279	578,637931	562,9215686	450,7901235
Bandwidth F4 (90%)	625,5348837	614,1724138	536,9803922	577,8395062
Centre of gravity (10%)	479,8953488	378,9827586	575,2156863	562,6419753
Standard deviation (10%)	314,4302326	319,1724138	320,6078431	378,9876543
Skewness (10%)	4,383372093	3,703103448	3,586078431	2,668024691
Kurtosis (10%)	257,2522093	191,9486207	182,2441176	60,96432099
Centre of gravity (90%)	419,2325581	303,2758621	465,3529412	477,6296296
Standard deviation (90%)	318,0697674	300,9137931	331,4509804	361,654321
Skewness (90%)	4,658488372	5,496206897	3,670588235	2,826666667

Kurtosis (90%)	222,7230233	345,3415517	105,5692157	82,38876543
Average values -				
[i]				
Duration	0,089491965	0,085226221	0,086967404	0,148643474
F1 slope	0,130543396	-1,998946408	0,19152988	0,254715095
F2 slope	1,365425316	2,827084683	-4,802577916	-11,2345001
F1 (10%)	369,3787879	445,375	351,7837838	334,9
F2 (10%)	1698,287879	1556,5	1826,513514	1796,4
F3 (10%)	2566,575758	2471,3125	2629,027027	2389,9
F4 (10%)	3482,863636	3424,625	3546,945946	3465,8
Bandwidth F1 (10%)	146,1212121	152,9375	74,21621622	77,4
Bandwidth F2 (10%)	632,5606061	839,125	497,5135135	486,7
Bandwidth F3 (10%)	499,5909091	253,5	464,8108108	333,5
Bandwidth F4 (10%)	493,3181818	447,0625	311,2972973	329,3
F1 (90%)	378,0454545	439,625	367,1891892	351,6
F2 (90%)	1687,681818	1662	1676,297297	1763,8
F3 (90%)	2535,772727	2512,0625	2453,864865	2660,1
F4 (90%)	3471,121212	3504,1875	3430,486486	3702,7
Bandwidth F1 (90%)	162,969697	257,625	90,83783784	109,7
Bandwidth F2 (90%)	649,1515152	1039,3125	661,5675676	537,5
Bandwidth F3 (90%)	574,0606061	473,5625	400,4594595	416
Bandwidth F4 (90%)	507,6212121	405	425,4054054	990,3
Centre of gravity (10%)	289,3939394	341,4375	325,4324324	301,9

Standard deviation (10%)	200,7121212	272,1875	262,3243243	277,5
Skewness (10%)	15,16939394	12,044375	10,78054054	8,446
Kurtosis (10%)	2129,803939	1986,56875	455,7943243	287,319
Centre of gravity (90%)	288,7727273	261,75	336,2702703	346
Standard deviation (90%)	220,6666667	204,3125	243,4864865	285,1
Skewness (90%)	13,03939394	17,911875	10,11351351	9,08
Kurtosis (90%)	1454,218636	3278,84125	591,42	637,337
Average values -				
[u]				
Duration	0,10515404	0,082248898	0,086694779	0,128351877
F1 slope	-0,555584805	0,106730136	-0,305746182	-1,52120732
F2 slope	-5,824985675	2,342329743	7,439145964	2,893665486
F1 (10%)	399,9076923	420,4	392,0952381	348,5
F2 (10%)	1272,538462	1028,8	1142,738095	990,1666667
F3 (10%)	2471,030769	2448,6	2402,214286	2444,083333
F4 (10%)	3604,215385	3460,95	3404,380952	3409,083333
Bandwidth F1 (10%)	168,4	261,9	218,1190476	411,1666667
Bandwidth F2 (10%)	910,0153846	398,7	648,7142857	352,9166667
Bandwidth F3 (10%)	586,0461538	484,05	624,7142857	315,3333333
Bandwidth F4 (10%)	637,6153846	616,15	499,9761905	613,9166667
F1 (90%)	390,4461538	412,45	387,7142857	373,1666667
F2 (90%)	1226,292308	1148,35	1286,5	1039,416667
F3 (90%)	2414,246154	2490,8	2383,380952	2407,666667
F4 (90%)	3450,461538	3543,684211	3364,452381	3322,416667
Bandwidth F1 (90%)	210,6923077	347,7368421	141,5238095	218,25

Bandwidth F2 (90%)	659,2	550,5	562,6666667	290,5
Bandwidth F3 (90%)	612,3384615	585,15	588,8333333	283,5833333
Bandwidth F4 (90%)	699,7692308	596,2631579	753,8333333	650,6666667
Centre of gravity (10%)	297,4923077	314,05	319,4047619	312,8333333
Standard deviation (10%)	158,0153846	214,5	180,547619	181,75
Skewness (10%)	12,27476923	8,199	12,00833333	15,11833333
Kurtosis (10%)	1584,706154	944,3495	1586,59	3201,448333
Centre of gravity (90%)	293,9538462	266,15	308,6666667	276,1666667
Standard deviation (90%)	167,1846154	211,25	184,7142857	191,9166667
Skewness (90%)	14,33261538	11,275	10,63190476	8,2075
Kurtosis (90%)	2164,872	1357,504	1082,14	828,8958333

Chapter 6: Phonetic and Phonological Research in Mai-Ndombe – A Few Preliminary Notes on Rhotics and Double-Articulations

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Abstract

Mai-Ndombe is one of the southwestern provinces of the Democratic Republic of Congo. Ecologically, it can be characterised as a transition zone between a moist, broadleaf rainforest ecotone in the north and shrubland/savannah areas in the south. Linguistically, Mai-Ndombe, along with the rest of southwestern Congo all the way down to the border with Angola, is among the least well-surveyed areas of the planet. Within its borders, several different Bantu (Guthrie's zones B, C, and H) varieties are spoken, near the newly identified West-Coastal Bantu homeland, it-self a hot spot of phonological diversity unlike any other in the West-Coastal Bantu domain. Phonetic and phonological accounts of its languages are particularly lacking (apart from impressionistic "grey literature" reports which seldom comply with the standards of present-day phonetic and phonological inquiry). This gap is particularly concerning as Mai-Ndombe is also an area of great anthropological diversity, with numerous hunter-gatherer Twa communities living deep in its eastern and northern forests. Their lects, collectively known as Lotwa, are severely endangered, as they face the threats of social stigma and the growing use of national and regional *linguae francae*. As part of the author's doctoral project (still underway), phonetic data were collected in the area between May and July 2021, specifically in Inongo (the provincial capital) and Nioki. The present contribution is intended as a brief note on the relevant results produced so far, mainly bearing on the analysis of some phenomena of interest in the languages of the region, including Sakata rhotics and labial-velars and the presence of unusual trilling/flapping realisations in Lotwa. The picture yielded by this preliminary exploration

is one of striking phonetic and phonological variation, possibly pointing to earlier stages of greater linguistic diversity than previously supposed. It is also tentatively proposed that one of the specific characteristics of the phenomena attested in the present contribution is that they tend to affect more than one language at a time, working rather as areal “phonetic possibilities” than language-bound outcomes of traditional sound change rules; in this sense, it is suggested that in-depth documentation and description can help re-shape our understanding of how language contact works in highly multilingual contexts.

Keywords: phonetics; phonology; Bantu; microvariation; typology

6.1 Introduction

The present contribution is a selective overview of a few phenomena of phonetic/phonological interest. It deals with some recently documented Bantu lects spoken in Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo (Map 7). The province, named after Lake Mai-Ndombe (Omasombo Tshonda et al. 2019), is divided into eight administrative units or “territories”, namely (from west to east): Kwamouth, Bolobo, Yumbi, Mushie, Inongo, Kutu, Kiri, and Oshwe. Extending latitudinally from the equator to S 4° 0' 0" and longitudinally from E 16° 0' 0" to E 21° 0' 0", Mai-Ndombe is at the centre of the Congo River Basin (*Cuvette centrale congolaise*) and is characterised by the presence of plateaus and low-level hills (Omasombo Tshonda et al. 2019: 21ff). Ecologically, it represents a transition zone between different ecoregions within the Afrotropical realm, to wit, a tropical moist broadleaf forest to the north and northeast and tropical shrublands to the south and southwest. Part of this transition zone features a so-called forest-savannah mosaic, an ecotone marked by the presence of patches of woodland interspersed with savannah clearings, frequently constituting forest corridors/galleries (Olson et al. 2001). Linguistically, Mai-Ndombe, along with the rest of southwestern Congo all the way down to the border with Angola, is among the least well-surveyed areas of the planet (Hammarström 2016). It hosts several different Bantu varieties (Guthrie's 1970 zones B, C, and H), and is located close to the newly identified West-Coastal Bantu (West-Coastal Bantu) homeland (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019, Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020), a hot spot of phonological diversity unlike any other in the West-Coastal Bantu area. Mai-Ndombe is also home to remarkable anthropological diversity, with numerous hunter-gatherer communities living deep in its eastern and northern forests.

Data for the present contribution were collected between May and July 2021 in Inongo and Nioki. Inongo is Mai-Ndombe's provincial capital and the province's most multilingual city. Nioki is the province's unofficial economic capital and its second most multilingual city. Recording conditions in the field were sub-optimal, and the resulting phonetic analysis is preliminary in nature, pending further data collection. An OSF link has been made available to provide the reader with the individual sound files associated with the spectrograms and oscillograms reported in the figures (https://osf.io/hs85b/?view_only=8c1b5e1ab3e541bb8e8d6be45e8648b3).

This contribution is divided into sections titled after specific phenomena of interest (rhotics, labial-velars). It deals with the following languages: Sakata, North Boma, Nunu, and Lotwa (see Map 7).

Sakata, ISO 639-3 [skt] / glottocode [saka1287], is the commonest glossonym used to refer to the Bantu varieties spoken by the Sakata people, a group indigenous to the Kutu territory in southern Mai-Ndombe (cf. Maselli et al. 2023). These have been variously classified as West-Coastal Bantu or Central-Western Bantu, and research on their exact place in the broader Bantu phylogeny is still ongoing (Grollemund et al. 2015, Pacchiarotti et al. 2019, Koile et al. 2022).

In Guthrie's (1970) referential classification, Sakata is inventoried as Bantu C34. In the author's own fieldwork experience, Sakata is better understood as a continuum of closely related varieties. As reported by Maselli et al. (2023: 3), the degree of mutual intelligibility among Sakata varieties is considerable, with consultants often identifying as speakers of different regiolects. The data discussed here were collected with speakers (pseudonymised) of the following regiolects:

Variety	Speaker	Age	Place of origin	Geocoordinates
Kinzinzale	A	52	Nioki	-2.72, 17.69
Kibayi	B	49	Tolo	-2.95, 18.57
Kingingia	C	52	Nioki	-2.72, 17.69
Kingingele	D	52	Mongobebe	-2.79, 17.87
Kitere	E	58	Kilima	-3.58, 18.54

The available linguistic literature on Sakata is scarce and largely unavailable to scholars outside the Democratic Republic of Congo, with specific phonetic and phonological information presented in Matabisi (1979), Ntuaremba (1986), Tylleskär (1987), Bontenge (1995), and Bokwankon Bosonkie (1997).

North Boma and Nunu are two closely related West-Coastal Bantu varieties respectively inventoried as B82 and B822 by Maho (2009); while North Boma was already reported in Guthrie's (1970) classification, Nunu was not. The two lects lack clear glotto- and ISO codes, with Hammarström et al. (2022) assigning North Boma the glottocode [boma1251] and linking it to the ISO 639-3 code [boh], and Eberhard et al. (2024) conflating two different languages, namely Boma Yumu (Bantu B80z) and

North Boma, under the same ISO 639-3 code [boh]; and Nunu not being assigned any codes at all.

The literature on North Boma and Nunu is scant, with the main source of information on the former being the outline provided by Stappers (1986), and the latter remaining largely undocumented to this day (see Pacchiarotti et al. 2019). Data were collected in collaboration with the following speakers:

Variety	Speaker	Age	Place of origin	Geocoordinates
North Boma	F	50	Mushie	-3.02, 16.92
	G	37	Bobala	-2.56, 17.52
	H	35	Mbali	-2.38, 17.29
Nunu	I	36	Eboli	-2.84, 17.42

North Boma is the object of recent research (Maselli et al.: forthcoming). Based on the information now available, the degree of mutual intelligibility between North Boma and Nunu is high; several phonetic phenomena are shared across the two varieties.

Finally, “Lotwa” is the collective exonym by which the Bantu varieties spoken by rainforest Twa hunter-gatherers (plural form: Batwa) are referred to throughout much of the central Congo Basin by their non-Twa neighbours. Most Mai-Ndombe hunter-gatherers live in the northern, forest territories of Kiri and Inongo, but a few small groups have also been reported in the southeastern territories of Oshwe and Kutu. The Batwa are generally considered to be autochthonous pre-Bantu forest dwellers (Quintana-Murci et al. 2008, Patin et al. 2009, Batini et al. 2011); however, unlike other autochthonous groups elsewhere in Africa (notably, the so-called “Khoisan” of southern Africa), the Batwa are presumed to have lost their original languages and to have adopted those of the “sedentary” Bantu-speaking newcomers (Hiernaux 1966, Motingea 1993, 1994, 2010, Grégoire 2003, Klieman 2003). The question of whether their pre-Bantu lects have left a trace on the current linguistic landscape of the Congo Basin – or, in other words, the issue of whether some of the characteristics of present-day Bantu can be explained in terms of “Twa substrate” – is a long-standing one in the relevant historical-linguistic literature (Trilles 1932, Schebesta 1949, Möhlig 1981, Bahuchet 1993, 2006, 2012, Olson & Hajek 2003).

In Mai-Ndombe, Twa communities speak Bantu varieties similar to those of their northeastern and eastern Mongo neighbours. The data discussed here were collected with speakers of the following:

Variety	Speaker	Age	Place of origin	Geocoordinates
L. Lolia	J	33	Bolia	-1.61, 18.36
L. Losenge	K	45	Bisenge	-3.47, 19.8
L. Lokonda A	L	43	Lioko	N/A
L. Lokonda B	M	51	Mpendjwa	-1.10, 19.11

No descriptions of the varieties at hand could be found in the literature; a fully blown phonological analysis is therefore still pending. Hammarström et al. (2022) do list a variety they call “Batswa of Nkundo-Ntomba-Ekonda” which they assign the glottocode [bats1244], but it remains unclear whether this refers to Lotwa Lokonda as reported in the present venue (see also Chabiron et al. 2013: 127-128). However, several peculiarities allegedly typical of Lotwa dialects across the forest have been reported by various scholars (see Motingea 2015 and the references cited therein).

As a collection of observations on various phenomena in different, often adjacent varieties, this report is meant to: a) contribute to the discussion on the cross-linguistic typology of these phenomena; and b) shed light on a severely under-surveyed area of the world, tentatively proposing that some of its more widespread phonetic and phonological features are shared across its local varieties as a set of common phonetic possibilities.

Throughout the article, lexical items are transcribed phonetically (i.e., in square brackets) as full-fledged phonological accounts of the varieties at hand are still pending. Phonemic transcription (slashes) is used for individual sounds when they are treated as input to sound change.

Map 7 - Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo with the approximate location of all varieties surveyed

6.2 Rhotics

6.2.1 Sakata

Available sources on Sakata phonology lack reliable phonetic analyses. As concerns rhotics, most of these sources concur that Sakata only features one, which Bokwankon Bosonkie (1997: 20) describes as a “uvular trill” (*vibrante uvulaire*) in central Sakata (from Mbantín).

The situation documented here is somewhat more nuanced, with several Sakata varieties exhibiting both a uvular fricative /ʁ/ sound and an alveolar trill /r/; see Figure 32 for examples from Kinzinzale (minimal pair involving the following: [ozára] “to rip” vs [ozáʁa] “to hit”). This is a typologically rare situation, in that most natural languages

only display one rhotic phoneme, and those that have two typically contrast a flap and a trill (Harris 1969, Lipski 1990, Padgett 2003, Wheeler 2005, Wiese 2011). However, it is a feature that is shared by other Mai-Ndombe lects, as shown below.

Figure 32 - Minimal pair involving a /r/ (left) vs /ɾ/ (right) opposition in Kinzinzale; audio files are available on OSF as Fig1-1 and Fig1-2

Both /ɾ/ and /r/ are present across all Sakata varieties (cf. [lek:éβə] “eyebrow”, a form present in Kibayi, Kinzinzale, Kingingia, Kingingele, and Kitere). While the phonological status of /ɾ/ is subject to a lot of regiolectal variation, the production of a voiced uvular fricative sound appears to be a readily available phonetic possibility throughout the Sakata domain. This is particularly interesting if we consider that some Sakata varieties, and particularly Kinzinzale, irregularly exhibit a voiceless uvular fricative in forms deriving from Proto-Bantu *k (in C₁ position); cf. *kómbó “broom” > Kinzinzale: [le:χwómo], *kúmbá “navel” > Kinzinzale: [mu:χúmá] (see Maselli et al. 2023: 7). Across varieties, /ɾ/ may also derive from a Proto-Bantu stop articulated around the velum, as appears to be the case in the following examples (1.a-f; the phenomenon itself is not new in the area, see Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020 and the literature cited therein):

1.a “hands”: Kibayi, Kinzinzale – [βwóβo] < *bókò

1.b “hole”: Kibayi – [if:óβo] < *pukú

- 1.c “cock”: Kibayi, Kinzinzale – [ŋkɔ́ɔ́] < *kókó
- 1.d “eyebrow”: all varieties examined – [lek:éɛə] < *kígè
- 1.e “spell”: Kibayi, Kinzinzale – [ndwóɔɔ] < *dòg
- 1.f “cooking pot”: Kibayi, Kinzinzale – [mpɔ́ɔ́] < *pùgí

Across varieties, /r/ appears to be more stable (i.e., subject to fewer / less frequent reduction phenomena) than /ɜ/ (only sporadically attested in Kingingia, Kingingele, and Kitere); see the following (2.a-e):

- 2.a “male”: Kibayi, Kinzinzale, Kingingia, Kingingele – [munʒírí], Kitere – [uʒ:írí]
- 2.b “to vomit”: Kibayi – [ídzərə́], Kinzinzale, Kingingia, Kingingele, Kitere – [ózərə́]
- 2.c “to pour”: Kinzinzale – [ózərə], Kingingia, Kingingele, Kitere – [ódzərə́]
- 2.d “load”: Kibayi – [bodzére], Kinzinzale – [bozére], Kingingia, kiNginge, Kitere – [ód:əré]
- 2.e BUT “sharp”: Kibayi – [mpúro], Kingingele, Kitere – [mpúɾə] vs Kingingia – [mpú.o]; “pirogue”: Kibayi, Kinzinzale – [váɾə], Kingingia, Kingingele, Kitere – [vá]; “debt”: Kibayi, Kinzinzale – [mbára], Kingingia, Kingingele, Kitere – [mbá]

Additionally, Kingingia and Kingingele (and possibly Kitere), i.e., the varieties in which /r/ appears least well-established (those in which it occasionally elides, see 2.e), are also those which drop /ɜ/ the most often (3.a-c):

- 3.a “manioc leaf”: Kibayi – [bedzəɔ́], Kinzinzale – [izáɛa] vs Kingingia – [bɛzí.a], Kingingele – [bezá]
- 3.b “cooking pot”: Kibayi, Kinzinzale – [mpɔ́ɔ́] vs Kingingia, Kingingele – [mpo.ó]
- 3.c “word”: Kibayi – [lɛláɛa], Kinzinzale – [ndáɛa] vs Kingingia – [ndí.a], Kingingele – [ndá]

The situation is less diversified for Kingingia, where /ɜ/ generally reduces to zero, and more so in Kingingele (and possibly in Kitere), where /ɜ/ is more frequently maintained – and corresponds, albeit occasionally, to other sounds (4.a-d; notably, Kingingele is also the variety which exhibits the highest degree of variation in the re-alisation of labial-velar consonants in the Sakata domain, see Maselli et al. 2023: 13):

- 4.a “sky”: Kibayi, Kinzinzale – [lóʋo], Kingingia – [ló:] vs Kingingele – [lóga]
- 4.b “ash”: Kibayi – [it:óʋo], Kinzinzale – [it:úʋu], Kingingia – [it:ó] vs Kingingele – [it:úgu]
- 4.c “to insult”: Kibayi – [it:úʋa], Kinzinzale – [ot:úʋa], Kingingia – [ot:ʃúa], Kitere – [untú] vs Kingingele – [et:úga]
- 4.d “on”: Kibayi – [ól:óʋo], Kinzinzale – [ól:úʋu], Kingingia – [ól:ú.u] vs Kingingele, Kitere – [ól:úya]

Rhotics in Sakata are also occasionally present as variants of lateral consonants, as can be seen in the following examples (5.a-g):

- 5.a “fingernail”: Kibayi – [ledzála] vs Kinzinzale – [ledzáʋa]
- 5.b “lung”: Kinzinzale – [féle] vs Kingingia, Kingingele – [fére]
- 5.c “scar”: Kinzinzale – [ib:áli] vs Kibayi – [éb:aʋé]
- 5.d “antelope”: Kinzinzale – [ɲkəbələ] vs Kibayi – [ɲkəbərə]
- 5.e “to rub”: Kingingia – [ópʰələ] vs Kibayi – [ipfúyurá], Kinzinzale – [ópʰurá], Kingingele, Kitere – [ápʰərə]
- 5.f “to fly”: Kingingia, Kingingele – [if:ələ] vs Kibayi – [ip:ébərə], Kinzinzale – [ópərə], Kitere – [óp:ərə]
- 5.g “to be satiated”: Kibayi – [iʒúla] vs Kinzinzale – [oʒúra]

Most of the rhotics and laterals reported in 5.a-g derive from Proto-Bantu *d in C₂ position (e.g. 5.a: *jádà, 5.b: *púd, 5.c: *bádà); this is a widely attested diachronic process known as rhotacism (when the alveolar stop is realised as a rhotic) or lambdacism (in the case of lateral realisations) (Vogelgesang 1993, Catford 2001, Hock 2001). For a number of reasons, I submit that lambdacism of *d occurred first, and that rhotacism of // (possibly in free variation with a lateral realisation) only intervened at a later stage. First of all, within West-Coastal Bantu, cognates of the forms listed above are more likely to exhibit a lateral than a rhotic as derivation of Proto-Bantu *d (e.g. 5.a *jádà > Mpiin B863Y [kínzá], Ngong B864X [kənzá], East Nsong B85dZ [lódzá], East Ding B68U [ludzá], East Lwel B862X [lədzá]/[ledzá]; 5.f *pudumuk > Nsambaan B85FX [kafula], East Ding B68U [kufúlá], East Lwel B862X [ofəl]/[ofələ], East Yans B85bY [kofula]; Bastin et al. 1999, Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2015). Second of all, a lot of synchronic alternation is reported between laterals and voiced alveolar stops both in the region and, more generally, throughout Congo

(Bokula 1970, Kutsch Lojenga 1991, 1994), and rhotacism of // has also been documented north of the area where Sakata is spoken, between the Congo and Ubangi Rivers (Lekens 1952, Samarin 1959, Walker & Samarin 1997), as well as in some Mai-Ndombe Lotwa varieties (see below). Lastly, while both lambdacism and rhotacism of voiced alveolar stops are fairly well documented sound change patterns, rhotacism or delateralisation of a lateral is generally considered less marked than its counterpart, i.e., lambdacism of a rhotic, as the former requires less articulatory precision (at least in the case of rhotacism to [r], which might have constituted a first step before subsequent developments to [r] and [ɮ]; Barry 1997, Barry & Russo 2002, 2003). Given the data currently available, it is not possible to assess whether rhotacism of // is phonologically conditioned. It is worth mentioning, though, that multiple repetitions of the same lexical item by the speakers often led to different realisations of the same target (i.e., one and the same person could often produce the same word with a lateral or a rhotic). This might indicate a still *in fieri* process of delateralisation of (singleton) // in intervocalic position.

Some Sakata varieties occasionally display complex rhotic clusters, presumably ensuing the fall of intervening vowels; specifically, in the case of the word for “animal” (probably from a Proto-Bantu form like *túg), some varieties present pre-nasalised monosyllabic sequences with syllabic rhotics: Kinzinzale [ntʃ̥], Kingingia [nsʃ̥]; cf. Kitere [ntúʃ̥].

The findings reported so far can be summarised as follows (where ++ = frequent occurrence, + = sporadic occurrence, – = not reported in the data):

Phenomenon	Kibayi	Kinzinzale	Kingingele	Kingingia	Kitere
Presence of /r/	++	++	++	++	++
Presence of /ɮ/	++	++	+	+	+
/r/ > 0	–	–	+	++	+
/ɮ/ > 0	+	+	++	++	++
/ɣ/, /g/ for /ɮ/	+	+	++	+	+
// > rhotic	+	++	+	+	+

The presence of an apical rhotic appears to be relatively well-established across the Sakata domain, whereas that of a uvular fricative is more stable in Kibayi and Kinzinzale and less so in Kingingia, Kingingele, and Kitere; reduction-to-zero

phenomena are more common in Kingingia, Kingingele, and Kitere; substitutions are rare, but particularly common in Kingingele; lastly, rhotacism of /l/ is ubiquitous but more prominently a feature of Kinzinzale. Grosso modo, this overview appears to describe two main dialectal areas, with Kibayi and Kinzinzale (stabler rhotics in the inventory) on the one hand, and Kingingia, Kingingele, and Kitere on the other.

If these findings were confirmed, given the specific lay of the Kutu territory (cf. Map), the demarcation provided by the Mfimi-Lukenye River complex would represent a (the?) major phonological isogloss in Sakata dialectology, cutting the area from east to west immediately to the south of Lake Mai-Ndombe, with Kibayi and Kinzinzale to the north and all other speech communities closer to the Kasai River. While this exceeds the scope of the present contribution, it is the author's impression that this situation tallies with the distribution of other sound changes in the area, e.g. the development of nasal vowels in Kingingia and Kingingele and the fricativisation of labial-velars (see below).

6.2.2 North Boma and Nunu

Regarding North Boma, Stappers (1986) describes a situation similar to that presented above for Sakata, i.e., one where an apical /r/ and a uvular fricative /ʁ/ alternate phonemically (as in [mpúro] “angry” vs [mpúʁo] “mouse”). This appears to hold true for Nunu as well. As was the case in Sakata, [ʁ] seems to be the reflex of a velar, and a certain degree of synchronic velar - (non-velar) rhotic alternation between the two varieties can still be detected; this occasionally extends to the apical (6.a-d):

6.a “trap”: North Boma – [kozjáʁampéro] vs Nunu – [kozígelempéro]

6.b “to reap”: North Boma – [kos:áʁó] vs Nunu – [kos:áɣaná]

6.c “eyebrow”: Nunu – [ek:íʁe] vs North Boma – [ek:éɣe]

6.d “grandson”: Nunu – [mut:úɣulemuzíri] vs North Boma – [mus:ú:yumuʒjúɣu]

The items reported in 6.d are particularly interesting, as they probably derive from the Proto-Bantu form *jintù “woman”, which must have undergone a process of semantic extension from “woman” to “human” to “man”; its acceptance of “man” is widespread

in Mai-Ndombe (it is present in all Sakata varieties, and has been reported in Boma Yumu; see Bastin et al. 1999, Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2012), and the /nt/ > (/nt/+TRILL) > TRILL change is one that deserves further scrutiny from the viewpoint of broader-scope cross-Bantu post-nasal trilling phenomena (cf. Shinagawa et al. 2022 and the literature cited therein).

Rhotacism of //, as observed for Sakata (see above for general considerations on the directionality of this specific sound change in the languages of Mai-Ndombe), is attested in North Boma and Nunu too. The phenomenon is, however, more markedly characteristic of Nunu; it also appears to have different outcomes in the two varieties, with North Boma favouring the fricative and Nunu the trill (7.a-g):

- 7.a “year”: Nunu – [ɱvɛlá] vs North Boma – [mwáɓa]
- 7.b “to smelt”: Nunu – [kok:ála] vs North Boma – [kok:áɓo]
- 7.c “antelope”: North Boma – [ɱvúli] vs Nunu – [ɱɛrí]
- 7.d “throat”: North Boma – [mu:elí] vs Nunu – [múɣurí]
- 7.e “oil”: North Boma – [ma:lí] vs Nunu – [ma:rí]
- 7.f “skirt”: North Boma – [mú:ɱfulé] vs Nunu – [mú:ɱfurí]
- 7.g “catfish”: North Boma – [mbelí] vs Nunu – [mbe:rí]

Interestingly, North Boma rhotics occasionally correspond to palatal approximants in Nunu, a feature which, to the best of my knowledge, is not shared by any other Mai-Ndombe varieties (8.a-d):

- 8.a “to boil”: North Boma – [kob:óɣoɓe] vs Nunu – [kob:óɣoɣé]
- 8.b “stock (bouillon)”: North Boma – [kɔb:óɣɔɓe] vs Nunu – [kɔb:óɣɔɣe]
- 8.c “thirst”: North Boma – [mpɹí] vs Nunu – [mpíja]
- 8.d “hole”: North Boma – [ipfurú] vs Nunu – [if:ují]

It can be hypothesised that Nunu rhotics have a greater degree of sonority than their North Boma counterparts (approximants are known to act as highly sonorous rhotics in some languages; see Colantoni 2006, Wiese 2011).

To summarise, North Boma and Nunu display similar sets of rhotics in their phonology; they do, however, exhibit typical Mai-Ndombe rhotic-related phenomena to

varying degrees, with Nunu being more prone to delateralisation and North Boma being more resistant to approximant-for-rhotic substitutions.

6.2.3 Lotwa

Concluding this section, a note on flapping (i.e., the production of a transient retroflex rhotic, see Laver 1994) in several eastern Mai-Ndombe Lotwa varieties. Numerous phonological peculiarities (allegedly) typical of Lotwa dialects across the forest have been documented in the literature (cf. Motingea 2015 and the references cited therein). For the purposes of the present contribution, the following observation by Motingea (2010: 205) on a Twa language of the Équateur (Democratic Republic of Congo) is of particular interest: “[...] there is one phoneme that one can hear among the Batwa, i.e., the flapped consonant /r/, which is otherwise represented in the literature as a rolled /r/ present in several local toponyms [...]. We can only assume that these phonetic traits are shared by all pygmy [sic] varieties” (my translation). This statement appears to match earlier claims by Vorbichler (1966/67), who reported that northeastern (non-Bantu) hunter-gatherer varieties from the Ituri show retroflexion (flapping) on both /r/ and /d/.

The data presented here appear to confirm the existence of a flap (/r/) in all four aforementioned Mai-Ndombe varieties as well; see Figure 33 for an example from Lotwa Lolia.

Figure 33 - Example of /ɽ/ in Lotwa Lolía; audio files available on OSF as Fig2

While flaps are attested in all four varieties surveyed, not all of them display them to the same extent. As a matter of fact, speaker J (and, to a lesser extent, K) often seemed to either produce a plain // where a flap had been recorded in Lotwa Lokonda, or to reduce the sound to zero (9.a-g):

9.a “beard”: L. Lokonda A, B – [lo.ɔɽé] vs L. Lolía – [lo:lé]

9.b “spirit”: L. Lokonda A, B – [boɽímu] vs L. Lolía – [bolíma]

9.c “hunter”: L. Lokonda A, B – [boɽíaciǎn:a:ma] vs L. Lolía – [bóli.aki.ónám:a], L. Losenge – [boja:kí.anáma]

9.d “to get on”: L. Lokonda A, B – [jóuɽɛɽa] vs L. Lolía – [joj:éla], L. Losenge – [uléa]

9.e “to wake up”: L. Lokonda A, B – [jóem:úɽa] vs L. Lolía – [jó.im:úa], L. Losenge – [zemúa]

9.f “co-wife”: L. Lokonda A, B – [bɔkǎ:ɽɛ] vs L. Losenge – [bok:á:lɪ]

9.g “to boil”: L. Losenge – [pe:ɽía] vs L. Lolía – [jóφelía]

The link between // and /ɽ/ appears to point in the direction of a similar phenomenon to the one described for Sakata, i.e., one of ongoing delateralisation of // in favour of various rhotic allophones. This claim is predicated on similar grounds to those

mentioned above for Sakata: most of the entries reported in 9 derive from protoforms which have been reconstructed with a *d in Proto-Bantu (e.g. 9.a: *dèdù, 9.b: *dímù) and have cognates in the general area which present a lateral rather than a rhotic (Embanga Aborobongui 2013) – this, of course, in addition to Motingea’s (2010, 2015) considerations. This process of delateralisation would be most advanced in Lotwa Lokonda and least so in Lotwa Lolia. Thus, delateralisation (possibly, an areal feature) and retroflexion / flapping (possibly, a substrate / contact feature deriving from the presence of hunter-gatherer communities in the area) appear to influence each other in the province’s Lotwa varieties. This is particularly interesting in that retroflexion, while generally rare in the area, has been documented in North Boma and Nunu (Stappers 1986, Maselli et al.: forthcoming), both of which exhibit nasal retroflexes in their phonological inventory. Historically, retroflexes are often the outcome of an articulatory shift in the presence of a rhotic (Bhat 1973, Bertinetto 2004), but the contexts in which they seem to arise in natural languages are limited. Therefore, their presence in specific regions has often been interpreted as a contact phenomenon, and independent internal development is generally excluded (Hamann 2003, Zhivlov 2016). As a matter of fact, sociophonetic factors have been claimed to influence the diffusion of retroflexes through neighbouring speech communities (Emeneau 1956, Hamp 1996, Hamann & Fuchs 2010, Tse 2015: 284ff). In this sense, while further data collection is pending, the presence of retroflexes in the North Boma / Nunu area might be connected to that of flaps in Lotwa.

6.3 Labial-velars

Labial-velar stops have been found in several varieties of Sakata. Labial-velar stops are doubly articulated sounds produced with simultaneous occlusions at different points of the oral cavity, one around the velum and one in the labial area (see e.g. Ladefoged 1968a,b, Ponelis 1974, Ohala & Lorentz 1977, Maddieson 1993, Connell 1994, Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996, Ladefoged 2003). These closures are released almost simultaneously, but the velar burst always seems to occur first (see Painter 1978, Connell 1987, 1991a,b, 1994, Dogil 1988, Maddieson & Ladefoged 1989, Cahill

& Hajek 2001, Cahill 2018: 154). Their presence in the phonological inventory of Sakata is interesting for several reasons.

First, labial-velar stops are rare in the world's languages, occurring in but 8% of the languages reported by Maddieson (2018). Other estimates do not differ significantly (see Cahill 2008). Labial-velars are mostly concentrated in Africa; according to Cahill's (2017) updated database of 848 languages with phonemic labial-velar stops, only 8% of them are spoken outside of Africa (chiefly in Papua – New Guinea, Oceania, South America). Within Africa, virtually all are spoken north of the Congo rainforest.

Second, labial-velars have often been interpreted as an areal feature typical of an alleged Sprachbund known as the Macro-Sudan Belt, a stretch of land extending contiguously from the western end of the African landmass to the Ethiopian escarpment in the east (Clements & Rialland 2008; Güldemann 2008, 2018: 479-486, Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021). In this area, shared linguistic features are attributed more to geographical proximity than to genealogical relationships. The prevalence of labial-velars in the Macro-Sudan Belt has been variously explained as retention and spread from Proto-Niger-Congo (Greenberg 1983), substrate interference from an unknown source (Vogler 2014, cited in Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021: 73), or transfer from undocumented hunter-gatherer forest languages (Schebesta 1949). The presence of labial-velar stops in some parts of the Bantu-speaking domain south of the Macro-Sudan Belt has been claimed to be contact-induced (cf. Bostoen & Donzo 2013; Cahill 2018: 156). However, Sakata, not being adjacent to the Macro-Sudan Belt, presents a unique case. While other southern Congo Bantu (esp. B80) varieties from Democratic Republic of Congo's Kwilu also exhibit labial-velar stops like /gb/ and /kp/ in their phonological inventories (see Maselli et al. 2021 for a recent overview), Sakata stands out in that it also presents the labial-velar nasal stop /ŋm/ (and, possibly, a labial-velar fricative; see below). In other words, Sakata's labial-velar set covers the entire series minus the rarer uvular and implosive counterparts.

The following relies heavily on the information (acoustic analyses) provided by Maselli et al.: 2023.

Figure 34 - Realisations of /kp/ (left) vs /gb/ (right) in Kinzinzale; audio files available on OSF as Fig3-1 and Fig3-2

Figure 34 shows F2 transitions marked by a steep rise into the subsequent vowel, as indicated by the red line in the spectrogram. A (partial) voicing bar, typically observed with voicing (see Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996, among others), is visible in [gb] (highlighted in red). However, this feature does not seem to distinguish the two as neatly as one might expect.

Figure 35 illustrates one realisation of a labial-velar nasal in Kitere. Labial-velar nasals have not been reported in any other languages of the region, but they are common in the Macro-Sudan Belt (cf. Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021). Despite the absence of visible release signs in the spectrographic trace, a steep F2 rise is still observable (indicated by the red line).

Figure 35 - Realisations of /ŋm/ in Kitere; audio file available on OSF as Fig4

A case of particular interest is the potential presence of labial-velar fricatives in certain Sakata varieties, as illustrated in Figure 36. While the physiological feasibility of articulations with two simultaneous sources of frication has been contested in the literature (Ladefoged and Maddieson 1996: 329-332, Cahill 2018), the concept of a voiceless labial-velar fricative is still recognised in the field of English dialectology (Schützler 2010, Bridwell 2019, Li & Gut 2022). No articulatory data are available to investigate the exact phonetic nature of the sounds in question. Nonetheless, it is interesting to note that these alleged labial-velar fricatives occur in Sakata in contexts where one would expect to find a labial-velar stop. As a matter of fact, labial-velars are often considered to be the result of a temporal compression phenomenon from a velar + labial-velar approximant sequence (*KW) to a full-fledged double articulation (KP; Ponelis 1974, Connell 1998/99). However, in Sakata, this compression occasionally yields [χw] or [ɬ]; see 10.a-d:

10.a *kú “to die” > Kibayi, Kinzinzale, Kingingia – [òkpá], Kitere – [ì:kpá]

10.b *kúá “inhabitant” > Kibayi, Kinzinzale – [múnɣbà], Kitere, Kingingia – [únɣbà]

10.c *kómbó “broom” > Kibayi – [lèkwámò], Kinzinzale – [lèχwómò]/-[mù], Kingingele, Kingingia, Kitere – [lèmó]

10.d *kúmbá “navel” > Kinzinzale – [mù:χúmá], Kingingia – [ù:mũá], Kingingele – [ù:kfũà]/[ù:pfũà].

In the case of the reflexes of Proto-Bantu *kómbó “broom”, the Sakata varieties surveyed here display a notable fricativisation process on the stop (/k/ > /χ/ in Kinzinzale), an outcome absent in the rest of West-Coastal Bantu (cf. Esiñji B76b [èkwóómò], Tio Bali B75U [kwúm]) or in Central-Western Bantu, the branch to which some recent studies ascribe Sakata based on geographic and lexical information (Koile et al. 2022) (cf. Ndengese C81 [lɔnkombɔ], Longandó C63 [lɔkómbɔ]). In turn, the back fricative + labial-velar approximant sequence appears to be subject to varying degrees of temporal compression in Kinzinzale (and possibly Kibayi), on the one hand, and in Kingingele, Kingingia, and Kitere on the other. Interestingly, Kingingele appears to take fricativisation even further than Kingingia and Kitere, by regularly substituting (in free variation) labial-velar stops with affricates such as [pf] (/ [kf]) and [dz] (see above, 10.d; Maselli et al. 2023). Regardless of the exact phonetic nature of this sound, the reflexes in 10 appear to indicate that both labial-velar stops and these newly documented fricatives constitute one sound class in Sakata. The sounds [χw], [m], and [kp]/[gb] in Sakata all seem to derive from Proto-Bantu *ku/kú.

Figure 36 - Realisations of /m/ (Kingingia, left) vs /χw/ (Kinzinzale, right); audio files available on OSF as Fig5-1 and Fig5-2

Sakata speakers consider the presence of labial-velar stops in their language as an identity marker distinguishing them from other Bantu speech communities in the area. Complementarily, their neighbours commonly identify Sakata speakers by their extensive use of labial-velar stops, thereby rendering this sound class a defining linguistic mark of the Sakata domain. This includes labial-velar fricatives as well as stops.

Summarising the results, the behaviour of labial-velars in Sakata partially matches that of rhotics, as presented above:

Phenomenon	Kibayi	Kinzinzale	Kingingele	Kingingia	Kitere
Presence of /kp/	++	++	+	++	++
Presence of /gb/	++	++	+	+	++
Presence of /ŋm/	++	–	–	++	+
Fricativisation	+	+	++	++	++
Affricativisation	–	–	++	–	–

Fricativisation seems to be more common in Kingingia, Kitere, and Kingingele, which again appear to constitute a regiolectal sub-group within Sakata (cf. the rhotic situation described above). The distribution of /ŋm/, however, does not match these preliminary findings.

6.4 Conclusions

To this day, the Mai-Ndombe province of the Democratic Republic of Congo, along with the rest of southwestern Congo, remains among the least well-surveyed areas of the planet in terms of linguistic and anthropological documentation. Detailed phonetic analyses of the languages spoken in the region are particularly lacking, as are reliable socio-linguistic accounts. This represents a severe gap in our knowledge of the West-Coastal Bantu domain for several reasons.

First, Mai-Ndombe is located in close proximity to the putative West-Coastal Bantu homeland (as recently redefined by Pacchiarotti et al. 2019). In turn, the West-Coastal Bantu homeland (between the Kamtsha and Kasai Rivers, in the Kwilu province of the

Democratic Republic of Congo, immediately to the south of Mai-Ndombe) is the region of highest linguistic diversity within the entire West-Coastal Bantu branch, hosting languages which exhibit a lot of phonological characteristics which are otherwise uncommon in Bantu, including rare vowel harmonies, umlaut effects, final vowel loss, systems of 9 and more vowels, and uncommon labial-velar stops and affricates (Daeleman 1977, Rottland 1977, Bostoen & Mundeke 2011a,b, Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2011, 2012, Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2021). Recent research, as summarised in this article, has shown that similarly exceptional features can be found well into Mai-Ndombe, where the languages reviewed here have been documented to present retroflexion, labial-velars, and systems of more than one non-flap rhotic. Considering that the existence of a pre-Bantu “forest substrate” (see above) has already been hypothesised to account for the great degree of linguistic diversity among the Bantu languages of western Central Africa, and that numerous hunter-gatherer Twa communities have been reported and documented in the broader area of interest, at least some of the diversity attested in the languages of Mai-Ndombe could be explained in terms of a Twa substrate, betraying signs of greater “archaic heterogeneity” (Hetzron 1976) than the relative uniformity of present-day Bantu might suggest. In this scenario, some of the rarer phenomena reported in the region could therefore constitute traces (“fossils”) of even greater (and now largely submerged) phonological and phonetic diversity. In particular, the co-occurrence of retroflexion in Lotwa and North Boma / Nunu begs the question of whether retroflexion as such should be considered as a substrate feature of the languages of the region.

Second, one of the specific characteristics of the phenomena attested in the present contribution is that they tend to affect more than one language at a time, working rather as “phonetic possibilities” than language-bound outcomes of traditional sound change rules. Phonemic double rhotics are a typologically rare feature that is however well established in the Sakata domain, itself a continuum of closely related dialects, and is attested in North Boma and Nunu too, suggesting that this specific characteristic is a common phonetic possibility in the area. Production of a retroflex flap in lieu of an intervocalic lateral is shared by all the Twa varieties documented here. This alternation often occurs as free variation, is distinctive of Twa groups in the Mongo area, and would appear to be shared by other hunter-gatherers in the central Congo Basin region. The presence of labial-velar consonants is another case in point: the variability in realisation of labial-velar sequences and the sporadic presence of more or less

temporally compressed labial-velar fricative sounds appear to affect the entire Sakata domain more than any specific Sakata lect individually. As a matter of fact, free variation between KW and KP is a very common occurrence in several southern Mai-Ndombe and Kwilu varieties, suggesting that the realisation of labial-velar sounds itself is actually a common phonetic possibility shared across the region, with different levels of phonologisation (from full-fledged phoneme, as in most Sakata lects, to mere variant of KW). In this sense, Mai-Ndombe is a unique testing ground to challenge traditional notions of sound change.

This contribution, meant as a report on the author's first foray into the region and intended to be chiefly exploratory in nature, represents the first attempt to tackle these issues organically and from an areal perspective.

Chapter 7: The emergence of interior vowels and heterosyllabic vowel sequences in Ngwi (Bantu B861, Democratic Republic of Congo)

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Abstract

In this article, we offer a historical account of the development of two phonemic “interior” vowels, [ə] and [ɤ], and heterosyllabic vowel sequences in Ngwi, a virtually undescribed West-Coastal Bantu language spoken in the western part of the Democratic Republic of Congo. While interior vowels phonologised due to the loss of their conditioning environment, most heterosyllabic vowel sequences come from the fission of an erstwhile palatal on-glide diphthong, itself originating in a long [– high] vowel. This origin is exactly the opposite of what has been reported for other language families such as Romance, where certain heterosyllabic vowel sequences of the *iV type evolved into diphthongs. The Ngwi data also show that phonemic interior vowels exist in languages of the Niger-Congo phylum where they had not been reported before. The historical development of heterosyllabic vowel sequences in Ngwi might have parallels in several other Bantu languages from the wider Congo rainforest area, where phonetic and phonological documentation is still embryonic.

Keywords: NA upon publication

7.1 Introduction

Ngwi [nlo] (a.k.a. Engwíí, Ngwí, Ngul, Nguli, Ngoli, Kingoli) is a West- Coastal Bantu (West-Coastal Bantu) language spoken south of the Lower Kasai River (-4.15, 19.08) in the Kwilu province of the Democratic Republic of Congo (Hammarström 2019: 27, Pacchiarotti et al. 2019: 209; see Map 8). In the updated version of Guthrie’s referential classification, Ngwi is inventoried as B861 (Maho 2009). The main objective of this paper is to provide a historically informed account of the emergence of the synchronic vowel system of Ngwi with a special focus on interior vowels and disyllabic vowel sequences. This is of interest for several reasons. First, the area of the Democratic Republic of Congo where Ngwi is spoken, the southern Congo Basin, is among the least well-documented linguistic regions of the world (Hammarstrom 2016), and dedicated phonetic/phonological studies of the languages spoken in this area are rare (see also Grégoire 2003: 351). In-depth research on the phonetics and phonology of languages such as Ngwi is therefore of great relevance for linguistic inquiry more generally.

Second, more specifically, Ngwi and other languages of the region such as Lwel B862 (Khang Levy 1979), Ding B86 (Mula 1977, Ebalantshim 1980), Yans B85 (Swartenbroeckx 1948, Rottland 1977), Nsambaan B85F (Mfum-Ekong 1979), and Nsong B85d (Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2019) display phonemic “interior vowels”, i.e., non-peripheral vowels located in the interior portion of the vowel space such as [i], [u], [ɜ] [ə] [ɹ], [ø], etc. (Rolle et al. 2017: 100). While interior vowels appear to be common in the African languages of the so-called Macro-Sudan Belt, a stretch of land spanning contiguously from the western end of the landmass to the Ethiopian escarpment in the east (Clements & Rialland 2008, Güldemann 2008), recent phonological surveys report them as absent south of this area, including the region of the Democratic Republic of Congo where Ngwi is spoken (Rolle et al. 2017: 101). In this paper, we provide evidence for the existence of phonemic interior vowels in this understudied area.

Third, a remarkable though poorly understood phonological feature of Bantu languages spoken in or near the Congo Basin rainforest, such as Ngwi, is their extreme tolerance for disyllabic vowel sequences (Grégoire 2003: 352). Besides the emergence of phonemic interior vowels, this paper focusses on the origin of

heterosyllabic /ɛ.a/ and /i.a/ vowel sequences in Ngwi and contributes to the understanding of this understudied phenomenon in western Bantu languages spoken in and around the Congo Basin rainforest. We show that /ɛ.a/ and /i.a/ sequences originate in the consolidation of an erstwhile palatal on-glide diphthong *ya* resulting from the breaking of [a:]. Through language-internal reconstruction, we demonstrate that the natural class of [– high] vowels, which emerged after the restructuring of the seven-vowel system of the protolanguage into a five-vowel system, played a crucial role in the emergence of both phonemic interior vowels and heterosyllabic vowel sequences.

In line with its objectives, this paper is organised as follows. In §7.2, we give a brief overview of the suprasegmental and phonotactic features of Ngwi which are immediately relevant to the developments discussed in the remainder of this paper. In §7.3, we present the synchronic vowel system of Ngwi along with a first exploration of its acoustic vowel space. In §7.4, we discuss the innovations that led to the emergence of present-day Ngwi vowel phonemes and the widespread presence of disyllabic vowel sequences in Ngwi. Specifically, in §7.4.1 we show that the inherited Proto-Bantu seven vowel system was reduced to five vowels. In §7.4.2, we outline the historical conditionings for the development of allophonic interior vowels which eventually phonologised and assess the phonetic groundedness of these phonological changes from a Dispersion Theory perspective. In §7.4.3 and subsections therein, we deal with the historical origins of disyllabic /ɛ.a/ and /i.a/ vowel sequences. In §7.4.4, we briefly discuss the origins of disyllabic vowel sequences other than /ɛ.a/ and /i.a/. Conclusions are in §7.5.

Throughout the paper, we use a phonetically driven transcription of Ngwi based on the International Phonetic Alphabet, with the exception of <y>, which we use for IPA [j]. In the Africanist tradition, <j> is often used as a grapheme to represent IPA [dʒ]. We note high tone as <á>, low tone as <à>, falling tone as <â>, and rising tone as <ǎ>. Throughout the paper, <.> indicates a syllable break, → means “surfaces phonetically as”, > means “historically evolved into”, < “historically derived from”, * introduces a protoform, and ** indicates a phonologically infelicitous form. This phonological account relies on a database of over a thousand lexical entries.

Map 8 - Approximate location of Ngwi B861 and other B80 languages

7.2 (Supra)segmental and phonotactic features of Ngwi

According to the latest and most comprehensive lexicon-based phylogeny of West-Coastal Bantu (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019), Ngwi B861 is one of the first parphyletic offshoots of the West-Coastal Bantu ancestral node together with Ding B86, Lwel B862, and Nzadi B865, as shown in Map 8. All these varieties are spoken in the putative West-Coastal Bantu homeland area.

Boone (1973: 243–245) identifies two groups of Ngwi speakers separated by and interspersed with intervening Lwel B862, Ding B86, and Nzadi B865 language communities. These are called Western and Eastern Ngwi (see also Maalu-Bungi et al. 2011: 18). This paper focusses on the vowel system of the Eastern variety of Ngwi as spoken in Mangai (−4.02, 19.53), a small town situated on the left bank of the Kasai River; see location of B861 on Map 8. Theses of Congolese students containing phonological data and reported in the literature could no longer be located by us

(Bwantsa Kafungu 1966, Obey 1984). The two morpho-phonological descriptions of the Western variety of Ngwi available to us, i.e., Bwantsa Kafungu (1979) and Kumpel Wossey (2001), suggest that there are remarkable differences between the two regiolectal varieties, certainly with respect to phonology. Data for this paper were collected during a one-month fieldwork mission (August–September 2019) within the BantuFirst project (<https://www.bantufirst.ugent.be/>) in Idiofa (-4.96, 19.59), where the first and last authors worked with two native Ngwi speakers originally from Mangai: Mr. Frédéric Mbeam-Oyuu Empenge Itobola (our main consultant) and Mr. Marako Wosama Ejem.

In Belgium, the first author subsequently crosschecked transcribed data and collected additional data in close collaboration with the main consultant. The exact number of Ngwi speakers today is unknown, but is definitely not higher than 10,000, and the language is certainly threatened by *linguae francae* such as Kongo ya Leta and Lingala.⁶⁴ Children born of parents speaking different West-Coastal Bantu “minority” languages, such as Ngwi and Ding, are mainly taught Kongo ya Leta and only a few words in the languages of their parents.

The Eastern variety of Ngwi documented here has 37 consonantal phonemes: /p, b, t, d, k, m, n, ɲ, ŋ, f, v, s, ʃ, ʒ, ɛ, pf, ts, dz, tʃ, dʒ, mp, mb, nt, nd, ŋk, ŋg, mf, mv, mpf, nts, ndz, ntʃ, ndʒ, r, w, y, l/. Pre-nasalised plosives, fricatives, and affricates only occur at the beginning of noun roots and are the outcome of the historical reanalysis of Proto-Bantu class (CL) 9/10 *N-/*N- homorganic nasal prefixes as part of a simple noun stem, e.g. Ø-ŋkwǎn ‘crocodile(s)’ < BLR 1446 *N-gòndé.⁶⁵ The word-internal distribution of consonants is phonotactically restricted: while all consonants except /ɛ/ and /r/ can appear in word- and/or syllable-initial position, only /m/, /n/, /ɲ/, /ŋ/, /r/, /ɛ/, /y/, and /b/ are attested in word- and/or syllable-final position. This left-to-right asymmetry in the occurrence of consonants within the stem is a common phenomenon in the northwestern part of the Bantu-speaking area (Hyman 2008: 331).⁶⁶ This asymmetry might be directly related to the fact that stem-initial position is a position of phonetic

⁶⁴ According to Niendéka & Djedje (1986, 42), the so-called “groupement Bangoli” of Oveke, the administrative territory uniting the Ngwi people, counted 8,401 inhabitants in the 1980s. However, not all people who identify ethnically as being Ngwi still speak the Ngwi language.

⁶⁵ BLR stands for Bantu Lexical Reconstructions 2/3, a database with approximately 10,000 Bantu reconstructed forms with various time depths (not all go back to PB) (Coupez et al. 1998; Bastin et al. 2002; Bostoen & Bastin 2016), see also section 4.

⁶⁶ The North-Western Bantu area includes Cameroon, Gabon, the Republic of the Congo, and parts of the Democratic Republic of Congo.

and phonological prominence not only in West-Coastal Bantu (cf. Paulian 1975 for the Teke variety Kukuya), but also in other northwestern Bantu languages and Niger-Congo languages spoken further north and west (cf. Van de Velde & Idiatov 2016, Lionnet & Hyman 2018: 651-655, Hyman et al. 2019: 196-199 and references therein).

Ngwi tone has considerable functional load (King 1967, Wang 1967, Surendran & Niyogi 2006, Oh et al. 2013). There are two primary tones or tonemes: High (H) and Low (L), which can combine to form R(ising) and F(alling) contour tones.⁶⁷ These four tonemes are lexically contrastive as shown by the following minimal pairs and triplets elicited in isolation. Attested contrastive tone patterns are illustrated for mono- (1), di- (2), and trisyllabic words (3).

(1)

H	F
ŋkúm ‘chief(s)’	ŋkûm ‘python(s)’
R	F
wũm ‘theft’	wûm ‘husband’
R	H
kǎβ ‘share’	káβ ‘tell’
L	F
wîŋ ‘arrow’	wîŋ ‘handle’

(2)

HH	LH	
kámá ‘bite, sting’	kàmá ‘steal’	
LL	LF	
ìtsùɓ ‘chicken coop’	ìtsûɓ ‘banana bunches’	
LF	LR	LL
ìkôm ‘broom’	ìkôm ‘Myrianthus arboreus (fruit)’	ìkòm ‘flaws’
LH	LF	
ìtsɘɓ ‘orphans’	ìtsûɓ ‘story, proverb’	

⁶⁷ Synchronically, sequences of LH and HL are always realised on two successive vowels belonging to different syllables. R and F occur only in closed syllables and they historically result from the loss of a word-final vowel whose tone was maintained and realised on the immediately preceding vowel, e.g., BLR 3749 *kúmà ‘python’ > Ngwi *ŋkûm*. Unlike level tones, contour tones involve phonetic lengthening of the host vowel. Ngwi does not have phonemic vowel length.

LH	LR
òkúr ‘fufu’	òkür ‘cob’
LH	HL
vîí ‘bones’	vîí ‘problems’

(3)

LLH	LHL	
àvèár ‘wives’	àvèàr ‘people’	
LLH	HHH	
kèàrá ‘give back’	kéárá ‘crawl’	
LHH	LHL	
èsúú ‘safou fruit’ ⁶⁸	èsúù ‘earth worm, bait’	
LLH	LHL	LHH
èkùó ‘sunset’	èkúò ‘tribes’	èkúó ‘umbilical cords’

The main tone process at the NP level in Ngwi is rightward H tone spreading. Both H tones and R tones can trigger it within the limits of the noun phrase as shown in (4)-(6).

(4) /ɲkúm è ikòlòŋò/ → [ɲkúm Ø ikólóŋó] ‘praying mantis’ (lit: chief of the spider)⁶⁹

(5) /ètèám èné/ → [ètèám éné] ‘this antelope sp.’⁷⁰

(6) /mbwǒm ìpè/ → [mbwǒm ípé] ‘two noses’

If the last constituent of a NP has a F (or a HL) tone or R (or LH tone), the spreading H tone cannot change this contour tone pattern into H or HH, as shown in **Error!**

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(7) /ɲkúm èmôɓ/ → [ɲkúm émôɓ] ‘one chief’

(8) /isǎŋ ì dzûɓ/ → [isǎŋ í dzûɓ] ‘trousers (lit: clothes of upstream)’

(9) /kyéŋ è kúù/ → [kyén é kúù] ‘ankle ring’ (lit: bracelet of leg)

⁶⁸ The scientific name of the safou tree, a.k.a the African plum, is *Dacryodes edulis*.

⁶⁹ (4) and (8)-(11) are instances of connective constructions where a head noun is modified by another noun usually introduced by a relator called connective, associative or genitive (Van de Velde 2013: 217). In Ngwi, the connective element triggered by the head noun is realised phonetically only if the following noun starts in a consonant.

⁷⁰ In the examples here and elsewhere, ‘n.’ stands for noun, ‘v.’ for verb, and ‘sp.’ for species.

(10) /òkǒr ò vên/ → [òkǒr ó vên] ‘toothbrush’ (lit: rope of teeth)

(11) /ndzèám è bùú/ → [ndzèám é bùú] ‘parent’ (lit: god of the earth)

The following are possible syllable shapes in Ngwi: CVC, VC, CV, and V. Due to the diachronic loss of final vowels (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2021), CVC is by far the most common. For the purposes of the present paper, however, VC and V are particularly relevant (see the historical discussion in sections 7.3.2 and 7.3.3). VC occurs only word-finally in di- or trisyllabic words. /ɛ/ and /a/ (in this order) are the only two vowels which can appear in CV.VC sequences, as shown in (12). Note that we treat a sequence of a nasal and a consonant as a prenasalised consonant, i. e., as a single consonantal unit.

(12)	(V.)CV.VC	ò.mpé.àm	‘man, male’	è.fé.àŋ	‘tobacco pipes’
		ò.ŋké.àr	‘woman’	à.pé.àɓ	‘coffins’
		ò.yè.áŋ	‘lie (n.)’	è.kè.ám	‘partridge’
		ndzè.ám	‘god(s)’	ké.àŋ	‘fry (v.)’
		mbè.áŋ	‘virgin forest(s)’	wè.ár	‘wife’
		è.té.ám	‘antelope (sp.)’	ò.vè.àm	‘whip’

V can occur word-initially, medially, or finally after a CV shape, as shown in (13) and (14). In CV_x.V_y words, there are restrictions on the quality of V_x and V_y. If V_x = V_y, these two vowels can only be /ɔ/, /u/, or /i/, as shown in (13).

(13)	CV _x .V _y	à.ki.í	‘eggs’ ⁷¹	è.wi.í	‘anthill’
	[V _x =V _y]	lí.ì	‘stream’	tì.í	‘excrements’
		à.tí.ì	‘ears’	ò.bí.ì	‘tuber, ear’
		mpó.ò	‘fetus’	ndzó.ò	‘elephant(s)’
		è.wú.ù	‘white hair’	è.bù.ú	‘pimple’
		è.kú.ù	‘leg’	à.yú.ù	‘hair’

⁷¹ /i/ in word final position, especially in CV.V word shapes, is realised as strongly palatalised and may sound almost as a fricative, e.g. /à.ki.í/ ‘egg’ [à.kíj].

If $V_x \neq V_y$ then V_x must be /u/ or /i/ while V_y can be /i/, /u/, /ɔ/, /ɛ/ or /a/, as in (14). Noun stems with the shape CV.V are considerably more frequent than CV.

(14)	CV _x .V _y	ndzú.à	'snake(s)'	mvú.á	'dog'
	[V _x ≠V _y]	ɲkú.ó	'snail, cowry'	ò.dzú.ò	'root'
		è.fù.é	'penis'	ì.tjú.é	'puff adder'
		ndzì.à	'hunger'	mì.á	'mother' ⁷²
		è.ndí.é	'white men'	ì.kí.é	'tobacco, cigarette'
		ví.ù	'mushroom(s)'	ì.dzì.ù	'grass, weeds'
		à.sú.ì	'saliva'	fù.í	'plant (v.)'

Sequences such as /u.a/, /u.o/, /u.e/, /i.a/, and /i.e/ as in (14) coexist in Ngwi with diphthongs, which are found in closed syllables whose last consonant is most commonly a nasal, as shown in (15) - see § 7.3 for further discussion.

(15)	ntfwoŋ	'leech(es)'
	àlwêṁ	'sperm'
	lyâm	'prepare'
	dʒwâṁ	'swim'
	fyêṁ	'blow (nose)'

Besides the fact that they are tone-bearing units, evidence to treat the vowel sequences in (13) and (14) as sequences of two vowels belonging to two different syllables — rather than analysing instances such as those in (13) as one long vowel and those in (14) as diphthongs — comes from vowel deletion processes. In Ngwi, sequences of two vowels across morpheme boundaries are reduced to one in fast speech. As shown in (16), where the apostrophe indicates vowel deletion, it is the last vowel of the first linear word which gets deleted.

(16)	
/ò.mvá ò né /	→ [ò.mv' ó né] 'this poor person'
/ntsé ìn é/	→ [nts' ìn é] 'these fish'

⁷² The /ia/ sequence in CV.V words, such as those for 'hunger' and 'mother', is realised phonetically as [ɪa] ~ [ea].

7.3 The vowel system of Ngwi

The seven vowel phonemes of the eastern variety of Ngwi are shown in Table 18.⁷³ Ngwi does not have phonemic vowel length.

Table 18 - Ngwi vowel phonemes

	FRONT	CENTRAL	BACK
HIGH	i		u
MID-HIGH			ɤ
MID		ə	
MID-LOW	ɛ		ɔ
LOW		a	

(Near) minimal pairs and triplets, proving the phonemic status of the segments in Table 18, are shown in (18).

- (18) /ə/ ηkêṃ ‘monkey(s)’ /ə/ èlêṃ ‘tongue’⁷⁴
 /ʉ/ ηkûṃ ‘python(s)’ /i/ èlîṃ ‘glues’
- /ə/ ndêβ ‘bell(s)’ /ə/ ìsəβ ‘horn, elephant tusk’
 /ɔ/ ndôβ ‘fish hook(s)’ /ɤ/ ìtsɤβ ‘orphans’
- /ə/ èté ‘fetish, medicine’ /ʉ/ ìpûβ ‘hole, obstacle’
 /ɛ/ èté ‘heads’ /ɤ/ ìpɤβ ‘livers’

⁷³ According to Kumpel Wossey (2001), western Ngwi has a 7-vowel system that is different from the one we report for eastern Ngwi in Table 1: /i/, /e/, /ɛ/, /a/, /ɔ/, /o/, /u/. It is an inventory more typical of the ‘Bantu languages of the forest’ in that it lacks /ɤ/ and /ə/ but has /e/ and /o/ (cf. Grégoire 2003).

⁷⁴ In the absence of a conditioning environment, the open-mid front and back vowels of Ngwi are realised as [ɛ] and [ɔ] respectively. However, the o- prefixes of CL1 (< Proto-Bantu *mù-) , CL3 (< Proto-Bantu *mù-) and CL11 (< Proto-Bantu *dù-) are always realised as [o] and the e- prefixes of CL4 (< Proto-Bantu *mì-) and CL7e (< Proto-Bantu *kî-) always as [e], as in è-lêṃ ‘tongue’ in (1). In 7-vowel Bantu languages such as Mongo C61 (de Rop 1958), [e] and [ɔ] usually arise diachronically from the lowering of Proto-Bantu *ɪ and *ʊ respectively. However, anywhere else in the Ngwi lexicon, Proto-Bantu *ɪ and *ʊ merged with Proto-Bantu *i and *u respectively, yielding /i/ and /u/ (see discussion in §**Error! Reference source not found.**). In principle, [e] and [ɔ] can be shown to contrast with vowels other than /ɛ/ and /ɔ/ in word initial position, e.g. è-tûṃ ‘CL7-enemy’ vs. ì-tûṃ ‘CL8-enemy’, ò-jûṃ ‘CL3-tree’ vs. è-jûṃ ‘CL4-tree’. Nevertheless, we refrain from giving [e] and [ɔ] phonemic/allophonic status, because their distribution is heavily restricted morphologically. They can occur only as realisations of noun class prefixes and agreement morphemes of nouns belonging to classes 1, 3, 11, 4, and 7e. For this reason, we consider them as sub-phonemic (Garrett 2014: 239; Honeybone & Salmons 2014).

/a/ ètà 'bows'

/u/ itûn 'doorway'

/ɔ/ itôn 'spot, speckle'

An exploratory analysis of the acoustic vowel space of Ngwi speaker Frédéric Mbeam-Oyuu Empenge Itobola (plotted for inverted values of F1 and F2) is provided in Figure 37.⁷⁵

Figure 37 - Acoustic vowel space of Ngwi

The interior vowels, /ə/ and /ɾ/, deserve particular attention. As can be seen in Figure 37, the values for /ə/ are spread over a vast, central portion of the space. In terms of height, the /ə/ area is clearly above the mid-low and below the high portion of the vowel space. This is in line with what one might expect from the under-specification theory, where “schwa is a vowel that lacks a well-defined target, and so assimilates strongly

⁷⁵ A higher resolution version of this Figure can be found here: https://osf.io/9x3v7/?view_only=88d0a95d1a714e8da1bd7c6e77e22359

to surrounding segments, resulting in substantial variation in the vowel quality of schwa” (Flemming 2009). On the other hand, available values for /ɾ/ are much more widely dispersed than anticipated, with an F2 range stretching from near to /u/ to near to /i/. These values seem to centre around a set of coordinates which is closer to that of /ʌ/ than to that of a prototypical mid-high unrounded vowel. For instance, Koffi (2018) reports the following cross-linguistic average values: for /ʌ/ — F1 565 Hz, F2 1258 Hz; for /ɾ/ — F1 414 Hz, F2 1248 Hz. These facts might be interpreted in different ways: a) the relatively high F1 levels for [ɾ] tokens might be due to a maximisation effect of the acoustic distance from /u/; b) such wide-ranging F2 values might indicate that /ɾ/ is actually treated as a non-peripheral vowel in Ngwi. This, in turn, would make it perceptually less salient than its peripheral counterparts /u/ and /ɔ/ (see Polka & Bohn 2003), and allow for greater dispersion at the acoustic level. While we hold that, auditorily, this vowel is indeed better described as /ɾ/ than /ʌ/, we still largely lack the data to further assess the situation.

Root-internally, /i/ and /u/ trigger progressive vowel heightening in the open-mid vowels /ɛ/ and /ɔ/ which are then realised as [e] and [o] respectively, as in (19). However, as shown in (20), the singular CL5 ì- noun class prefix and plural CL8 ì- noun class prefix never trigger such progressive vowel heightening across morpheme boundaries. There are no ù- noun class prefixes in Ngwi.

- (19) /liè/ → [liè] ‘cry (v.)’
 /ntʃúè/ → [ntʃúè] ‘electric fish’
 /dzùó/ → [dzùó] ‘civet cat(s)’
 /lòtʃúù/ → [lòtʃúù] ‘yesterday’

- (20) /ì-kór/ → [ikór] ‘frog, toad’
 /ì-tôr/ → [itôr] ‘wells’

In the next section, we discuss the major historical sound changes which shaped the Ngwi vowel system as we observe it today by focussing on the phonologisation of /ə/ and /ɾ/ (see Table 18) and the emergence of /ɛ.a/ and /i.a/ sequences in (13) and (14).

7.4 Historical developments

In order to trace the historical developments undergone by the present-day vocalic system of Ngwi, we used a top-down approach and relied on the nearly 10,000 protoforms available in the Bantu Lexical Reconstructions (BLR) 2/3 database (Coupez et al. 1998; Bastin et al. 2002; Bostoen & Bastin 2016). Some of these protoforms go back to Proto-Bantu while others are reconstructible only to lower nodes in the Bantu family tree. In all examples in the following subsections, we give the form and meaning of the protoforms along with their index number as found in the BLR database, e.g. BLR 1265 *dù mbù ‘mouth’. Protoforms without an index number are not officially included in the BLR 2/3 database but are tentatively proposed based on comparative West-Coastal Bantu data collected during the ERC-funded projects KongoKing (<http://www.kongoking.org/>) and BantuFirst (<https://www.bantufirst.ugent.be/>) led by the last author of this paper. For greater clarity, we segment the noun class prefix from the noun root in the Ngwi reflexes of nominal reconstructions, e.g. ò-dzûm ‘mouth’. The symbol Ø- preceding a noun root means that the noun takes a zero noun class prefix, e.g., Ø-mvûy ‘pig(s)’. Whenever possible, we use as examples Ngwi reflexes of protoforms with a widespread distribution in the Bantu domain and a high reliability score (see Bostoen & Bastin 2016 for details). Finally, we specify the meaning of a Ngwi reflex only when it differs from the one(s) posited for the corresponding protoform.

7.4.1 The 7>5 vowel merger

The reconstructed Proto-Bantu vowel system is given in Table 19 (Bastin et al. 2002). Although Bastin et al. (2002) represent * ϵ and * ɔ with the graphemes <*e> and <*o>, we adopt here the more phonetically transparent notation * ϵ and * ɔ for greater clarity.

Table 19 - The Proto-Bantu vowel system

	FRONT	CENTRAL	BACK
HIGH	i		u
MID-HIGH		ɪ	ʊ
MID			
MID-LOW	ɛ		ɔ
LOW		a	

Two restructurings of this system are particularly common in Bantu languages: 5-vowel systems where *i and *ɪ merged into /i/ and *u and *ʊ merged into /u/ or 7-vowel systems where Proto-Bantu *ɪ and *ʊ lowered to /e/ and /o/ (Schadeberg 1995; Bostoen 2019; Hyman 2019). These restructurings are illustrated in Table 20 and Table 21 respectively.

Table 20 - Typical Bantu 5-vowel system

	FRONT	CENTRAL	BACK
HIGH	i		u
MID-HIGH		ɪ	ʊ
MID			
MID-LOW	ɛ		ɔ
LOW		a	

Table 21 - Typical Bantu 7-vowel system (especially in languages of the Congo Basin rainforest; elsewhere, 7-vowel languages tend to maintain the Proto-Bantu system)

	FRONT	CENTRAL	BACK
HIGH	i		u
MID-HIGH	e	ɪ	ʊ
MID			o
MID-LOW	ɛ		ɔ
LOW		a	

Ngwi displays a synchronic 7-vowel system which is only partially the result of one of the aforementioned restructurings. At an earlier stage, like numerous West-Coastal Bantu languages belonging to the Kikongo Language Cluster (Bostoen & Goes 2019),

Ngwi underwent the 7 > 5 vowel merger illustrated in Table 20. Evidence for this merger is provided in (21)–(27). As shown in (21) and (22), Proto-Bantu *u and *ɔ yielded /u/.

(21)	Proto-Bantu *u	BLR 1265	*dùmbù ‘mouth’	> ò-dzùm
		BLR 2112	*kúm ‘come from’	> kùm ‘arrive’
		BLR 3131	*túng ‘tie up’	> túnɣ
		BLR 368	*búdà ‘rain, year’	> Ø-mvúyè
		BLR 1536	*gùdú ‘pig’	> Ø-mvûy
		BLR 2108	*kúdù ‘land turtle’	> Ø-mfûr
		BLR 2118	*kúmú ‘chief’	> Ø-ɣkúm
		BLR 1545	*kùnd ‘bury’	> ò-pfũɣ ‘burial’ ⁷⁶
		BLR 761	*cùgù ‘day’	> è-fúù
		BLR 3778	*cùnì ‘meat, flesh’	> ò-sûɣ ‘muscle’
		BLR 5395	*gútù ‘calabash’	> è-pfûy
		BLR 360	*bùá ‘nine’	> ì-wùá
	(22)	Proto-Bantu *ɔ	BLR 1509	*gùndà ‘forest’
		BLR 303	*búdì ‘goat’	> Ø-mbûr
		BLR 316	*búgà ‘path’	> Ø-mbûɛ
		BLR 1179	*dúk ‘vomit’	> lúà
		BLR 2642	*púkù ‘mouse’	> Ø-mfúù
		BLR 4152	*túmè ‘messenger’	> Ø-ntùm
		BLR 2041	*kún ‘plant, sow’	> kûn
		BLR 2042	*kùnì ‘firewood’	> è-kûɣ
		BLR 1490	*gùdù ‘leg’	> è-kúù
		BLR 1223	*dúngú ‘pepper’	> è-lúɣ
		BLR 2664	*pútá ‘wound’	> Ø-mpúr
		BLR 1628	*jùndò ‘hammer’	> Ø-ndʒûn
		BLR 1621	*jùgú ‘groundnut’	> è-yũɛ

⁷⁶ The deverbative noun of which òpfũɣ ‘burial’ is a reflex must have ended in a high vowel, i.e., either *kù nd-ú or *kù nd-í, as these are the only contexts in which the alveolar nasal — also when followed by a consonant as in *nd — gets palatalised. See, for instance, its near-homonym ipfũɣ ‘stomach’, which is a reflex of BLR 1545 *kùndú ‘stomach’.

Similarly, Proto-Bantu *i and *ɪ yielded /i/ in Ngwi, as shown in (23) and (24).

(23)	Proto-Bantu *i	BLR 1046	*dím ‘be extinguished get lost’	> dzîm
		BLR 3356	*jímì ‘pregnancy’	> dz-îm
		BLR 9667	*jini ‘pubes’	> dz-îŋ ‘vagina’
		BLR 1854	*kítà ‘oil’	> v-îr
		BLR 237	*bìmò ‘abdomen’	> è-bîm ‘chest’
		BLR 1845	*kíngó ‘neck’	> Ø-ŋkíŋ
		BLR 2585	*pììpí ‘darkness’	> Ø-mpîb
		BLR 2572	*pìn ‘press, squeeze with fingers’	> è-pîŋ ‘finger’
(24)	Proto-Bantu *ɪ	BLR 2506	*pìcì ‘bone’	> w-îí
		BLR 1378	*gìdì ‘egg’	> i-kîí
		BLR 1801	*kímb ‘wander about’	> kîm ‘run away’
		BLR 940	*dì ‘be’	> li
		BLR 959	*dìd ‘cry’	> liè
		BLR 1592	*jíbò ‘house’	> dz-îb
		BLR 3364	*jîmbò ‘song, dance’	> Ø-lîm
		BLR 985	*dîmbò ‘birdglue’	> ò-lîm
		BLR 249	*bîndò ‘dirt’	> Ø-mbîn
		BLR 3431	*jîjî ‘stream’	> Ø-lîi
		BLR 579	*cîndí ‘squirrel’	> è-ŋín
		BLR 6207	*jîjab ‘know’	> ʒíà

As seen in (25)–(27), respectively, Proto-Bantu *ɔ, *ɛ, and *a were retained in Ngwi.

(25)	Proto-Bantu *ɔ	BLR 261	*bòmà ‘python’	> Ø-mbôm ‘boa’
		BLR 1429	*gòmà ‘drum’	> Ø-ŋôm
		BLR 1088	*dób ‘fish (v.)’	> lób
		BLR 1127	*dòng ‘speak, teach’	> lônŋ ‘teach, advise’

	BLR 1106	*dògò ‘witchcraft’	> <i>i-lôɓ</i>
	BLR 1927	*kómbó ‘broom’	> <i>i-kôm</i>
	BLR 1147	*dóótì ‘dream’	> \emptyset - <i>ndôy</i>
	BLR 1607	*jògù ‘elephant’	> \emptyset - <i>ndzòò</i>
	BLR 664	*cónì ‘shame’	> <i>è-ntsôŋ</i>
	BLR 6515	*cómí ‘eldest child’	> \emptyset - <i>ntsôm</i>
(26)	Proto-Bantu *e		
	BLR 900	*dègè ‘weaver bird’	> <i>è-lêɓ</i>
	BLR 919	*démb ‘be tired’	> <i>lěm</i>
	BLR 897	*dèdù ‘beard’	> <i>è-léy</i>
	BLR 2166	*méémé ‘sheep’	> <i>i-mémé</i>
	BLR 1583	*jénjé ‘cricket’	> \emptyset - <i>ndzén</i>
	BLR 2255	*nénè ‘big’	> <i>nên</i>
	BLR 508	*cèd ‘be slippery’	> <i>sêr</i>
	BLR 3295	*jén ‘see’	> <i>yên</i>
	BLR 2469	*pèep ‘blow (wind)’	> <i>fébé</i>
(27)	Proto-Bantu *a		
	BLR 3252	*játò ‘canoe’	> <i>w-âr</i>
	BLR 1	*bá ‘palm oil nut’	> <i>è-bá</i>
	BLR 61	*bàgú ‘stumbling block’	> <i>i-bǎɓ</i> ‘stump’
	BLR 3180	*nyàmà ‘animal’	> \emptyset - <i>ŋâm</i>
	BLR 812	*dàgá ‘promise’	> <i>è-lǎɓ</i>
	BLR 2410	*pàpá ‘wing’	> <i>i-pǎβ</i>
	BLR 1695	*kámá ‘hundred’	> \emptyset - <i>ŋkám</i>
	BLR 1274	*gàb ‘divide, give away’	> <i>kǎb</i>
	BLR 2744	*támà ‘cheek’	> <i>i-tâm</i>
	BLR 1739	*kájí ‘leaf’	> <i>è-káy</i>
	BLR 9605	*pákù ‘honey’	> \emptyset - <i>mpâɓ</i>
	BLR 394	*càbuk ‘cross river’	> <i>sǎβ</i>
	BLR 496	*cátù ‘three’	> <i>i-sâr</i>
	BLR 9207	*táà ‘bow’	> <i>ò-tá</i>

7.4.2 The phonologisation of [ə] and [ɣ]

After the 7 > 5 vowel merger had taken place, /i/ as the merged reflex of Proto-Bantu *i and *ɪ developed two allophones in V₁ position in a *C₁V₁C₂V₂ template, namely the interior vowels [ə] and [ɣ]. The conditioning environments which historically triggered [ə] and [ɣ] as allophones of /i/ in V₁ are given in (28: Proto-Ngwi *i in C₁ > [ə]/__ C₂ *ɛ, *a, *ɔ) and (29: Proto-Ngwi *i in C₁ > [ɣ]/__ C₂ *u) respectively. In this section, unless otherwise specified, the asterisk next to a segment not preceded by the label BLR refers to a form presumably present in an earlier stage of Ngwi.

(28)	BLR 3464	*jínà ‘name’	> dz-ên
	BLR 1798	*kímà ‘monkey’	> Ø-ɲkâm
	BLR 6108	*cìkà ‘girl, woman’	> ò-sêɓ ‘young girl’
	BLR 2139	*mà ‘thing’ ⁷⁷	> Ø-vâm
	BLR 957	*dìbò ‘bell’	> Ø-nděb
	BLR 3472	*jínò ‘tooth’	> dz-ên
	BLR 574	*cígé ‘horn’	> ì-séɓ
	BLR 1828	*kígè ‘eyelash’	> è-kêɓ
	BLR 971	*dímè ‘tongue’	> è-lêm
	BLR 2936	*tnde ‘wax’	> tsăn ‘earwax, pus’
	BLR 2898	*tín ‘cut’ + suffix	> ì-tsên ‘stalk’ (e.g. of sugar cane) ⁷⁸
	BLR 6024	*bít ‘lie down’ + suffix	> vêr ‘sleep’
(29)	BLR 193	*bìdú ‘cola nut’	> ì-bÿr
	BLR 6196	*tígúé ‘young orphan’	> è-tsÿɓ ‘orphan’
	BLR 8151	*pèkúá ‘raphia fiber’ ⁷⁹	> ì-pÿɓ ‘raphia palm’
	BLR 2569	*pígù ‘kidney’	> ì-pÿɓ ‘liver’

⁷⁷ This protoform possibly had a noun prefix with an /i/ which was reanalyzed in Ngwi as part of the simple noun stem.

⁷⁸ We hypothesise that the deverbative nouns ‘stalk’ and ‘sleep’ were derived from their respective verb roots through the Proto-Bantu deverbative noun suffixes *-ò or *-è (cf. Schadeberg & Bostoen 2019: 189–190, which they write as *-ò and *-è respectively).

⁷⁹ This protoform has a low reliability score in BLR 2/3 (Coupez et al. 1998, Bastin et al. 2002) and is attested only in zone C languages. Since several zone C languages underwent the restructuring of the inherited Proto-Bantu system illustrated in Table 4, where Proto-Bantu *ɪ merged with Proto-Bantu *ɛ, it is entirely possible that current BLR 8151 should actually be reconstructed as *pìkúá .

BLR 6113 *cíkù ‘hiccup’ > à-sísɾɛ

This gave rise to the system in Table 22.

Table 22 - The emergence of /ə/ and /ɾ/ in Ngwi

	FRONT	CENTRAL	BACK
HIGH	i		u
MID-HIGH			ɾ
MID		ə	
MID-LOW	ɛ		ɔ
LOW		a	

As was the case with other West-Coastal Bantu varieties spoken along the Lower Kasai in the Democratic Republic of Congo, Ngwi underwent final vowel loss (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2021). Once this diachronic sound change took place, the conditioning environment which originally triggered [ə] and [ɾ] as allophones of /i/ was lost and phonemic split arose. Roots starting out with an identical V₁ but a different V₂ end up with a different V₁ and without a V₂, e.g. BLR 3356 *jímì ‘pregnacy’ > dʒ-îm, but BLR 3472 *jínò ‘tooth’ > dz-ən.⁸⁰ Loss of a conditioning environment is one of the best-known sources for the creation of phonemic splits (Hock 1991: 56, Labov 1994: 332). See Bostoen & Koni Muluwa (2011, 2014) for other cases of phonologisation of root-internal vowel allophones due to the loss of a conditioning final vowel in several West-Coastal Bantu languages spoken in the Lower Kasai region.

The assimilation processes in (28) and (29) did not target all suitable lexical items. While evidence for (29) is scanty, there is evidence that several lexical items escaped the change in (28), as shown in (30). To show that this irregularity is not attributable to any conditioning environment, in (30), each lexical item which was not targeted by the assimilation in (28) is followed by a formally similar or identical item which was targeted by this innovation.

(30) BLR 1973 *kídà ‘tail’ > ò-yîr

⁸⁰ ‘Pregnancy’ and ‘tooth’ in Ngwi both belong to class 5. Class 5 nouns starting in a vowel take dʒ- as a noun class prefix. This prefix is depalatalised to [dz] when the noun root starts with /ə/.

But	BLR	*pɪda ‘family, clan’ > Ø-mpêy ‘uncle’
	BLR 1592	*díbò ‘house’ > Ø-dʒɪb ‘house for birds’
But	BLR 957	*dìbò ‘bell’ > Ø-ndêb
	BLR 3364	*jímbò ‘song, dance’ > Ø-lîm ‘song’
But	BLR 3472	*jɪńò ‘tooth’ > dz-ên
	BLR 985	*dìmbò ‘birdlime’ > ò-lîm
But	BLR 2936	*tìndè ‘wax’ > Ø-tsên ‘earwax, pus’
	BLR 3354	*jímad ‘stand, stop’ > yímá ‘be standing’
But	BLR 2895	*tímà ‘heart’ > ò-tâm
	BLR 1854	*kít à ‘oil’ > v-îr
But	BLR 6024	*bít ‘lie down’ > vêr
	BLR 237	*bìmò ‘abdomen’ > è-bím ‘chest’
But	BLR 1798	*kímà ‘monkey’ > Ø-ɲkêm

All lexical items in (30) had the right environment for the change *i > [ə] to take place. In all instances, V₁ *i is followed by V₂ *ɔ, *a, or *ɛ which cause centralisation of *i to [ə] as shown in (28). Nevertheless, some V₁ *i were retained instead of undergoing assimilation.⁸¹ Additionally, there is evidence that the shift *i > [ə] was irregularly extended to words which did not have the right conditioning environment for this change to occur, as can be seen in (31). Word-finality cannot be considered as a triggering factor here. The very few Ngwi CV roots we have observed so far end in any vowel except /ɾ/.

(31)	BLR 2881	*tí ‘tree, stick’	è-té ‘medicine, fetish’
	BLR 751	*cúí ‘fish’	Ø-ntsé
	BLR 285	*bùè ‘stone’	ì-vè ‘big stone’

Finally, there is evidence that partially nativised borrowings (easily detectable by the presence of a final vowel), did not undergo the shift *i > [ə], e.g. è-tʃímà ‘whirlwind’ < BLR 5882 *tìm bà ‘whirlpool.’ This kind of irregularity in sound change is pervasive in

⁸¹ When a conditioning environment disappears, speakers have two options: (a) retain the assimilation and phonologise the allophone or (b) give up the assimilation which is no longer required phonetically. It seems as if Ngwi speakers chose (a) for some lexical items such as those in (28), and (b) for some others, such as those in (30).

West-Coastal Bantu (and probably Bantu more generally) and is observed with other diachronic sound changes (see Pacchiarotti & Bostoen: forthcoming for possible explanations). Even if lexical borrowing can salvage the sound change regularity hypothesis in some cases, many ‘exceptions’ cannot be accounted for by borrowing.

We conclude this section with some further phonological considerations with respect to the assimilation processes in (28) and (29). The phonological conditioning in (28) and (29) arose once the 7 > 5 vowel merger had left the language with a vowel space clearly split into two relevant natural classes, i.e., [– high] (/a/, /ɔ/, /ɛ/) and [+ high] (/i/, /u/). As we will see in sections 7.4.3.2 and 7.4.4, [– high] appears to be a salient class in Ngwi phonology. This process is in line with what we know from the study of phonetic biases on phonological learnability: more complex phonological patterns, with either an arbitrary distribution of features or a more complicated architecture thereof, are harder to acquire for (adult) language learners (Pycha et al. 2003, Peperkamp et al. 2006; for an overview of the relevant literature within models of Artificial Grammar Learning, see Finley 2012). In this sense, a system with two high vowels opposed to three non-high vowels (either mid-low or low, i.e., not mid-high) is more economical than the system in Table 20 from which contemporary Ngwi originated, where the organisation of features into significant natural classes is more problematic.⁸² Of course, a simple formal architecture of phonological features does not necessarily stem from phonetic groundedness; see Greenwood (2016: 31). However, the closer a vowel is to the lower end of the space, the more salient its definition as [– high] is (Ladefoged 1971, Boersma 1997), making the [– high] class at this stage of the evolution of Ngwi both formally simple and phonetically grounded. This [– high] class triggered the distant regressive assimilation phenomenon illustrated by the change in (28), which can be reformulated with features as in (32).

(32) C₁V₁[+ high, + front]C₂V₂ > C₁V₁[– high, – front, – back]C₂V₂/___ V₂[– high]

⁸² The ‘problematic’ aspect lies in the presence of near-high counterparts to /i/ and /u/, namely /ɪ/ and /ʊ/, a class of non-high vowels that would not appear to pattern with the other non-high vowels of the system. However, it is worth mentioning that the emergence of lower vowels in the grammar is generally predicted to have an earlier (‘easier’ or ‘more natural’) onset in traditional Dispersion Theory models (Liljencrants & Lindblom 1972, Vaux & Samuels 2015: 576).

The change in (32) raises at least two different questions: a) why did V₁ lose [+ high]?; b) why did V₁ not become [+ low] (or [+ mid-low])?⁸³ The first point can be resolved as follows: [+ high] harmonised to a [– high] class thus becoming [– high] in its own turn. The second question is probably harder to answer satisfactorily and entails a deeper understanding of the problems posed by a): a priori, one might have expected that the centralisation of /i/ would result in /ɜ/ or /e/ (i.e., somewhere lower in the vowel space and more in line with the low F1 values of /a/, /ɔ/, and /ɛ/). However, “schwa”, i.e., the mid-central vowel commonly transcribed as [ə] in the International Phonetic Alphabet, is arguably an underspecified vowel subject to reduction phenomena in phonological processes, i.e., to assimilation to its segmental context, which makes it highly context-sensitive in terms of phonetic realisation (see Flemming 2009: 1). Incidentally, this could also explain the considerable dispersion observable for [ə] tokens in the Ngwi vowel space in Figure 37. As such, the underspecified mid-central vowel [ə] is the ideal output of any centralisation process where backness is undefined. Additionally, lower central vowels are cross-linguistically much rarer, a fact which might be due to their relatively high position in proposed vowel sonority scales (Gordon et al. 2012: 221). In this sense, the phonetic output of the centralisation phenomenon in (32) is unsurprising.

As for the change in (29), it can be reformulated as in (33).

(33) C₁V₁[+ high, + front]C₂V₂ > C₁V₁[– high, – front, + back]C₂V₂/___ V₂[+ high]

The assimilation to [+ back] in (33) is problematic because it entails an apparently odd change in height, whereby a high vowel assimilated to another high vowel by becoming mid-high. A seemingly more expectable output might have been either /u/ or, since /i/ is unrounded, /ʊ/. However, from a Dispersion Theory perspective (Liljencrants & Lindblom 1972, Lindblom 1986), vowels tend to disperse across the vowel space to enhance perceptibility. In this sense, a system with three back vowels

⁸³ A possible third question would be: why did V₁ lose both its [+front] and [+back] specifications? In an earlier version of this paper we proposed to address the issue as follows: since the [– high] class described above is unspecified for backness, the most reasonable solution was for /i/ to converge to the centre (centralisation). However, as was pointed out to us by Pavel Iosad (p.c.), this stipulation would require that one subscribe to the notion that schwa is actually necessarily [– front] and [– back], which is only one of the possible ways to characterise its under-specification for backness. The fact that /i/ converged to the centre can therefore be explained as an effect of its target being either unspecified for backness ([0 backness]?) or explicitly specified as [– front], [– back]. We will leave this point for future consideration, as neither hypothesis substantially affects the argument at hand.

(a high one, a mid-high one, and a mid-low one) is definitely better balanced than one with two back high vowels and a mid-low one. In fact, /ɣ/ is expected to be part of the optimal 7-vowel system proposed by Lindblom (1990). Since high vowels are cross-linguistically less likely to trigger round harmony (Finley 2012), /ɣ/ (as opposed to, say, /o/) should not be taken as a surprising outcome. Alternatively, as suggested to us by Pavel Iosad (p.c.), one could posit that since there is no contrast between [ɣ] and [ʉ], [ɣ] is phonologically [+ high].

7.4.3 The emergence of /ɛ.a/ and /i.a/ vowel sequences

In the following subsections we provide evidence for the claim that most /ɛ.a/ sequences found in CV.VC words and /i.a/ sequences found in CV.V words originate in the fission of an erstwhile palatal on-glide diphthong ya (phonetically [ja]), itself originating in a long /a:/, into a sequence of two vowels belonging to two successive syllables. We refer to this process as the syllabification or fission of [ja] into /ɛ.a/ and /i.a/ sequences. The long vowel at the origin of the ya diphthong arose diachronically from several distinct phonological environments. Due to the immediate relevance of diphthongs for the emergence of /ɛ.a/ and /i.a/ sequences, we first discuss them briefly in the following subsection.

7.4.3.1 *The crucial role of diphthongisation*

As discussed in detail in Koni Muluwa & Bostoen (2012), on-glide diphthongs in Lower Kasai languages such as Ngwi have their origin in the automatic vowel lengthening that commonly happens in Bantu before a nasal consonant cluster (NC) (cf. Hyman 2019). It is well known that vowel length is an ideal phonetic environment for the emergence of diphthongs, not only in Bantu but also in other language families both within and outside of Africa (see Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2012, 370 for a list of relevant references). The most common diphthongs in Ngwi, /wɔ/ and /yɛ/, arose from the automatically lengthened Proto-Bantu mid vowels *ɔ and *ɛ. Consider the data in (34)–(35).

(34)	BLR 2986	*tòndò 'roof'	> ò-twôn
	BLR 265	*bòmbó 'nose'	> Ø-mbwǒm
	BLR 117	*dòndà 'pain, wound, abscess'	> Ø-lwôn 'birth pain'
	BLR 3001	*tòngò 'sleep'	> Ø-lwǒŋ
	BLR 6806	*póngò 'fat'	> Ø-mpwôn 'marrow'
	BLR 6731	*kóndè 'bean'	> è-kwôn
	BLR 1446	*gòndé 'crocodile'	> Ø-ŋkwǒn
	BLR 1445/BLR 1447	*gòndè ~ *gòndò 'moon'	> Ø-ŋgwôn
	BLR 1128	*dòngà 'river, valley, channel'	> Ø-ndwǒŋ 'marsh'
	BLR 1434	*gòmbè 'cattle'	> Ø-ŋgwóm
	BLR 665	*còng 'show (v.)'	> ʃwǒŋ
	BLR 655	*còmb 'borrow, lend'	> tʃwǒm
(35)	BLR 2846	*ténd 'groan, grunt'	> ì-tyên 'gossip' ⁸⁴
	BLR 2853	*téndé 'thorn'	> ì-tyén
	BLR 1362	*gènd 'walk, travel, go (away)'	> kyên
	BLR 7535	*bémbédé 'mosquito'	> è-byémé
	BLR 2458	*pénjù 'cockroach'	> ì-pyéŋ

All the protoforms in (34) contain a NC in C₂ position which is reduced to a nasal (N) in Ngwi, just like in other Lower Kasai languages. The vowel preceding this historical NC tends to be automatically lengthened in Bantu languages, as was probably also the case in Proto-Bantu (Meeussen 1979: 2). Diphthongs such as /wɔ/ and /yɛ/ arose from lengthened *ɔ: and *ɛ: respectively through the following chain of changes, where G stands for glide: CVNVCV > CV:N > CGVN (see Rottland 1977: 382, Hyman 2003: 50, Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2012). This sound change is quite pervasive in Ngwi, but in this case too several suitable targets escaped it, e.g., BLR 1927 *kómbó 'broom' > ì-kôm, BLR 919 *démb 'be tired' > lěm, BLR 1583 *jénjé 'cricket' > Ø-ndzɛ n. Finally, by way of analogy with the diphthongisation of protoforms containing a NC in C₂ position which was simplified to N, several protoforms with a historical N in C₂ position underwent the same change, e.g., BLR 6506 *tóm 'chew, drink' > twôm 'chew', BLR

⁸⁴ In many West-Coastal Bantu languages, reflexes of this protoform mean 'talk, chat'.

1359 *gèni ‘stranger, visitor’ > ò- ñgìngyèn. However, this analogical change was irregular as it did not apply systematically to all suitable lexical items, e.g., BLR 1429 *gò mà ‘drum’ > Ø- ñòm, BLR 2255 *nénè ‘big’ > nèn.

7.4.3.2 /ɛ.a/ sequences in CV.VC words

Synchronic /ɛ.a/ sequences in contemporary Ngwi only occur in word-medial position in a synchronic CV.VC structure. In the light of the discussion in the preceding subsection, it seems highly plausible that the /ɛ.a/ sequences in (36) arose from a chain of changes such as the following: CaNCV > Ca:N > CyaN > Cɛ.aN, as in *gàngà > òngà:ŋ > òngyàŋ > òngèáŋ.

(36)	BLR 1332	*gàngà ‘medicine man’	> ò-ñgèáŋ ‘doctor’
	BLR 1706	*kàndá ‘letter’	> ò-ñkèáŋ
	BLR 1321	*gàndá ‘clan’	> ò-ñkèáŋ ‘grandchild’
	BLR 844	*dàmbá ‘cloth’	> è-lèám
	BLR 2400	*pángà ‘cave’	> ò-péàŋ ‘parcel of land, fence’
	BLR 97	*bánjá ‘dwelling place, courtyard, etc.’	> Ø-mbèáŋ ‘battle, war’
	BLR 8407	*pàmbí ‘antelope bushbuck’	> Ø-mpèám
	BLR 3196	*jàmbé ‘god’	> Ø-ndzèám
	BLR 8741	*tàngí ‘bedstead’	> Ø-ntèáŋ
	BLR 2394	*pànjí ‘side of body’	> è-pèáŋ
	BLR 1719	*káng ‘fry, roast’	> kéàŋ
	BLR 8650	*dàng ‘like, desire’	> lèáŋ ‘want, love, desire’
	BLR 9390	*cánk ‘be happy’	> ò-séàŋ ‘joy’

Koni Muluwa & Bostoen (2012: 368) report the [– high] vowel *a becoming [ya] in several other Lower Kasai languages besides Ngwi. Possibly, the breaking of a long /a:/ vowel into a diphthong might have been triggered by the fact that other [– high] vowels such as /ɔ/ and /ɛ/ show a strong tendency to diphthongise in Ngwi. At the same time, the crystallisation of ya into two vowel nuclei did not act as an attractor,

i.e., diphthongs emerged out of mid-vowels ϵ and ɔ did not become sequences of two vowel nuclei.⁸⁵

At some point, this on-glide *ya* diphthong syllabified in Ngwi and two vowel nuclei were created, i.e., $ya > \xi a > \epsilon.a$. This change is schematically represented in terms of syllable-internal restructuring in Figure 38, where σ = syllable, O = Onset, N = Nucleus and C = Coda. The syllabification process out of an original palatal on-glide *ya* diphthong is illustrated for the simple noun stem *ŋgèán* ‘medicine man’ without its synchronic noun class prefix, see (36). The syllable-internal structure of phonological diphthongs reflects their general understanding in the relevant literature as complex vowel units where both vowel elements are part of the syllable nucleus (Ladefoged 1993).

Figure 38 - creation of / $\epsilon.a$ / sequences in Ngwi

On the other hand, the / $\epsilon.a$ / sequences in (37) did not arise from protoforms containing a NC in C_2 position.

- | | | | |
|------|----------|-------------------|----------------|
| (37) | BLR 8255 | *jána ‘palm wine’ | > v-èán ‘wine’ |
| | BLR 8211 | *pámì ‘man, male’ | > ò-mpéàm |
| | BLR 6434 | *nàinà ‘eight’ | > ì-nèàní |

⁸⁵ Pavel Iosad (p.c.) has suggested to us that since [a:] goes a step further compared to [ɔ] and [ɛ] in the fission of the erstwhile diphthong, a reasonable progression of sound change is one where lengthening > diphthongisation > fission happens with /a/ before spreading to the mid vowels. This hypothetical pathway, phonetically grounded in the inherent length of /a/ compared to [ɛ] and [ɔ], predicts that if a language has diphthongs involving mid vowels [ɛ] and [ɔ], it also has diphthongs involving low vowels such as /a/. According to the survey in Koni Muluwa and Bostoen (2012: 370), this prediction is only partially borne out: a few Lower Kasai languages such as Ntsambaan B85F, Nsong B85d, and Mbuun B87 apparently only have diphthongs from mid-vowels [ɛ] and [ɔ]. Detailed data collection might (dis)prove this fact.

BLR 1674	*kádí ‘woman, wife’	> ò-ηκέάρ ‘woman, female’ ⁸⁶
BLR 3158	*jàdí ‘girl at puberty, woman’	> Ø-wèár ‘wife’
BLR 9467	*mat ‘run’	> mèàrá ‘trample on’
BLR 2433	*pègà ‘shoulder’	> ì-πέαβ

The first three entries in (37) are reflexes of protoforms with a simple nasal in C₂ position. These are readily explained by analogical extension: the same process described above for original *NC which were simplified to N was extended to historical *N in C₂ position as in *pámì ‘man, male’ (see above for analogical extension happening with wɔ and ye diphthongs). Cases where no simple nasal is present in (37) might be accounted for in a different way. Protoforms such as *kádí ‘woman, wife’ and *jàdí ‘girl at puberty, woman’ have a front vowel in *V₂ position. BLR 9467 *mat ‘run’ might also have been followed by a verbal derivational suffix with a front vowel, such as the applicative *-ɪd. In other Lower Kasai languages, the reflexes of protoforms with *a in *V₁ and a front vowel in *V₂ often have a palatal-glide diphthong ya in V₁, e.g., BLR 1674 *kádí > B85bT mu-kyáy, B85e ð-kyáy, B86 mù-kyáy, B862 ηkyál (Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2012: 376–377). In these cases, ya diphthongisation can be considered an instance of umlaut or anticipatory assimilation to the palatal segment *i that used to be present in the protoform *kádí (Schürr 1970: 3 cited in Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2012). In other varieties, V₁ *a undergoes umlaut, whereby *a > ε under the influence of a V₂ front vowel, e.g., BLR 1674 *kádí > B85d mò-kets, B85F bà-kés, B87W ù-kéts. Yet in other varieties, the open-mid vowel ε resulting from umlaut further diphthongises to ye, e.g., BLR 1667 *kádī ‘bitter, fierce’ > B85bV kyéy (see Bostoen & Koni Muluwa 2014 for a typology of umlaut in these languages). Thus, the ya diphthong which gave rise to /ε.a/ sequences in ò-ηκέάρ and Ø-wèár might have been triggered by the presence of a historical front vowel. However, this development cannot account for protoforms which have *a in *V₂ position and a front vowel in *V₁ such as *pègà ‘shoulder’. In fact, ì-πέαβ as a reflex of BLR 2433 *pègà remains unexplained. Even if one were to posit that ì-πέαβ arose out of a vowel that was lengthened as a compensatory strategy for the loss of the final vowel of forms such as *pègà ‘shoulder’, e.g., *pègà > °pèèβ, ε: in Ngwi diphthongises into ye, not ya.

⁸⁶ Both ò-ηκέάρ ‘woman, female’ and Ø-wèár ‘wife’ are irregular reflexes because *d in C₂ did not become zero as expected.

7.4.3.3 /i.a/ sequences in CV.V words

/i.a/ sequences only occur in Ngwi in word/syllable-final position. Phonetically, they are realised as [ɪ.a] or [e.a], but when they participate in vowel deletion processes, /a/ gets deleted and the remaining vowel surfaces as [i], as illustrated in (38).

- (38) /èsià/ [èsíà] ~ [èséà] ‘feather’
 /èsià èné/ [èsí’ èné] ‘this feather’

Diachronically, unlike /ɛ.a/ sequences, all /i.a/ sequences arose due to the loss of a C₂ consonant in a C₁V₁C₂V₂ template. Numerous different combinations of vowels are involved in the creation of /i.a/ sequences in this historical template.

Some /i.a/ sequences in Ngwi are simply the result of the coming together of a historical V₁ *ɪ and V₂ *a due to the loss of *d in C₂ position, as in (39). Note that the loss of an intervocalic consonant in Ngwi did not trigger loss of syllable boundaries and the coalescence of a two-vowel sequence into one long vowel (see de Chene 2014: 26–27 for examples of languages where vowel length was created in such contexts).

*V₁=ɪ; *V₂=a

- (39) BLR 183 *bídá ‘call, announcement’ > Ø-mbià ‘greeting’
 BLR 5884 *jíjà ‘fire’ > Ø-tjíá
 BLR 6207 *jíjab ‘know’ > ò-zíà

Recall that whenever a C₂ was not lost but preserved, Proto-Bantu *ɪ or *i in V₁ followed by a Proto-Bantu non-high vowel such as *a in V₂ gave rise to an allophonic [ə] in V₁ position, see (28). The fact that the /i.a/ sequences in (39) did not further develop into /ə.a/ suggests that regressive assimilation occurred only when the triggering segment and its target were not adjacent.

A few other synchronic /i.a/ sequences seem to have arisen diachronically from the coming together of a historical V₁ *a and V₂ *i due to the loss of *d in C₂ position, as in (40).

*V₁=a; *V₂=ɪ

(40)	BLR 3161	*jàdí ‘village’	> w-íà
	BLR 412	*cádí ‘work (n.)’	> ò-tjíà
	BLR 404	*cád ‘work (v.)’	> tǰíà ‘weed, clear ground’ ⁸⁷

To account for the reflexes in (40), one needs to posit metathesis, whereby CaCi > Cai > Cia or CaCi > CiCa > Cia. Metathesis could have been triggered by analogy with the /i.a/ sequences historically originating in V₁ *ɪ and V₂ *a as in (39) or more commonly from V₁ *a and V₂ *a in (41).

*V₁=a; *V₂=a

(41)	BLR 1662	*kádà ‘embers, charcoal’	> ì-kíà
	BLR 1294	*gádà ‘finger nail’	> è-kíà ‘nail, claw, fish scale’
	BLR 1555	*jàdà ‘hunger’	> Ø-ndzià
	BLR 406	*cádá ‘feather’	> è-síà
	BLR 1557	*jàdà ‘rubbish heap’	> Ø-dǰià
	BLR 2140	*máá ‘mother’	> Ø-miá ⁸⁸
	BLR 2806	*tààtá ‘father’	> Ø-tiá

At first glance, the /i.a/ sequences in (41) look like the outcome of distant regressive dissimilation. When two low vowels were found in adjacent syllables, the first low vowel became [– low], schematically: CaCa > CiCa > Cia or CaCa > Caa > Cia. Apparently, this sound shift is widely attested in Oceanic languages, where aCa > eCa/əCa or more rarely iCa (Blevins 2009), as well as Kera (Chadic) (Pearce 2007) and some Russian dialects (Botma et al. 2015).⁸⁹

However, considering the explanation for the emergence of /ɛ.a/ sequences set forth above, there is at least one more way to account for the reflexes in (41). In their comparative study of diphthongisation in West-Coastal Bantu languages belonging to

⁸⁷ The infinitive form tǰià is included in (40) because we assume that it is historically derived from BLR 404 *cád ‘work’ plus a semantically compatible derivational suffix with a front vowel such as Proto-Bantu applicative *-ɪd.

⁸⁸ BLR 2140 *máá exists alongside BLR 2146 *mààmá. On the other hand, there is no **tàà reconstruction alongside *tààtá for ‘father’. Nevertheless, it is possible that tiá ‘father’ in Ngwi was formed by way of analogy with miá ‘mother’ which could in turn be diachronically derived from a shortening of BLR 2146 *mààmá.

⁸⁹ We thank Pavel Iosad (p.c.) for pointing us to the existence of this phenomenon in languages other than Oceanic.

Guthrie's B70 and B80 referential groups, Koni Muluwa & Bostoen (2012) report instances where diphthongs cannot be explained by conditioning factors such as umlaut phenomena or compensatory lengthening due to the loss of a segment. These cases are illustrated with data from West and East Yans B85a and B85b respectively and Mpur B85e in (42). Note that these unexplained diphthongs occur in reflexes of protoforms with *a in both *V₁ and *V₂ position, just like those in (41).

*V₁=a; *V₂=a

(42)	BLR 1294	*gádà 'nail'	> B85e ńnyâ
	BLR 812	*dàgá 'promise'	> B85b lyàk
	BLR 425	*càkà 'sorghum'	> B85b syák
	BLR 1684	*kákà 'anteater'	> B85b kyák
	BLR 820	*dákà 'tongue, language'	> B85a ndeak

Factoring in the data in (42), one could posit that the Ngwi /i.a/ sequences in (41) arose out of a palatal on-glide ya diphthong just like the /ɛ.a/ sequences in CV.VC words. Unlike what happened with /ɛ.a/ sequences, where ya originated in a long [a:] vowel created via automatic lengthening before a NC, in the case of the /i.a/ sequences in (41), the ya diphthong originated in a long [a:] vowel created due to the loss of C₂, e.g., BLR 1662 *kádà > káà > kyâ > kíà. As was the case with /ɛ.a/ sequences, the ya diphthong was resyllabified as a sequence of two full vowels. Under this account /ɛ.a/ and /i.a/ sequences would have the same origin: the fission of a /ya/ diphthong out of a long [a:] vowel. The resulting heterosyllabic vowel sequence is realised as /ɛ.a/ in word medial position and as /ɪ.a/ or /e.a/ in word final position.

Another advantage of this unified account is that it can provide an explanation for the apparently unexplainable cases of diphthongisation in (42). Palatal on-glide diphthongs in other Lower Kasai varieties such as Mpur B85e and East Yans B85b can be explained by positing that a long /a:/ was created as a compensatory strategy for the loss of the final vowel. This long /a:/ then broke into a ya diphthong, e.g. CVCV > CVC > CV:C > CGVC, or BLR 812 *dàgá > Yans B85b lăk > làák > lyàk. What is more, the development /ya/ > /ɛa/ might be attested even in dialectal varieties of presumably the same language, compare the East Yans B85b forms in (42) displaying /ya/ with West Yans B85a ndeak < BLR 820 *dákà, where presumably <ea> does not represent

a diphthong but a series of two vowels. Similarly, in the eastern variety of Ding B86, when the applicative suffix -il combines with CVC verb roots where V is /a/, the result is [ɛa], e.g. /lâm-il/ ‘prepare-APPL’ > [lɛam] (fieldwork data collected by the first author in consultation with Donatien Musimar Aleben). One could posit that the /i/ of applicative -il causes anticipatory assimilation of V₁ a to ya which then undergoes syllabification.

In Table 23, we present a possible seriation of changes to account for the /i.a/ outcome in Lower Kasai languages like Ngwi B861 and the /ya/ outcome in Lower Kasai languages like Mpur B85e, out of protoforms with a C₁V₁C₂V₂ shape where C₂ is not a N or a NC and V₁ and V₂ were both *a. The chronology of C₂ loss and final vowel loss is based on Pacchiarotti & Bostoen (2021).

Table 23 - Possible chronology for i.a and ya outcomes in Lower Kasai languages

	BLR 1294 *GÁDÀ ‘NAIL’	NGWI B861	MPUR B85E
	loss of C2	káà	—
	final vowel loss	—	ɲál
	compensatory lengthening	—	ɲáàl
	diphthongisation	kyâ	ɲyâl
	syllabification	kíà	—

In an experimental study on the heterosyllabic vs. diphthongal realisations of inherited *iV Late Latin sequences in five Romance languages, Chitoran & Hualde (2007: 55, 59) find that the general evolutionary tendency for heterosyllabic [iV] sequences to be shortened to diphthongs is inhibited when vowel sequences are found in word-initial (stressed) syllables, because they have a greater duration than vowel sequences found in non-initial (unstressed) syllables. Considering these experimental findings, the creation of heterosyllabic /i.a/ sequences in Ngwi might have been favoured by the fact that a historical disyllabic word became, at some point in earlier stages of Ngwi, a monosyllabic CV: stressed word. Tone might also have played a role in the syllabification process.

7.4.3.4 Other V.V sequences

In this section we briefly discuss the historical development of word final V.V sequences other than /i.a/. Unlike /i.a/ sequences discussed in the last subsection, the V.V sequences discussed here arose from three different proto-syllable shapes, namely: *CVCV, *CVV, and *CV.

Those which arose from *CVCV structures can be roughly subdivided into three groups depending on the quality of historical *V₁ and *V₂. If *V₁ and *V₂ were both [– high], that is *ɔ, *ɛ, or *a, the long vowel created by the loss of the intervocalic consonant broke into a diphthong which then syllabified into a sequence of two vowels, e.g. *jòbó > dzòó > dzwǒ > dzùó. Some examples of this sound change are given in (43). As suggested above, this sound change provides further evidence for [– high] as a natural phonetic class in Ngwi.

*CV_[– high]CV_[– high] > *CV_[+ high].V_[– high]

(43)	BLR 6882	*jòbó ‘civet cat’	> Ø-dzùó ⁹⁰
	BLR 1891	*kódò ‘grandparent, female ancestor’	> ò-kúò ‘tribe, ethnicity’
	BLR 7003	*kódó ‘snail, cowry’	> Ø-ŋkúó
	BLR 2594	*pódò ‘calmness’	> Ø-púó ‘be silent’
	BLR 260	*bókò ‘arm’	> è-wúò
	BLR 893	*ndédé ‘white man’	> ò-ndié
	BLR 7809	*gèdé ‘downstream’	> Ø-ŋgié
	BLR 3536	*jókà ‘snake’	> Ø-ndzúà
	BLR 647	*còká ‘axe’	> ì-júà

Another possibility to account for the reflexes in (43) would be to posit that the two historical [– high] vowels dissimilated and historical *V₁ became [+ high], e.g. *jòbó > dzòò > dzùó or *jòbó > dzùbó > dzùó. However, positing a long vowel which develops

⁹⁰ Note that while intervocalic loss of Proto-Bantu *d, *c, and *j is a mostly regular sound change in Ngwi, the loss of an intervocalic Proto-Bantu *b occurred only very sporadically. Similarly, while the loss of the merged Proto–West-Coastal Bantu reflex *k of Proto-Bantu velar stops *k and *g in C₂ is very common throughout West-Coastal Bantu (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020), the loss of Proto–West-Coastal Bantu *k in C₂ in Ngwi occurs in a very limited number of words (the most common reflex of Proto–West-Coastal Bantu *k in C₂ is /ɬ/).

into a diphthong that then undergoes syllabification is more appealing, as this is essentially the same process at play in the creation of other V.V sequences.

When *V₁ and *V₂ were both [+ high], they were retained as such as can be seen in (44). Sporadically, total assimilation occurred (cf. *túkì ‘insult’ > ì-tíì).

*CV_[+ high]CV_[+ high] > CV_[+ high].V_[+ high]

(44)	BLR 4570	*bùdú ‘swart, pimple’	> è-bùú
	BLR 1490	*gùdù ‘leg’	> è-kùù
	BLR 1168	*dùdù ‘bitterness’	> ò-lùù
	BLR 2642	*púkù ‘mouse’	> Ø-mfúù
	BLR 761	*cùgù ‘day’	> è-ǰùù
	BLR 2506	*pìcì ‘bone’	> w-ìí
	BLR 1378	*gìdì ‘egg’	> ì-kíí
	BLR 5755	*bìdì ‘leaf’	> ò-bíì ‘tuber, ear (e.g. of corn)’
	BLR	*bìdì ‘heat’	> Ø-mbìí
	BLR 3431	*ǰíǰì ‘stream’	> Ø-líì
	BLR 6040	*tìtì ‘excrement’	> Ø-tìí
	BLR 5638	*ǰìbù ‘mushroom’	> vìù
	BLR 2073	*kùpí ‘short’	> kùì
	BLR 5339	*túkì ‘insult’	> ì-tíì

When either *V₁ or *V₂ was [+ high], the [– high] historical vowel was fully assimilated to the [+ high] vowel regardless of its phonotactic position as shown in (45). This assimilation process corroborates [+ high] as a natural phonetic class as opposed to [– high] in Ngwi.

*CV_[+ high]CV_[– high] ~ *CV_[– high]CV_[+ high] > CV_[+ high].V_[+ high]

(45)	BLR 230	*bìcà ‘back, rear’	> Ø-mbìì
	BLR 1607	*ǰògù ‘elephant’	> Ø-ndzúù ⁹¹
	BLR 2677	*púdò ‘foam’	> è-fúù
	BLR 9461	*cákú ‘safou fruit’	> è-súú

⁹¹ This form is attested in the western variety of Ngwi. In the eastern variety, ‘elephant’ is Ø-ndzòò.

V.V sequences also arose from the reanalysis of historical *CVV shapes, where VV was likely a diphthong in Proto-Bantu, into a sequence of two vowel nuclei, as shown in (46). While *u/*ɔ followed by *a were retained as such, other *CVV shapes show irregularity, compare for instance ì-tîi < BLR 3030 *túi and ò-dzúù < BLR 6463 *dìù where *V₁ fully assimilates to *V₂ with è-wúù < BLR 364 *búi where *V₂ fully assimilates to *V₁.

*CVV > CV.V

(46)	BLR 282	*búà ‘dog’	> Ø-mvúá ⁹²
	BLR 3030	*túi ‘ear’	> ì-tîi
	BLR 364	*búi ‘white hair’	> è-wúù
	BLR 6463	*dìù ‘root, fiber’	> ò-dzúù ‘root’

There is also scanty evidence that *CV shapes developed into CV.V, possibly through a stage where V.V was a diphthong, see (47). In this case, too, the [– high] natural class seems to have played an important role. Crucially, the only two examples available involve *ɔ. This change possibly happened by analogy with the creation of two vowel nuclei out of diphthongs from lengthened [– high] vowels elsewhere in the language.

*CV>CGV>CV.V

(47)	BLR 1855	*kò ‘banana’	> ì-ŋkùò
	BLR 7178	*tó ‘caterpillar’	> ò-túò

7.5 Conclusions

In this paper we have shown that Ngwi, a West-Coastal Bantu language spoken in the Democratic Republic of Congo, has two phonemic interior vowels /ə/ and /ɾ/ and great tolerance for heterosyllabic vowel sequences. After the restructuring of the inherited Proto-Bantu seven vowel system, Ngwi was left with five phonemic vowels which

⁹² In elicitation, this word often sounds as [mvá]. However, whenever a word starting in a vowel follows, the /u/ surfaces, e.g. /mvúá èné/ > [mvú éné] ‘this dog’.

formed two natural classes. The [+ high] class contained /i/ and /u/, while the [– high] class contained /ɛ/, /ɔ/, and /a/. The interior vowels were originally allophones of /i/ in V₁ position in a C₁V₁C₂V₂ template, triggered by distinct conditionings. [ə] was the allophonic realisation of Proto-Ngwi *i whenever V₂ was [– high], while [ɾ] was the allophonic realisation of Proto-Ngwi *i whenever V₂ was [+ high, + back]. Once the diachronic sound change of final vowel loss took place, the conditioning V₂ environment was lost and the interior allophonic vowels phonologised.

The great majority of heterosyllabic vowel sequences in Ngwi, whether word-medial or word-final, originate in the lengthening of a [– high] vowel. This [– high] vowel broke into a diphthong which then syllabified as a sequence of two vowel nuclei. There were two main sources for vowel lengthening depending on the historical phonotactic shape from which the synchronic vowel sequence derives. The first source is automatic vowel lengthening in front of a nasal consonant cluster in C₂ position which was reduced to a simple nasal in Ngwi, i.e., CaNCV > Ca:N > CyaN > Cɛ.aN. While the other two [– high] vowels /ɛ/ and /ɔ/ diphthongised to yɛ and wɔ respectively, only the ya diphthong arising from a long [a:] became a sequence of two vowel nuclei in word-medial position, namely /ɛ.a/. The second source is a long [– high] vowel (or the coalescence of two distinct [– high] short vowels) created by the loss of an intervocalic consonant in a *CV_[– high]CV_[– high] historical shape, i.e., *CVCV > CVV > CGV > CV.V, where G stands for glide. This second source gave rise to /i.a/, /i.e/, /u.o/, and /u.a/ sequences. Vowel sequences of [+ high] vowels such as /i.i/, /u.u/, /i.u/, and /u.i/ may also originate from the loss of an intervocalic consonant in a *CVCV shape but do not involve any intermediate diphthongisation step. Finally, word/syllable final V.V sequences in CV.V words where V_[+ high].V_[– high] may also originate in *CVV shapes where VV was presumably a diphthong which was reanalysed as two vowel nuclei. Thus, diphthongisation originating in long vowels has been the major driving force in the creation of vowel sequences in Ngwi. While in some language families *iV sequences evolved into diphthongs (see, e.g., Chitoran & Hualde 2007), the diachronic-phonological account proposed here offers evidence for the exact opposite development in Ngwi, i.e., /ɛ.a/ and /i.a/ sequences originating in diphthongs.

We conclude with a few region-specific observations which might be of interest for future diachronic phonological and phonetic research in the area. Diphthongs originating from vowel breaking are rare in Bantu languages but extremely common in all Lower Kasai languages spoken in the West-Coastal Bantu homeland (Koni Muluwa

& Bostoen 2012). Diphthongisation appears to be a strong areal feature in the West-Coastal Bantu homeland and the fission of diphthongs into heterosyllabic vowel sequences might have parallels in other languages. In fact, this feature makes a good candidate for substrate interference. In support of this speculation, Motingea (2010: 156) observes that in Bantu languages such as Ntomba C35a, spoken north of the West-Coastal Bantu homeland in the Mai Ndombe province, on-glide diphthongs such as [wV] undergo what he calls “revocalisation” (*revocalisation* in the original French text), whereby the labiovelar glide becomes a full vowel, e.g., mbwé ‘gray hair’ is often realised as mbùé. Motingea (2010) suggests that the phonetic realisations involving a glide should be considered as a recent development. Apparently, surrounding Pygmy groups speaking a variety of Mongo C61 display the same phenomenon (Hulstaert 1948) as the one observed in Ntomba C35a (and in Ngwi B861 as described in this paper). Note that the chronology proposed by Motingea (2010), i.e., two heterosyllabic vowel sequences becoming a diphthong, is the opposite of what we propose in this venue, i.e., a diphthong crystallising into two consecutive vowel nuclei. Without being able to say more at present, just like final vowel loss (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2021, 458), diphthongisation occurs in languages belonging to distinct West-Coastal Bantu phylogenetic subgroups (see Figure 39), is entirely absent in the remainder of the branch, and is geographically restricted to the homeland area.

Figure 39 - Distribution of diphthongisation and suspected cases of heterosyllabic vowel sequences in West-Coastal Bantu branches

Similarly, the fission of an erstwhile diphthong into a sequence of two vowel nuclei occurs in Ngwi B861 and very likely in Ding B86 and Yans B85 varieties based on evidence found in Rottland (1977) — see Figure 39. The suspected existence of fission in Ding B86 and Yans B85 should of course be corroborated by targeted research.

As such, diphthongisation and fission make good candidates for substrate interference, i.e., the exposure to a shared external source through language contact is a plausible explanation for the geographic distribution of these features.

Another areal feature which could be the result of ancestral interactions with non-Bantu speaking populations is the presence of interior vowels. As briefly discussed in § 7.1, these appear to be quite common (and in complementary distribution with –ATR harmony) in the Macro-Sudan Belt. Within Bantu, they are particularly common in the northwestern area where languages from zones A and B are spoken and rainforest hunter-gatherer groups are still present, but not elsewhere. For instance, besides Ngwi and other West-Coastal Bantu varieties belonging to Guthrie’s referential zone B (see section 1), they are attested in Nen A44 (Mous 2003), Kpa? A53 (Guarisma 1969), and Makaa A83 (Heath 2003). Outside of Bantu zone A, they are also present in Bantoid

languages such as Isu. Whatever the case might be, fine-grained, both low-level phonetic and historically informed phonological research are pivotal for understanding the linguistic landscape of prehistoric central Africa and the phonological systems of poorly described languages found on the southern outskirts of the Congo Basin rainforest.

Chapter 8: Conclusions

8.1 Summary of the results

8.1.1 What are the synchronic features of labial-velar stops in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai?

Labial-velar stops have been reported in three of the four main African language phyla, i.e., Afro-Asiatic, Nilo-Saharan, and Niger-Congo. Their geographical distribution has been described as a local feature of northern sub-Saharan Africa, more specifically limited to the following branches: Chadic (Afro-Asiatic), Membi-Mangbetu-Efe, Moru-Madi, Sara-Bongo-Bagirmi, Nilotic (Nilo-Saharan), Adamawa-Ubangi, Kwa, Gur, Atlantic, Mande, Ijoid, Kru, and Benue-Congo (Niger-Congo) except most of Narrow Bantu outside the Bantu-Ubangi contact zone to the north of the Congo Basin rainforest, i.e., outside Guthrie's (1970) zones A, C, and D (Clements & Rialland 2008, Güldemann 2008, 2018). Labial-velar stops have been interpreted as a distinctive characteristic of the Macro-Sudan Belt (Clements & Rialland 2008, Güldemann 2008, 2018), albeit one with relatively low diagnostic power (Hyman 2011, Cahill 2017). However, to the south of the rainforest, labial-velar stops have also been reported in several Lower Kasai West-Coastal Bantu languages of Guthrie's B80 group, such as Tiene B81 (Ellington 1977: 28), Nsong B85d (Dibata Mimpya 1979: 14), Mpur B85e (Kibwenge India'Ane 1985: 39-40), Nsambaan B85F (Katona Makani 2017: 16), Ding B86 (Mula 1977: 7, Munkyen Okab 1990: 208), Ngwi B861 (Nsumuki 1993: 12), Lwel B862 (Khang Levy 1977: 20, 1979: 4), Nzadi B865 (Crane et al. 2011: 21), Mbuun B87 (Mundeke 2011: 29), as well as in Sakata C34 (alternatively considered a West-Coastal or a Central-Western Bantu variety / dialect cluster, see Grollemund et al. 2015, Koile et al. 2022; Bokwankon Bosonkie 1997: 20, Clements & Rialland 2008: 44). Sakata is a language of wide communication in the northern Lower Kasai spoken well into the Equatorial Lakes region where varieties belonging to Mongo C60 are

dominant. Following two fieldwork missions to Kwilu (2019) and Mai-Ndombe (2021), the presence of labial-velar oral stops has been confirmed in Lwel (Chapter 2) and Sakata (Chapter 3, with reference to the Sakata regiolects known as Kibayi, Kinzinzale, Kingingele, Kingingia, and Kitere; and Chapter 4, with reference to Kimbantin and Kimbamushie). In addition, Sakata has now been documented to present labial-velar nasal stops and fricative realisations of labial-velar oral stops. Data collected during the same fieldwork missions also suggest that phonetic labial-velar stops are often realised in free variation with sequences of velar / labial oral stop + labial-velar approximant + vowel of the KWA-PWA kind by speakers of North Boma B82 and Nunu B822, as well as Sakata and Lwel, matching earlier reports on Ngwi (Nsumuki 1993: 12) and Mbuun (Mundeke 2011: 29). These findings indicate that the Lower Kasai region, to the south of the Congo Basin rainforest, is a major zone of labial-velar stop spread. The Lower Kasai hosts the newly identified West-Coastal Bantu homeland (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019), and most of the languages spoken within its bounds belong to West-Coastal Bantu, making the presence of labial-velar stops in the languages surveyed in this thesis both an areal feature and a recognisable hallmark property of the local West-Coastal Bantu languages. This importantly complicates previous typologies of the phenomenon in Africa, with Clements & Rialland (2008) only mentioning one language (Sakata) with labial-velar stops south of the northern Bantu borderland and Idiatov & Van de Velde (2021: 74-76) only reporting three (unidentified in the prose).

Labial-velar stop phonemes are relatively rare / marginal in the languages that feature them (Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021: 77). This information is confirmed by the findings reported in Chapters 2 and 3. Khang Levy (1977, 1979) reports 11 forms with labial-velar stops in Lwel, of which we could only unequivocally verify the existence of the ones containing voiceless labial-velar oral stops. As for Sakata, data collected in Mai-Ndombe indicate the presence of around 20 roots with labial-velar consonants across five different varieties; these only partly match findings from data collected in 2023 (Chapter 4), suggesting a high degree of variability across speakers and regiolects. The stability of labial-velar stops in the phonology of Lwel and Sakata is influenced by a number of factors and seems to vary from one lexical item to another, ranging from a few core roots that consistently display labial-velar stops (namely, reflexes of Proto-Bantu *gúá “salt” BLR 1521, *kùá “yam” BLR 1968, *kúá “inhabitant” BLR 1969, *kùá “death” BLR 2069, *kú “to die” BLR 2089, *kúá “how much/many” BLR

10353, *kua “flea” BLR 10381) to others that can select a labial-velar realisation but by no means do so consistently (virtually every form exhibiting a KW- sequence, especially in fast connected speech). We lack sufficient data to determine the extent to which this selectivity is rooted in specific aspects of the vocabulary, i.e., whether there are any shared elements characterising the lexicon that contains labial-velar stops in Lwel and Sakata; however, at this stage, Idiatov & Van de Velde’s (2021) hypothesis that labial-velar stops are more common in expressive parts of the lexicon than in the general vocabulary does not appear to be borne out in the Lower Kasai data, possibly indicating a substantive difference from the languages of the Macro-Sudan Belt.

Both in Sakata and in Lwel, labial-velar stops have been reported to exhibit common typological properties of their sound class, such as a steep F2 rise into the following vowel (though, for example, no specific tendency to display multiple formant loci could be found in either of the two languages; see Connell 1994, Cahill 2018). Labial-velar stops in Lwel are predominantly voiceless (Chapter 2), and voiced labial-velar stops tend to behave more like implosives / sonorants (Kaye 1981, Clements 2000, Botma 2011) than full-fledged explosive stops. The fact that /kp/ is clearly present while the existence of /gb/ is dubious is typologically uncommon, given that phonological systems featuring phonemic labial-velar stops tend to display both voicing specifications. If only one of the two stops is attested, it is usually /gb/. This is phonetically motivated by the fact that /kp/ is already partly in the “voiced camp” (Cahill 2008), since labial-velar stops of either voicing specification often deploy an ingressive airstream mechanism in addition to the pulmonic egressive one and tend to display some negative VOT even when they are phonologically voiceless (see also Ohala 1979) – a circumstance observed in Lwel too. The few sound systems that favour /kp/ over /gb/ also tend to have other phonological gaps (Cahill 2008). This is certainly the case in West-Coastal Bantu. Due to the merger of Proto-Bantu *k and *g into /k/ in Proto–West-Coastal Bantu (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2020), all West-Coastal Bantu languages lack /g/, except postnasally. This situation appears to extend to labial-velar stops in Lwel. In terms of future diachronic developments, the Lwel labial-velar stop voicing contrast could evolve into a) a merger of /kp/ and /gb/ into [kp] (a merger which crosslinguistically tends to favour [gb]), or b) an instance of phonological neutralisation, with /gb/ being realised as a plosive or an implosive. Tentatively, despite some variability in the data, it can be proposed that the latter scenario is the more likely

based on the 2019 data presented in this venue, where the labial-velar stop reflexes of Proto-Bantu *gʷ forms in Lwel as reported by Khang Levy (1977, 1979) consistently behave more like sonorants than labial-velar stops (though the available data are insufficient to determine whether this neutralisation is due to actual changes intervened in the language since Khang Levy documented it in the late 1970s or to idiosyncrasies of the consultants, free variation in speech, or differences in transcription). As for Sakata (Chapters 3 and 4), labial-velar stops appear to be a lot better established in the lexicon than in Lwel (especially in the regiolects spoken north of the Mfimi-Lukenye River complex, see Chapter 6), with instances of both voiced and voiceless labial-velar oral stops (partially distinguished by common acoustic features of oral stop voicing oppositions such as the characteristic presence of low-frequency energy concentrations during the closure) as well as labial-velar nasal stops and possible fricative realisations of labial-velar oral stops. Labial-velar nasal stops differ from their oral counterparts for the lack of a visible burst, but they display the steep F2 rise typically observed in labial-velar stops. Data from central Sakata (Chapter 4) confirm previous findings in the literature concerning the relative duration of voiceless vs. voiced labial-velar oral stops (Demolin 1992, Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996), with the former exhibiting higher values than the latter.

Aerodynamic evidence is analysed in Chapter 4 to infer properties of labial-velar stop articulations in central Sakata (Kimbantin and Kimbamushie). Labial-velar oral stops display clear signs of air rarefaction between the points in time when a) the first (velar) closure is completed and b) the two closures are fully released, indicating an expansion of the inter-closure cavity probably achieved through a backwards displacement of either the tongue body or the larynx (or both). The timing of the articulatory events characterising voiceless and voiced labial-velar double articulations in Sakata is essentially the same, but in the case of voiced labial-velar stops, which are always prenasalised in the available data, the onset of the articulation precedes that of its oral section by a margin of 10/15 ms. This suggests that, while voiced labial-velar oral stops are considerably shorter than their voiceless counterparts, the articulatory gestures accompanying their realisations do not differ significantly in duration. While statistically significant effects of both oral airflow and mouth pressure were detected on the opposition between voiceless and voiced labial-velar oral stops, specific disparities in effect size suggest that pressure fluctuations distinguish the two articulations better than differences in airflow. Voiceless labial-velar double

articulations seem to be characterised by a more important expansion of the inter-closure portion of the vocal tract than their voiced counterparts. In this sense, they appear to be articulatorily more salient than their voiced counterparts, a pattern of relative prominence between the two segment types which matches the situation found in Lwel.

8.1.2 What are the synchronic features of retroflex consonants in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai?

Retroflex consonants have been interpreted as a secondary areal characteristic of northern sub-Saharan Africa (Bhat 1973: 14), more specifically restricted to a few varieties belonging to the following branches: Chadic (Afro-Asiatic), Membi-Mangbetu-Efe, Moru-Madi, Sara-Bongo-Bagirmi, Nubian (Nilo-Saharan), Mel, Kwa, and Benue-Congo (Niger-Congo) limited to Eastern Bantu. Within Niger-Congo, Merrill (2022) posits that a sound similar to [ɽ] or [ɽs] likely goes back to Proto-Atlantic. Outside Atlantic, Laver (1994: 222) mentions the presence of “voiced alveolar retroflex flapped stops” in Gbaya (Ubangi) and Shona (Bantu S10). Tse (2013, 2015) focusses on the diachrony of retroflexes in Kizigua (Bantu G311, Somalia); another relatively well-documented case is that of retroflex / flapped consonants in Kinyarwanda (Bantu JD61, Rwanda), for which acoustic, articulatory, and phonological accounts are available in the literature (Sibomana 1974, Kimenyi 1979, Walker & Mpiranya 2006, Walker, Byrd & Mpiranya 2008). In some western and northern Congo hunter-gatherer Bantu languages of Equateur and greater Bandundu (Motingea 2010: 205; earlier accounts of a similar phenomenon in northeast Congo can be found in Vorbichler 1966/67), laterals, rhotics, and occasionally alveolar stops have been reported to allow a flapped / retroflex realisation. Regarding the Lower Kasai, Stappers (1986) reported nasal retroflexes in North Boma (Bantu B82). After two fieldwork missions in 2021 and 2022 to Mai-Ndombe and Kwilu, the presence of nasal retroflexes in North Boma could be confirmed (Chapter 5); a similar sound was also found in Nunu B822, but not in either of the two regional varieties most closely related to North Boma and Nunu, i.e., Tiene B81 and Mpe B821. Additionally, the presence of a retroflex flap in free variation with

laterals and rhotics in the intervocalic position was confirmed for four different Lotwa varieties of the Equatorial Lakes region, immediately to the north of the Lower Kasai and in direct contact with the northern Lower Kasai borderland where North Boma and Nunu are spoken (Chapter 6).

Nasal retroflexes are phonotactically restricted segments in North Boma, only occurring in C_2/C_3 position. Historically, these sounds are the reflexes of Proto-Bantu *n and *nd. Most likely, the latter sequence simplified to *n and subsequently merged with the reflexes of the former. Finally, etymological *n as well as *n deriving from the cluster reduction of *nd developed into /ŋ/ in C_2/C_3 position. In C_1 position, Proto-Bantu *n and *nd were maintained as such. The regular correspondence of /ŋ/ to Proto-Bantu *n and *nd provides some information regarding the relative chronology of this sound change, which must have happened after the reduction of voiced nasal - voiced oral consonant clusters, such as *nd, to simple nasals, such as *n. This simplification path is widespread in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai (Pacchiarotti et al.: forthcoming). As this simplification also occurs in North Boma's closest relatives, i.e., Mpe, Nunu, and Tiene, it probably began in the most recent common ancestor of all four languages. However, /ŋ/ itself is not attested in North Boma's closest relatives except Nunu. Consequently, its adoption in the sound inventory of North Boma (and Nunu) must be a relatively recent phenomenon. However, the implementation of these sound changes was not as regular as one might suppose, to the point that, occasionally, historical *n sounds (whether from Proto-Bantu *n or *nd) were maintained as alveolar nasals in C_2 . Our comparative synchronic study also shows that this sound's frequency varies across speakers and varieties of North Boma, suggesting a position of particular volatility in the language's consonantal inventory and indicating possible individual biases affecting its realisation. Another factor that complicates the position of nasal retroflexes in the phonological inventory of North Boma is the fact that they do not co-occur with any other retroflex sounds. Out of 399 languages reported to have a nasal retroflex in their phonological inventory by PHOIBLE (Moran & McCloy 2019), only 43 (mostly from northern and western Australia) present inventories without any obstruent retroflexes, and only 2 (namely Syan, or Saya, a Chadic language of Nigeria, see Schneeberg 1971; and Mandara, or Wandala, another Chadic language spoken in Cameroon and Nigeria, see Fluckinger 1981) display a nasal as their sole retroflex phoneme. North Boma also features the nasal as its sole retroflex phoneme, which is an almost unique typological situation;

the presence of a phonemic retroflex flap similar to the one reported in Lotwa is documented by Stappers (1986) but remains dubious based on our own personal data (where flaps occur, they are generally in free variation with intervocalic laterals or rhotics). None of the Equatorial Lakes hunter-gatherer Lotwa varieties described here exhibit nasal retroflexes; the presence of a retroflex flap in Lotwa is subject to a lot of regiolectal variation, with different groups of Lotwa Lokonda more prone to it than Lotwa Losenge and Lotwa Lolia.

Acoustically, nasal retroflexes in North Boma have been found to differ significantly from their non-retroflex counterparts, which indicates great acoustic salience in the set. In North Boma, nasal retroflexes exhibit greater concentrations of energy in the lower regions of the spectrum and fewer / less identifiable higher-frequency intensity peaks (i.e., a more blurred formant structure throughout the sound). Nasal retroflexes are shorter than their non-retroflex counterparts and present the lowest F2, F3, and F4 average values of the whole North Boma nasal set. Apart from F1, which showed greater bandwidth values for retroflexes than for non-retroflexes (possibly indicating a more diffuse murmur), no major effect of retroflexion on bandwidth was found. Nasal retroflexes appear to have the sharpest F1 slopes both in onset and offset position, but no specific effect of retroflexion could be detected on F2 onset and offset slopes. As for spectral moment analysis, nasal retroflexes show higher skewness and kurtosis values than their non-retroflex counterparts, indicating higher / more peaked concentrations of energy in the spectral area below their centroid frequency; lower centre of gravity values tally with these findings. Multiple Factor Analyses, an extension of Principal Component Analysis, were performed on the dataset (quantitative variables grouped as: “duration”, “formant values”, “bandwidth values”, “slope values”, “spectral moments”; qualitative variables grouped as: “segment”, “retroflexion”). A first Multiple Factor Analysis, run on the set’s median values, showed that the retroflex / non-retroflex opposition is better suited to explain the plane’s inertia than “segment”. Retroflexion was shown to be significantly correlated (inversely) to segment duration, F2 bandwidth, centre of gravity, and F2 offset slope values, and (positively) to skewness, kurtosis, F1 bandwidth, and F1. This confirms that North Boma nasal retroflexes are significantly shorter than their non-retroflex counterparts and exhibit more energy concentrated in the lower regions of the spectrum, while no specific effect of retroflexion was found on F3. This is at variance with the available typological literature (see Hussain et al. 2017). In line with the available acoustic

literature (Stevens & Blumstein 1975), though, an F3-4 pinch was observed, but no effect of F2-3 convergence, which, again, sets the North Boma case apart from other well-documented cases (see Hamann 2002, 2003). Lower centre of gravity and standard deviation and higher skewness and kurtosis suggest that North Boma retroflexes are articulated with the tongue tip rising perpendicularly to the hard palate, which in turn is compatible with the F3 findings (a less retracted constriction location also requires less curling of the tongue tip). Multiple Factor Analyses were also performed on nasals with values sampled at the 10%- and 90%-duration temporal marks, to test whether retroflexion in North Boma is a dynamic articulation targeting different places at the sound's onset and offset (Ladefoged & Maddieson 1996). This was not found to be the case, suggesting that nasal retroflexes in North Boma do not behave as quickly flicking flaps as previously hypothesised based on specific characteristics of the speech of one of the consultants. Multiple Factor Analyses were also run on modified versions of the dataset to account for duration biases and other related issues, including the sensitivity of spectral moment values to background noise and vocalic context. The results of these Multiple Factor Analyses, conducted on specially balanced subsets of the entire dataset, do not significantly differ from those obtained from the analyses run on all median values, suggesting that the distinction between nasal retroflexes and non-retroflexes in North Boma is stable and not a side effect of intrinsic durational differences or a by-product of the measures. Vowel adjacency effects were also analysed. Multiple Factor Analyses were performed on three cardinal vowels (/a/, /i/, and /u/). No significant effect of retroflexion was found on nasal-adjacent vowels. This also sets the North Boma case apart from other cases documented in the literature, where adjacency to a retroflex has been linked to lowered F3 values on vowels. No acoustic data on retroflexion in Nunu or Lotwa were analysed in this thesis. No articulatory data were collected on any of the varieties surveyed in this venue.

8.1.3 What are the synchronic features of interior vowels in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai?

Interior vowels have recently been identified as a secondary areal feature of the Macro-Sudan Belt predominantly attested in languages spoken in two ATR-deficient zones centred respectively around the Nigeria-Cameroon borderland (tapering eastward into Chad and the Central African Republic) and Guinea; these languages mainly belong to Adamawa-Ubangi, Kainji, Delta-Cross, Jukunoid, Bantoid (disputably Niger-Congo), Chadic (Afro-Asiatic), and Sara-Bongo-Bagirmi (Nilo-Saharan), with the density of interior vowel systems thinning to the east and south in Benue-Congo and Ijoid (Niger-Congo). Interestingly, though, interior vowels have also been reported in several Lower Kasai Bantu languages such as Lwel (Khang Levy 1979), Ding (Mula 1977, Ebalantshim 1980), Nsambaan (Mfum-Ekong 1979), Nsong (Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2019), and Yans B85 (Swartenbroeckx 1948, Rottland 1977). In this venue, interior vowels have been documented in Ngwi (Chapter 7). In particular, Ngwi has been shown to display two phonemic interior vowels, i.e., /ə/ and /ɾ/. In terms of diachronic phonology, after a 7 > 5 restructuring of the inherited Proto-Bantu vowel system, Ngwi developed five phonemic vowels that formed two natural classes. The [+ high] class contained /i/ and /u/ and the [– high] class contained /ɛ/, /ɔ/, and /a/. The two interior vowels were originally allophones of /i/ in V₁ position in a C₁V₁C₂V₂ template, triggered by distinct conditionings: [ə] was the allophonic realisation of Proto-Ngwi *i when V₂ was [– high], while [ɾ] was the allophonic realisation of Proto-Ngwi *i when V₂ was [+ high, + back]. Once final vowel loss took place, the conditioning V₂ environment was lost and the two interior allophonic vowels phonologised.

The emergence of /ə/ and /ɾ/ specifically, rather than other possible interior vowels, in Ngwi was explored from a low-level phonetic perspective. First, formant values were calculated for all Ngwi vowels. Formant values for /ə/ are spread over a vast, central portion of the vowel space. In terms of height, the /ə/ area is clearly above the mid-low and below the high portion of the vowel space. This is in line with what one might expect from the under-specification theory of schwa, which predicts high variability in the phonetic implementation of this sound (Flemming 2009). On the other hand, available values for /ɾ/ are much more widely dispersed than anticipated, with an F2 range stretching from /u/ to /i/. These values seem to centre around a set of

coordinates closer to that of /ʌ/ than to that of a prototypical mid-high unrounded vowel (Koffi 2018). On the other hand, the assimilation to [+ back] observed in /i/ > [ɣ] is problematic because it entails an apparently odd change in height, whereby a high vowel assimilated to another high vowel (in this case, /u/) by becoming mid-high. More natural outputs might have included either /u/ or, since /i/ is unrounded, /ʊ/. Due to the acoustic data's lack of clarity and mismatch with phonological expectations, the nature of this second vowel was further examined from a Dispersion Theory perspective (Liljencrants & Lindblom 1972, Lindblom 1986). According to Dispersion Theory, vowels tend to disperse across the vowel space to enhance perceptibility. In this sense, a system with three back vowels (a high one, a mid-high one, and a mid-low one) is better balanced than one with two back high vowels and a mid-low one. In fact, /ɣ/ is expected to be part of the optimal 7-vowel system proposed by Lindblom (1990), which supports our transcription of this vowel against other possible candidates such as /ʌ/. Since high vowels are cross-linguistically less likely to trigger round harmony (Finley 2012), /ɣ/ (as opposed to, say, /o/) should not be taken as a surprising outcome.

8.1.4 How did labial-velar stops, retroflex consonants, and interior vowels emerge in Lower Kasai Bantu languages and do these sound classes have the same diachronic origins?

The emergence of labial-velar stops in the languages of the Lower Kasai is likely due (at least in part) to population movements from the north, and especially from the Bantu-Ubangi borderland. These migrations, occurring over several centuries, brought together different linguistic and cultural groups and influenced the phonological landscape of the area. This notion is substantiated by our understanding of the migratory history of the Sakata people (Chapter 3; Van der Kerken 1944, Van Bulck 1948, Motingea 2009, Omasombo Tshonda et al. 2019). Significant demic diffusion of the Sakata people has been claimed to have happened over a period that started as early as the 11th or 12th century (Omasombo Tshonda et al. 2019: 114) and highlights a significant north-to-south population movement along the Congo River eventually resulting in spread into the Lower Kasai. As a matter of fact, Idiatov & Van de Velde

(2021: 100-101) argue that labial-velar stops emerged in the West-Coastal Bantu branch after they were imported by speakers of ancestral North-Western Bantu A80 and A90 languages that already had these sounds in their phonological inventories. These groups would have moved southwards into the rainforest and then shifted to West-Coastal Bantu. However, this explanation is complicated by the potential role of substrate interference. The process of Proto-Bantu *g fortition to /k/ in West-Coastal Bantu, which has been attributed to pre-Bantu substrate reflecting the articulatory habits of shifting ancestral speakers (Möhlig 1981: 270), aligns with the loss of voiced labial-velar stops in Lwel (Chapter 2). This suggests a complex interplay between contact with North-Western Bantu and Ubangi speech communities and substrate interference from extinct hunter-gatherer forest languages. The presence of labial-velar stops as a characteristic of certain Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai thus emerges as an areal feature possibly influenced by long-standing interactions with hunter-gatherer communities in the region. This is further confirmed by the fact that labial-velar stops are absent in low-node, non-Lower Kasai West-Coastal Bantu language groups, such as the Kikongo Language Cluster. Ultimately, the presence of labial-velar stops in Sakata and Lwel might be explained in two different but complementary ways. The Lwel people, on whose migratory history a lot less has been written than on that of the Sakata, might have developed labial-velar stops through contact with pre-Bantu hunter-gatherer speakers (Chapter 2), or they might have adapted them from the speech of northern settlers such as the Sakata. The Sakata, on the other hand, might have already displayed labial-velar stops in the phonological inventories of their different regiolects before they migrated from the north, and, upon settling in the Lower Kasai and shifting to West-Coastal Bantu, they may have adapted their labial-velar stop series to those of the groups they found in the region (Chapter 3). This would explain the uncommon reflexes attested in Kingingele, where affricates as substitutes of voiced labial-velar stops have been shown to bespeak a trajectory of sound change that is not grounded in well-documented articulatory patterns. This phenomenon has been proposed to result from explicit language manipulation (Thomason 2007), reinforcing the idea that labial-velar stops emerged in Lwel and Sakata following different historical scenarios. However, an alternative, unified interpretation could also be advanced: if both Lwel (and, possibly, peoples speaking other Bantu B80 lects) and Sakata settlers immigrated into the Lower Kasai from the Bantu-Ubangi borderland, they could have imported labial-velar stops together and

then adapted their phonological inventories (to varying degrees) to those of the pre-Bantu varieties they found in the region, assimilating their articulatory habits. Lwel might have done so to a higher extent than Sakata, which would explain why voiced labial-velar stops were (/are being) lost in the former but not in the latter.

As for retroflex consonants, their presence in North Boma and Nunu is plausibly linked to substrate interference from the languages of pre-Bantu hunter-gatherers. This notion is underpinned by evidence showing that nasal retroflexes in North Boma exhibit traces of an origin in loan phonology (Chapter 5); even though no specific data analysis was conducted on Nunu, it can be supposed that the situations of the two language communities are to an extent comparable. While the overall rarity of retroflex sounds in Bantu is a first indication of loan phonology, their positional / phonotactic restrictions are further proof of contact-induced imposition from a non-Bantu source language. Another indicative factor lies in the presumed timing of retroflexion emergence in North Boma. As mentioned above, the regular correspondence of North Boma /ŋ/ to both Proto-Bantu *n and *nd, following a pattern of consonant cluster simplification widespread in the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai, offers insights into the relative chronology of this sound shift. Specifically, it suggests that the adoption of /ŋ/ into the North Boma sound system, as well as into that of closely related languages such as Nunu, is a relatively recent phenomenon, which, in turn, strengthens the argument for substrate interference. Furthermore, the acoustic salience of these nasal retroflexes aligns with linguistic expectations regarding the ease of phonetic pattern spread (Fleischacker 2000, Kenstowicz 2001, 2003, Steriade 2001a,b, Kang 2002, Blevins 2017: 12): essentially, phonetic patterns that are more perceptually salient are likelier to be adopted and maintained across languages. Additionally, the hypothesis that retroflexion in North Boma could be traced back to now-extinct languages spoken by pre-Bantu populations matches earlier attestations of retroflexion in hunter-gatherer languages spoken across the Congo Basin (Vorbichler 1966/67, Motingea 2010). Retroflex flaps have now been reported in languages spoken in the immediate vicinity of the Lower Kasai (i.e., on the southern fringes of the Equatorial Lakes region) too (Chapter 6). Given the relative markedness of retroflex consonants, independent emergence of retroflex sounds in neighbouring languages is generally eschewed in favour of areal explanations (Hamann 2003, Zhivlov 2016). Moreover, retroflexes are often the outcome of an articulatory shift in the presence of a rhotic (Bhat 1973, Hamann 2003, Bertinetto 2004), and highly

unusual sound systems containing two phonemic non-flap (and non-tap) rhotics have been reported in Sakata, North Boma, Nunu, and Lotwa (Chapter 6). This is probably another areal characteristic of the Lower Kasai, and one which could be tied to retroflexion (given the intrinsic link between rhoticity and retroflexion) and backstop our understanding of the two phenomena, both occurring in Equatorial Lakes hunter-gatherer Lotwa lects, as instances of substrate interference.

Finally, as concerns the emergence of interior vowels in Ngwi, the more plausible explanation appears to be substrate interference, rather than recent import from northern languages (Chapter 7). Within Bantu, interior vowels are particularly common in the North-Western area, where languages belonging to zones A and B are spoken and rainforest hunter-gatherer groups are still present, but they are extremely uncommon everywhere else. For instance, besides Ngwi and other West-Coastal Bantu zone B varieties, interior vowels are attested in Nen A44 (Mous 2003), Kpa A53 (Guarisma 1969), and Makaa A83 (Heath 2003). Notably, other phenomena of interest affecting vowels in Ngwi, such as the presence of heterosyllabic vowel sequences originating from vowel breaking which are overall very rare in Bantu languages but extremely common in the West-Coastal Bantu homeland (Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2012), seem to match findings reported for some hunter-gatherer languages of the Equatorial Lakes region. As a matter of fact, Motingea (2010: 156) observes that in Bantu languages such as Ntomba C35a, spoken in the Mai-Ndombe sector of the Equatorial Lakes region, on-glide diphthongs of the WV- kind tend to break into heterosyllabic U.V- sequences. Motingea (2010) suggests that phonetic realisations involving a glide should be considered as a recent development and mentions that neighbouring hunter-gatherer groups speaking a variety of Mongo display the same phenomenon (Hulstaert 1948).

8.2 General discussion

This thesis analyses three significant phonetic and phonological phenomena in a few select Bantu varieties of the Lower Kasai region of the Democratic Republic of Congo. This region was chosen for targeted phonetic / phonological documentation and description for several reasons: a) the Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai have been

documented to exhibit numerous typologically unusual phenomena (including, but not limited to, the three mentioned above; see Daeleman 1977, Rottland 1977, Mfum-Ekong 1979, Ebalantshim Masuwan 1980, Bostoen & Mundeke 2011a,b, Bostoen & Koni Muluwa 2014, Koni Muluwa & Bostoen 2019, Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2021, 2022) which set them apart from neighbouring Bantu speech communities; b) the Lower Kasai, straddling the two provinces of Kwilu and Mai-Ndombe, hosts the putative ancestral homeland of West-Coastal Bantu, i.e., the area of maximum internal linguistic diversity in the branch, to which the majority of the Bantu lects spoken in the Lower Kasai belong (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019); c) concurrent (complementary or opposing) views attribute this diversity to either recent imports from northern sub-Saharan African languages (Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021) or substrate interference from extinct pre-Bantu languages spoken by hunter-gatherer groups (Motingea 2010), of which some are still scattered in rainforest pockets of the Equatorial Lakes area immediately to the north of the Lower Kasai and in direct contact with a few of its language communities.

The three phenomena analysed in the text were selected because they had the potential to shed light on all three points of interest of the Lower Kasai: a) they have been reported in numerous Lower Kasai languages, possibly representing an areal feature of this region; b) all the languages they have been reported in belong to West-Coastal Bantu (with the possible exception of Sakata, see Grollemund et al. 2015, Koile et al. 2022; further investigation is pending) or to Central-Western Bantu hunter-gatherer languages which are in contact with West-Coastal Bantu and are spoken by communities which, at some point in time, are presumed to have spoken pre-Bantu varieties later submerged by the Bantu Expansion (Bahuchet 2012); c) as hinted at above, they have been variously considered hallmark features of a huge contact macro-area known as the “Macro-Sudan Belt” (Clements & Rialland 2008, Rolle et al. 2017, 2020, Güldemann 2008, 2018, Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021) stretching over most of northern sub-Saharan Africa and from where speech communities possibly migrated into the Lower Kasai, or as defining characteristics of pre-Bantu hunter-gatherer languages, two possibilities which are indicative of different contact scenarios.

Several Bantu languages of the Lower Kasai have been selected to investigate these phenomena. The languages (or language clusters) reported on in this venue, i.e., Lwel, Sakata (Kibayi, Kinzinzale, Kingingia, Kingingele, Kitere, Kimbamushie, Kimbantin), North Boma, Nunu, Ngwi, Lotwa Lokonda (two different varieties), Lotwa

Losenge, and Lotwa Lolia, have been chosen for their particular interest in relation to these three phenomena. Specifically, labial-velar stops (and their affricate and fricative realisations) have been described in Lwel and Sakata, retroflexion has been described in North Boma and Lotwa, and the emergence of interior vowels has been studied in Ngwi.

The approach adopted in the studies presented in this venue results from the combination of low-level phonetic analysis with the tools of diachronic-phonological reconstruction. This approach was informed by the notion that fine-grained phonetic evidence can complement the study of phonological patterns and reveal significant aspects of the integration strategies adopted by each speech community in the transfer of sounds in contexts of intense language contact. This approach has yielded detailed insights into both the synchronic and diachronic phonology as well as the acoustics and articulation of the target sounds. An example of this combined approach can be drawn from the case of retroflexion (Chapter 5): the diachronic-phonological analysis of the origin of nasal retroflexes in North Boma shows clear signs of loan phonology in terms of specific phonotactic restrictions, and their acoustic study confirms their relative salience in the language's nasal set, buttressing the idea that their integration in its phonological inventory is the result of contact. Another case of interest is that of labial-velar stops. In the case of Kingingele (Chapter 3), the absence of patent articulatory reasons behind the allophony of labial-velar stops and affricates has been interpreted as a consequence of explicit language manipulation on the part of the Kingingele speech community at some point in time during the migrations of the Sakata people into the Lower Kasai; specific acoustic differences in the implementation of voiced labial-velar stops in Lwel and Sakata have been considered traces of different integration strategies into the two languages' phonology (Chapter 2). In Ngwi, formant analysis has allowed for a Dispersion Theory approach to the study of the language's present-day acoustic vowel space, reinforcing the notion that one of its uncommon vowel phonemes is in fact an interior vowel against other peripheral candidates (Chapter 7). Adopting this integrated approach was crucial for several reasons: a) this is the first time that low-level phonetic data is used to complement the study of the phonology of the languages of the Lower Kasai; b) this method manages to be diagnostic of numerous issues at once, including phonetic and phonological typology and historical and contact linguistics; c) it allows for fine-grained phonetic evidence to contribute to a multi-disciplinary take on the study of Bantu

expansions in the region, which already includes contributions from historical linguistics, archaeology, and genetics.

The results of these four years of research, summarised above (§8.1), reveal a situation (both in reference to the Lower Kasai's language landscape and to the phonetic and phonological typology of the individual sounds analysed) which is considerably more nuanced than previously assumed. The following considerations are meant as a general reflection on these preliminary results; they are still very speculative at this stage, given the nature of the data collected and presented in this venue and the fact that parallel findings from the fields of archaeology and genetics are still being annotated and analysed. However, they retain their usefulness as bases for historico-linguistic hypotheses to inform future explorations in the region.

The presence of labial-velar stops, retroflexion, and interior vowels in the Lower Kasai likely results from diverse sociohistorical dynamics. Labial-velar stops were probably imported from northern languages presumably spoken by migrating language groups such as the Sakata before they switched to West-Coastal Bantu. However, upon their arrival in the Lower Kasai, these language groups probably adopted different strategies in adjusting their phonological inventories to those of the local languages. The disappearance (a marked trend, at this stage) of voiced /gb/ in Lwel, which bucks widely attested typological preferences for /kp/ in cases of loss of voicing-based oppositions in labial-velar consonant sets in the world's languages (Cahill 2008), might indicate that present-day Lwel speakers acquired specific local phonological features from languages they found in the Lower Kasai, namely, the loss of voicing-based oppositions on velars, and extended them to labial-velar stops. On the other hand, the Sakata may have been more resilient to this interference, maintaining the (presumably, given the fact that it is typologically less marked than the situation found in Lwel) original voicing opposition of /kp/ vs. /gb/. Within Sakata, specific groups might have opted to distance themselves more or less markedly from others, which in turn might have led to the selection of articulatorily ungrounded affricate allophones in Kingingele (Thomason 2006a,b, 2007, 2008; see also Trudgill 1986, Thurston 1987, 1989, 1994). As for retroflexion, it seems North Boma (and Nunu) speakers acquired it through contact, most likely with hunter-gatherer varieties that displayed retroflex sounds in their phonological inventories, and the same appears to hold for interiority in Ngwi.

The emergence of retroflexion and interiority in the languages of the Lower Kasai is probably an instance of substrate interference from a source language to a recipient language actuated by speakers of the former, i.e., a case of “imposition” under “source language agentivity” in Van Coetsem’s (1988) terms (see also Winford 2003: 17). This matches expectations for a situation of language shift (Thomason & Kaufman 1988: 50), in which speakers of communities present in the territory where North Boma (and Nunu) is (are) spoken today switched to the languages of the new Bantu settlers but imported specific elements of their phonology into their new language systems. In Ross’s (2003: 191) interpretation, this circumstance is most plausible in cases of communities with loose internal relationship links switching to a more prestigious lect, possibly maintaining aspects of their original tongues as an “accent” (an indication of this “exotic” quality of the sound class at hand in North Boma would be its acoustic salience in the language’s nasal set). Retroflexion, now stabilised in North Boma’s (and Nunu’s) recipient phonology, likely represents such a case. The quality of this sound class as a group identifier connected to hunter-gatherer speech is all the more evident in the case of Lotwa, where ancestral speakers, whose presence in the Equatorial Lakes region predates the advent of Bantu, switched to Bantu, following one (or more) Bantu Expansion events that imposed a more advantageous variety but maintained retroflexion as a characteristic of their accent. This feature is also documented in Efe, spoken by the Bambuti hunter-gatherers of the Ituri sector of the Congo Basin rainforest (Vorbichler 1966/67), as well as in other Twa varieties of Equateur (Motingea 2009), reinforcing the notion that retroflexion is a hunter-gatherer feature. Given the relative phonetic markedness of retroflex segments (Hamann 2003), it is improbable that neighbouring languages developed retroflexion independently of each other, making the substrate scenario particularly convincing. Interestingly, given the well-documented link between retroflexion and phonetic variation in the presence of a rhotic (Bhat 1973, Hamann 2003: 88, Bertinetto 2004), one would expect sound systems in the Lower Kasai to display greater-than-average variation in rhotic realisations. This expectation is confirmed by some new data presented in this thesis, which indicate that (typologically unusual) systems of more than one non-flap phonemic rhotic are frequent in the region (and include, among others, those of North Boma, Nunu, and Sakata). Some uvular fricative realisations which now behave as rhotics in the languages of the Lower Kasai have also been attributed to substrate interference from hunter-gatherer lects (Pacchiarotti & Bostoen 2022).

A similar line of reasoning can be extended to the emergence of interiority. Interior vowels are relatively common in languages belonging to Guthrie's zones A and B spoken in areas of Cameroon where rainforest hunter-gatherer groups are still present (Guarisma 1969, Mous 2003, Heath 2003), which supports the notion that they may have emerged across the Bantu domain due to imposition from pre-Bantu lects. Moreover, other phenomena of interest affecting vowels in Ngwi, such as the tendency to develop heterosyllabic vowel sequences, match data from some hunter-gatherer languages of the Equatorial Lakes region (Hulstaert 1948, Motingea 2010: 156).

The labial-velar stop case, however, poses more interpretational problems. Labial-velar stops were originally considered to be a typically hunter-gatherer feature (Schebesta 1949) but have now been documented across a considerable number of Central African non-hunter-gatherer languages (Demolin & Teston 1997, Clements & Rialland 2008, Güldemann 2008, Bostoen & Donzo 2013). Their emergence in the languages of the Lower Kasai would appear to be another instance of "imposition" or "source language agentivity" (Van Coetsem 1988), but one with a different relative chronology than that proposed above for retroflexion and interiority. Specifically, the source language community/ies from which labial-velar stops are supposed to have been transferred to West-Coastal Bantu is/are hypothesised to have migrated from the north and settled into the Lower Kasai once West-Coastal Bantu was already there, which would explain why language shift occurred in favour of West-Coastal Bantu. In other words, local languages of the Lower Kasai assimilated labial-velar stops from migrant populations coming from the north (possibly the Bantu-Ubangi borderland in the Macro-Sudan Belt, where labial-velar stops are present). Once labial-velar stops were acquired, they underwent (Lwel) or resisted (Sakata) phonological change prompted by the convergence of Proto-Bantu *k and *g to /k/ documented in West-Coastal Bantu (Pacchiarotti et al. 2019). In turn, this change must have taken place in the branch's most recent common ancestor in the West-Coastal Bantu homeland sector of the Lower Kasai, i.e., when Bantu had already spread to the Lower Kasai. This means that the introduction of labial-velar stops in the Lower Kasai is the result of a subsequent spread event. The hypothesis that labial-velar stops in Lwel derive from substrate interference from pre-Bantu hunter-gatherer lects was also advanced (Chapter 2) but appears less likely in the light of the considerations summarised in this paragraph and the evidence from Sakata.

It can thus be hypothesised that retroflexion and interior vowels were already present in the languages of the Lower Kasai region and/or its immediate vicinity before the arrival of Bantu speakers. However, labial-velar stops probably were not. Retroflexion and interiority may result from contact with pre-Bantu varieties of the forest; on the other hand, labial-velar stop spread may be attributed to the arrival of North-Western Bantu (or non-Bantu) languages possibly coming from the Macro-Sudan Belt, and the loss of the /kp/-/gb/ voicing opposition in Lwel may be due to contact between these other languages and West-Coastal Bantu. If that were the case, the presence of labial-velar stops in the Lower Kasai would be more recent than that of retroflexion and interiority. That being said, the emergence of retroflexion in North Boma has also been considered a relatively recent phenomenon, which must have occurred after reflexes of Proto-Bantu *n and *nd merged to /n/ in C₂ and C₃ position in North Boma. If, indeed, that is the case, then one could tentatively hypothesise that North Boma developed this merger before settling around present-day Mushie (moving away from the West-Coastal Bantu homeland?), where North Boma speech communities would have absorbed the pre-existing hunter-gatherer communities that, shifting to North Boma, imposed retroflexion. Some time after this event (though the relative chronology of these two occurrences is harder to unpack), another spread from the north would have imported labial-velar stops into the region. A possible timeline is presented below (Table 24).

Table 24 - Proposed chronology of phonological transfer events in the Lower Kasai

<u>< Space ></u>			
	North (Macro-Sudan Belt?)	Lower Kasai (other than the homeland region)	West-Coastal Bantu homeland
Time 1	Languages display labial-velar stops	Languages display retroflexion and interiority (hunter-gatherer substrate)	Languages undergo Proto-Bantu *k/*g merger (possibly a substrate feature)
Time 2			North Boma (and possibly other lects) develops *n/*nd merger
Time 3		North Boma spreads to the retroflexion area and integrates phonemic nasal retroflexes (hunter-gatherer substrate, source language agentivity)	North Boma and other West-Coastal Bantu groups disperse outside the homeland
Time 4	“Northern” speech communities with labial-velar stops in their inventory spread to the region where the *k/*g merger is active	These northern speech communities switch to West-Coastal Bantu and transfer labial-velar stops to their new languages (source language agentivity). Labial-velar stop systems either resist the merger or adjust their phonology to that of the local languages	

Note that no specific chronology is proposed for the imposition of interiority. If, however, the phenomenon is to be attributed to substrate interference, it most likely occurred sometime around Time 3.

Regardless of relative chronology, labial-velar stops appear well-established as a phonetic possibility in the region before they are as full-fledged phonemes in individual Lower Kasai languages. As a matter of fact, labial-velar stops have been documented as (synchronic) free variants of velar stop + labial-velar glide sequences in numerous Lower Kasai languages (Nsumuki 1993: 12, Mundeke 2011: 29); these reports match findings from the data collected for this thesis. In fast connected speech, KW- is often realised as KP- in the languages of the Lower Kasai, irrespective of how stable labial-velar stop phonemes are in their individual phonological inventories. In this sense, and from a synchronic perspective, the realisation of labial-velar stops is a readily available phonetic possibility shared across the Lower Kasai. In describing the diffusion of clicks outside Southern Africa, Lionnet (2021) argues that these speech sounds “radiate” from a centre of highest (phonological) functional load (i.e., Southern Africa, where they are phonemic) to gradient peripheries of lower functional load, where they are often used as verbal gestures (Grenoble 2014) or otherwise “liminal” (Dingemanse 2020) language signs. He also contends that the definition of a full typology of clicks belonging to these latter categories is complicated by the fact that they are seldom reported in language descriptions due to their perceived “extra-linguistic” nature. The case of labial-velar stops in the Lower Kasai is, of course, importantly different to that of clicks: labial-velar stops are never used in isolation as liminal language sounds, they are not a “bodily” phenomenon liable to occur independently of language production, and they are subject to considerable gradience in phonological load while still being phonemic (in that they can be more or less marginal in the languages where they are phonemic and occur in more or less restricted portions of the lexicon; Idiatov & Van de Velde 2021). However, in other respects, and with reference to the Lower Kasai alone, they also exhibit a few remarkable similarities. First of all, their realisation in the local languages varies in frequency, with a centre of maximum frequency around the Sakata language cluster, thinning in density the further away one moves from the Sakata domain, eventually disappearing (outside loanwords; cf. Lingala *gbagba* “bridge”) in most local Central-Western Bantu varieties; this matches the situation of clicks, especially non-phonemic clicks, as described by Lionnet (2021) for the Macro-Sudan Belt, which he considers to be an area of great click verbal gesture diffusion. Second,

not only are labial-velar segments more or less frequent: they are also more or less acoustically salient in the languages of the region, taking once again Sakata as the point of greatest salience; again, this matches the click situation. Click verbal gestures are described by Lionnet (2021) as less and less salient (lower conventionalisation, fewer available types) the further away one moves from the Macro-Sudan Belt, in a gradient fashion. Third, the presence of labial-velar stops as phonetic possibilities in all Lower Kasai Bantu languages mimics the behaviour of a verbal gesture defined as “a set of sounds or segments which stand outside a language’s phonemic inventory but are still part of the communicative system of the language” (Grenoble 2014), in that they are realisations which are common across languages in the region but uncommon in the greater area of reference, be it Central Africa (geographically defined) or Bantu (as a language family). This matches expectations for situations of intense small-scale multilingualism (Lüpke 2016), insofar as the average Lower Kasai speaker is polylectal and invariably operates (or resists, as is the case in Kingingele) “labial-velarisation” in all the varieties they speak.

The situation of retroflexion is somewhat different, though in part comparable to that of labial-velar stops. Where they are not fully phonemic, retroflexes emerge in free variation; this is the case in Lotwa. Lotwa speakers tend to produce retroflex flaps in lieu of intervocalic laterals or rhotics in all the languages they speak. In this sense, retroflexion can be considered a shared phonetic possibility in the Lotwa domain. However, this feature is limited to hunter-gatherer speech communities, which marks their specific accent more than it does (areally) the sector of the Equatorial Lakes region where they are present. The fact that retroflexion was transferred to North Boma and Nunu indicates that, at some point in time, there may have been more variation in the synchronic implementation of intervocalic laterals and rhotics and/or that retroflex realisations may have been a common phonetic possibility in the region. This might have been accompanied by greater-than-average variability in rhotic realisations (see above). However, these aspects would now be “fossilised” in individual Lower Kasai lects and no longer active in synchrony (with the exception of flapping in Twa speech communities).

The situation described for the Lower Kasai also complicates long-standing typological notions regarding two of the three sound classes described in this venue. It is a known fact that typologically unusual sounds / sound realisations are often found in little-documented languages. In reference to language documentation in general,

Miyaoka (2001) states: “Many endangered minor languages may have the potential of providing data unobtainable anywhere else that are valuable for issues concerning typology and universality, as well as for historical studies of language and culture”. Now, while it is true that the vitality of most of the languages dealt with in this venue is often described as “stable” (§1.1.2.3), the reality in the field is a lot more dire. As a matter of fact, small-scale multilingualism in the Lower Kasai is slowly losing ground to a few major *linguae francae* such as Lingala or Kongo ya Leta. Varieties of higher social prestige, such as Kinzinzale or Kitere within Sakata, may resist this tendency for a longer time, but others are bound to change considerably in the near future under the influence of more advantageous vehicular lects. This is in line with general, worldwide trends regarding language diversity loss, which necessarily entails the loss of phonetic and phonological diversity: as a matter of fact, not only are we as a species hurtling towards the most devastating “pandemic of linguicide” (Koffi 2021) to record, but the information we have about a considerable portion of humankind’s already documented linguistic heritage is uneven at best.

Four years of research into the languages of the Lower Kasai have unearthed numerous unexpected phonetic and phonological phenomena, which challenge traditional typologies. Retroflex sounds have been shown to occur in North Boma with acoustic correlates that only partly match typological expectations; more specifically, it has been found that F3 lowering on retroflex-adjacent vowels is not a reliable cue to the identification of nasal retroflexes in this language. Labial-velar stops have been shown to merge to voiceless rather than voiced under the influence of pre-existing neutralisations, a circumstance which complicates previously held assumptions about their cross-linguistic behaviour. In terms of articulation, labial-velar gestures have been shown to maintain their duration across phoneme boundaries, a situation which poses very interesting questions to models of speech production such as Articulatory Phonology (Browman & Goldstein 1992, Goldstein et al. 2006). These findings represent significant shifts in our understanding of the sound classes to which they pertain, and they would not have been possible had specifically targeted phonetic and phonological data collection not been conducted in the Lower Kasai. In fact, chances are it will not be possible to replicate them in the future, as the linguistic landscape of the region shifts and original phonetic and phonological *rarissima* (and, with them, the last available traces of prehistoric contact events) are lost.

8.3 Limits of the present research

The data presented in this venue have been collected over different fieldwork missions conducted by different investigators. Most of the data collected in the field is lexical (word lists) and acoustic (recordings). These have proved essential for the elaboration of preliminary phonetic studies, but have a few major limitations, chiefly the fact that field settings are often suboptimal for the purposes of fine-grained phonetic analysis. An example can be drawn from the North Boma case: the study of antiformants, which are among the most reliable acoustic cues to nasal articulations (Johnson 2012) and require conditions of ideal quiet with no noise discernible in the background, is virtually impossible with audio recorded in the field. Preliminary conclusions inferred from the exploration of the data collected in the field have been buttressed with targeted aerodynamic data, but a) this extension was limited to the labial-velar stop case, b) other techniques can be explored for the study of the articulation of labial-velar stops and other sounds of interest reported here, and c) articulatory and aerodynamic data collection has not been taken to the field yet.

The number and sociolinguistic comparability of the speakers interviewed for the studies presented here vary considerably from variety to variety. In the case of North Boma, acoustic and lexical data were collected with four speakers coming from different areas of the North Boma domain. In the case of Sakata, one speaker was interviewed for each regiolect, with the exception of Kimbamushie (two speakers). Additionally, speaker selection was not balanced for sex, which limits the scope of these preliminary phonetic findings.

The phenomena analysed in this thesis were predominantly studied in the context of words in isolation / carrier sentences, with limited attention paid to their realisation in connected speech. This is an important limitation in the study of free variation, a phenomenon heavily influenced by speech rate and context.

Additionally, as concerns the historical component of this research, genetic and archaeological data still need to be analysed to confirm (or debunk) linguistic inferences about prehistoric contact in the Lower Kasai. At this stage, the scope of any inferences regarding possible prehistoric contact scenarios is necessarily biased by the lack of data from fields other than linguistics.

8.4 Future research

With reference to each research question, I believe that future research should focus on a few specific issues, which I will break down as follows:

- Labial-velar articulations: specifically targeted acoustic data should be collected and analysed from all Lower Kasai languages which have been reported to present labial-velar stops in their phonological inventories or as free variants of KW- sounds. These include: Kikimi B70r, Teke Kenkuu B80x, Tiene B81, North Boma B82, Mpe B821, Nunu B822, Nsong B85d, Mpur B85e, Nsambaan B85F, Ding B86, Ngwi B861, Nzadi B865, Mbuun B87; however, this list is probably not exhaustive and more attention to labial-velar stop realisations in free variation should be paid in general linguistic data collection on the region's languages in future fieldwork missions. Preliminary acoustic accounts of these sounds should be provided, as well as information concerning their frequency in the lexicon and their availability as free variants of KW-. Subsequently, aerodynamic data should be collected on all Lower Kasai varieties for which the acoustics of labial-velar stops has been established. Ultimately, a typology of labial-velar phonetics, lexical frequency, and tendency to emerge in free variation with KW- in the languages of the Lower Kasai should be produced (this would be an extension of Idiatov & Van de Velde's 2021 approach restructured to include low-level phonetic information as well as differences between systems with fully phonemic labial-velar stops and others in which they are only present as verbal gestures). Subsequent investigations could extend the same approach to areas of northern sub-Saharan Africa from which present-day Lower Kasai speech communities supposed to have imported labial-velar stops into the region might have originated. Acoustic, aerodynamic, and lexical data should be used to assess whether any specific area/s is/are particularly likely to have been the original point/s of diffusion of Lower Kasai labial-velar stops;
- Retroflexion: acoustic data should be collected on Nunu, and static-palatographic and ultrasound data should be collected on North Boma and Nunu to ground the preliminary acoustic findings presented here in articulation. Ultrasound data should be collected on Lotwa to investigate flapping

mechanisms. Findings on retroflexion from these three varieties should be integrated to evaluate matches and mismatches;

- Interiority: acoustic and lexical data should be collected on Yans B85, Nsambaan, Nsong, Ding, and Lwel; as is the case with labial-velar stops, though, this list is probably incomplete and a region-wide reconnaissance of all the relevant vowel systems should also be conducted. The exact nature of interior vowels in these languages should be described taking into account evidence from formant values to provide a clear idea of their individual vowel spaces. The diachronic development of interior vowels in these languages should be analysed with the tools of the comparative method. Subsequently, a typology of interior vowel systems should be presented and tested against the predictions of Dispersion Theory;
- Language history: findings from the previous three points should be integrated to test the relative chronology proposed in §8.2. This revision of the proposed timeline should then be tested against genetic and archaeological evidence. Genetic data were collected during the three fieldwork missions mentioned in this thesis and are currently in the process of being analysed as part of a long-standing collaboration between the African Studies department of Ghent University and the Evolutionary Biology laboratory at Uppsala University. Archaeological evidence was also collected by BantUGent team members and is currently being analysed at Ghent University (Coutros et al. 2024).

Lastly, efforts should not be spared to share any and all findings resulting from possible future research on this subject with the interested parties in the Democratic Republic of Congo. These include local academic institutions as well as syndicates dealing with hunter-gatherer populations, starting from the *Dynamique Générale des Peuples Autochtones*. All relevant datasets should be shared with the local institutions that participate in the data collection process.

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Appendix 1: Comparative Lotwa lexicon

Comparative Lotwa lexical data from four different Lotwa varieties are presented in this appendix. Audio and relative .eaf files can be found on OSF:

https://osf.io/fxdmb/?view_only=204483df54704ed3969361e578b25f02.

MEANING	LOTWA LOKONDA (MPENDJWA)	LOTWA LOKONDA (LIOKO)	LOTWA LOLIA	LOTWA LOSENGE
ABDOMEN	ndú	éalú:du	N/A	N/A
ADVICE	N/A	N/A	iláko	miláko
ADVISOR	N/A	N/A	N/A	egá:ɓi
ALL	é:kuma	é:kuma	bánku:má	okumá
ALLIGATOR	lokesé / pl. kesé	lokehé / pl. kehé	lo:ehé	N/A
ALONE	N/A	N/A	N/A	ké:dem:éni
ANCESTRAL GENIE	ndóki	vukálu	bulókéle	bo:dóki
ANCESTRAL POT	N/A	N/A	ikéngo	N/A
ANIMAL	ná:m:a	ná:m:a	ɲá:ma	náma
ANIMAL FAT	N/A	N/A	ba.íta (ɲá:ma)	N/A
ANT	lipúba	lipúba	éwa:wa	pú:ba
ANT (SPECIES 1)	kogó.odó/kogó. otó	kogó.odó/kogó .otó	N/A	N/A
ANTELOPE (GENERIC)	námahá:ga	námahá:ga	N/A	mbóloko
ANTELOPE (SPECIES 1)	mbe:géla	mbe:géla	N/A	N/A
ANTELOPE (SPECIES 2)	kuɽupá	kuɽupá	N/A	N/A
ANTELOPE (SPECIES 3)	pa:bí	pa:bí	N/A	N/A
ANTELOPE (SPECIES 4)	N/A	N/A	bó:loko	N/A
ANTELOPE (SPECIES 5)	N/A	N/A	ɲkúlupá	N/A

ANTHILL	e:béři	e:béři	e:βéβi	ebébo
ANUS	bo:tutú	bohóba	bo:tútu	mpókakúa
ARM	N/A	N/A	lo:βó	lo:bó
ARMPIT	lis:ába / pl. bas:ába	lihahába / pl. bahahába	i:hámba	bis:á:ba
ARROW	i:kulá	i:kulá	i:kulá	boséle, bosíki
ARROW TIP	N/A	N/A	N/A	sóli
ASH	botóko	botóko	betóko	botóko
AXE	řis:úa	řis:úa	ihú.a	řis:úa
BABOON	hóli	hóli	N/A	kísekise
BABY	mónaiβósa	mónaiβósa	N/A	móna.i:bós:a
BACHELOR	N/A	N/A	bondzémba	bozé:ba
BACK	bokógo / pl. bekógo	bokógo / pl. bekógo	mbúha	bokó:go
BACKWATER	N/A	N/A	e:tókwa	N/A
BAD	bo:bé	bo:bé	i:bé	bo:bé
BAD LUCK	N/A	N/A	bjongé.ibé	N/A
BALAFONG	N/A	N/A	ηόmα	N/A
BAMBOO	N/A	N/A	bákombó	bó:da/bó:ða/bo :kóβe
BANANA	ndemé	ndemé	i:ko:ndó	lik:ó:do
BAOBAB	bopéba	bopéba	N/A	N/A
BASKET	N/A	N/A	bo.íka	bo.úka
BAT (HOME DWELLING)	lokío	lokío	lonyémbó	N/A
BAT (SMALL)	lókukusá	lókukúha	lopokuhá	púkúsá
BAT (TREE DWELLING)	bokóma	bokóma	boηkó	bokóma
BEACH	boáři	pó:tá	řku.(w)óto	póta
BEAN	řřřikó / pl. ba:řřřikó	řřřikó / pl. ba:řřřikó	N/A	N/A
BEARD	lo.ore / pl. ndzo.ore	lo.ore / pl. ndzo.ore	lo:lé	bé.osá:βjaβá:γ a
BEAUTIFUL GIRL	N/A	N/A	ipókú	N/A
BEAUTIFUL, HANDSOME	bo:lágala	bo:lágala	ilánnga:la	N/A

BED BUG	lobósó	lobó	lohíliβón̄ga	lobólo
BED MADE OUT OF VINES	ta:gé	ta:gé	N/A	N/A
BEDDING	mbéto	mbéto/elá:lo	N/A	N/A
BEE	lo:ndzói	lo:ndzói	lo:ndzú.e	zóe
BEFORE, IN FRONT OF	to:déa	to:déa	ntóndo	enét:ó:do
BELL	nḡu:ga	nḡu:ga	nḡónḡa	botólo
BELLY	ɽiudú	luudú	í:kundí	lu:dú
BETWEEN	kát(s)inékó	kát(s)inékó	íhá:mbí	enéginágjobab ípe:
BIFURCATED POST	etáka	etáka	ikóndi	líodí
BIG	bonéne	bonéne	bonéne	monéne
BILE	e.ít̄ei	e.ít̄ei	ɽŋ̄ũ	N/A
BIRD	pu:ɽú	pu:ɽú	N/A	pu:ɽú
BITTER	bololo	bololo	bolólo	lolíci
BLACK	boíɽo	boíɽo	φ̄i:	lo.íɽo
BLADDER	esápu	ehápu	N/A	ésa:pú
BLESSING	N/A	N/A	bokáko/bahóci	bokáku
BLIND	áβuɽiáliso	áβuɽiábího	bontoȳnófalá: βε.íko	ntɽpéna
BLOOD	licilá	licilá	ba:lónḡo	ba:kilá
BLUNT	bo:t̄fi:ɽí	bo:t̄fi:ɽí	bot̄ái:ɽí	botí:ɽí
BODY	bokú:ɽu	bokú:ɽu	bío:nḡé	bɽɽḡi:amótu
BONE	bo.ódz̄o / pl. be.ódz̄o	boehé / pl. be.ehé	lokú.a	bú:esé
BONE MARROW	N/A	N/A	bo:nḡóβokílokú a	pó:go
BORDER	bó:ɽé:lo	bó:ɽé:lo	N/A	N/A
BOW	botá	botá	bo:ntá	botá
BOY	loéle	loéle	bónolo:ndo	móna:lé:ɽi
BRAIN	bo:gó / pl. beo:gó	bo:gó / pl. beo:gó	N/A	bó:go
BRANCH	etápi	etápi	ɽkóko	etápe
BRAVE	késó	kého	N/A	N/A

BREAST	lib:ále / pl. ba:βále	liβále	i:βéle	i:bále
BRIDGE	N/A	N/A	etála	N/A
BROOM	N/A	N/A	lo.ómbo	lo.óbo
BROTH	N/A	N/A	jó.u	N/A
BROTHER	boákume	boákume	bo.ína:mi / ηγάnelo:ndo	bosíkolo
BUCK	tá:bauwab:o.ómi	tá:bauwab:o.óm i	ntάβelo:ndo	N/A
BUFFALO	N/A	N/A	pakáha	N/A
BULL	ηγόbe.abo.ómi	ηγόbe.abo.ómi	ηγόmbélo:ndo	N/A
BURDEN	bořitó	bořitó	N/A	bóřitó
BUSH	bohó:βε	bohó:βε	N/A	e:sóbi
BUTTOCK	bisó	řihó	ihókɔ	íkelé
CALABASH	e:kútu	e:kútu	bótutu/ikútu	ekóli
CALF (BODY PART)	φέλο / pl. bipélo	φέλο / pl. bipélo	épéló	ep:élo
CANOE	bo:áto	bo:áto	wátu	bu.wáto
CARTRIDGE	N/A	N/A	iháfi	bisási
CASE	botú:βawaj:ága	utúba:j:a	bó:no:túmba	lik:á:dú
CASSAVA	li:kápi	li:kápi	í:hɔ:	isó:
CASSAVA (SPECIES)	N/A	N/A	ikáfi	N/A
CAT	ηγόjeříma	ηγόjeříma	bóřu.ató	řáo
CATERPILLAR	bo:tó	bo:tó	botó	be:tó
CATERPILLAR (SPECIES 1)	N/A	N/A	mbάβaηga	N/A
CATERPILLAR (SPECIES 2)	N/A	N/A	be:la:ηgá	N/A
CATFISH	ηγόlo	lóβε:ří	mbé:ři	N/A
CHAMELEON	N/A	N/A	lónηoηóli	N/A
CHANCE	N/A	N/A	bjongé.ilo	bokáko
CHEAP	N/A	N/A	ndombémbe.íl: o	N/A
CHEEK	ditáma/litáma / pl. batáma	ditáma/litáma / pl. batáma	i:táma	ditáma

CHEST	tolo	tolo	ntólo	tólo
CHICKEN	kókɔ.abo.ári	kókɔ.abo.ári	kókɔ.iβe.ínto	kókɔ
CHIKWANGUE	N/A	N/A	N/A	isó
CHIN	e:me:kú / pl. bi:me:kú	e:me:kú / pl. bi:me:kú	lo:βáŋga	lobá:ga
CLAN	N/A	N/A	N/A	bitúma
CLAW	lokála / pl. kála	lokála / pl. kála	N/A	kálajanáma
CLEAN	ɾi:ɾá:gaɾa	ɾi:ɾá:gaɾa	N/A	loóba
CLOSE TO	N/A	N/A	ntíka	N/A
CLOTHING	esé:dʒa	ehé:dʒa	e:hénda	etógo
CLOUD	lituté/dituté	lituté/dituté	é:lombé	batuté
CO-WIFE	bɔká:ɾe	bɔká:ɾe	mpála	bok:á:lí
COAL	ba.álala	ba.álala	ba.ála	li.átatála
COBWEB	bópópé	bópópé	bot:é.o.íφóφε	(síkea)lípopé
COCK	kókɔ.abo.ómi	kókɔ.abo.ómi	N/A	N/A
COIN	bɔsólo	bɔhólo	bɔhólo	palá:ga
COLA NUT	li:kó	li:kó	i:kó	likó
COLD	péo	péo	mpío	lopéo
CONCUBINAGE	N/A	N/A	ihóke/ikáŋgo	dis:á:ba
CONVERSATION	N/A	N/A	N/A	ŋ(ρ)φeá:béa
CONVERSATION (2)	N/A	N/A	lompéne	N/A
COPPER, GOLD	eβe:d:è/eβe:dé	eβe:d:è/eβe:dé	N/A	N/A
CORPSE	é.βé:b:e	é.βé:b:e	wohóβí	ebéβi
COST	N/A	N/A	bohío	N/A
COUGH	loko:sú	loko:hú	lo:ke:hú	loko:sú
COW	ŋgóbe	ŋgóbe	ŋgóme	gó:be
CRAB	lípópe	lípópe	ékokójo	lípopé
CRANIUM	lo:βéka	lo:βéka	lo:βéke / pl. méke	lóboló:go
CRICKET	N/A	N/A	ndzéndzu/i.én dze	N/A
CRIES	N/A	N/A	i:lélo	N/A
CROCODILE	ko:dé	ko:dé	ŋko:ndé	ga:dó
CROW	N/A	N/A	enkáŋka	jágá:ga

CRY (N.) TO DRAW EACH OTHER'S ATTENTION IN THE FOREST; OF HUNTERS	N/A	N/A	υ:ϱύ	N/A
CURSEN (N.)	N/A	N/A	άοταίκαηκό:λο	lokólo (pl. kólo)
DANCE	téko	téko	nsámbo	zé:ba.éba
DAUGHTER	βοίτο/μόνawaβ οίτο	βοίτο/μόνawa βοίτο	βόνοβε.ίντο	μόnamί.aβo.ít o/μόnaβo.ίto
DAUGHTER-IN-LAW	bokiló.υαβοίτο / pl. bakilóbá:βαίτο	bokiló.υαβοίτο / pl. bakilóbá:βαίτο	bociló:βε.ίντο	bokílυαβοίτο
DAY	boín:a	boín:a	bokólo	mo.ína
DEAF	ά.ίτάβató:ndi	ά.ίτάβató:ndi	e:kínda	ló:póko
DEATH	i:w:á	i:w:á	i:wa	ewú:a
DEBT	N/A	N/A	bompúlu	N/A
DEEP	ndzi:ϱó	ndzi:ϱó	bólindó	enélosé
DEFECATION	kúa	kúa	nzéke	kúwa
DEPTH	ndzi:dó	li:ϱó	N/A	N/A
DEW	ϱi.ási	ϱi.ási	i.áhi	bi.ási
DIRT	lo:mbe:d3o	lo:mbe:d3o	N/A	N/A
DIRTY	lo:mbe:d3o	lo:mbe:d3o	lo:βίνδο	lobído
DISCUSSION	N/A	N/A	ihía	bapójaóko
DIVORCE (N.)	N/A	N/A	iβála.ίβο:ηgwá	ndam:úa
DOG	mboa	mboa	mbwá	mbóa
DOG BELL	N/A	N/A	eléφó	élepó
DOOR	ep:é:le	ep:é:le	έφέle	lókuké
DOWRY	N/A	N/A	i:há.ί	lolá:ga
DREAM	ilótó/biϱótó	ilótó/biϱótó	ndó:tai	ílotó:(lo)
DRUM	bokéko	bokéko	ηόmo	mpó:da
DRY SEASON	beúwa	beúwa/bawá	bō	bówa
DUCK	dí:bá:ta	dí:bá:ta	i:βa:tá	ímá:ta
DUST	N/A	N/A	bo.i:tú	bó.utú
EACH	mótolamoto	mótolamoto	bontolo.όντο	ómola.όmo

EACH THING	eóbalaeoba	eóbalaeoba	jómbemaliémb o	N/A
EAR	litói / pl. batói	litói / pl. batói	it.ó.i	litói
EARTH	baβú	baβú	N/A	N/A
EAST	N/A	N/A	N/A	enékamwáne. óro
EBONY	bokóg(i)ε	bokóg(i)ε	N/A	N/A
EEL	bosó:bi	bosó:bi	bo:hómbi	N/A
EEL (SPECIES 1)	bokálá	bokálá	N/A	N/A
EEL (SPECIES 2)	he:be	he:be	nsémbe	sé:be
EGG	boερέ / pl. be.ερέ	boερέ / pl. be.ερέ	N/A	bo:ερέ
EIGHT	moámbi	moámbi	m:u.ámbi	mᵛᵛáβi
EIGHTEEN	diómulamóamb i	diómulamóám bi	li.ómulamó.ám bi	di.ómulamᵛᵛáβi
EIGHTY	tukumoá:mbi	tukumoá:mbi	ntúkumo.ámbi	túku.mᵛᵛáβi
ELDER TWIN	N/A	N/A	mbó	po
ELECTRIC FISH	N/A	N/A	ntúla/lolóndo	túla
ELEPHANT	ndzóu	ndzóu	ndjó.u	zóu
ELEPHANT TRAP	N/A	N/A	N/A	bokálo
ELEVEN	duómulaémᵛᵛ/di ómulaímᵛ	duómulaémᵛ/d iómulaímᵛ	li.ómulemᵛ	di.ómula.ómᵛ:
EMPTY	N/A	N/A	lájombáφu	kola.éβa
ENCAMPMENT	ndá:d:a/ndá:ɖa	ndá:d:a/ndá:ɖa	i:háŋga	ŋká:duɖa
END	N/A	N/A	nsúci	súka
EVENING	ŋkólᵛ	ŋkólᵛ	íkólᵛ	íkólᵛ
EVERYDAY	N/A	N/A	N/A	éβala.éβa
EVIL	ɾiáɾe	ɾiáɾe	ɾi.ále	N/A
EXPENSIVE	botúja	botúja	N/A	tálo
EYE	N/A	N/A	lího	N/A
EYEBROW	N/A	N/A	iŋkíci	kító
EYELASH	N/A	N/A	ŋkóŋki	tó
FACE	élo:gi	élo:gi	iló:ji	eló:gi
FALLOW	ɾi.óbú	ɾi.óbú	lupumbá	mᵛᵛá:gu
FAMILY	N/A	N/A	N/A	íkólᵛ, pl. tókólᵛ
FAR	bo:tále	bo:tálela	N/A	N/A

FAT	bi.íta / pl. baúta	bi.íta / pl. baúta	mpóηγο	ba.úta
FAT (ADJ.)	baú:ta	biú:ta	ba.íta	N/A
FATHER	papá/is:é	i:hé	mótai.ó:lo	i:sé
FATHER-IN-LAW	iseábokílo	iseábokílo	bociló:lo:ndo	N/A
FATIGUE	e:se:ρί	e:he:ρί	ehé:ρί	éseρί
FEAR	N/A	N/A	boφólu	mo.óma
FEATHER	lusála	luhála	N/A	losála
FEVER	pép:e:le	pép:e:le	pé:pele/φέ:φel e/lonγómba	bíogé
FIELD	ηγό:d:a/ηγό:δα	ηγό:d:a/ηγό:δα	boλέmo	gó:da
FIFTEEN	diómulabíta:no	diómulabíta:no	li.ómula.ítáno	di.ómulabetán o
FIFTY	tuku.i:tá:no	tuku.i:tá:no	ntúku.ítáno	túkut:á:no
FIN	N/A	N/A	ηκάηgu	N/A
FINE (N.)	eβίρο	eβίρο	N/A	N/A
FINGER	busái / pl. besái	busái / pl. besái	bóhé.i	bósa.í
FIRE	li.íja	li.íja	tsi:é	bi.íja
FISH	síe	híe	nsí	síe
FISH HOOK	N/A	N/A	ilópo	ilópa
FISHING CHARM	N/A	N/A	N/A	pa:bó
FIST	N/A	N/A	N/A	ébotú
FIVE	bitá:no	bitá:no	ítán(o)	betáno
FLASH OF LIGHTNING	lok:áriari	lok:áriari	boká:ri.á:ri	bokáli.áli
FLEA	ekóa	ekóa	bekú.á	ekóa
FLESH	N/A	N/A	bóhu:ni	bosúni
FLOWER	fuléle/fuléle	fuléle/furéle	ndjópo	fuléle
FLY (N.)	boká:ga/lotí:go	boká:ga/lotí:go	ikáηga	N/A
FOG	loβó:ge	loβó:ge	N/A	N/A
FOOD	éobá	éobá	i:lé	li.óba
FOOT	likáka/dikáka	likáka/dikáka	i:káká	ikáka
FOREST	li:á/ri.á / pl. ba:ri:á	li:á/ri.á / pl. ba:ri:á	li:á	ri:á
FOREST RAT	botó:ba	botó:ba	botsómba	N/A

FORGE	N/A	N/A	ηκúκα	motéti
FORTUNE	N/A	N/A	ηκάηγα	ηγά:ga
TELLER				
FORTY	tuku.ín:ei	tuku.ín:ei	ntúku.ín:ei	túku.ín:ei
FOUR	bínei	bínei	íne.i	ménei
FOURTEEN	diómulaβín:ei	diómulaβín:ei	li.ómula.ín:ei	di.ómulaménei
FROG	limote	limote	í:mó:tea	límóte
FRUIT	lomúma	lomúma	λόβόμα	βοβύμα
FULL MOON	βοέρι.ορινέκατσι κάτσι	ερίρι	N/A	N/A
FURIOUS	λοβέρι	λοβέρι	N/A	N/A
GECKO	ékukuřambú:řa	ékukuřambú:řa	ékunǵóli	N/A
GIANT	N/A	N/A	N/A	ep:áko
GOAT	tá:ba	tá:ba	ntáβa	tá:ba
GOD	ndzǵá:go:ba	dzǵá:be / pl. bandzǵá:be	ηάηkomba	zábe
GOITRE	N/A	N/A	N/A	go:goří
GOOD	bołót(s)i	bołót(s)i	ílo	bołóti
GORILLA	N/A	N/A	é:ři.á	eřía
GRAIN	N/A	N/A	móm:a.ín:i.ó	mpúma
GRAND- DAUGHTER	bokánaβoító	bokánaβoító	boηkánoβe.ínt o	bokána
GRAND-FATHER	faé.ealoe:le	haéaloe:le	ncé:lo:ndo	is:é.aiǵá:pi/káe
GRAND-MOTHER	faé.eaβoító	haéaβoító	ncé.iβe.ínto	k:a.éuαβo.ító
GRAND-SON	bokánaloéle / pl. bakánabá:βéle	bokánaloéle / pl. bakánabá:βéle	boηkánolo:ndo	wánabaké:kéle
GREEN	eηǵúdǵá	eηǵúdǵá	N/A	másibákéti
GREEN SNAKE	N/A	N/A	lo:βéηgo	bogwǵwi
HAIL	N/A	N/A	ηǵandá	N/A
HAIR	/ pl. baúo	liío / pl. baúo	li.ío	ba.úo
HAIR (SING.)	bo:sá	bo:há	bo:hó/íbo:to	bo.ɔsá
HAMMER	ma:la:tó	ma:la:tó	éβo:tú	N/A
HAND	bitáka / pl. batáka	bitáka / pl. batáka	í:káta	likáta
HANGAR	iβá:ga	iβá:ga	iηǵómba	igó:ba

HARD	bo.ólo	bo.ólo	bo.ólo	bo.óló
HARP	N/A	N/A	lókómbi	bókotí
HAT	isukú	ihukú	ihu:kú	N/A
HEAD	botói	botói	bo:té	botóa
HEALER	botútji	botútji	ηkán̄ga	gá:ga
HEART	botéma	botéma	botéma	botéma
HEARTH	N/A	N/A	ιρίο	N/A
HEARTH STONE	N/A	N/A	ikéngo	bá.igélo
HEAVY	bo:ri:tó	bo:ri:tó	boṛito	boṛito
HEEL	litji:dzi	litji:dzi	iké	bití:di
HERB	ṛi.óbi	ṛi.óbi	i:wúhú	jóbi
HERE	ané	ané	a:né	áne
HICCUGH	N/A	N/A	N/A	bisí.asíki
HILLOCK	ηgó:ba	ηgó:ba	N/A	bóq̄ji
HIP	dikó:go/likó:go	dikó:go/likó:go	N/A	N/A
HIPPO	ηgubú	ηgubú	ιη(g)ú	kibóko
HITTING STICK	boβáyo	boβáyo	ikómba	N/A
HOE	lougu / pl. dʒó:gu	lougu / pl. dʒó:gu	lo.óngo	lo.óbo
HOLE	boíso	boího	ipóku	ditóka
HOMONYM	ndo.í	ndo.í	N/A	N/A
HONEY	baútabá:ndzói	páko/baútabá: ndzói	mpáko	ba.útabá:zóe
HORN	liséké	lihéké	ihéké	liséto
HORSE	pú:da/pú:ɖa	pú:da/pú:ɖa	mpúnda	pú:ɖa
HOST	βoβútu	βoβútu	bo.útu	boβútu
HOT	ηgagéṛi	ηgagéṛi	jó:ηgéla	di.ía
HOUSE	botó:ba/botú:ba	botó:ba/botú:b a	botúmba	síki
HOW	ηgámo	ηgámo	nán̄ka	N/A
HOW MANY, HOW MUCH	botujáno	botujáno	bohí.on:o	tálo.íné
HUNGER	ndzála	ndzála	ndzála	ezála
HUNTER	boṛíacián:a:ma	boṛíacián:a:ma	bóli.aki.óṛám:a	boja.kí.anáma
HUNTING POWDER	N/A	N/A	lolíci	N/A

HUSK	N/A	N/A	mpoyó	lóposó
HYENA	sí:ba	(h)í:ba	N/A	N/A
IN GOOD FETTLE	N/A	N/A	íl(a)owíke	N/A
INSIDE	nékát(s)i.éa	nékát(s)i.éa	mpéiko:ntánda	enéginá
INSULT (N.)	N/A	N/A	N/A	lobé:go
INTELLIGENCE	ʒi.ána	ʒi.ána	wáɲa	di.ána
INTESTINES	losopó / pl. sopó	lohópó / pl. hopó	lóko:pó / pl. nso:pó	losópó
IRON	pé:ɹu	pé:ɹu	mpéko	N/A
ISLAND	léd:ʒe / pl. ndʒéd:ʒe	léd:ʒe / pl. ndʒéd:ʒe	e:túɾi/etúi	esá:ga
JAW	mbá:ga / pl. mbá:ga	lobága / pl. mbá:ga	N/A	N/A
JOY	N/A	N/A	eméɲɔ	básalá:ga
JUG	N/A	N/A	kéɲgo	N/A
KID	N/A	N/A	bóna	N/A
KIDNEY	bokólo / pl. bekólo	bokólo / pl. bekólo	boɲkólo	bokóló
KNEE	libólógo	lik:úluβógo	i:βóɲgo	ibó:go
KNIFE	i:k:ulájaj:áha	i:k:ulájaj:áha	N/A	N/A
KNIFE (2)	N/A	N/A	bohío.bo.íke	N/A
KNOWLEDGE	jo.é:βa	jo.é:βa	N/A	N/A
LANGUAGE (FACULTY)	loláka	loláka	loláka	ebe.éɾi
LANGUAGE (TONGUE)	loláme / pl. ndáme	loláme / pl. ndáme	lolému / pl. nému	lolému
LARGE	bo:tále	bo:tále	botál:e	N/A
LARGE CLOTHING	N/A	N/A	N/A	zá:baɾá
LAW	βoβéko	βoβéko	N/A	N/A
LAZY	N/A	N/A	bóɲgo:ɲú	et:úla / bo.ólu
LEADER, KING	kúmu	kúmu	ɲkúmu	kúnu
LEAF	lokási / pl. kási	lokási / pl. kási	lokáha	lokási
LEAF SKIRT	N/A	N/A	ɲká.ɲkóɲgo	N/A
LEG	lólul:o	lólul:o	lóko:lo	lól:lo
LEOPARD	kói	kói	ɲkó.i	N/A

LEPER	N/A	N/A	N/A	bakóko
LETTER	boka:dá	boká:ra	N/A	N/A
LIANA	N/A	N/A	lokɔ:ɾí	bo.óle
LIE	bojága	bojága	boŋgá:la	bokó:yoɾo
LIGHT	boháɾi	boháɾi	boháɾi	épalabolíto
LIGHT (N.)	lo.éɾía	lo.éɾía	jénéle	éd:ué
LIGHTNING	káki	káki	ɱká:ke	káke
LION	kósi	kósi	ɱkóhi	kói/tá:bo
LIP	lo:βéβu / pl. mbéβu	lo:βéβu / pl. mbéβu	ló:βé:u	bi:ɾéɾi
LITTLE, THIN	N/A	N/A	nió:	N/A
LIVER	lopíko / pl. píko	lopíko / pl. píko	lopiko	lopíko
LIZARD	bos:e:ɾía	he:lé	bosé:ɾé	bosíɿi
LONG	bo:tále	bo:tále	N/A	bot:álé
LOUSE	los:éɾi	lohí:ɾi	lóhí:n:a	losíɿi
LUNG	bisólo / lisólo	ɾihólo/dihólo	íháfací	bisólo
LYNX	N/A	N/A	boβáŋga	N/A
MACHETE	lo:kulá	lo:kulá	mpálo	mpé:ɾí/mpé:dí
MADNESS	N/A	N/A	ú.ejú	ekó:βé
MAGIC	bɔlekéɔ	bɔlekéɔ	bólokéleboŋkú mu	ndóki
MAGIC TRICK	N/A	N/A	bólokéle	bólokéɔ
MAGISTRATE	N/A	N/A	iwúka	N/A
MONKEY				
MAIZE	likógo	likógo	ihá.ú	botó
MAN	loéle	loéle	ló:ndo / pl. bé:le	béɾi
MANY	boíte	boíte	bo.íké	bo.íe
MARE	pú:ɖaɯab:oáɾi	pú:ɖaɯab:oáɾi	mpúnda.íβe.ínt o	N/A
MARKET	zá:ndo	zá:ndo	N/A	zá:do
MARKET DAY	bókoló.ázá:ndo	bókoló.ázá:nd o	N/A	m(w)ínowá.kw azá:ɾi
MARSH	lis:ápa	lihápa	lu:éndze	mítepú
MASS	N/A	N/A	N/A	monéne
MAT	i:tókó	i:tókó	lokála	í:tokó

MATERNAL AUNT	boákume	boákuméam:a	naŋíβó:fa	N/A
MATERNAL AUNT	iséaboíto	ihéaβoíto	mótʃoleβa.ínto	is:é.aβoíto
MATERNAL AUNT (OLDER THAN ONE'S MOTHER)	N/A	N/A	N/A	na:gó.igá:bi
MATERNAL AUNT (YOUNGER THAN ONE'S MOTHER)	N/A	N/A	N/A	na:gó.aibósa
MATERNAL UNCLE	nagwáloé:le	nagwáloé:le	naŋíló:ndo	ná:gopá:mi
MEAT	bosúni / pl. besúni	bohúni / pl. behúni	bóhu:ni	bosúni.anáma
MEDICINE	bo:té	bo:té	beló	be:té
MESSAGE	N/A	N/A	lotómu	lotómu
METAL	N/A	N/A	mpéko	N/A
MIDDLE POST	ndo:bé	ndo:bé.aʃi.ó:dʒ i	ikondíndombé	líodíja:dóbi
MILK	li:βále	li:βále	i:βéle	N/A
MODERN MEDICINE	N/A	N/A	móma	N/A
MOMENT	N/A	N/A	ntáŋgɛmɔ:	N/A
MONKEY	kéma / pl. kéma	kéma / pl. kéma	ŋkéma	kéma
MONKEY (SPECIES 1)	N/A	N/A	nsóʃi	N/A
MONKEY (SPECIES 2)	N/A	N/A	ŋge.é	N/A
MONKEY (SPECIES 3)	N/A	N/A	ŋkolongó	N/A
MONKEY (SPECIES 4)	N/A	N/A	e:βjá	N/A
MONTH	sá:dʒa	há:dʒa	N/A	sá:za

MOON	boéɽi	boéɽi	wéli	bo.óɽi
MORNING	késa	késa	mpéni	pé:ɖu
MORTAR	N/A	N/A	N/A	ibóka
MOSQUITO	loβéb:éle	loβéb:éle	loβémbéle	loβé:βele
MOTHER	na:gó	na:gó	ɲgó	na:gó
MOTHER-IN-LAW	nagwábokiló	nagwábokiló	bociló:βe.ínto	N/A
MOUNTAIN	bo:dzǐ	bo:dzǐ	ɲgómba/botóm bo.ú:ɲki.áu	gó:ba
MOURNING	N/A	N/A	lokáha	it:áli
MOURNING PERIOD	N/A	N/A	jópandjólaloká ha	N/A
MOUSE	poi	poi	mpó	bokóma
MOUTH	bonuá	bonuá	bó:ɲa	mo:núa
MUD	mbótɔ	mbótɔ	lo:póndo	lisópo
MUSHROOM	N/A	N/A	bó.iwó	bitífi
MUTE	N/A	N/A	e.ú:	olópobéa / lo.ími
NAIL (BODY PART)	lokála / pl. kála	lokála / pl. kála	lokála	lokála
NAME	lína	lína	lína	dína
NAPE	mbús:a.eacíku	mbúhací:go	mbúheɲcǐɲgo	N/A
NATURAL GENIE	eɽíma	eɽíma	eɽíma	bekálo
NAVEL	lotolú	lototú	bó:tolɔ	lopóle/bótɔlú
NEAR	tu:tála	tú:ta	N/A	túta
NECK	cíku	cíku	ɲcǐɲgo	kí:go
NET	N/A	N/A	boháka	N/A
NEW	N/A	N/A	ihó:ló	sá:go
NEW MOON	βίβα:g:ɔɽiag:ɔéɽ i	βίβα:g:ɔɽiag:ɔé ɽi	N/A	bo.áli.ók:aβá:g a
NIGHT	N/A	N/A	botǎio	betúo
NINE	lib:uá/lib:uá	lib:uá/lib:uá	líβu.á/liwá	libó.á
NINETEEN	diómulalib:uá	diómulalib:uá	li.ómulalíβu.á	di.ómulalibóa
NINETY	tukulib:uá	tukulib:uá	ntúkuliβu.á	túkulibóa
NOISE	póso	póso	N/A	N/A
NONE	ólala.émo	ólala.émo	lájombalém:o. óφu	kóla.émo

NORTH	N/A	N/A	N/A	enélíko
NOSE	bo.ólo / pl. beólo	bo.ólo / pl. beólo	bo.ólo	bo.ólo
NOTHING	bókoko	bókoko	N/A	N/A
NOTHING (2)	N/A	N/A	em:ómpé:φa	kólaléjeba
OATH	N/A	N/A	N/A	seṛéka
OIL	bosúku	bosúku	bohúku	ba.úta
OLD MAN	engabí.aloiḍo / biṅgabíbjabe.éṛ e	engabí.aloiḍo / biṅgabíbjabe.é ṛe	éṅgambé:ló:nd o	N/A
OLD WOMAN	engabí.aḃoíto	engabí.aḃoíto	éṅgambé:ḃe.in to	N/A
ON	né	né	ó:likó	lélikó
ONE	emó	emó	emó	omóko:
ONE HUNDRED	káma	káma	ḡkáma	káma
ONE HUNDRED AND ONE	N/A	N/A	N/A	kámaléomó:
ONE HUNDRED AND TWO	N/A	N/A	N/A	kámalaḃépe:
ONE MILLION	miṛió	miṛió	miljó.emo	kótuṛi.ómu
ONE THOUSAND	miṛiém:ɔ	miṛiém:ɔ	míljemo	kótu
ONION	bi:tungúlu	bi:tungúlu	ḡkwa:tu:ḡgúṛu	N/A
ORPHAN	N/A	N/A	e:tíce	etíke
OTHER	nó.ɔmɔ	nó.ɔmɔ	iṅkíná	ncína
OUTSIDE	néḃokiré.owá	néḃokiré.owá	mpé(i)ko:ḡgála	enébonó:go
OWL	N/A	N/A	éhukúlu	ésokúṛi
OX	N/A	N/A	bókélé	N/A
PADDLE	tápí	tápí	ḡkápi	kái
PALM NUT	e:mbá	e:mbá	mbá	e:ḃá
PALM TREE	ṛi:bá	ṛi:bá	N/A	N/A
PANGOLIN	N/A	N/A	ḡkálawóndzo	kálamoḡá
PATERNAL UNCLE	isé.eaébosa	isé.eaébosa	mótɔoleḃóha	N/A
PATERNAL UNCLE (OLDER)	isé:aengá:bi	ihéengá:bi	N/A	is:é.aiḡá:pi

THAN ONE'S FATHER)				
PATERNAL UNCLE (YOUNGER THAN ONE'S FATHER)	boákume / pl. baákume	ihéaefoyá	N/A	is:é.aiβúsa
PEANUT	lonjúba	lonjúba	lo:ndjókó	gúba
PENIS	losu:ka	losu:ka	lóφο:lo	losú:ga
PEPPER	liβé:ga	liβé:ga	N/A	N/A
PERSON	moto	moto	bó:nto	mótu
PESTLE	N/A	N/A	N/A	βο.όγο
PHEASANT	N/A	N/A	λο:kάηga	lokóko
PHEASANT (DOMESTIC)	λοkokú	λοkokú	N/A	N/A
PHEASANT (WILD)	loká:ga	loká:ga	N/A	N/A
PIECE	N/A	N/A	bohúni	eténi
PIG	N/A	N/A	ηγúlu	só:bu
PIGEON	dímbé:be	dímbé:be	embenjá	libé:ga
PIPE	N/A	N/A	mbóηgo	bó:ma
PLANTAIN	likóδο	likóδο	etá:βε	étábe
PLANTATION	é:lá:ga	é:lá:ga	é:láηga	N/A
PLATE SHEET (LEAF USED AS A DISH)	N/A	N/A	ηκοηγο	N/A
POISON	ndzé:dze	ndzé:dze	boló	lolíki
POLYGAMOUS MAN	ndo:gó	ndo:gó	N/A	N/A
POOR	N/A	N/A	bombó:lo	bo:(m)βólo
PORCUPINE TRAP	N/A	N/A	é:bobo	N/A
POT	N/A	N/A	mpo:ké	N/A
POT	po:ké	po:ké	N/A	ké:go
POTTER	boéni.oá.poké	boéni.oá.poké	N/A	borí.apoké
PROHIBITION	jona:gá	jona:gá	N/A	N/A

PROSTITUTE	N/A	N/A	ba.ínto.o:ndúm ba	bozé:ba
PROUD	lipóro	lipóro	N/A	N/A
PROVERB	N/A	N/A	mba:tándja	bat:ó:dja
QUIVER (N.)	bokáke	bokáke	ihó:j:á	mpá:go
RAFFIA SKIRT	N/A	N/A	íhkekwa	N/A
RAFFIA TREE	bipéké	bipéké	N/A	N/A
RAIN (N.)	N/A	N/A	mbúla	mbúla
RAINBOW	N/A	N/A	bóseké	N/A
RAINY SEASON	téla	téla	elekékimbúla	ílekoj:á:yúla
RAT TRAP	N/A	N/A	N/A	póku
RAW	N/A	N/A	intel:é/bo.ólu	ép:olu
RAY OF LIGHT	N/A	N/A	ibáři	baé(υ)abábitó: ba
RED	ηgóla	ηgóla	ηgóla	xóla (?)
RED ANT	loβóba	loβóba	í:pumba	N/A
RED PEPPER	libéga	libéga	ibénga	biβéga
REED	N/A	N/A	N/A	nde:lége
RELIGIOUS STATUE	ekekó.éalosáβ o	ekekó.éalosáβ o	N/A	N/A
RICE	líso / pl. baíso/lóso	líso / pl. baíso/ lóho	lóho	lo.óso
RICH	N/A	N/A	ikókuláka	bókuláka
RIDDLE	N/A	N/A	tótó	N/A
RIFLE	N/A	N/A	bondóci	bodóki
RING	liηgéte	liηgéte	loπέte	N/A
RIPE	N/A	N/A	jo:kémba	kéaké:ba
RIVER	boéři	boéři	bokéři	bé:ři
ROCK	biβó:ko	biβó:ko	í:βóko	mbá:ya
ROOF	bokúko	bokúko	jángo	N/A
ROOM	loténa	loténa	ló:u:řú	ot:énajasíki
ROOT	bo.iri	bo.iri	bolío/mpémba	bo.iri
ROPE	lo:ři / pl. ndzo:ři	lo:ři / pl. ndzo:ři	bohínga	bo.óle/biséke
ROUTE	bálaβála	boβóko	mbóka	ηvóka
RUBBER VINE	botóte	botóte	N/A	N/A

SADNESS	N/A	N/A	i:hé.i	íse.í
SAFOU	losáu	loháu	lohá.u	los:á.ú
SALIVA	sói	hói	nsói	sóji
SALT	bohúá	bohúá	bó:ku.á	bó:gúá
SAME	N/A	N/A	botáíndó:mo:	de:gém:o
SAND	lo:kó:gó / pl. le:kó:gó	lo:kó:gó / pl. le:kó:gó	bá:hengé	zélo
SATCHEL	N/A	N/A	mban(g)o/íβa:t é	mpá:go
SAUCE	bosáka	boháka	ka:mbírí	bosúku
SCABIES	N/A	N/A	lopóte	póte
SCAR	é:ɾi	é:ɾi	lónónnda	N/A
SCISSORS	bokási / pl. bekási	bokáhu / pl. bekáhu	bokáhi	N/A
SCORPION	likátɛi	likátɛi	ɱko:tó	kotó
SEED	N/A	N/A	bjón:ója	lomóto
SEVEN	sá:mbo	sá:mbo	nsámbo	sá:βo
SEVENTEEN	diómulasá:mbo	diómulasá:mb o	li.ómulansámb (o)	di.ómulasá:βo
SEVENTY	tukusá:mbo	tukusá:mbo	ntúku:sámbo	túkusá:βo
SHADOW	bo.íríma	bo.íríma	irjáríngi	didjá:ɾídi
SHALLOW	N/A	N/A	kéngéne	N/A
SHAME	N/A	N/A	nsóni	sóni
SHARP	péa	péa	mpía	bi:áɾi
SHELL	N/A	N/A	lopuɣó	N/A
SHINY	N/A	N/A	engéngɛ	N/A
SHOE	ekotó	ekotó	sa:pátu	sapató
SHORT	bo.ú:wé	bo.ú:wé	bokú.e	boúwe
SHOULDER	lipéa / pl. bapéa	lipéa / pl. bapéa	í:péke	ipéa
SICK	fá:ji	fá:ji	N/A	N/A
SICKLE	N/A	N/A	ɱkóta.ɱkɛɱkú mu	igó:da
SICKNESS	nói	nói	wá:ɛ	bo.áli
SIDE	bopá:dʒé / pl. pa:dʒé	lopá:dʒé / pl. pa:dʒé	lo:pa:ndjé	lop:á:zí

SILVER	bo:sólo	bo:sólo	bɔhɔlɔmpéko	N/A
SISTER	boákume	kán:ə	ɲgána(βe.ínto)	karíane
SIX	botóa	botóa	botóβa	botóa
SIXTEEN	diómulaboto:a	diómulaboto:a	li.ómula.ot:óβa	di.ómulabotóa
SIXTY	tukubotóa	tukubotóa	ntúku.otó:βa	túkuβotóa
SKIN	loposó / pl. posó	lophó / pl. pohó	lophóhó	ísupú/loposó
SKY	loβóla	loβóla	li:kó	lobóla
SLAVE	í:ɾaitfé	í:ɾaitfé	bɔɲgám̩ba	bo.óβo
SLEEPING HUT	N/A	N/A	ɪɲkúsa	N/A
SLIM	bo.ód̩u	bo.ód̩u	bo.ón̩du	N/A
SLUMBER	iló	iló	iló	i:ló
SMALL	ljása	jáha	N/A	bokéke
SMALL BELL	ɲgóga	ɲgóga	buntóle	loko:gá (pl. ko:gá)
SMALLNESS	N/A	N/A	ni:ó	N/A
SMOKE (N.)	boɾí:gǎ	boɾí:gǎ	bolímba	boɾí:ga
SNAIL	N/A	N/A	lɔkólɔ	lɔkólɔ
SNAIL	lɔkólɔ	lɔkólɔ	N/A	N/A
SNAKE	ndzóa	ndzóa	ndzó	zóa
SNAP OF THE FINGERS	N/A	N/A	bɔsót̩ʃa	N/A
SNEEZE (N.)	N/A	N/A	i:káɲe	N/A
SO, THUS	ndá.iko	ndá.iko	móní	N/A
SOIL	βa:βú	βa:βú	ba:ú	lomóto
SOLID	bo.ólo	bo.ólo	N/A	eké:ba
SON	món:a	món:a	bóna	móna
SON-IN-LAW	bokilóealoé:le / pl. bakilóbá:βe:le	bokilóealoé:le / pl. bakilóbá:βe:le	bociló:lo:ndo	bokílo
SONG	lwojéb:o	lwojéb:o	bolémo	lo.é:bo/boálo
SOUR	bo:kái	bo:kái	bokái	bokái
SOURCE	e:tókwa / pl. bi:tókwa	e:tókwa / pl. bi:tókwa	e:tókwá	tɛína:boéli
SOUTH	N/A	N/A	N/A	enélosé
SPARK	N/A	N/A	n(t)sáhi	ɲvá:βe

SPARROW	N/A	N/A	N/A	έσσηρία
SPARROWHAWK	kó:be	kó:be	ηκόμβε	kó:bu
SPEAR	N/A	N/A	ικσηγή	likó:ga
SPEECH	N/A	N/A	N/A	ba.ói
SPIDER	lopópe	lopópe	ίφο:φέ	N/A
SPIRIT	bořímu	bořímu	bolíma	N/A
SPIRIT OF THE DEAD	bolím:a:bokálu	bolím:a:bokálu	N/A	N/A
SPOUSE (F.)	N/A	N/A	wáři	bwáři
SPOUSE (M.)	N/A	N/A	bo.óme (pl. bo.ómε)	mo.ómi
SQUASH, GOURD	e:kútu	e:kútu	N/A	N/A
SQUIRREL	es:é:dze	ehé:dze	ehénde	esé:ze
SQUIRREL TRAP	N/A	N/A	keléte	N/A
SQUIRE	η:dzi.é	η:dzi.é	ndi:é	ndi:é
STAR	mboétřia	mboétřia	bo.óto	ijóti
STICK	ekóka	ekóka	boté	N/A
STOMACH	ři.udú	e:řudú	N/A	N/A
STRAW TORCH	N/A	N/A	i:βάβα	boé:zí
STRIAGHT	ljása	jáha	boβóko	sa.íakopá
STRONG	N/A	N/A	N/A	bo.ólo
SUGARCANE	bosógo	bosógo	bohóngo	bókokó
SUGARY	řířié	řílé	él:i.é/éři.é	éři:é
SUN	bijéle	bijéle	wané/bo.ína	mo.áni
SUNRISE	N/A	N/A	řéle	N/A
SWAMP FOREST	N/A	N/A	lu:éndze	N/A
SWEAT (N.)	botokí	botokí	bo:tóki	botóki
SWEET	N/A	N/A	N/A	akobéá
SWEET POTATO	řime:dzé	řime:dzé	nšeléngi	N/A
SWORD	lokulál:waj:áha	lokulál:waj:áha	ntóto	letíti
TABLE FOR OFFERINGS	N/A	N/A	eháka	ipána
TABOO	N/A	N/A	epókelám:e	N/A
TABOO	N/A	N/A	N/A	e.íla
TABOO (2)	N/A	N/A	bokéka	N/A

TAIL	bukólo / pl. bakólo	bukólo / pl. bakólo	i:βón̄go.i:lo:βó	ik:ólojal:bó
TAIL	boéla	boéla	wéla	boéla
TALE	N/A	N/A	ihói	N/A
TALE	N/A	N/A	N/A	mosímo
TAMTAM	N/A	N/A	N/A	mpó:da
TANGY	sáisai	háihai	háihai	bató:βa
TEAR (N.)	N/A	N/A	bo.ího:li	e.ísořía
TEN	duómu	duómu	li.ómu	di.ómu
TERMITE	ndzelelí:a/ndze řeřía	ndzelelí:a/ndz eřeřía	béŋko:ndí	zéleřía
TERMITE MOUND	bo:dzǐ	bo:dzǐ	lohéléjá	litó:ge
TESTICLE	likútu	likútu	i:li:ká	dikútu
THAT	N/A	N/A	e.íko	ení
THERE	ení/əní	ení/əní	mpé.ikopéni	éne
THICK	bo.ódu	bo.ódu	bóhú:ni	N/A
THIEF	eíba	eíba	N/A	N/A
THIEF (2)	N/A	N/A	bo.íβi	móto.íba
THIN	bo:ké	bo:ké	N/A	N/A
THING	eóba / pl. bióba	eóba / pl. bióba	i:ómba	é:βa
THIRST	posía	pohía	mpóhá	posía
THIRTEEN	diómulabisáto:	diómulabisáto:	li.ómula.íháto	di.ómulabésát o
THIRTY	tuku.ísáto:	tuku.ísáto:	ntúku.íháto	túku.ísáto
THIS	N/A	N/A	ené	éne.ekajénənía
THORN	bu.édze	bu.édze	nsénde	bó.igé
THREE	bisato	bisato	íháto	bísáto
THROAT	lig:oló:ma	liŋgoló:ma	bo:ří	N/A
THUNDER	ekon̄góla	ekon̄góla	élundjá	ék:ugúla
TICK	N/A	N/A	N/A	isó:ga
TIME	ŋgóuga	ŋgóuga	ntán̄go	éké:ko
TIN	kóug:á	kóug:á	N/A	N/A
TIPLESS ARROW	N/A	N/A	loβáhi	N/A
TO ACCEPT	jó.im:eřía	jó.im:eřía	N/A	N/A
TO ACCOMPANY	jóha:búla	jóha:búla	itôtsiká	lojáté:ře

TO ACCUMULATE, TO ADD	jó:bakísa	jó:bakísa	nsáηgǵá(β)o.ík eβo.íke	vakísa
TO ACCUSE	jófú:ɖa	jófú:ɖa	N/A	N/A
TO ADD	N/A	N/A	jókokía.ηkíná.í ko	N/A
TO ADVISE	N/A	N/A	bo:láki	jólakía
TO AMBLE	N/A	o:lekáleka	ikendé:kende	sóbotána
TO ANOINT	N/A	N/A	N/A	jábísa
TO ANSWER	jó.inonia	jó.inonia	jówutóla	zinója
TO APPEASE	ljét:érǵáβotéma	ljét:érǵáβotéma	N/A	N/A
TO ARRANGE	N/A	N/A	jówonǵía	bo:gía
TO ASK	jótía	jótía	jojíwojá	jólú:la
TO AVOID	N/A	N/A	hé:ŋa	dwálutá
TO BARK	N/A	N/A	jówowá	bwábuba
TO BE DARK	bo.íríma	bo.íríma	N/A	N/A
TO BE EQUAL	N/A	N/A	bókokó:mo	N/A
TO BE FLAT	ékóβúre.á	ékóβúre.á	N/A	N/A
TO BE FULL	jojo:la	jojo:la	N/A	N/A
TO BE IN A RUSH	N/A	N/A	jólalámo:iβáηg oiβáηgo	lobágoloba:go
TO BE LATE	jóbo.úβa	jóbo.úβa	N/A	N/A
TO BE LYING DOWN	jó:kala:gána	jó:letána	jóka(β)étamí.a	iléboló:go
TO BE POSSIBLE	N/A	N/A	íηkumá.ílo	é.írú.á
TO BE ROTTEN	N/A	N/A	jópondó	N/A
TO BE SATISFIED	N/A	N/A	N/A	kjáki:ɖa
TO BE SEATED	N/A	N/A	jókihá	zitá:íta
TO BE STANDING	N/A	N/A	jó.emála	zemána
TO BE SUSPENDED	N/A	N/A	ndé:leme	kakéma
TO BE TIRED	jó:kæ:se:ɾí	jó:kæ:se:ɾí	jóló:lo	N/A
TO BE USED TO	N/A	N/A	wékehé:lo	mómesála
TO BE WET	N/A	N/A	jówowó	sótótálaβúla
TO BITE	N/A	N/A	jólamáta	kó:kóna
TO BLESS	N/A	N/A	jóléηkó:lo	botwáku

TO BLOW ON FIRE	N/A	N/A	N/A	káyp:iaɾi.ía
TO BLOW WITH ONE'S MOUTH	N/A	N/A	jóφuφά	N/A
TO BOIL	jótakía	jótakía	jóφelía (seulement l'eau: éwu:já)	pe:ɾía/ndá:lá:b a
TO BORROW	N/A	N/A	bohómbo	N/A
TO BRAID	jotúg:ea	jotúg:ea	jólembá	tú:géa
TO BREAK	N/A	N/A	jó.olá	mp ^h éabé:la
TO BREASTFEED	jómé:nia	ɾiɾó.umía	jóleim:ía	ndóumía
TO BREATHE	jojómo	jojómo	jojóma	gwáñúmu
TO BRING	jotó:ba	laɾía	jótombé:la	ódaɾí:e
TO BUILD	jótó:ga	tó:ga	N/A	zé:mi.a
TO BUILD (2)	N/A	N/A	jóló:	N/A
TO BURN	jótu:ba	tú:ba	(jólɔŋgójá) jótumba	dibéba/twátu:b a
TO BUY	N/A	N/A	jóhómbo	sóasó:ba
TO CARRY	jólóta	jólóta	jó.ε:kéte	βjábe.éba
TO CIRCUMCISE	N/A	N/A	jótenákampúlu	kotéti
TO CLOSE	jólitá	jólitá	jóliφά	ndjálipa
TO CLOSE ONE'S HAND INTO A FIST	N/A	N/A	kaŋgá.ibóto	ká:kaβéi̯bo:tú
TO COHABIT	N/A	N/A	jókihándi.émó	zit.á.it:a
TO COMB	N/A	N/A	nsa.ín:óla	N/A
TO COME	jojá	jojá	jója	zin:óa
TO COME BACK	N/A	N/A	jójalaló:ŋkína	o:ínóa
TO CONTROL ONESELF	jó:kagabotémá	jó:kagabotémá	N/A	N/A
TO COVER	N/A	N/A	jólipá/jójihá	ndjá:lípa
TO CRY	N/A	N/A	jo:káwa	mpiábjalabúlu
TO CURSE	N/A	N/A	áhó:lɔko	dwálóka
TO CUT	jokáta	jokáta	N/A	N/A
TO CUT	jókɔta	jo:téna	jótená:ka	téaténa
TO CUT UP	N/A	N/A	óhehe (náma)	sjásésa

TO DANCE	N/A	N/A	jóhambóla	d3é:baéba
TO DEFECCATE	jónεkakúa	jónεkakúa	jón:eké:sépe	djánεkakúa
TO DENY	N/A	N/A	lwán:á:lo	N/A
TO DEPRECATE	jót:i.o:la	jót:i.o:la	N/A	N/A
TO DESCEND	si:řóa	kiřiřóa	johúlu.á	su:zá
TO DESIRE	jó:póna/jólá:ga	jó:póna/jólá:ga	juwámbá	posía
TO DIE	N/A	N/A	jówa	dzúa.úa
TO DIMINISH	N/A	N/A	jo.ím:olandám benkína	einzía
TO DISCUSS	jó:lalopé:ne	jó:lalopé:ne	ihía	lo:péne/lopéne
TO DIVIDE	N/A	N/A	jókapá	zapá:pa
TO DIVORCE	N/A	N/A	jókatóna (iβála)	N/A
TO DO	jó.ela	jó.ela	jókelá	zelá.ila
TO DREAM	jóemúa	emóa	jóló:to (ndótai)	ilótóa
TO DRESS UP	jólotá	jólotá	jólóto	ndwá:lota
TO DRILL	N/A	N/A	jo:táim:a	kjat:ímo
TO DRILL	N/A	N/A	jókotobóla	du:dóla
TO DRINK, TO SWALLOW	me:ná	me:ná	jóminá	βjámina
TO DRY	N/A	N/A	jómbo	ndíbóla
TO DRY	N/A	N/A	jwán:i.á	zóma.oma
TO EAT	jóléa	léa	jóle	déaléa
TO END	N/A	N/A	johé:ja	sí:řía
TO ENTER	o:tóa	o:tóa	N/A	otóa
TO ENTOMB	jó.ud:á/jó.udá	jó.ud:á/jó.udá	jókundá	zu:dá.uda
TO ENVELOP	N/A	N/A	jóló:téia/jókuká	ndzot:ója
TO EXPAND	jópá:d3ola	jópá:d3ola	N/A	N/A
TO EXPLAIN	jó:libó:la	jó:libó:la	N/A	N/A
TO FALL	N/A	N/A	ηκό:kɔ	kwáku.a
TO FILL	N/A	N/A	jo:lía (?)	lóuřía
TO FLY	jó.íba	jó.íba	mpungwá	pu:bβóa
TO FOLLOW	ikáma/jobokí:m a	ikáma/jobokí:m a	jó.ikám:a	kja:kíma
TO FORGE	N/A	N/A	jotúla	lotúlo
TO FORGET	N/A	N/A	jóβοφέla	mpópeléa

TO GATHER	jókokanía	jókokanía	jóhokí:a	zeté.itamáto
TO GIVE	N/A	N/A	jópa	ka:kája
TO GIVE BIRTH	N/A	N/A	joβóta	mpwá:buta
TO GO	N/A	N/A	jóta	ze:dá.eda
TO GO OUT	óla	óla	jóhóló:	óla
TO GROW	N/A	N/A	jokémba	mpuyápú:la
TO GROWL	jojóma	jojóma	N/A	N/A
TO GUT, TO HOLLOW OUT	N/A	N/A	jóbukóla	N/A
TO HANG (UP)	N/A	N/A	N/A	béam:éma
TO HATE	ló.un:ó	ló.un:ó	N/A	N/A
TO HAUNT	N/A	N/A	jó:tó:	N/A
TO HEAR	jóka	jóka	jó:ka	aɾía
TO HEAVE	ljóngeɾía	ljóngeɾía	N/A	N/A
TO HELP	N/A	N/A	íhungí	sá:ɾi.a
TO HIDE	jówó.uɖa/jówó. ud:a	jówó.uɖa/jówó. ud:a	jóka.íha	ɾísa.ísa
TO HIT	jókóta	jókóta	N/A	kwákúla
TO HIT	jo.áma	jo.áma	jóle:mbé/jóbéte	zjá:nia
TO HOE	N/A	N/A	N/A	bápísa
TO HUNT	N/A	N/A	jókomba/jo:íta mía	zítanía
TO INCREASE	N/A	N/A	jótɛiká.o.íke	ndzúɾeɾía
TO INFLATE	N/A	N/A	já:mama	zamá:ma
TO INSULT	jót:ó:la	jót:ó:la	jó(w)u:ndá	jobé:ga
TO JUMP	N/A	N/A	jóhotó	pu:βóa
TO KILL	jóɾiáka	i.áka	jóɾi.áka	di.áka
TO KISS, TO HUG	N/A	N/A	jókaha:ngwéla	sa:gánía
TO KNOCK	N/A	N/A	N/A	kokóma
TO KNOW	N/A	N/A	iwéwa	ka.éba
TO LACK	N/A	N/A	ɱkámba (je manque de?)	záɱá:ga
TO LAUGH	N/A	N/A	jô:ló	zóla.óla
TO LICK	jo.ábu:na	jo.ábu:na	jó:φé:φe	kotó.uma/ndó. uma
TO LIFT	N/A	N/A	jóhe:kéte	zulelía

TO LOOK FOR	jón̄ta	jón̄ta	N/A	N/A
TO LOOK LIKE	N/A	N/A	ilé̄ngalé̄m̄o	kokána
TO LOVE	jolá:ga	jolá:ga	N/A	N/A
TO MARRY	N/A	N/A	jóbála	twá:túka
TO MOULD A POT	ji.óinapoké	ji.óinapoké	N/A	N/A
TO MOUNT	jó̄ūɾeɾa	jó̄ūɾeɾa	joj:éla	uléa
TO MOUNT AN ANIMAL	N/A	N/A	jókondélaná:m a	N/A
TO OBSTRUCT	jólipámbóka	jólipámbóka	N/A	N/A
TO OBTAIN	N/A	N/A	joβá:ta	mpá:ta
TO OCCUPY	jó̄ɛsa	jó̄ɛha	N/A	N/A
TO OPEN	jólipo:la	jólipo:la	jó̄liφóla	dipóla
TO POUND	N/A	N/A	jo:tóko	twátó.a
TO POUR	N/A	N/A	jó.utúm:olá	zu:βé̄ɾía
TO PROMISE	N/A	N/A	joteí:a	N/A
TO PULL	bé:la	bé:la	jóhú:m:a	zesá.ésa
TO PUNISH	bo:nóko	bo:nóko	N/A	N/A
TO PUSH	jó:loa	jó:loa	jóhukóla	óbasáwulé
TO PUSH (2)	jotí:ɖa/jotí:da	tí:ɖa/tí:da	N/A	N/A
TO PUT DOWN	sé:nía	hé:nía	johé:ɲ:a	tía
TO PUT DOWN	N/A	N/A	johé̄nálíkó.in̄kí	tíatía
TO READ	jotá:ga	jotá:ga	jótanḡaŋkóma	táta:ga
TO REFUSE	jo:tóna	jo:tóna	jotóna	twátún(ə?)
TO REMEMBER	N/A	N/A	N/A	ilé.azeɾéa
TO RESPECT	jotosa	jotosa	N/A	N/A
TO REST	N/A	N/A	N/A	zo:ɾía
TO REST (2)	jólála	jólála	jó:ja	N/A
TO ROAST	jókalá:ga	kalá:ga	jo:kálaŋga	sa:ɾí
TO ROCK	jólé:lá	lé:lá	jólaketóna	ndé.aléla, kábobó:ta
TO RUB	N/A	N/A	jókulúta	nda:góla
TO RUN	sóa	kuhóa	jóφuhú.a	kuɾumóa
TO SAY	jo:tépéla	jo:tépéla	jóteφéla	mphé.abé.a/m bé:ɾéa

TO SAY	N/A	N/A	boβéko	mpékolá
GOODBYE TO				
TO SCRATCH	N/A	N/A	jóka:kwahóla	jákóla
ONESELF				
TO SEE	jóéna	jóéna	jó.én:e	le:idá
TO SEIZE	N/A	N/A	mbwá.útə	bwá:buta
TO SELL	N/A	N/A	jótéke	téatéka
TO SEND	jotí:ɖa/jotí:da	jotí:ɖa/jotí:da	N/A	N/A
TO SEVER	N/A	N/A	ka:φólá	nda:múna
TO SEW	joha:ba	joha:ba	N/A	sá:ságo
TO SHAKE	N/A	N/A	jóηηία	nza:ίηιά
TO SHARE	N/A	N/A	jók:άφα	zapápa
TO SHIVER	N/A	N/A	lóβilímo	tutúma
TO SHOUT	N/A	N/A	wáhi.áhi	mpwábúba
TO SHOW	N/A	N/A	jó.én:ía	zéneníá
TO SING	jó.eba	jó.eba	jo.émbá	zé:ba.é
TO SIT DOWN	N/A	N/A	jókihá	N/A
TO SKIN, TO	οβólapóso	οβólapóso	N/A	N/A
PLUCK				
TO SLEEP	jolála	lála	jólá:la	ndálála
TO SLIDE	N/A	N/A	johélem:wá	N/A
TO SMELL	jókalo.utú	jókahólu	N/A	okósuɾu
SOMETHING				
TO SMELT	N/A	N/A	ηsélu:á	ndá:góla
TO SMOKE	N/A	N/A	jóminá (ikája)	vi.á:mína
TO SNEEZE	jók:aseléa	kahéléa	(jókela?) i:káhe	káseríia
TO SOIL	N/A	N/A	N/A	bóp:o:ɖú
ONESELF				
TO SOUGH	N/A	N/A	N/A	lókaleka
TO SOW	N/A	N/A	jonó:na	kwákóne
TO SQUAT DOWN	bosódʒo/bɔhód	bɔhódʒo	N/A	N/A
	ʒo			
TO START	λό:βά:ga/(l)jó:β á:ga	λό:βά:ga/(l)jó:β á:ga	jóβaηgá	mpába:ya
TO STEAL	N/A	N/A	lo.ίβα	zíba.íba

TO STICK, TO JAM	joka:ga	joka:ga	i:βámba	N/A
TO STRIKE DOWN	jó:kóta	jó:kóta	N/A	N/A
TO STUDY	N/A	N/A	jó.ékóla	zesésani:ána
TO SUCK	N/A	N/A	né.im:á	N/A
TO SUCKLE	N/A	N/A	N/A	ndó.umía
TO SURPASS	N/A	N/A	jólekía	ndekía
TO SURPRISE	N/A	N/A	ntónía	sasímwa
TO SWEEP	N/A	N/A	jó(:/ɔ)mbó	nzó:βαóba
TO SWIM	N/A	N/A	itúnga	kwákúla
TO TAKE	N/A	N/A	jókɔhó	zésa.ésa
TO TAKE A WALK	N/A	N/A	jókendé	is:ónanáβε.éb o
TO TASTE	jóaríá	haríá	jólóngotɛjándó na (?)	lé:teɾéa
TO TEACH	jólaka	jólaka	jólaká	nda:kía
TO TEAR INTO PIECES	jo.átola	atóla	N/A	zá:táta
TO TELL (A STORY)	jós:ga.esa.í	johá:ga	jóɸa.íholó	kakájamatusá: go
TO THINK, TO REMEMBER	N/A	N/A	jok:ánisá	kakánisá
TO THROW	N/A	N/A	ntúméte	bí.aríka
TO TICKLE	N/A	N/A	ihúi	pé:kútu
TO TIE	jórig:ula	jórig:ula	jotúndi.á.ihúi	N/A
TO TIE IN A KNOT	jóug:éa	jóug:éa	jówombó	tu:géa
TO TILT	N/A	N/A	lonténga	nzé:gáma
TO TOUCH	jóbutá	jóbutá	jó.u:tá	butá
TO TRAP	N/A	N/A	jo:léβε	isótía:baló:ga
TO TRAVEL	joédalɔédɔ	joédalɔédɔ	N/A	N/A
TO TURN ON (A LIGHT)	jóeríá	eríá	jópe:táia	ze:ɾía/katíalía
TO TWIST	joáma	joáma	na:máma	zá:máma
TO UNDRRESS	jó.unjaβisédʒa	ómjaβihédʒa	jímo:lá	zú:mía
TO UNTIE	N/A	N/A	jolítolá	dip:óla

TO URINATE	jónɛkabisápu	jónɛkabisápu	jón:ekjá:(φυ)	N/A
TO VANISH	N/A	N/A	jóɣolím:wa	dzúm:a.úm:a
TO VOMIT	N/A	N/A	ndwálú:a	ndókóla
TO WAIT	jó:ka	jó:ka	ó:ka	djálíla
TO WAKE UP	jóem:úra	jóem:úra	jó.im:úa	zemúa
TO WALK	jó:ɛɔáɛɔ	jó:ɛɔáɛɔ	jókendé	N/A
TO WATER (PLANTS)	N/A	N/A	jóbokáhi	zu:βé:ría
TO WEAVE	N/A	N/A	N/A	toát:o:ga
TO WEED OUT	N/A	N/A	juwá	is:ón:i.ámibáya
TO WIN	jo:lóba	jo:lóba	N/A	N/A
TO WRITE	jókóma	komá	jó:kómá	kwá:kuma
TO YAWN	N/A	N/A	jóló	teáteka
TOBACCO	N/A	N/A	ikája	bó:gólo
TODAY	lólóko	ólóko	lolókene	lolóko
TOENAIL	bos:aí.oálo.o:lo	bohái	N/A	N/A
TOMORROW	ló:βi	ló:βi.aléka.óje	lóβení.oj:é	N/A
TOOTH	lín:o / pl. baín:o	lín:o / pl. baín:o	líno	líno
TOTEM	N/A	N/A	námjatóno/ná mekíla	namé:íla
TRADITIONAL PORRIDGE	emóló	emóló	mbe:tu	N/A
TRAP	N/A	N/A	i:lónɣa	N/A
TRAP FOR SMALL ANIMALS	N/A	N/A	ló:kombo	N/A
TRAVEL (N.)	joédo / pl. ndzɔédo	loédo	N/A	N/A
TRAVELLER	bokɔɣándzédɔ	bokɔɣándzédɔ	N/A	N/A
TREE	bote	bote	boté	i.égo
TRUNK	bitfína	bitfína	N/A	bokúdo.aéko
TRUTH	só:sɔlo	hóhólo	hóló	bɔsó:lo
TURTLE	kúlu	kúlu	ɣkúlu	e.úlu
TWELVE	duómulaβípě/di ómulaβípě	duómulaβípě/d iómulaβípě	li.ómula.íφε	di.ómulaβé:pe
TWENTY	tukuíp:e:	tukuíp:e:	ntúku.íφε	túku.íp:e:

TWENTY-ONE	tukuíp:e:laém:ɔ	tukuíp:e:laém:ɔ	ntúku.íφeIemó	túku.íp:éIa.óm: ɔ:
TWENTY-THREE	tukuíp:elaβísát o:	tukuíp:elaβísát o:	ntúku.íφéIa.ihá to	túku.íp:éIa.βés :áto
TWENTY-TWO	tukuíp:e:laβípe: :	tukuíp:e:laβípe :	ntúku.íφéIa.íφe	túku.íp:éIa.βép :e:
TWIN	N/A	N/A	li.áha	ba.ása
TWO	bípe	bípe	íφe	bépe
UGLY	N/A	N/A	N/A	bosú:bu
UNCIRCUMCISED MAN	N/A	N/A	βɔIóIɔ	butútu
UNDER	nésé:a	nésé:a	ó:se	eléIosé
URINE	bisápu	bisápu	ihápo	N/A
VAGINA	Io:sóɽi	Io:sóɽi	Iohóɽi	losóIi
VALLEY	bo:ki:ɽí	bo:ki:ɽí	N/A	N/A
VEIN	bosí:ba	bohí:ba	bóhi:mbwá	bosí:βa
VILLAGE	e:sé / pl. bi:sé	e:hé / pl. bi:hé	e:hé	e:sé
VOICE	Iopóɔɔ / pl. póɔɔ	Iopóho / pl. póho	jói	bogógo
VOMIT (N.)	N/A	N/A	ndói	N/A
WALL	é:tu:tú	é:tu:tú	étutú	ep:ére
WAR	etú:ba	etú:ba	é:túmba	bít:u:ba
WASP	N/A	N/A	iháha	N/A
WATER	mási	máhi	báhi	mási
WEAK	bo:sú	bo:hú	N/A	N/A
WEAVER	botó:gi.oá.bá:tó ko	botó:gi.oá.bá:t óko	bolói	N/A
WELL (N.)	diβúɽu	diβúɽu	iyúIujáhi/ipokuj éηki.áhi	libúlu
WEST	N/A	N/A	N/A	enékamwáneɽí solála
WHAT	Iínáno	Iínáno	jombékóno	γábu.a
WHEN	mbo:gáno	Iéɽé	Iohí.ondo	Ia.íγá
WHERE	e:já	e:já	úηko	éá
WHIP	N/A	N/A	bó:β(w)ámbo	N/A
WHISPER (N.)	N/A	N/A	boηgóηγε	béɔgó.ɔgé

WHISTLE (N.)	N/A	N/A	bóngotǽí	N/A
WHITE	pé:be / boélo	pé:be / boélo	malekáni	lo.óbá
WHITE MAN	bɔndéle	bɔndéle	N/A	N/A
WHO	ú:kónɔ / moténo	ú:kónɔ / moténo	okóno	ókɔ.in:é / móto.in:é
WHOLE	N/A	N/A	bokúndu	bok:údu
WHY	ɾitǽináno	tǽiná	itǽináno	la.íné
WIND	bopépe	bopépe	bo.ó.i	bopépe
WINE	kwátuku	kwátuku	ba.ána	βa.án:a
WING	li:pa:pú	li:pa:pú	N/A	lípapó
WIZARD	N/A	N/A	bõᅇkúmũ	N/A
WOLF	lo:βóa	lo:βóa	N/A	N/A
WOMAN	boíto	boíto	be:ínto	bo.ító
WORD	líká:bo	líká:bo	mbó	N/A
WORK (N.)	bosála	bohála	bɔhálá	bosála
WORM	bɔsópi / pl. besópi	bɔhópi / pl. behópi	lo:ambwá/bɔhó ci	besóto
WRATH	N/A	N/A	mbé:ɾi	kéle
YAM	é:polé	é:polé	i:wá	épolé
YAWN (N.)	N/A	N/A	N/A	ése:ɾí
YEAR	mbú:la	mbú:la	mbúla	mbúla
YELLOW	losáká	loháká	N/A	busáka
YESTERDAY	lóβi.en:í.e:leká	lóβi.e:leká	ló:βenélekáki	lóβi
YOUNG GIRL	boíto.oálitokú	boíto.oálitokú	eβóhiβe:ínto	N/A
YOUNG MAN	bolágala	bolágala	eβóhélo:ndo	N/A
YOUNGER TWIN	N/A	N/A	mpía	pía

Appendix 2: Metadata spreadsheet associated with the 2021 fieldwork mission to Mai-Ndombe

FILENAME	lok&iko_ID_20210530_INO_01		lok&iko_ID_20210530_INO_02		lok&iko_ID_20210530_INO_03		mbo_ID_20210601_INO_01	mbo_ID_20210601_INO_02	put_ID_20210601_INO_01	put_ID_20210601_INO_02	put_ID_20210601_INO_03
DATE	30/05/2021	30/05/2021	30/05/2021	30/05/2021	30/05/2021	30/05/2021	01/06/2021	01/06/2021	01/06/2021	01/06/2021	01/06/2021
LANGUAGE	kitwa	kitwa	kitwa	kitwa	kitwa	kitwa	lotwa	lotwa	lotwa	lotwa	lotwa
INTERVIEW LANGUAGE	lingala		lingala		lingala		lingala	lingala	lingala	lingala	lingala
ORIGIN	Pumenyam	Bokomu	Pumenyam	Bokomu	Pumenyam	Bokomu	Inongo	Inongo	Indongese (sect. Bolia)	Indongese (sect. Bolia)	Indongese (sect. Bolia)
MOTHER'S ORIGIN	Nzele	Bekongu	Nzele	Bekongu	Nzele	Bekongu	Bisengi	Bisengi	Yombo (Ndongese)	Yombo (Ndongese)	Yombo (Ndongese)
FATHER'S ORIGIN	Pumenyam	Bokomu	Pumenyam	Bokomu	Pumenyam	Bokomu	Bisengi	Bisengi	Bolingo	Bolingo	Bolingo
AGE	60	58	60	58	60	58	47	47	26	26	26
SPEAKER	Ikoli	Lokengi	Ikoli	Lokengi	Ikoli	Lokengi	Mboketu	Mboketu	Putela	Putela	Putela
TOPIC	general introduction		general introduction		general introduction		ideophones	ideophones	ideophones	ideophones	ideophones
COORDINATES	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"
LOCATION	INO		INO		INO		INO	INO	INO	INO	INO
INVESTIGATOR	JD and LM		JD and LM		JD and LM		JD and LM	JD and LM	JD and LM	JD and LM	JD and LM
RECORDER	Z		Z		R		R	Z	R	R	Z
MIC	built-in		built-in		built-in		clip-on	built-in	clip-on	clip-on	clip-on
SAMPLING RATE	44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s
INPUT MAX	75%		75%		75%		75%	75%	75%	75%	75%
FORMAT	wav		wav		wav		wav	wav	wav	wav	wav
DEPTH	24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit
SIGNAL	stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo
RECORDING SPACE	open air, under a porch		open air, under a porch		open air, under a porch		open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree
NOTES	retroflex /d/?		retroflex /d/?		retroflex /d/?		paralinguistic clicks	paralinguistic clicks	breathy vowels? nasal vowels?	breathy vowels? nasal vowels?	breathy vowels? nasal vowels?
RECORDING SESSION	INO1		INO1		INO1		INO2	INO2	INO3	INO2	INO3

jac_ID_20210602_I_NO_04	jac_ID_20210602_I_NO_01	jac_ID_20210602_I_NO_03	jac_ID_20210602_I_NO_02	jac_ID_20210602_I_NO_01	mpu_ID_20210601_I_NO_01	baw_ID_20210601_I_NO_02	baw_ID_20210601_I_NO_01	ese_ID_20210601_I_NO_02	ese_ID_20210601_I_NO_01	bit_ID_20210601_I_NO_02	bit_ID_20210601_I_NO_01
02/06/2021	02/06/2021	02/06/2021	02/06/2021	02/06/2021	01/06/2021	01/06/2021	01/06/2021	01/06/2021	01/06/2021	01/06/2021	01/06/2021
lotwa/lolia	lotwa/lolia	lotwa/lolia	lotwa/lolia	lotwa/lolia	lotwa	lotwa	lotwa	lotwa	lotwa	lotwa	lotwa
french	french	french	french	french	french	lingala	lingala	lingala	lingala	lingala	lingala
Bolla	Bolla	Bolla	Bolla	Bolla	Pendjwa	Bolingo	Bolingo	Pendjwa	Pendjwa	Beronge	Beronge
Bolla	Bolla	Bolla	Bolla	Bolla	Pendjwa	Bolingo	Bolingo	Pendjwa	Pendjwa	Beronge	Beronge
Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Pendjwa	Bolingo	Bolingo	Pendjwa	Pendjwa	Beronge	Beronge
33	33	33	33	33	37	53	53	52	52	30	30
Bokolo Ewanzala Jacques	Bokolo Ewanzala Jacques	Bokolo Ewanzala Jacques	Bokolo Ewanzala Jacques	Bokolo Ewanzala Jacques	Mputu Luba	Bawi Sieli Bernard	Bawi Sieli Bernard	Eseka	Eseka	Bitumba	Bitumba
wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	ideophones	ideophones	ideophones	ideophones	ideophones	ideophones
S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5" E	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5" E	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5" E	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5" E	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5" E	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5" E	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5" E	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5" E	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5" E			
INO	INO	INO	INO	INO	INO	INO	INO	INO	INO	INO	INO
JD and LM	LM and JD	JD and LM	JD and LM	LM and JD	LM and JD	JD and LM	JD and LM	JD and LM	JD and LM	JD and LM	JD and LM
R	Z	Z	Z	R	R	Z	R	Z	R	Z	R
clip-on	built-in	built-in	built-in	clip-on	clip-on	built-in	clip-on	built-in	clip-on	built-in	clip-on
44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s
75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%
wav	wav	wav	wav	wav	wav	wav	wav	wav	wav	wav	wav
24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit
stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo
open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree			
it is unclear whether this is lolia, lotwa na lolia, or what the difference between	it is unclear whether this is lolia, lotwa na lolia, or what the difference between	it is unclear whether this is lolia, lotwa na lolia, or what the difference between	it is unclear whether this is lolia, lotwa na lolia, or what the difference between	retroflex /d/ as variant of /l/?	retroflex /d/ as variant of /l/?	implosives for elephant and big animals; fricative lateral?	implosives for elephant and big animals; fricative lateral?	breathiness, creakiness, nasalisation	breathiness, creakiness, nasalisation	nasal vowels?	nasal vowels?
INO12	INO10	INO9	INO8	INO7	INO7	INO6	INO6	INO5	INO5	INO4	INO4

pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_09	pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_08	pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_07	pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_06	pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_05	pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_04	pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_03
05/06/2021	05/06/2021	05/06/2021	05/06/2021	05/06/2021	05/06/2021	05/06/2021
lotwa/lokonda						
french						
Lioke (Pendjwa)	Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)	Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)	Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)
Lioke (Pendjwa)	Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)	Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)	Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)
Lioke (Pendjwa)	Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)	Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)	Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)
43	51	43	51	43	51	43
Louis	Patrick	Louis	Patrick	Louis	Patrick	Louis
wordlist						
S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"						
INO						
LM and JD						
R	Z	R	Z	R	Z	R
clip-on	built-in	clip-on	built-in	clip-on	built-in	clip-on
44 kHz/s						
75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%
wav						
24 bit						
stereo						
open air						
two varieties of "lotwa"						
INO19	INO18	INO18	INO17	INO17	INO16	INO16

pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_15		05/06/2021		pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_14		05/06/2021		pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_13		05/06/2021		pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_12		05/06/2021		pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_11		05/06/2021		pat&iou_LM_20210605_INO_10	
lotwa/lokonda	lotwa/lokonda																				
french		french		french		french		french		french		french		french		french		french		french	
Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)																				
Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)																				
Pendjwa	Lioke (Pendjwa)																				
51	43	51	43	51	43	51	43	51	43	51	43	51	43	51	43	51	43	51	43	51	43
Patrick	Louis																				
wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist	
S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	
INO		INO		INO		INO		INO		INO		INO		INO		INO		INO		INO	
LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD	
R		Z		R		Z		R		Z		R		Z		R		Z		R	
clip-on		built-in		clip-on		built-in		clip-on		built-in		clip-on		built-in		clip-on		built-in		clip-on	
44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s	
75%		75%		75%		75%		75%		75%		75%		75%		75%		75%		75%	
wav		wav		wav		wav		wav		wav		wav		wav		wav		wav		wav	
24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit	
stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo	
closed room		open air																			
two varieties of "lotwa"		two varieties of "lotwa"		two varieties of "lotwa"		two varieties of "lotwa"		two varieties of "lotwa"		two varieties of "lotwa"		two varieties of "lotwa"		two varieties of "lotwa"		two varieties of "lotwa"		two varieties of "lotwa"		two varieties of "lotwa"	
INO22		INO21		INO21		INO21		INO21		INO20		INO19									

psl_ID_20210606_1 NO_01	06/06/2021	lotwa/osenge	lingala	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	JD and LM	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	songs and chants	INO99
pbl_ID_20210606_1 INO_02	06/06/2021	lotwa	lingala	Terr. Bikoro	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	JD and LM	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Twa variety from Bikoro	INO37
pkl_ID_20210606_1 NO_03	06/06/2021	lotwa	lingala	Terr. Kiri	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	JD and LM	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Twa variety from Kiri	INO36
pkl_ID_20210606_1 NO_02	06/06/2021	lotwa	lingala	Terr. Kiri	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	JD and LM	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Twa variety from Kiri	INO35
pkl_ID_20210606_1 NO_01	06/06/2021	lotwa	lingala	Terr. Kiri	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	JD and LM	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Twa variety from Kiri	INO34
pol_ID_20210606_1 INO_03	06/06/2021	lotwa/osenge	lingala	Terr. Oshwe	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	JD and LM	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Twa variety from Oshwe	INO33
pol_ID_20210606_1 INO_02	06/06/2021	lotwa/osenge	lingala	Terr. Oshwe	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	JD and LM	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Twa variety from Oshwe	INO32
pol_ID_20210606_1 INO_01	06/06/2021	lotwa/osenge	lingala	Terr. Oshwe	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	JD and LM	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Twa variety from Oshwe	INO31
ise_LM_20210606_1 INO_13	06/06/2021	sakata	french	Motangili (Kutu)	Koku (Kutu)	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	LM and JD	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Lvs, odd vowel system	INO30
ise_LM_20210606_1 INO_12	06/06/2021	sakata	french	Motangili (Kutu)	Koku (Kutu)	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	LM and JD	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Lvs, odd vowel system	INO29a
ise_LM_20210606_1 INO_11	06/06/2021	sakata	french	Motangili (Kutu)	Koku (Kutu)	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	LM and JD	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Lvs, odd vowel system	INO29a/b
ise_LM_20210606_1 INO_10	06/06/2021	sakata	french	Motangili (Kutu)	Koku (Kutu)	N/A	N/A	N/A	INO	LM and JD	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	Lvs, odd vowel system	INO28

lio_ID_20210608_J NO_02	08/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	french	Bisengi	Bisengi	Bisengi	45	Liongolo Bando	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	kitwa variety from Oshwe	INO49	INO40
lio_ID_20210608_J NO_01	08/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	french	Bisengi	Bisengi	Bisengi	45	Liongolo Bando	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	R	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	kitwa variety from Oshwe	INO49	INO40
lio_ID_20210607_J NO_02	07/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	french	Bisengi	Bisengi	Bisengi	45	Liongolo Bando	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	kitwa variety from Oshwe	INO48	INO40
lio_ID_20210607_J NO_01	07/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	french	Bisengi	Bisengi	Bisengi	45	Liongolo Bando	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	R	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	kitwa variety from Oshwe	INO48	INO40
lio_ID_20210606_J NO_02	06/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	french	Bisengi	Bisengi	Bisengi	45	Liongolo Bando	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	kitwa variety from Oshwe	INO47	INO40
lio_ID_20210606_J NO_01	06/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	french	Bisengi	Bisengi	Bisengi	45	Liongolo Bando	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	R	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	kitwa variety from Oshwe	INO47	INO40
psi_ID_20210606_J NO_08	06/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	lingala	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	PAs in Inongo	songs	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	songs and chants	INO46	INO40
psi_ID_20210606_J NO_07	06/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	lingala	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	PAs in Inongo	songs	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	songs and chants	INO45	INO40
psi_ID_20210606_J NO_06	06/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	lingala	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	PAs in Inongo	songs	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	songs and chants	INO44	INO40
psi_ID_20210606_J NO_05	06/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	lingala	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	PAs in Inongo	songs	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	songs and chants	INO43	INO40
psi_ID_20210606_J NO_04	06/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	lingala	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	PAs in Inongo	songs	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	songs and chants	INO42	INO40
psi_ID_20210606_J NO_03	06/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	lingala	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	PAs in Inongo	songs	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	songs and chants	INO41	INO40
psi_ID_20210606_J NO_02	06/06/2021	lotwa/losenge	lingala	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	PAs in Inongo	songs	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD and LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	songs and chants	INO40	INO40

nga_LM_20210609_INO_05	nga_LM_20210609_INO_04	nga_LM_20210609_INO_03	nga_LM_20210609_INO_02	nga_LM_20210609_INO_01	pat_LM_20210609_INO_03	pat_LM_20210609_INO_02	pat_LM_20210609_INO_01	pat_LM_20210608_INO_02	pat_LM_20210608_INO_01	lio_ID_20210608_INO_04	lio_ID_20210608_INO_03
09/06/2021	09/06/2021	09/06/2021	09/06/2021	09/06/2021	09/06/2021	09/06/2021	09/06/2021	08/06/2021	08/06/2021	08/06/2021	08/06/2021
lotwa/losenge	lotwa/losenge	lotwa/losenge	lotwa/losenge	lotwa/lokonda	lotwa/lokonda	lotwa/lokonda	lotwa/lokonda	lotwa/lokonda	lotwa/lokonda	lotwa/losenge	lotwa/losenge
french	french	french	french	french							
Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Pendjwa	Pendjwa	Pendjwa	Pendjwa	Pendjwa	Pendjwa	Bisenji	Bisenji
Beronge	Pendjwa	Pendjwa	Bisenji	Bisenji							
Beronge	Pendjwa	Pendjwa	Bisenji	Bisenji							
21	21	21	21	21	51	51	51	51	51	45	45
Mbo Bankoto Ngala	Patrick	Patrick	Patrick	Patrick	Patrick	Liongolo Bandio	Liongolo Bandio				
wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	sentences	sentences	sentences	sentences	sentences	wordlist	wordlist
S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6"E 018°16'45.5"							
INO	INO	INO	INO	INO							
LM	LM	LM	LM	LM	LM and LM	LM and ID	LM and ID	LM and ID	LM and ID	ID and LM	ID and LM
R	E	R	E	Z	Z	Z	Z	Z	Z	Z	R
clip-on	built-in	clip-on	built-in	built-in	built-in	built-in	built-in	built-in	built-in	built-in	clip-on
44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s							
75%	not-verified	75%	not-verified	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%
wav	wav	wav	wav	wav							
24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit							
stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo							
open air, under a porch	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree						
twa variety spoken in the Oshwe territory	lotwa from Kir/Pendjwa	lotwa from Kir/Pendjwa	kitwa variety from Oshwe	kitwa variety from Oshwe							
INO59	INO58	INO58	INO57	INO57	INO55	INO54	INO53	INO52	INO51	INO50	INO50

bob_LM_20210609_INO_05		bob_LM_20210609_INO_04			
09/06/2021		09/06/2021			
bobangi		bobangi			
french		french			
Bolobo	Boyanga	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Kinshasa	Bolobo
Bolobo	Boyanga	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Bolobo	Bolobo
Bolobo	Boyanga	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Bolobo	Bolobo
42	34	37	35	58	34
Nyense Niga Mbangi	Makalia Endemboli Jean	Bolia Bolungwa Gaylain	Bekanga Mateta Constantine	Mbombo Nkasa idlephone	Bosanz Léa
wordlist		wordlist		wordlist	
S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	
INO		INO		INO	
LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD	
Z		Z		E	
built-in		built-in		built-in	
44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s	
75%		not verified		not verified	
wav		wav		wav	
24 bit		24 bit		24 bit	
stereo		stereo		stereo	
open air, at 26 Provinces		open air, at 26 Provinces		open air, at 26 Provinces	
they call their language bobangi		they call their language bobangi		they call their language bobangi	
INO68		INO67		INO67	

bob_LM_20210609_INO_07		bob_LM_20210609_INO_06							
09/06/2021		09/06/2021							
bobangi		bobangi							
french		french							
Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Kinshasa	Bolobo	Bolobo	
Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	
Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	
34	37	35	34	37	35	58	34	36	
Makalia Endemboli Jesh	Bolia Bolungwa Goyain	Bekanga Mateta Constantine	Makalia Endemboli Jesh	Bolia Bolungwa Goyain	Bekanga Mateta Constantine	Mhembo Nikasa Idiphense	Bosanzi Léa	Ngesi Eomba	
wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist	
5 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		5 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		5 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		5 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		5 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	
INO		INO		INO		INO		INO	
LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD		LM and JD	
Z		Z		Z		Z		Z	
built-in		built-in		built-in		built-in		built-in	
44 khz/s		44 khz/s		44 khz/s		44 khz/s		44 khz/s	
75%		75%		75%		75%		75%	
wav		wav		wav		wav		wav	
24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit	
stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo	
open air, at 26 Provinces		open air, at 26 Provinces		open air, at 26 Provinces		open air, at 26 Provinces		open air, at 26 Provinces	
they call their language bobangi		they call their language bobangi		they call their language bobangi		they call their language bobangi		they call their language bobangi	
INO69		INO69		INO69		INO69		INO69	

bol_LM_20210610 _INO_03	bol_LM_20210610 _INO_01	bob_LM_20210609_INO_08	
10/06/2021	10/06/2021	09/06/2021	
lontomba	lontomba	lontomba	bobangi
french	french	french	french
Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Boyanga
Inongo (Ntomba)	Inongo (Ntomba)	Inongo (Ntomba)	Boyanga
Ngembo (Bolia)	Ngembo (Bolia)	Ngembo (Bolia)	Boyanga
73	73	73	34
Bolia Alphonse	Bolia Alphonse	Bolia Alphonse	Makalia Endemboli Jean
wordlist	general introduction	general introduction	wordlist
S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"
INO	INO	INO	INO
LM	LM	LM	LM and ID
R	Z	R	E
clip-on	built-in	clip-on	built-in
44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s
75%	75%	75%	not verified
wav	wav	wav	wav
24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit
stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo
open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, under a tree	open air, at 26 Provinces
bilingual Iolia and lontomba	bilingual Iolia and lontomba	bilingual Iolia and lontomba	they call their language bobangi
INO71	INO70	INO70	INO69

glo_ID_20210610_INO_04	10/06/2021	sakata (Mbamushie)	french	Semendwa	Semendwa	Semendwa	22	Abbé Glodine	wordlist	INO	LM	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	LVS (voiced and voiceless stops and nasals), ndrondroza, etc	INO79
glo_ID_20210610_INO_03	10/06/2021	sakata (Mbamushie)	french	Semendwa	Semendwa	Semendwa	22	Abbé Glodine	wordlist	INO	LM	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	LVS (voiced and voiceless stops and nasals), ndrondroza, etc	INO78
glo_ID_20210610_INO_02	10/06/2021	sakata (Mbamushie)	french	Semendwa	Semendwa	Semendwa	22	Abbé Glodine	wordlist	INO	LM	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	LVS (voiced and voiceless stops and nasals), ndrondroza, etc	INO77
glo_ID_20210610_INO_01	10/06/2021	sakata (Mbamushie)	french	Semendwa	Semendwa	Semendwa	22	Abbé Glodine	wordlist	INO	LM	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	LVS (voiced and voiceless stops and nasals), ndrondroza, etc	INO76
glo_ID_20210610_INO_03	10/06/2021	sakata (Mbamushie)	french	Semendwa	Semendwa	Semendwa	22	Abbé Glodine	short story and sentences	INO	LM	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	LVS (voiced and voiceless stops and nasals), ndrondroza, etc	INO75
glo_ID_20210610_INO_03	10/06/2021	sakata (Mbamushie)	french	Semendwa	Semendwa	Semendwa	22	Abbé Glodine	short story and sentences	INO	LM	R	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	LVS (voiced and voiceless stops and nasals), ndrondroza, etc	INO75
glo_ID_20210610_INO_02	10/06/2021	sakata (Mbamushie)	french	Semendwa	Semendwa	Semendwa	22	Abbé Glodine	sound-specific elicitation	INO	LM	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	LVS (voiced and voiceless stops and nasals), ndrondroza, etc	INO74
glo_ID_20210610_INO_01	10/06/2021	sakata (Mbamushie)	french	Semendwa	Semendwa	Semendwa	22	Abbé Glodine	sound-specific elicitation	INO	LM	R	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	LVS (voiced and voiceless stops and nasals), ndrondroza, etc	INO74
jac_ID_20210610_INO_04	10/06/2021	lotwa/lolia	french	Bolla	Bolla	Inongo	33	Bokolo Ewanzala Jacques	wordlist	INO	LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	it is unclear whether this is lolia, lotwa na lolia, or what the difference between	INO73
jac_ID_20210610_INO_03	10/06/2021	lotwa/lolia	french	Bolla	Bolla	Inongo	33	Bokolo Ewanzala Jacques	wordlist	INO	LM	R	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	it is unclear whether this is lolia, lotwa na lolia, or what the difference between	INO73
jac_ID_20210610_INO_02	10/06/2021	lotwa/lolia	french	Bolla	Bolla	Inongo	33	Bokolo Ewanzala Jacques	wordlist	INO	LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	it is unclear whether this is lolia, lotwa na lolia, or what the difference between	INO72
jac_ID_20210610_INO_01	10/06/2021	lotwa/lolia	french	Bolla	Bolla	Inongo	33	Bokolo Ewanzala Jacques	wordlist	INO	LM	R	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	it is unclear whether this is lolia, lotwa na lolia, or what the difference between	INO72
bol_ID_20210610_INO_04	10/06/2021	lontomba	french	Inongo	Inongo	Ngembou (Bolla)	73	Bola Alphonse	wordlist	INO	LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	bilingual lolia and lontomba	INO71

bob_LM_20210610_INO_03		bob_LM_20210610_INO_02		bob_LM_20210610_INO_01		eI_LM_20210610_INO_01	
10/06/2021		10/06/2021		10/06/2021		10/06/2021	
bobangi		bobangi		bobangi		lotwa/lokonda	
french		french		french		french	
Iyumbi	Kinshasa	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Kinshasa	Iyumbi	Mpendjwa
Iyumbi	Bolobo	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Bolobo	Iyumbi	Mpendjwa
Iyumbi	Bolobo	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Bolobo	Iyumbi	Mpendjwa
37	58	34	37	37	58	35	29
Bolia Bolungwa Guyain	Mbembo Nkasa Iidiphonse	Makalia Endimboli Jean	Bolia Bolungwa Guyain	Bekanga Mateta Constantine	Mbembo Nkasa Iidiphonse	Bekanga Mateta Constantine	Elise
wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		songs	
S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"		S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	
INO		INO		INO		INO	
LM		LM		LM		LM	
E		E		E		Z	
built-in		built-in		built-in		built-in	
44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s	
not verified		not verified		not verified		75%	
wav		wav		wav		wav	
24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit	
stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo	
open air		open air		open air		open air	
they call their language bobangi		they call their language bobangi		they call their language bobangi		Bantu and Batwa songs	
INO83		INO82		INO81		INO80	

bob_LM_20210610_INO_05	bob_LM_20210610_INO_04											
10/06/2021	10/06/2021											
bobangi	bobangi											
french	french											
Iyumbi	Kinshasa	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Kinshasa	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Boyanga
Iyumbi	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Boyanga
Iyumbi	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Bolobbo	Boyanga
35	58	34	36	34	37	35	58	34	36	42	34	
Behanga Mateta Constantine	Mhembo Niasa Ildephense	Bosanzi Léa	Nigeli Eomba	Makalia Endemboli Jean	Bola Bolungwa Guyain	Behanga Mateta Constantine	Mhembo Niasa Ildephense	Bosanzi Léa	Nigeli Eomba	Nyense Nga Mbabangi	Makalia Endemboli Jean	
wordlist	wordlist											
S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"											
INO	INO											
LM	LM											
E	E											
built-in	built-in											
44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s											
not verified	not verified											
wav	wav											
24 bit	24 bit											
stereo	stereo											
open air	open air											
they call their language bobangi	they call their language bobangi											
INO85	INO84											

ped_ID_20210610 _INO_01	bob_LM_20210610_INO_06												
10/06/2021	10/06/2021												
sengele	bobangi												
french	french												
Mbalo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Kinshasa	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Iyumbi	Iyumbi
Mbalo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Iyumbi	Iyumbi
Mbalo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Boyanga	Iyumbi	Iyumbi	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Bolobo	Iyumbi	Iyumbi
52	34	36	42	34	34	37	35	58	34	36	42	34	37
Mpeti Pedro	Bosnzi Léa	Ngeli Emba	Nyansé Nga Mbangi	Makalia Endemboli Jean	Bolia Bolungwa Guyann	Belanga Meteta Constantine	Mbembé Nkasa Idiophone	Bosnzi Léa	Ngeli Emba	Nyansé Nga Mbangi	Makalia Endemboli Jean	Bolia Bolungwa Guyann	37
wordlist	wordlist												
S 01°55'31.6" E 048°16'45.5"	S 01°55'31.6" E 048°16'45.5"												
INO	INO												
JD	LM												
Z	E												
built-in	built-in												
44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s												
75%	not verified												
wav	wav												
24 bit	24 bit												
stereo	stereo												
open air, under a tree	open air												
Sengele de Mbalo	they call their language bobangi												
INO87	INO86												

ban_ID_20210611_INO_08	11/06/2021	lolendo	french	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	60	Banango Natuya	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	N/A	INO117	INO107
ban_ID_20210611_INO_07	11/06/2021	lolendo	french	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	60	Banango Natuya	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	N/A	INO116	INO108
ban_ID_20210611_INO_06	11/06/2021	lolendo	french	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	60	Banango Natuya	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	N/A	INO115	INO109
ban_ID_20210611_INO_05	11/06/2021	lolendo	french	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	60	Banango Natuya	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	N/A	INO114	INO108
ban_ID_20210611_INO_04	11/06/2021	lolendo	french	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	60	Banango Natuya	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	N/A	INO113	INO108
ban_ID_20210611_INO_03	11/06/2021	lolendo	french	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	60	Banango Natuya	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	N/A	INO112	INO108
ban_ID_20210611_INO_02	11/06/2021	lolendo	french	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	60	Banango Natuya	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	N/A	INO111	INO108
ban_ID_20210611_INO_01	11/06/2021	lolendo	french	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	Lokolama	60	Banango Natuya	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	JD	E	built-in	44 kHz/s	not verified	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a porch	N/A	INO110	INO108
bol_LM_20210611_INO_18	11/06/2021	lontomba	french	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	73	Bola Alphonse	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	lingual lola and lontomba	INO109	INO108
bol_LM_20210611_INO_17	11/06/2021	lontomba	french	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	73	Bola Alphonse	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	LM	R	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	lingual lola and lontomba	INO109	INO108
bol_LM_20210611_INO_16	11/06/2021	lontomba	french	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	73	Bola Alphonse	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	lingual lola and lontomba	INO108	INO108
bol_LM_20210611_INO_15	11/06/2021	lontomba	french	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	73	Bola Alphonse	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	LM	R	clip-on	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	lingual lola and lontomba	INO108	INO108
bol_LM_20210611_INO_14	11/06/2021	lontomba	french	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	Inongo	73	Bola Alphonse	wordlist	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	INO	LM	Z	built-in	44 kHz/s	75%	wav	24 bit	stereo	open air, under a tree	lingual lola and lontomba	INO107	INO107

gll_LM_20210620_NIO_02	20/06/2021	mpe	english/french		vis_ID_20210611_J_NO_01	vis_ID_20210611_J_NO_02	vis_ID_20210611_J_NO_03	vis_ID_20210611_J_NO_04	vis_ID_20210611_J_NO_05	gll_LM_20210620_NIO_01	vis_ID_20210611_J_NO_01	mar_LM_20210611_J_NO_01	ped_LM_20210611_J_NO_03	ped_LM_20210611_J_NO_02	ped_LM_20210611_J_NO_01	ban_ID_20210611_J_NO_10	ban_ID_20210611_J_NO_09
					11/06/2021	11/06/2021	11/06/2021	11/06/2021	11/06/2021	20/06/2021	11/06/2021	11/06/2021	11/06/2021	11/06/2021	11/06/2021	11/06/2021	11/06/2021
					lwele	lwele	lwele	lwele	lwele	mpe	lwele	lotwa/ontomba	sengele	sengele	sengele	lolendo	lolendo
					french	french	french	french	french	english/french	french	french	french	french	french	lolendo	lolendo
					Matu (Sedzo)	Iba/Bampe	Matu (Sedzo)	Bobangi	Mbelo	Mbelo	Mbelo	Lokolama	Lokolama				
					Matu (Sedzo)	Iba/Bampe	Matu (Sedzo)	Bobangi	Mbelo	Mbelo	Mbelo	Lokolama	Lokolama				
					Maboko Nzeke (Sedzo)	Badia	Maboko Nzeke (Sedzo)	Bobangi	Mbelo	Mbelo	Mbelo	Lokolama	Lokolama				
					62	62	62	62	62	49	62	47	52	52	52	60	60
					Clovis Lutondo Misuk	Gilles Yolo Mpotso	Clovis Lutondo Misuk	Ilanga Mara	Mipeti Pedro	Mipeti Pedro	Mipeti Pedro	Banango Natuya	Banango Natuya				
					wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	Sarah Greene's questionnaire	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	sentences	sentences
					S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 01°55'31.6" E 018°16'45.5"										
					INO	INO	INO	INO	INO	NIO	INO						
					JD	JD	JD	JD	JD	LM & JD	JD	LM	LM	LM	LM	JD	JD
					Z	Z	Z	Z	Z	R	Z	R	R	R	R	E	E
					built-in	built-in	built-in	built-in	built-in	clip-on	built-in	clip-on	clip-on	clip-on	clip-on	built-in	built-in
					44 kHz/s												
					75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	not verified	not verified
					wav												
					24 bit												
					stereo												
					inside, in the living room	open air, under a porch											
					Sarah	Sarah	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Sengele de Mbelo	Sengele de Mbelo	Sengele de Mbelo	Sengele de Mbelo	N/A	N/A
					NIO1	NIO1	INO127	INO126	INO125	INO124	INO123	INO122	INO121	INO120	INO119	INO118	INO118

sak_LM_20210622_NIO_02				sak_LM_20210622_NIO_01				gll_LM_20210620_NIO_07		gll_LM_20210620_NIO_06		gll_LM_20210620_NIO_05		gll_LM_20210620_NIO_04		gll_LM_20210620_NIO_03															
22/06/2021				22/06/2021				20/06/2021		20/06/2021		20/06/2021		20/06/2021		20/06/2021															
sakata (Mabie/Kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/Kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (Mabie/Kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/Kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	mpe	mpe	mpe	mpe	mpe	mpe	mpe	mpe	mpe															
french								english/french																							
Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe															
Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe	iba/Bampe															
Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Badia	Badia	Badia	Badia	Badia	Badia	Badia	Badia	Badia															
52	52	52	49	52	52	52	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49															
Moke Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Datus	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Moke Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Datus	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto															
general interview								Eugene Chan's questionnaire /								Sarah Greene's questionnaire															
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"								S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"								S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"															
NIO								NIO								NIO															
LM & JD								LM & JD								LM & JD															
E								Z								Z															
built-in								built-in								clip-on															
44 kHz/s								44 kHz/s								44 kHz/s															
not verified								75%								75%															
wav								wav								wav															
24 bit								24 bit								24 bit															
stereo								stereo								stereo															
inside, in the living room								inside, in the living room								inside, in the living room															
comparative Sakata data								comparative Sakata data								Sarah															
NIO5								NIO5								NIO3								NIO2							

sak_LM_20210622_NIO_06	sak_LM_20210622_NIO_05	sak_LM_20210622_NIO_04	sak_LM_20210622_NIO_03
22/06/2021	22/06/2021	22/06/2021	22/06/2021
sakata (kibal)	sakata (kibal)	sakata (kibal)	sakata (kibal)
sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)
sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)
sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Mabie/kingingele)
french	french	french	french
Tolo	Tolo	Tolo	Tolo
Vuna	Vuna	Vuna	Vuna
Boku	Boku	Boku	Boku
49	49	49	49
Beseuku Monkaja Ila Rocky			
wordlist	wordlist	wordlist	wordlist
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"			
NIO	NIO	NIO	NIO
LM & JD	LM & JD	LM & JD	LM & JD
E	Z	E	Z
built-in	built-in	built-in	built-in
44 khz/s	44 khz/s	44 khz/s	44 khz/s
not verified	75%	not verified	75%
wav	wav	wav	wav
24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit
stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo
inside, in the living room			
comparative Sakata data	comparative Sakata data	comparative Sakata data	comparative Sakata data
NIO7	NIO7	NIO6	NIO6

sak_LM_20210622_NIO_09		sak_LM_20210622_NIO_08					sak_LM_20210622_NIO_07					
22/06/2021		22/06/2021					22/06/2021					
sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (Mable/kingingele)	sakata (Lernwia Nord/kinginga)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (Mable/kingingele)	sakata (Lernwia Nord/kinginga)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (Mable/kingingele)	sakata (Lernwia Nord/kinginga)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)
french												
Nioki	Tolo	Mongobele	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Mongobele	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Mongobele	Nioki	Nioki
Mpanza	Vuna	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza
Kesekenda	Boku	Dwakumbé	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Dwakumbé	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Dwakumbé	Kilima	Kesekenda
52	49	52	52	52	49	52	52	52	49	52	52	52
Bopila Mbalela Fredy	Besevuku Monheja Ila Rocky	Molie Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbalela Fredy	Besevuku Monheja Ila Rocky	Molie Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbalela Fredy	Besevuku Monheja Ila Rocky	Molie Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbalela Fredy
wordlist												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
LM & JD												
Z												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
75%												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO9												
wordlist												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
LM & JD												
E												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
not verified												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO8												
wordlist												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
LM & JD												
Z												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
75%												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO8												

sak_LM_20210622_NIO_12				sak_LM_20210622_NIO_11				sak_LM_20210622_NIO_10					
22/06/2021				22/06/2021				22/06/2021					
sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	french	sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)
Nioki	Mpanza	Tolo	french	Mongobele	Nioki	Mpanza	Tolo	Mongobele	Nioki	Mpanza	Tolo	Mongobele	Nioki
Mushiemini	Keselenda	Vuna	french	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Vuna	Vuna	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Vuna	Vuna	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini
Kilima	Boku	Boku	french	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Boku	Boku	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Boku	Boku	Dwakumbe	Kilima
52	49	49	french	52	52	49	49	52	52	49	49	52	52
Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	french	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius
Eugene Chan's questionnaire / numerals				Eugene Chan's questionnaire / numerals				wordlist					
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"				S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"				S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"					
NIO				NIO				NIO					
LM & JD				LM & JD				LM & JD					
E				Z				E					
built-in				built-in				built-in					
44 kHz/s				44 kHz/s				44 kHz/s					
not verified				75%				not verified					
wav				wav				wav					
24 bit				24 bit				24 bit					
stereo				stereo				stereo					
inside, in the living room				inside, in the living room				inside, in the living room					
Eugene				Eugene				comparative Sakata data					
NIO10				NIO10				NIO9					

sak_LM_20210622_NIO_15					sak_LM_20210622_NIO_14					sak_LM_20210622_NIO_13					
22/06/2021					22/06/2021					22/06/2021					
sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kiba)	sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kiba)	sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kiba)	sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kiba)
french															
Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo
Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna
Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku
52	52	52	49	52	52	52	49	52	52	52	49	52	52	52	49
Moke Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky	Moke Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky	Moke Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky	Moke Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky
sound-specific elicitation (labial-velar)															
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"															
NIO															
LM & JD															
Z															
built-in															
44 kHz/s															
75%															
wav															
24 bit															
stereo															
inside, in the living room															
comparative Sakata data (labial-velar)															
NIO12															
wordlist															
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"															
NIO															
LM & JD															
Z															
built-in															
44 kHz/s															
75%															
wav															
24 bit															
stereo															
inside, in the living room															
comparative Sakata data															
NIO11															
wordlist															
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"															
NIO															
LM & JD															
Z															
built-in															
44 kHz/s															
75%															
wav															
24 bit															
stereo															
inside, in the living room															
comparative Sakata data															
NIO11															

bmn_LM_20210624_NIO_04		bmn_LM_20210624_NIO_03			
24/06/2021		24/06/2021			
mpe	nunu	boma	nunu	boma	nunu
french					
liba/Bampe	Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mushie	Iba/Bampe
liba/Bampe	Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mushie	Iba/Bampe
Badia	Bopapa	Mushie	Izono	Mushie	Badia
49	36	50	37	50	49
Gilles Iyolo Mipoto	Mputu Kabakuni	Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-René	Mpia Mokutu Lenoir	Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-René	Gilles Iyolo Mipoto
wordlist					
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"					
NIO					
LM & JD					
E					
built-in					
44 kHz/s					
not verified					
wav					
24 bit					
stereo					
inside, in the living room					
comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mipe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data					
NIO22					

bmn_LM_20210624_NIO_03		bmn_LM_20210624_NIO_04			
24/06/2021		24/06/2021			
mpe	nunu	boma	nunu	boma	nunu
french					
liba/Bampe	Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mushie	Iba/Bampe
liba/Bampe	Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mushie	Iba/Bampe
Badia	Bopapa	Mushie	Izono	Mushie	Badia
49	36	50	37	50	49
Gilles Iyolo Mipoto	Mputu Kabakuni	Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-René	Mpia Mokutu Lenoir	Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-René	Gilles Iyolo Mipoto
wordlist					
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"					
NIO					
LM & JD					
Z					
built-in					
44 kHz/s					
75%					
wav					
24 bit					
stereo					
inside, in the living room					
comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mipe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data					
NIO22					

bmn_lm_20210624_NIO_07		bmn_lm_20210624_NIO_06		bmn_lm_20210624_NIO_05			
24/06/2021		24/06/2021		24/06/2021			
boma		boma		boma			
mpe		nunu		mpe			
nunu		boma		nunu			
boma		boma		boma			
french		french		french			
Mushie	Bobala	Mbali	Mbali	Mushie	Bobala	Mushie	Mbali
Mushie	Bobala	Mbali	Mbali	Mushie	Bobala	Mushie	Mbali
Mushie	Izono	Izana	Izana	Mushie	Izono	Mushie	Izana
50	37	35	35	50	37	50	35
Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-René	Mpia Mokutu Lendri	Mputu Ikwembe Tresor	Mputu Ikwembe Tresor	Gilles Iyolo Mipoto	Mpia Mokutu Lendri	Gilles Iyolo Mipoto	Mputu Ikwembe Tresor
wordlist		wordlist		wordlist		wordlist	
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"		S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"		S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"		S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	
NIO		NIO		NIO		NIO	
LM & JD		LM & JD		LM & JD		LM & JD	
Z		E		Z		Z	
built-in		built-in		built-in		built-in	
44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s	
75%		not verified		75%		75%	
wav		wav		wav		wav	
24 bit		24 bit		24 bit		24 bit	
stereo		stereo		stereo		stereo	
inside, in the living room		inside, in the living room		inside, in the living room		inside, in the living room	
comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data		comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data		comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data		comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data	
NIO24		NIO23		NIO23		NIO23	

bmm_lm_20210624_NIO_10	bmm_lm_20210624_NIO_09	bmm_lm_20210624_NIO_08
24/06/2021	24/06/2021	24/06/2021
boma	mpe nuu boma	mpe nuu boma
french	french	french
Mbali	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mushie Bobala Mbali	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mushie Bobala Mbali
Mbali	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mushie Bobala Mbali	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mushie Bobala Mbali
Izana	Badia Bopapa Mushie Izone Izana	Badia Bopapa Mushie Izone Izana
35	49 36 50 37 35	49 36 50 37 35
Mputu Iliwebe Tresor	Gilles Iyolo Mpotu Mputu Kebakuni Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-Rene	Gilles Iyolo Mpotu Mputu Kebakuni Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-Rene
wordlist	wordlist	wordlist
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"
NIO	NIO	NIO
LM & JD	LM & JD	LM & JD
E	Z	E
built-in	built-in	built-in
44 khz/s	44 khz/s	44 khz/s
not verified	75%	not verified
wav	wav	wav
24 bit	24 bit	24 bit
stereo	stereo	stereo
inside, in the living room	inside, in the living room	inside, in the living room
comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a	comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data	comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data
NIO25	NIO25	NIO24

bmn_LM_20210624_NIO_12		bmn_LM_20210624_NIO_11			
24/06/2021		24/06/2021			
nunu	boma	mpe	nunu	boma	nunu
french					
Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mibali	Mushie	Bobala
Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mibali	Mushie	Bobala
Bopapa	Mushie	Izono	Izana	Mushie	Izono
36	50	37	35	50	37
Mputu Kabakuni	Kababa Mbo Isete Jean-Rene	Mpia Mikututu Lenair	Mputu Ikweshe Tresor	Kababa Mbo Isete Jean-Rene	Mpia Mikututu Lenair
wordlist					
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"					
NIO					
LM & JD					
E					
built-in					
44 kHz/s					
not verified					
wav					
24 bit					
stereo					
inside, in the living room					
comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mipe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV: diphthong data					
NIO26					

bmn_LM_20210624_NIO_11		bmn_LM_20210624_NIO_11			
24/06/2021		24/06/2021			
mpe	nunu	boma	mpe	nunu	nunu
french					
Ibz/Bampe	Ibole	Bobala	Mibali	Ibz/Bampe	Ibole
Ibz/Bampe	Ibole	Bobala	Mibali	Ibz/Bampe	Ibole
Badia	Bopapa	Izono	Izana	Badia	Bopapa
49	36	37	35	49	36
Gilles Iyolo Mpototo	Mputu Kabakuni	Mpia Mikututu Lenair	Mputu Ikweshe Tresor	Gilles Iyolo Mpototo	Mputu Kabakuni
wordlist					
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"					
NIO					
LM & JD					
Z					
built-in					
44 kHz/s					
75%					
wav					
24 bit					
stereo					
inside, in the living room					
comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mipe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV: diphthong data					
NIO26					

sak-kit_LM_20210625_NIO_03		sak-kit_LM_20210625_NIO_02					sak-kit_LM_20210625_NIO_01					
25/06/2021		25/06/2021					25/06/2021					
sakata (wara/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibal)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (Mable/kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (wara/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibal)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (Mable/kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (wara/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibal)	mpe
french												
Nioki	Tolo	Kilima	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Kilima	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Iba/Bampe
Mpanza	Vuna	Seble	Mbenzankwi	Mushienini	Mpanza	Vuna	Seble	Mbenzankwi	Mushienini	Mpanza	Vuna	Iba/Bampe
Kesekenda	Boku	Semasa	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Semasa	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Badia
52	49	58	52	52	52	49	58	52	52	52	49	49
Bopila Mbakela Fiedy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Kenay Jean-Pierre	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kenay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Fiedy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Kenay Jean-Pierre	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kenay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Fiedy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Gilles Iyolo Mipoto
wordlist												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
LM & JD												
Z												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
75%												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO28												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
LM & JD												
Z												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
75%												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO27												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
LM & JD												
Z												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
75%												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO27												

sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_05										sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_04									
25/06/2021					25/06/2021					25/06/2021					25/06/2021				
sakata (kitere)	sakata (Mabe/kingingele)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinanzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (Mabe/kingingele)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinanzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (Mabe/kingingele)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinanzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (Mabe/kingingele)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)		
french										french									
Kilima	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Kilima	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Kilima	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Kilima	Mongobebe	Nioki		
Seble	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Seble	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Seble	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Seble	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini		
Semasa	Dwakumbé	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Semasa	Dwakumbé	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Semasa	Dwakumbé	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Semasa	Dwakumbé	Kilima		
58	52	52	52	49	58	52	52	52	49	58	52	52	52	49	58	52	52		
Kemay Jean-Pierre	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius		
wordlist										wordlist									
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"										S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"									
NIO										NIO									
LM & JD										LM & JD									
Z										E									
built-in										built-in									
44 khz/s										44 khz/s									
75%										not verified									
wav										wav									
24 bit										24 bit									
stereo										stereo									
inside, in the living room										inside, in the living room									
comparative Sakata data										comparative Sakata data									
NIO29										NIO28									

sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_08				sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_07				sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_06				
25/06/2021				25/06/2021				25/06/2021				
sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (Mbie/kinginge)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (Mbie/kinginge)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzale)	sakata (kibai)
french												
Nioki	Mpanza	Tolo	Kilima	Mongobele	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Kilima	Mongobele	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo
Mushiemini	Keselenda	Vuna	Sebie	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Sebie	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna
Kilima	52	Boku	Semasa	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Keselenda	Boku	Semasa	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Keselenda	Boku
52	49	49	58	52	52	52	49	58	52	52	52	49
Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Mohe Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Mohe Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Freddy	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky
wordlist												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
LM & JD												
E												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
not verified												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO30												
wordlist												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
LM & JD												
E												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
not verified												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO30												
wordlist												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
LM & JD												
E												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
not verified												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO29												

sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_13				sak+kit_LM_20210625_NIO_12			
25/06/2021				25/06/2021			
sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kiba)	sakata (Mabie/kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kiba)
french							
Mongobele	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Mongobele	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo
Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna
Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku
52	52	52	49	52	52	52	49
Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Prédy	Besvuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Prédy	Besvuku Monkaja Ila Rocky
sound-specific elicitation (labial-velar)							
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"							
NIO							
LM & JD							
Z							
built-in							
44 kHz/s							
75%							
wav							
24 bit							
stereo							
inside, in the living room							
comparative Sakata data							
NIO33							
french							
wordlist							
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"							
NIO							
LM & JD							
E							
built-in							
44 kHz/s							
not verified							
wav							
24 bit							
stereo							
inside, in the living room							
comparative Sakata data							
NIO32							

sak-kit_ID_20210625_INO_02		sak-kit_ID_20210625_INO_01					sak-kit_ID_20210625_INO_14					
25/06/2021		25/06/2021					25/06/2021					
sakata (wara/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (wabe/kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (wara/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (wabe/kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (wara/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (kitere)
french												
Nioki	Tolo	Kilima	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Kilima	Mongobebe	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Kilima
Mpanza	Vuna	Seble	Mbenzankwi	Mushienini	Mpanza	Vuna	Seble	Mbenzankwi	Mushienini	Mpanza	Vuna	Seble
Kesekenda	Boku	Semasa	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Semasa	Dwakumbe	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Semasa
52	49	58	52	52	52	49	58	52	52	52	49	58
Bopila Mbakela Pedy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Pedy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Pedy	Besevuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Kemay Jean-Pierre
sentences												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
JD & LM												
E												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
not verified												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO34												
sentences												
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"												
NIO												
UM & JD												
E												
built-in												
44 kHz/s												
not verified												
wav												
24 bit												
stereo												
inside, in the living room												
comparative Sakata data												
NIO33												

sak+kit_ID_20210626_NIO_02					sak+kit_ID_20210626_NIO_01					kit_LM_20210626_NIO_01			
26/06/2021					26/06/2021					26/06/2021			
sakata (Mabie/Kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/Kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibal)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (Mabie/Kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/Kingingia)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (kibal)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (Mabie/Kingingele)	sakata (Lemvia Nord/Kingingia)
french													
Mongobele	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Kilima	Mongobele	Nioki	Nioki	Tolo	Kilima	Kilima	Kilima	Mongobele	Nioki
Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Sebie	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini	Mpanza	Vuna	Sebie	Sebie	Sebie	Mbenzankwi	Mushiemini
Dwakumbé	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Semasa	Dwakumbé	Kilima	Kesekenda	Boku	Semasa	Semasa	Semasa	Dwakumbé	Kilima
52	52	52	49	58	52	52	52	49	58	58	58	52	52
Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Prédy	Besvuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Bopila Mbakela Prédy	Besvuku Monkaja Ila Rocky	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Kemay Jean-Pierre	Mole Mubata Guillaume	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius
sentences													
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"													
NIO													
JD & LM													
E													
built-in													
44 kHz/s													
not verified													
wav													
24 bit													
stereo													
inside, in the living room													
comparative Sakata data													
NIO36													
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"													
NIO													
LM & JD													
Z													
built-in													
44 kHz/s													
75%													
wav													
24 bit													
stereo													
inside, in the living room													
comparative Sakata data													
NIO35													

roc_ID_20210626_NIO_02	roc_ID_20210626_NIO_01	sak+kit_ID_20210626_NIO_04	sak+kit_ID_20210626_NIO_03
26/06/2021	26/06/2021	26/06/2021	26/06/2021
sakata (kibai)	sakata (kibai)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)	sakata (Lemwia Nord/kingingia)
	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)	sakata (waria/kinzinzale)
	sakata (kitere)	sakata (kitere)	sakata (kitere)
french	french	french	french
Tolo	Tolo	Nioki	Nioki
Vuna	Vuna	Mpanza	Mpanza
Boku	Boku	Kesekenda	Kesekenda
49	49	52	52
Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky	Besevuku Monkeja Ila Rocky	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius	Moja Mayo Kemay Darius
story	story	sentences	sentences
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"
NIO	NIO	NIO	NIO
LM & JD	LM & JD	JD & LM	JD & LM
E	Z	E	Z
built-in	built-in	built-in	built-in
44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s	44 kHz/s
not verified	not verified	not verified	75%
wav	wav	wav	wav
24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit
stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo
inside, in the living room	inside, in the living room	inside, in the living room	inside, in the living room
free connected speech	free connected speech	comparative Sakata data	comparative Sakata data
NIO38	NIO38	NIO37	NIO37

bmm_lm_20210627_NIO_04	bmm_lm_20210627_NIO_03	bmm_lm_20210627_NIO_02
27/07/2021	27/07/2021	27/07/2021
boma	mpe nuu boma	mpe nuu boma
french	french	french
Mbali	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mbali Bobala Bobala Izana 35	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mbali Bobala Bobala Izana 35
Mbali	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mbali Bobala Bobala Izana 35	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mbali Bobala Bobala Izana 35
Izana	Badia Bopapa 36	Badia Bopapa 36
35	49	49
Mputu Iliwebe Tresor	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto Mputu Kebakuni Mputu Iliwebe Tresor	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto Mputu Kebakuni Mputu Iliwebe Tresor
wordlist	wordlist	wordlist
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"
NIO	NIO	NIO
LM & JD	LM & JD	LM & JD
E	Z	E
built-in	built-in	built-in
44 khz/s	44 khz/s	44 khz/s
not verified	75%	not verified
wav	wav	wav
24 bit	24 bit	24 bit
stereo	stereo	stereo
inside, in the living room	inside, in the living room	inside, in the living room
comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe It's a	comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe It's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data	comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe It's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data
NIO46	NIO46	NIO45

bmn_lm_20210627_NIO_06		bmn_lm_20210627_NIO_05			
27/07/2021		27/07/2021			
nunu	boma	mpe	nunu	boma	nunu
french					
Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mibali	Mushie	Bobala
Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mibali	Mushie	Bobala
Bopapa	Mushie	Izono	Izana	Mushie	Izono
36	50	37	35	50	37
Mputu Kabakuni	Kababa Mbo Isete Jean-Rene	Mpia Mikututu Lenair	Mputu Ikweshe Tresor	Kababa Mbo Isete Jean-Rene	Mpia Mikututu Lenair
wordlist					
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"					
NIO					
LM & JD					
E					
built-in					
44 kHz/s					
not verified					
wav					
24 bit					
stereo					
inside, in the living room					
comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mipe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data					
NIO47					
wordlist					
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"					
NIO					
LM & JD					
Z					
built-in					
44 kHz/s					
75%					
wav					
24 bit					
stereo					
inside, in the living room					
comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mipe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data					
NIO47					

bmn_ID_20210628_NIO_01		bmn_LM_20210627_NIO_08				bmn_LM_20210627_NIO_07				
28/07/2021		27/07/2021				27/07/2021				
boma		mpe	nunu	boma		mpe	nunu	boma		
french		french								
Bobala	Mbali	Iba/Bampe	Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mbali	Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mbali
Bobala	Mbali	Iba/Bampe	Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mbali	Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mbali
Izono	Izana	Badia	Bopapa	Mushie	Izono	Izana	Bopapa	Mushie	Izono	Izana
37	35	49	36	50	37	35	36	50	37	35
Mpia Mokutu Lenoir	Mputu Iliwebe Tresor	Gilles Iyolo Mpototo	Mputu Kabakuni	Kababa Mbho Isete Jean-Rene	Mpia Mokutu Lenoir	Mputu Iliwebe Tresor	Mputu Kabakuni	Kababa Mbho Isete Jean-Rene	Mpia Mokutu Lenoir	Mputu Iliwebe Tresor
sentences		wordlist								
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"		S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"								
NIO		NIO								
JD & LM		LM & JD								
Z		Z								
built-in		built-in								
44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s								
75%		not verified								
wav		wav								
24 bit		24 bit								
stereo		stereo								
inside, in the living room		inside, in the living room								
comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data		comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data								
NIO49		NIO48								

bmn_LM_20210628_NIO_01				bmn_ID_20210628_NIO_02			
28/07/2021				28/07/2021			
mpe	nunu	boma		mpe	nunu	boma	
french							
ibay/Bampe	ibole	Mushie	Mballi	ibay/Bampe	ibole	Mushie	Mballi
ibay/Bampe	ibole	Mushie	Mballi	ibay/Bampe	ibole	Mushie	Mballi
Badia	Bopapa	Mushie	Izana	Badia	Bopapa	Mushie	Izana
49	36	50	35	49	36	50	35
Gilles Iyolo Mphoto	Mputu Kabakuni	Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-René	Mputu Iliwebe Trésor	Gilles Iyolo Mphoto	Mputu Kabakuni	Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-René	Mputu Iliwebe Trésor
sentences							
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"							
NIO							
LM & JD							
Z							
built-in							
44 kHz/s							
75%							
wav							
24 bit							
stereo							
inside, in the living room							
comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mipe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data				comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mipe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data			
NIO50				NIO49			

bmn_lm_20210628_NIO_04		bmn_lm_20210628_NIO_03		bmn_lm_20210628_NIO_02	
28/07/2021		28/07/2021		28/07/2021	
boma		boma		boma	
french		french		french	
Mushie	Bobala	Mbali	Bobala	Mbali	Mbali
Mushie	Bobala	Mbali	Bobala	Mbali	Mbali
Mushie	Izono	Izana	Izono	Izana	Izana
50	37	35	37	35	35
Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-René	Mpia Mokutu Lendri	Mputu Ikwembe Tresor	Mpia Mokutu Lendri	Mputu Ikwembe Tresor	Mpia Mokutu Lendri
sentences		sentences		sentences	
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"		S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"		S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	
NIO		NIO		NIO	
LM & JD		LM & JD		LM & JD	
E		Z		E	
built-in		built-in		built-in	
44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s	
not verified		75%		not verified	
wav		wav		wav	
24 bit		24 bit		24 bit	
stereo		stereo		stereo	
inside, in the living room		inside, in the living room		inside, in the living room	
comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data		comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data		comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data	
NIO51		NIO51		NIO50	

bmm_lm_20210629_NIO_03	bmm_lm_20210629_NIO_02	bmm_lm_20210629_NIO_01
29/07/2021	29/07/2021	29/07/2021
boma	mpe nunu boma	mpe nunu boma
french	french	french
Mbali	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mushie Bobala Mbali	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mushie Bobala Mbali
Mbali	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mushie Bobala Mbali	Iba/Bampe Ibole Mushie Bobala Mbali
Izana	Badia Bopapa Mushie Izone Izana	Badia Bopapa Mushie Izone Izana
35	49 36 50 37 35	49 36 50 37 35
Mputu Iliwebe Tresor	Gilles Yolo Mpoto Mputu Kebakuni Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-Rene	Gilles Yolo Mpoto Mputu Kebakuni Kebaba Mbo Isete Jean-Rene
sentences	sentences	sentences
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"
NIO	NIO	NIO
LM & JD	LM & JD	LM & JD
Z	E	Z
built-in	built-in	built-in
44 khz/s	44 khz/s	44 khz/s
75%	not verified	75%
wav	wav	wav
24 bit	24 bit	24 bit
stereo	stereo	stereo
inside, in the living room	inside, in the living room	inside, in the living room
comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a	comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data	comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data
NIO53	NIO52	NIO52

bmn_lm_20210629_NIO_05		bmn_lm_20210629_NIO_04	
29/07/2021		29/07/2021	
nunu	boma	mpe	nunu
french		french	
Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mibali
Ibole	Mushie	Bobala	Mibali
Bopapa	Mushie	Izono	Izana
36	50	37	35
Mputu Kabakuni	Kababa Mbo Isete Jean-Rene	Mpia Mikutu Lenoir	Mputu Ikwembe Tresor
sentences			
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"			
NIO			
LM & JD			
Z			
built-in			
44 kHz/s			
75%			
wav			
24 bit			
stereo			
inside, in the living room			
comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mipe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data		comparative data: retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mipe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LV; diphthong data	
NIO54		NIO53	

bmn_LM_20210629_NIO_08		bmn_LM_20210629_NIO_07		bmn_LM_20210629_NIO_06	
29/07/2021		29/07/2021		29/07/2021	
boma		boma		boma	
mpe	nunu	mpe	nunu	mpe	nunu
french		french		french	
Bobala	Mbali	Iba/Bampe	Ibole	Mushie	Mbali
Bobala	Mbali	Iba/Bampe	Ibole	Mushie	Mbali
Izono	Izana	Badia	Bopapa	Mushie	Izana
37	35	49	36	50	37
Mpitu Ikwébe Tresor	Mpitu Ikwébe Tresor	Gilles Iyolo Mpoto	Mpitu Kabakuni	Kababa Mbo Isete Jean-René	Mpita Mokutu Lenoir
sentences		sentences		sentences	
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"		S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"		S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	
NIO		NIO		NIO	
LM & JD		LM & JD		LM & JD	
E		Z		E	
built-in		built-in		built-in	
44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s		44 kHz/s	
not verified		75%		not verified	
wav		wav		wav	
24 bit		24 bit		24 bit	
stereo		stereo		stereo	
inside, in the living room		inside, in the living room		inside, in the living room	
comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data		comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data		comparative data; retroflex nasals (in Boma and occasionally in Nunu, in Mpe it's a plain alveolar nasal); LVs; diphthong data	
NIO55		NIO55		NIO54	

dan_LM_20210630_NIO_05		dan_LM_20210630_NIO_04		dan_LM_20210630_NIO_03		dan_LM_20210630_NIO_02		dan_LM_20210630_NIO_01		bmn_LM_20210629_NIO_09																			
30/06/2021		30/06/2021		30/06/2021		30/06/2021		30/06/2021		29/07/2021																			
tiene		tiene		tiene		tiene		tiene		mpe		nunu		boma		mpe		nunu											
french		french		french		french		french		french																			
Mpuni	Ibale	Mushie	Bobala	Mbali	Iba/Bampe	Ibale	Mushie	Mushie																					
Mansele	Ibale	Mushie	Bobala	Mbali	Iba/Bampe	Ibale	Mushie	Mushie																					
Mpuni	Bopapa	Mushie	Izono	Izama	Badia	Bopapa	Mushie	Mushie																					
25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	36	50	37	35	49	36	50	50												
Dany Ngwe Molutu	Gilles Iyolo Mphoto	Kehaba Mbo Isete Jean-Rene	Mpia Mokutu Lendur	Mputu Iliwebe Treor	Gilles Iyolo Mphoto	Mputu Kehakuni	Kehaba Mbo Isete Jean-Rene																						
sentences		stories																											
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"																													
NIO																													
LM																													
Z	R	Z	R	Z	R	Z	R	Z	Z																				
built-in	clip-on	built-in	clip-on	built-in	clip-on	built-in	clip-on	built-in	built-in																				
44 kHz/s																													
75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%	75%																				
wav																													
24 bit																													
stereo																													
inside, in the living room																													
Dani spoke very softly																													
NIO59	NIO58	NIO58	NIO57	NIO57	NIO57	NIO57	NIO57	NIO57	NIO56																				

dan_LM_20210630 _NIO_09	dan_LM_20210630 _NIO_08	dan_LM_20210630 _NIO_07	dan_LM_20210630 _NIO_06
30/06/2021	30/06/2021	30/06/2021	30/06/2021
tiene	tiene	tiene	tiene
french	french	french	french
Mpuni	Mpuni	Mpuni	Mpuni
Mansele	Mansele	Mansele	Mansele
Mpuni	Mpuni	Mpuni	Mpuni
25	25	25	25
Dany Ngwe Molutu	Dany Ngwe Molutu	Dany Ngwe Molutu	Dany Ngwe Molutu
story	wordlist	sentences	sentences
S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"	S 02°42'51.2" E 017°41'57.7"
NIO	NIO	NIO	NIO
LM	LM	LM	LM
R	R	R	R
clip-on	clip-on	clip-on	clip-on
44 khz/s	44 khz/s	44 khz/s	44 khz/s
75%	75%	75%	75%
wav	wav	wav	wav
24 bit	24 bit	24 bit	24 bit
stereo	stereo	stereo	stereo
inside, in the living room			
Dani spoke very softly	Dani spoke very softly	Dani spoke very softly	Dani spoke very softly
NIO62	NIO61	NIO60	NIO59